

Amazigh Intangible Cultural Heritage:

A qualitative exploration of gender and the role of women in the preservation and transmission of traditional cultures within Algerian policies

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Author's Declaration

This thesis is the result of my own original research and has not been submitted for any other degree or award at any other university or institution. I have acknowledged all the sources of information that I have used in this thesis, both in the text and in the list of references. I have obtained the written permission from the proprietors of any third-party material that I have included in this thesis. I have followed the Chapter 4 regulation on Research Degrees of the University of the West of Scotland, which covers the ethical and academic standards for conducting research.

Zinai Fatima Zohra

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Abstract

This research is a qualitative exploration of intangible cultural heritage (ICH) in North Africa, particularly investigating the Algerian context. The thesis emphasises the importance of ethnic minorities and their cultures, and their importance within the history and communities of Algeria. The core focus is the Amazigh, the original peoples of Algeria. Their ICH and its relation to gender offer the context for analysing the role of women in the cultural transmission process. Alongside the investigation of Amazigh cultural heritage, governmental policies and measures adopted to protect and preserve this legacy are analysed, tracking their evolution and impacts.

The methodological approach is qualitative, as appropriate to investigate the ideas, experiences, and perceptions of ICH for Amazigh women, as well as how, collectively, community and government practices constitute social worlds in Algeria. This study adopts a constructivist approach, which underpins the qualitative methods applied. These comprise one-to-one interviews with Amazigh women, structured interviews with cultural managers in the main cities where the Amazigh live, and a document analysis covering both Algerian and UNESCO ICH policies. These data are triangulated to assure the robustness of findings and highlight any inconsistencies.

Reviewing the studies showed a limited literature in the field of Amazigh heritage, highlighting the need to establish a more comprehensive research base on this ethnic group. Tamazight is predominantly represented in a folklorised context, focusing on forms such as dance, arts, and crafts, while its use in more formal or official domains remains minimal (El Guabli, 2023). In the cultural sphere, in which minorities are being marginalised, through actions such as a lack of language integration, as seen by Banhakeia and Frankfort (2022), with the Amazigh language considered inferior to Arabic in Algeria. Cultural representation at different levels, such as in the educational system, shows the struggles and challenges these ethnic groups encounter, such as the misjudgements and the wrong impressions of their culture and traditions. On another side, the biased gendered perspectives that manifest in the discrimination between gender roles, and the inadequate acknowledgement of women in both academic works and in society, despite the responsibilities that women bear in such communities (Macdonald, 2021).

In summary, this research strives to contribute to a deeper understanding of Amazigh intangible cultural heritage, with a particular focus on gender variables and governmental interventions such as funding, supporting organisations, and promoting the Amazigh intangible heritage in a global form. The findings from this study aim to contribute to academic enrichment, cultural inclusion, and the promotion of gender equality, advocating for a more comprehensive and objective representation of heritage and culture.

The original contribution of this study lies in underscoring the significant role of Amazigh women in transmitting and preserving intangible heritage. It also offers insights about the role of Algerian policy within the ICH framework, and the role of the government to support cultural inclusion, reduce marginalisation, and safeguard Amazigh heritage. The research aims to address cultural preservation, inequality in policy implementation through giving a platform for Amazigh women to express themselves and bridge the gap between folklorised exotic culture to a national lineage. This thesis uniquely adopts Hofstede's cultural dimensions in a qualitative approach dealing with a marginalised indigenous context, advancing theoretical understanding of ICH in non-Western settings.

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List of Abbreviations

- **ANGEM** Agence Nationale de Gestion du Microcrédit (National Agency for Microcredit Management, Algeria).
- **FFS** Front des Forces Socialistes (Socialist Forces Front, Algeria).
- **FLN** Front de Libération Nationale (National Liberation Front, Algeria).
- **ICH** Intangible Cultural Heritage.
- **IRCAM** Institut Royal de la Culture Amazighe (Royal Institute of Amazigh Culture, Morocco).
- **MAK** Mouvement pour l'Autodétermination de la Kabylie (Movement for the Self-Determination of Kabylia).
- **MENA** Middle East and North Africa.
- **MOC** Ministry of Culture.
- **NGO** Non-Governmental Organisation.
- **SILA** Salon International du Livre d'Alger.
- **UNESCO** United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation.
- **WIPO** World Intellectual Property Organisation.

Chapter One – Introduction

The Middle East and North Africa (MENA) are regions comprising several countries that share cultural, religious, economic, and environmental conditions, the context of this thesis focuses on Algeria. One of the shared cultural and ethnic attributes in North Africa is the diversity in ethnicities, languages, traditions, habits, and norms. An ethnic group is defined as a group with several similarities, such as history, ancestry, culture, roots, the sense of belonging to a land “homeland,” and solidarity with a particular group ([Zagefka, 2015](#)). Being a part of a minority in any region of the world promotes feelings of exclusion and neglect. According to Weber (1987), exclusion is one type of "social closure," which is an attempt by one status group to gain a privileged position at the expense of other small groups.

This cycle of neglect and privilege of certain groups over others is not limited to ethnic groups and minorities. In some instances, within the same group, individuals build and govern by superiority of higher positions, riches, properties, and gender. Gender inequality has been a topic well-covered throughout history. Several feminist scholars have been addressing this issue from many perspectives, such as Simone de Beauvoir's (1949) works defending her sex and expressing the inequality women are facing, or Betty Friedan's work on “the feminine mystique” that argues the idea of women as a reproduction machine. Feminist waves through history have introduced women from a rigid point of view that objectified them as a homogenous group of humans. In contrast, individuals with different cultural identifications broaden this group beyond its similitude of gender.

In North African countries, women from different ethnic groups are responsible for the biological and cultural bearing of the coming generation. Their leading role in society is to bear children and raise them to fit in their own culture, saturated by traditions and cultural norms. Yuval-Davis (1993:627) argues that ethnic women are regarded as “biological and cultural reproducers. As cultural embodiments and collective representations, women are often regarded as bearers of honour and active participants in their national and ethnic struggles. These cultural norms and roles, such as marriage, dictate and determine women's social status and roles. In the context of this study on Amazigh women and their narratives in Algeria, a gap exists within academic work concerning gender studies and ICH. The advocacy, activism and academic literature, mainly in Arabic or French, primarily focuses on women's rights as a homogeneous group, without considering women's differences and diverse experiences. It also dismisses the fact

that the cultural and societal norms in ethnic groups act in ways that limit ethnic women's rights and their decisions. Furthermore, it shows scant interest in the recesses of Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH) and its relationship with ethnic women. These mainstream discourses are impacted by patriarchal perspectives, cultural inequality, low political representation, and the absence of academic work, which requires addressing the needs and priorities of Amazigh women from the grassroots level. This thesis aims to fill the notable absence of Amazigh women within the discourses mentioned above.

Gagliardi (2019, 2021) and Sadiqi (2014) argue that the mention of Amazigh women within “hegemonic feminist discourses” is mainly related to terminologies such as “*rural women, illiterate, in need of aid, and passive beneficiaries of aid*”. These stereotypical images generated from the narrow scope of knowledge minimise Amazigh women, suppress their identity, cover their specificity, and diminish the challenges they face as Amazigh women.

One of the cultural attributes of Amazigh is their language, Tamazight, the native language mainly used in their cities and among Amazigh themselves. Whereas many rural Amazigh women are monolingual, using only Tamazight can be an obstacle for them in communicating while accessing public and government services, noting that authorities in the country use either Arabic or French. As a form of intangible cultural heritage, language is an identity marker. It can also be a barrier and a challenge for them in day-to-day activities.

Sadiqi has published many works on Amazigh women, covering cultural aspects such as language, identity, gender, oral literature of Amazigh women, and their history as gatekeepers of Amazigh culture. She used culture to bring perspective and context from within as an Amazigh herself. The author of this thesis, while being an outsider to the Amazigh culture, she is however, a part of it in ways. The author shares the same background, nationality, and religion, but most importantly, the close contact that she has with an Algerian woman who had similar experiences to the participants of this study. Sadiqi dealt with Amazigh culture and arts, and crafts and how they better the everyday life of Amazigh women through her fieldwork with Amazigh rural women, delivering one side of the story. Unlike Gagliardi’s publications, which provided the other side, she investigated Amazigh women from a post-colonial, human rights, and international regulations perspective related to minority rights and indigenous/ ethnic people. Gagliardi’s fieldwork strategies involved interviewing Amazigh women and exploring through their testimonies how Amazigh women are marginalised and discriminated against; she analysed these

forms of discrimination based on attributes such as sex, gender, identity, and socio-economic status. The results were that Amazigh women are experiencing structural and cultural violence.

The works of Sadiqi and Gagliardi were focused on Morocco and addressed Moroccan Amazigh. This PhD thesis contributes to the Algerian context by studying Algerian Amazigh women and Algerian intangible cultural heritage. There is limited academic work done in English addressing this specific topic and revealing the challenges Amazigh women face. The thesis also adopts the strategies of the scholars mentioned above, and the thesis author's fieldwork notes capture interviewing participants in their environment. Acknowledging and documenting women's experiences from their perspectives and experiences is crucial. Recognising women's experiences gives value to their lives, emphasising the importance of giving them voices and viewpoints and not imposing narratives that may lead to bias, and valuing their agency in acting independently, choosing freely, and leaving a mark in history, teaching the coming generations, and proving resilience and courage. Offering guidance on navigating different situations and encouraging the potential of their experiences and contributions (Comins Mingol, 2016).

In alignment with these ideas, this thesis brings the voices of Amazigh women to the forefront, to reveal the invisible side of the intangible cultural heritage about gender. Amazigh women's strength and resilience by participating in traditional cultures preservation is a topic that endures an epistemological invisibility in Algerian literature. Whereas their representation is focused mainly on their honourable role in transmitting and preserving ICH and not on their adversities, challenges on one side or their resilience and strength with which they continue living on the other.

Amazigh women express how they see the world by enriching their culture; they translate their struggles and resilience to weaving carpets with symbols, shaping pottery, designing motifs onto clothes, and tattooing their bodies, marking history with their perspectives and views. However, these perspectives remained experiences that limited Amazigh women to traditional roles of wives and mothers, and contributions that are underestimated by their societies. To achieve its aim, this study focused on Algerian Amazigh women in four major cities: Batna, Ghardaia, Tizi-ouzo, and Tamanrasset. The global COVID-19 pandemic situation had an impact on the study, including opportunities for field work and sample size. They were very welcoming and patient during the fieldwork. A triangulation method that combines field notes, Semi-structured in-depth interviews with Amazigh women that endeavours to humbly contribute to the voices of Amazigh women's narratives, strengths, and resilience, from within to support the representation

of female contributions to traditional cultures in Algeria, both in literature and in activism. In addition to safeguarding intangible cultural heritage in Algeria, these testimonies are homage to the oral knowledge and discourses of Amazigh women. Accordingly, providing Amazigh women's testimonies and experience as an academic contribution to fill the gap in the literature, which originates from both feminist and cultural studies, considering both critical and constructive works that contribute to knowledge and culture.

1.1. The Conceptual Framing of the Project

There has been a growing interest in the field of heritage and intangible heritage, especially in Algeria (Charef, 2022). Algeria has witnessed a positive movement toward the safeguarding of national heritage and its promotion, particularly through UNESCO agendas and policies from 2015 to the present. However, Amazigh heritage remains neglected and receives limited attention (B76anhakeia and Frankfort, 2022), largely due to its status as a minority culture (ibid., 2022). Despite this marginalisation and perceptions of primitiveness (Hilton-Simpson, 1922), Amazigh heritage forms a significant part of Algerian identity, representing the oldest existing culture in the Maghreb, as evidenced by prehistoric paintings in Tassili n'Ajjer dating back to 10,000 BC. The dynamics surrounding the Amazigh heritage can be analysed through Hofstede's dimensions of national culture, particularly power distance, individualism vs. collectivism, and long-term orientation vs. short-term orientation. After Algeria's independence in 1962, state policies emphasising modernisation, homogenization, and Arabization marginalised Amazigh communities (Maddy Weitzman, 2011). The high-power distance in Algerian governance, reflected in centralised policies, prioritised Arabic/Muslim identities while suppressing regional and minority expressions of identity, such as the Amazigh culture. This approach contributed to the so-called "Berber question in Algeria," wherein the linguistic, historical, and anthropological dimensions of Amazigh culture were ignored (Yezza, 2013). The Amazigh language was acknowledged as a national language in 2002 and as an official language alongside Arabic in 2016. Political movements, such as the founding of the "Rally for Culture and Democracy" in 1989, reflect the collectivist push within the Amazigh community to assert their identity, contrasting with state-driven narratives rooted in homogenization. These tensions align with Hofstede's individualism vs. collectivism dimension, as Amazigh activism highlights community bonds and shared cultural practices that are at odds with the state's emphasis on a unified national identity. In terms of long-term orientation, the limited scholarly focus on Amazigh heritage in Algeria underscores a short-

term orientation toward immediate political and social narratives rather than long-term preservation of cultural diversity. While Amazigh communities have maintained their traditions over generations, their representation in academic discourse remains underdeveloped, with much of the literature produced by foreign scholars. In contrast, neighbouring Maghreb countries have given more comprehensive attention to the Amazigh heritage (Zoubir and Fernandez, 2008). This study focuses on the critical role of Amazigh women in transmitting and preserving intangible cultural heritage in Algeria. As gatekeepers of cultural continuity, Amazigh women have a central role in sustaining identity through practices that align with the masculinity vs. femininity dimension of Hofstede's model. Their contributions, which emphasise relational and community-oriented values, contrast with the masculine-driven policies that often overlook their roles (Gagliardi, 2020). By exploring the narratives of twenty Amazigh women aged over 45 years and engaging with four heritage association managers, this research seeks to shed light on the gendered transmission of heritage, the significance of Amazigh intangible heritage as an identity marker, and the Algerian government's efforts in safeguarding this cultural legacy.

1.2. Positionality of the Researcher

It is pivotal to set out the researcher's positionality before conducting the research. As an Algerian female researcher, I, the author, contribute an original perspective to this study of Amazigh women and Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH). Although I am not an Amazigh, I have close relationships with Amazigh women as friends, distant family members, neighbours, and citizens of the same country. Those close relationships have granted me a direct insight into Amazigh communities and their lifestyles. Furthermore, it had also guided me to investigate the challenges and adversities on one side, and the empowerment and resilience of the Amazigh women on the other side.

The debate on the researcher's positionality, including the researcher's experiences, beliefs, and their possibility to significantly influence the qualitative research, is acknowledged and discussed. Positionality can affect many aspects of the research, including research questions, data collection and analysis (Wilson et al., 2022). Therefore, my positionality as an Algerian Arab female researcher, an individual who is not a member of the Amazigh community, my positionality informs my research approach by adopting an outsider perspective. This perspective guides my curiosity, shapes my investigative lens, and frames the questions I seek to explore in this study.

I acknowledge the significance of understanding the different experiences of the Amazigh women from various perspectives, including those of Algerian culture managers who have expertise in the field of Intangible Cultural Heritage. Through harnessing my personal experiences and networks, to achieve the objective of this thesis, my aim is to contribute to both the Amazigh culture preservation and to the academic works related to this ethnic group in Algeria. Furthermore, my aim also includes enriching the comprehension of female dynamics in ICH domains and the overall understanding of the importance of ICH.

The researcher's positionality has played a crucial role in shaping both the methodological and analytical approach of this study. As a North African researcher with cultural and linguistic familiarity with the Amazigh context, my identity influenced the research process in several ways. This positional awareness facilitated access to participant communities, particularly among women, and allowed for more culturally sensitive engagement during interviews and data collection. However, it also required careful reflexivity to mitigate potential bias, particularly when interpreting culturally embedded practices or traditions. The sampling strategy was influenced by this dual position of familiarity and critical distance, selecting diverse Amazigh subgroups (Kabyle, Chaouia, Mزاب, Tuareg) and intentionally incorporating a gendered lens to ensure that women's voices and lived experiences were prioritised within the research design.

The methodology was constructed with an awareness of insider/outsider dynamics, ensuring that power relationships were balanced, and that participants' perspectives were represented authentically. This included adopting open-ended, narrative-style interviews and iterative coding practices that allowed participant voices to guide the analysis rather than imposing rigid theoretical categories. The positionality discussion helps frame the broader themes explored in this chapter and underscores the importance of researcher reflexivity in cultural studies.

1.3. Aim, Objectives, and Research Questions

This research aims to explore the critical role of Amazigh women in transmitting and preserving intangible cultural heritage (ICH) and to understand how Algerian governmental policies align with the preservation and promotion of this heritage. This study investigates the intersection of gender, culture, and policy within the socio-political framework of Algeria, focusing on the resilience of Amazigh women despite the adversities they face.

The objectives of this research are as follows:

1. **Examine Algeria’s cultural policies and their impact on Amazigh heritage preservation:** This includes analysing the extent to which these policies support or hinder efforts to safeguard Amazigh ICH, with attention to the implementation and local adaptation of state policies.

2. **Explore the influence of gender roles on Amazigh women’s resilience and empowerment in heritage preservation:** This objective seeks to understand how societal norms shape women’s roles in their communities, either supporting or constraining their agency.

3. **Identify strategies employed by Amazigh women to sustain and transmit ICH amidst socio-economic challenges:** These strategies include communal initiatives, artisanal crafts, and oral traditions that help maintain cultural practices despite economic and social pressures.

4. **Document the lived experiences and cultural practices of Amazigh women:** Capturing their challenges and resilience provides an in-depth understanding of their contributions to cultural heritage preservation.

To address these aims and objectives, the research poses the following overarching question:

How do Amazigh women in Algeria navigate and contribute to the preservation and transformation of their cultural identity within the context of national and regional policies, socio-political challenges, and modernisation pressures?

This main question is supported by the following sub-questions:

- How do Algeria’s national policies on cultural heritage and identity impact Amazigh women's efforts to preserve intangible cultural heritage?
- In what ways do traditional gender roles and social norms shape Amazigh women’s empowerment and resilience in heritage preservation?
- How do Amazigh women navigate the tension between cultural preservation and modernisation within their communities?
- What strategies do Amazigh women employ to sustain and transmit intangible cultural heritage amidst socio-economic challenges and shifting national identities?
- How do the experiences and practices of Amazigh women in Algeria contribute to intangible culture preservation despite the adversities they face?

1.4. Methodology

This research adopts a social constructivist paradigm to explore the transmission and preservation of Amazigh intangible cultural heritage (ICH) through the lived experiences of Amazigh women. Ontology, the study of reality, is rooted in the belief that reality is socially constructed and dynamic, shaped by cultural, linguistic, and gendered interactions (Smith, 2012). This aligns with the epistemological framework of interpretivism, which holds that knowledge is co-constructed through subjective experiences and social practices (Chamberlain, 2015). Building on this philosophical foundation, the research employs a qualitative methodological approach, emphasising depth and contextual understanding over generalisation. The qualitative design is supported by a triangulation of methods, including semi-structured interviews, structured interviews, and document analysis. This multi-method strategy ensures a holistic exploration of the role of Amazigh women in preserving cultural heritage while addressing socio-political challenges and modernisation pressures.

Data were collected from two key participant groups: the first participants, twenty Amazigh women from diverse regions in Algeria, representing major Amazigh communities (Kabyle, Chaoui, Mzab, and Tuareg), and the second participants, four cultural managers from regional directorates. Participants were selected using purposive sampling, ensuring their relevance to the study's aims. Thematic analysis was employed to interpret the data, enabling the identification of patterns and themes related to cultural identity, resilience, and empowerment. This methodological approach reflects the study's focus on understanding cultural heritage as a lived, socially constructed phenomenon (Atkinson, 2015) emphasising the centrality of women's roles in its preservation and transmission. Through the lens of constructivism, the research bridges participant narratives, policy analysis, and academic discourse to contribute to the broader understanding of ICH and gender dynamics in Algeria.

Sample description

This study focuses on two primary participant groups to examine the preservation and transmission of Amazigh intangible cultural heritage (ICH) in Algeria, with an emphasis on the role of women. The first group consists of twenty Amazigh women from four major regions: Tizi Ouzou (Kabyle), Batna (Chaoui), Ghardaia (Mzab), and Tamanrasset (Tuareg). These women, all over the age of 45, were purposefully selected. Their experiences provide valuable insights into the

intersection of gender, ethnicity, and cultural preservation, reflecting diverse traditions and practices across Algeria's Amazigh population. The second group includes four cultural managers from the same previously mentioned regions; they provided a complementary perspective on Algerian institutional efforts to safeguard ICH. Together, these participant groups provide a view of both the personal and structural dimensions of cultural preservation, enabling a comprehensive exploration of how Amazigh heritage is preserved in the face of modernisation and socio-political challenges.

1.5. The Structure of the Thesis

The thesis is structured in nine chapters. The focus of each chapter is briefly described below.

This first chapter, Introduction, is dedicated to introducing the research, laying out the problem and rationale for the research, including the scope of the research, its context, and significance, the research aims and objectives, the research question and sub-questions, the methodology and the structure of the thesis.

The second chapter, Culture and Cultural Theories, is a brief conceptualisation of culture. First, it attempts to define and unpack the concept of intangible cultural heritage and its emergence from the notions of 'heritage', 'culture', 'tradition', and 'folklore'. Secondly, it presents cultural theories related to intangible cultural heritage, such as cultural imperialism and cultural relativism. Thirdly, it introduces Hofstede's cultural dimensions, which will be the conceptual framework for this thesis.

The third chapter, Gender Dynamics in Amazigh Intangible Cultural Heritage, addresses the Algerian context, Amazigh, gender, and orality. This chapter briefly explains the historical background of the Amazigh indigenous people in Algeria and North Africa. It also explores the distinctiveness of Amazigh as an ethnic group in the country, their cultural norms, and traditions. Moreover, the chapter examines Amazigh during the colonial period and during the independence with the Arabization policies. Furthermore, it describes Arabization policies and their implications on Amazigh societal and political lives.

The fourth chapter, methodology and methods, explains the qualitative methodological strategy and methods (document analysis and interview methods) used to answer the research questions and achieve the study's aims and objectives. The chapter is organised into five sections. This chapter provides an overview of the research design, emphasising the use of a qualitative approach and triangulation to enhance data validity and deepen analysis. It outlines the sampling

framework, detailing participant selection criteria, sampling methods, and sample size, ensuring a purposeful and systematic approach aligned with the study's qualitative nature. The chapter also discusses the data collection tools, including semi-structured and structured interviews as well as document analysis, which collectively capture the multifaceted nature of the research topic. Furthermore, it explains the data analysis process, describing the systematic interpretation of collected data. The chapter concludes by addressing ethical considerations, underscoring the importance of ethical rigour in qualitative research.

The fifth chapter examines the relationship between UNESCO's evolving policies on intangible cultural heritage (ICH) and Algeria's national strategies for heritage preservation. It discusses Algeria's commitment to safeguarding cultural heritage, demonstrated by its early ratification of the 2003 UNESCO Convention and its legislative efforts to protect and promote its cultural legacy. The analysis highlights both the progress made, and the challenges faced in effectively implementing these policies. Through exploring Algeria's cultural policies and initiatives, the chapter aims to illuminate the country's efforts to preserve its rich cultural heritage in the face of globalisation and contemporary societal pressures.

The sixth chapter examines the challenges and adversities faced by Amazigh women in Algeria, including the hardships of rural life and the constraints of patriarchal society. Reflecting on insights and experiences shared by participants closely connected to traditional lifestyles and cultural practices, the chapter investigates the intersection of gender, cultural marginalisation and socio-economic limitations in shaping their lives. Additionally, it explores the empowerment these women achieve through their active participation in preserving intangible cultural heritage. Through safeguarding traditions, rituals, language, and oral practices, these women demonstrate resilience and agency in maintaining their cultural identity despite systemic challenges.

The seventh chapter presents findings from structured interviews with four cultural authority figures from diverse Algerian regions: Tizi Ouzou, Batna, Ghardaia, and Tamanrasset. These interviews shed light on the interplay between cultural dynamics and professional responsibilities within Algeria's rich and varied cultural landscape. It also examines how individuals in leadership and management roles address challenges, particularly in navigating the balance between national governance and regional autonomy. Furthermore, the chapter covers aspects of Algeria's centralised governance system, cultural Hybridity, challenges facing policy and cultural activism.

The eighth chapter, Discussion, provides a link between chapters six and seven as it deals with themes such as cultural identity, empowering Amazigh women, Amazigh women as guardians of ICH, and the quest of Amazigh women for gender equality. This chapter discusses findings from the analysis for the aim of preserving ICH, acknowledging Amazigh women's contributions within the cultural policies in Algeria.

The ninth chapter, Conclusions, is dedicated to summarising the key findings through answering the research question, reflecting on the research by discussing the implications of the research. Furthermore, acknowledging the limitations, proposing recommendations, and highlighting contributions in literature and policy.

1.6. Conclusion

This chapter introduces the key elements of the research, starting with the research context, which highlights the importance of Amazigh women in preserving intangible cultural heritage in Algeria. It presents the conceptual framing, outlining the theoretical frameworks and the challenges faced by Amazigh communities, including marginalisation and cultural neglect. The chapter defines the aims and objectives of the study, alongside the research questions, which focus on exploring the role of Amazigh women and the impact of governmental policies on cultural preservation. Additionally, the chapter addresses the researcher's positionality. Finally, it provides an overview of the thesis structure, briefly summarising the focus of each subsequent chapter to guide the reader through the study's framework.

Chapter Two - Culture and Cultural Theories

This study aims to explore intangible cultural heritage (ICH). In order to achieve this, an investigation on culture, its forms, and its theories was needed. This chapter unpacks the conceptualisation of culture from different academic disciplines (sociology and anthropology) and through different timelines, investigating the different cultural takes in different contexts, by discussing aspects of culture, its importance, and its continuity. Since the research is about society and female transmitting culture, this section will provide insights regarding female culture, cultural elements, culture and society, traditions, and habits. Furthermore, it will devote greater attention to the influence of culture on society, cultural changes over time, and the meaning of cultural identity.

The chapter is structured in eight main sections., The first sections explore the concept of culture, and its forms material (tangible) and the non-material (intangible). Sections 2 to 2.7 of the chapter investigate the dynamics of cultural identity, assimilation, and resistance, Section 2.3. explores the concept of cultural imperialism, a theory that examines the mechanisms through which dominant global powers impose their cultural values and systems upon less dominant societies, often undermining local identities and traditions. The discussion transitions to the African context, highlighting the continent's historical encounter with cultural imperialism through colonialism and globalisation. These forces reshaped indigenous cultural landscapes, leading to the marginalisation of local traditions, languages, and identities. While globalisation has facilitated the transmission of cultural knowledge, it has also created imbalances, diminishing African societies to a predominantly passive role. Yet, communities have adapted to modern technologies, hoping to safeguard and promote their heritage. Within Algeria, the impact of cultural imperialism is evident in the colonial and post-colonial eras. The French colonial administration sought to impose cultural assimilation through language, education, and religion, marginalising both Arab and Amazigh identities. Despite these efforts, the shared struggle for independence forged a collective Algerian identity, despite the continuous struggle with the complexities of cultural plurality in the post-independence period. This struggle was particularly pronounced for the Amazigh community, whose advocacy for cultural recognition resulted in riots and movements like the Berber Spring, underscoring the resilience of marginalised identities against both colonial and state-imposed assimilation.

The chapter further integrates theories such as cultural relativism and ethnocentrism in sections 2.3 and 2.4 to examine the broader sociocultural dynamics shaping identity formation and preservation. It contextualises these theories within the framework of Hofstede's cultural dimensions, explored in detail in section 2.5, offering a nuanced perspective on how values such as collectivism, uncertainty avoidance, and power distance influence the Amazigh community's efforts to maintain their cultural heritage. Lastly, the section addresses the concept of cultural assimilation, tracking its historical application during French colonial rule in Algeria. It explores the dual strategies of soft and coercive assimilation employed to eliminate local cultural identities, particularly among the Amazigh. However, the unintended blending of Arab and Amazigh identities during this period fostered a unified resistance against colonial rule and later contributed to the assertion of Amazigh cultural heritage within the national framework. Through mixing these theoretical and historical perspectives, this section provides a comprehensive understanding of the forces shaping cultural identity in Algeria, with a focus on the Amazigh community's enduring efforts to preserve their heritage in the face of external and internal challenges.

2.1. Defining Culture

In this section, the notion of culture is defined chronologically to provide an understanding of the development and change that occurred to the concept through time and according to several cultural scholars.

Culture has always been a difficult concept to define since early times. Eliot (1948) labelled culture anthropologically as the manner a given community live together in a shared place and stated that "It includes all the characteristic activities and interests of a people: Derby Day, Henley Regatta, Cowes, the twelfth of August, a cup final, the dog races, the pin table, the dartboard, Wensleydale cheese, boiled cabbage cut into sections, beetroot in vinegar, nineteenth-century Gothic churches and the music of Elgar" (Eliot, 1948: 31). During the mid-twentieth century, researchers attempted to further define culture. One of those definitions was provided by Kluckhohn (1962), who presented an array of meanings to the notion by asserting that culture socially is a way of life, a human legacy, and an aspect of thinking. Anthropologically is the way for a group of people to act. On that premise, Geertz (1973) describes Culture as a structure of perspectives expressed in symbols by which people connect; he goes further, claiming that culture makes the world meaningful and understandable. From another perspective, Boyd and Richerson

(1985) state that culture is what they call "heuristics" or "thumb rule" that serves people's decision-making in complicated and doubtful situations. To find the right decision in the previously mentioned situations, people tend to rely on beliefs, values and feelings. They argue that culture consists of the process of decision-making.

According to Greif (1994), culture is a combination of social and anthropological aspects; in his view, culture is the reflection of society and its behaviours. He argues that beliefs are one of the major features of the culture itself. Since they govern the way people interact among themselves and other groups, beyond that, he asserts that a certain group maintains those beliefs and connects through them without the need to analyse, prove or empirically discover them.

In a recent definition, Guiso et al. (2006: 23) construe culture "as those customary beliefs and values that ethnic, religious and social groups transmit fairly unchanged from generation to generation". In agreement with Greif, Guiso formalises the notion of beliefs as a "thumb rule" in which individuals adapt in uncertain situations, whereas values are inclinations of each individual. Roland (2015) argues that beliefs and values are the units that construct culture. He asserts that the collections of beliefs that a certain community trusts to explain how the world works and the rules of behaviour they acquire from their values are what truly define culture.

In a current discussion, the definitions of the term vary according to the domain they are applied to and the purposes they are intended to perform (Castellani, 2018). This makes culture unlimited and influential in different domains. As stated by JinHyo (2020), culture affects behaviour not by providing the ultimate principles to which action is guided, but by forming a repertoire or "toolkit" of behaviours, abilities, and styles from which individuals create "action strategies".

Assembling all the above-mentioned contributions to define culture, threefold features can be deduced. Firstly, that culture is a communal way of life passed through generations. Secondly, culture restrains people indirectly through what is called beliefs and values. Lastly, culture is a form of knowledge that societies establish and promote.

French and Bell (1995) define culture as an iceberg; The figure below illustrates the concept; the small visible part indicates the material aspects of culture, whereas the larger part that contains all the non-material aspects is hidden (French and Bell, 1995).

Figure 2.1: Culture iceberg

Source: French and Bell (1995)

2.2 Cultural Aspects

This section is devoted to the aspects of culture material, and non-material, as well as its elements such as values, rituals, heroes, symbols, and practices. It dwells also on some notions important to this thesis aims, such as cultural imperialism, cultural relativism, and ethnocentrism.

Torres (2008: 81) states, "the way of life of a people. It includes their eating habits, dressing, mannerism, and any other socially learned and transmitted behaviour, ideas, norms, values, and beliefs". As defined, culture consists of two basic components, namely, material (artefacts) and non-material (symbolic). The former encompasses cuisine, architecture, costumes, and all the tangible elements. Whereas the latter comprises all the non-material attributes such as music, dance, values, language, behaviours, rituals, religion, and so on.

This section is devoted to both material and non-material aspects of culture, along with their elements, such as values, rituals, heroes, symbols, and practices. It also explores key concepts relevant to this thesis, including cultural imperialism, cultural relativism, and ethnocentrism. Hofstede's 'onion' model is particularly useful for unpacking the layered and often implicit nature of cultural identity, which is vital in analysing how Amazigh communities engage with and express heritage values.

In this context, the distinction between material and immaterial culture is critical and is framed by two key international instruments: the 1972 UNESCO Convention Concerning the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage, which addresses *tangible* heritage (such as monuments, sites, artifacts); and the 2003 UNESCO Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage, which recognises *intangible* forms such as oral traditions, performing arts, rituals, and traditional craftsmanship. As discussed further in Chapter 5, these conventions offer a useful framework for understanding how both tangible and intangible dimensions of Amazigh heritage are preserved, practised, and politicised across different regions of Algeria.

2.2.1. Material culture (tangible culture)

Scholars in material history have defined material culture as a purposely human-made segment that includes simple and complicated artefacts, governed by cultural norms, resulting in actions such as manufacturing, using, and producing (Clellan, 1937; Deetz, 1977; Schlereth, 1985).

These artefacts objectively mirror a perspective for practice and order versioned by a society from which beliefs, attitudes, and values can be interpreted (Bronner, 1985; Marshall, 1981). The realm of the artefacts that encompasses people is found in an array of objects, goods, roads, furniture, architecture, monuments, buildings, and even technical materials such as computers, phones, and machines of all sorts. It also consists of the use, consumption, invention, and commerce of the physical objects, as well as the norms and rules that they create or engage in (Aronin, 2018).

According to a recent definition, material culture is the study of objects, their meaning, utilisation, their connection to heterogeneous systems, and the link between individuals, materials, and routines (Lawn and Grosvenor, 2005). In his work, Gabryś-Barker (2014) presents an example illustrated in Portuguese sugar bags, a mundane material object but noteworthy in the Portuguese culture, traditions, and historical events. He emphasises the significant part of Portuguese life and their coffee-drinking habit, which is such a ubiquitous item. Artefacts are cultural tools that point out the way communities exist, thrive, and develop, and express the group choice through which values, attitudes and beliefs are implanted in a certain culture. Thus, when using or acquiring other people's material culture, we are sharing their culture and making assumptions about them and the group they fit in (Scollon et al., 2012).

The importance of the material side of any culture is demonstrated in many aspects, such as language. Scollon et al. (2012) think that artefacts come in 'sets' and they strengthen and

complement other instruments. Since material culture and language are sets of culture, they fortify each other. In his investigation, Hornsby (2014) sheds light on minorities' languages. He states that the latest generation of speakers expels the minority language, even in the very material culture. For example, Gaelic speakers in Scotland, Hornsby asserts, that the language thrives "authentically" only in a "certain milieu".

As a conclusion, the true meaning of culture is concealed in its material form. Materials guide researchers to which culture they take part in, and introduce them to its traditions, views, and mindsets (Aronin, 2018).

2.2.2. Non-material culture (Intangible culture)

Non-material culture is the intangible resources created through the history of nations, such as religion, science, living customs and traditions, laws and regulations, and historical memories (Throsby, 2001). Unlike the material form of culture these elements cannot be measured or seen, these assets can only be fathom and appreciated, for the fact that they are proofs of power, spirituality, and life (Nemati, 2012). Those cultural attributes are demonstrated in many ways. From an abundance of concepts that define non-material culture, the subsequent four manifestations contain the notion accurately: symbols, values, rituals, and heroes (Hofstede et al., 2010). Hofstede (2010) illustrates the conceptualisation of those manifestations as an onion (see Figure 2 below) where he indicates that symbols are the superficiality of culture, values are the profound of the term, whereas rituals and heroes are in between.

Figure 2.2: Cultural manifestation of onion

Source: Hofstede, Hofstede and Minkov. (2010).

We acquire values from an early age. Our physiology equips us with an absorbing period which is the childhood period, in which we unconsciously get basic clues from and about our entourage and surroundings, including symbols (as language), heroes (as parents), and rituals (such as eating training), and, more importantly, it includes our vital values. Eventually, when this period passes, we start consciously and differently learning about new practices (Hofstede et al., 2010). Each of these will be explained in turn.

Values

The thought of basic human values, and how we measure them, has been an intriguing idea from the times of Allport, Vernon and Lindzey in 1931 to the present day. Revealing those values, and discovering ways of surveying them, will provide important acumen of cultural differences and ease the coexistence among others (Hills, 2002).

Cultural values are the implied or elucidated common ideas, thoughts, and views, with arrows each have a plus and a minus, such as evil vs good, dangerous vs safe, ugly vs beautiful, rational vs irrational, moral vs immoral, right vs wrong and so on. These attributes are unique to an individual or peculiar and particular to a group (Kluckhohn, 1951; William, 1970; Hofstede, 2001).

According to Hofstede (2010), some of our values are unconscious because we acquire them at a very young age; therefore, they cannot be explained nor directly noticed, and if we ask anyone why they act in a certain way under certain situations, their answer will be based on a feeling that their conscious provided. When saying values are implicit, we mean they exist in our minds' invisible software. Roughly all our other mental outlooks as beliefs, behaviours, emotions, motives and so on bear a value in them (Kluckhohn, 1951).

Florence Kluckhohn and Fred Strodtbeck (1961) came up with values orientation theory, in which they proposed five main problems to be fixed. These problems manifest in considering the complexities of human existence, and several fundamental questions arise. First, should our focus be on the past, present, or future? Each time facet offers unique insights and lessons but understanding where to concentrate can shape our worldview and actions. Second, in our interactions with the environment, do humans position themselves as masters over nature, act submissively in response to natural forces, or strive for a harmonious relationship? Third, how do humans relate to one another? Are people seen as equals, judged by individual qualities, or organised hierarchically? Fourth, what drives human behaviour — what underlying motives

compel us to act as we do? Lastly, is human nature inherently good, bad, or a mix of both? Determining the essence of human nature involves exploring these facets and understanding the core of what makes us human.

As an example, for the above-mentioned theory, we find that norms are moulded by cultural values. In Japan group harmony is a basic value in the society, litigations and lawsuits are rare because Japanese individuals tend to solve problems amicably even when quarrels happen, otherwise, they will be treated as a non-ideal citizen (Upham, 1976; Schneider and Silverman, 2010).

Rokeach (1979) indicated that humans hold no more than 36 values, which he believed were perhaps universal. He exemplified his claim by stating that notions such as honesty and courage, peace, and wisdom are perceived in all human cultures. However, Kluckhohn and Strodtbeck's values theory stand to be universally used (Hills, 2002).

Rituals

The idea of ritual primarily appeared in the nineteenth century as a precise term for analysis to recognise what was assumed to be a global division of human legacy. Accordingly, the notion signified the start of a massive alliteration in the way European culture contrasted itself with a different culture. From that point forward, numerous different meanings of custom have been created connected to an ample assortment of academic undertakings (Bell, 1992).

Psychiatrists have used the term "ritual" has been used in a manner closely related to, and at times interchangeable with, the concept of "ceremony," a notion initially introduced in Freud's writings on rituals (1907). Freud's work is regarded as a significant contribution to the exploration and understanding of rituals as a subject of study. In which he favoured the German word *Zeremoniell*, which means ceremonial; in this manner, he emphasised the sacred character of these practices, and various common, repeated but still adjusting interactions among individuals (Erikson, 1966).

Anthropologically and sociologically, the terms "ritual" and "ceremony" encompass a wide range of communal events, not limited to religious contexts. Leach (1968) emphasises that the concept of ritual can be interpreted in numerous ways, reflecting its broad and diverse applications. Similarly, Zuesse (1987) highlights the challenges in defining "ritual," noting that few terms within the study of religion have been as complex to conceptualise or apply. This

underscores the intricate and multifaceted nature of rituals in both scholarly investigation and practical contexts.

Bell (1992) states that religion, society, and culture are comprised of rituals that are considered and viewed as authoritative attributes of the different cycles of life. She claims that ritual is represented as especially a spontaneous act that emerged from routine, habits, obsession, or mimesis, subsequently emphasising straightforward formal, supplementary, and tangible interpretations of previously rational ideas and theories about ritual that are completely installed in larger dialogues. Regardless of whether the ritual is portrayed as a wide phenomenon or barely a practised hypothetical build, the idea of ritual both demonstrates and promotes the dialogue within which it is elaborated. Furthermore, Bell (1997) describes six features that rituals display to varying degrees. She also states clearly that the features below are not restricted to religion. These features are explained in turns: first, formalism, which is the formal use of codes of discourse and activity that individuals use daily; secondly, traditionalism is the application of "archaic"¹ or "anachronistic"² elements; thirdly, invariance, which is the employment of rigid, or repeated, models; fourth, is rule-governance, which is the supervision of rigorous rules that control appropriate conducts; fifth, Sacral symbolism involves the incorporation of sacred elements, while performance refers to the engagement in public spectacles or displays

Rappaport (2004) agrees that ritual is the denotation of invariable arrays of proper acts, expressions and their performance that is not utterly ciphered by the performers. Furthermore, he argues that his definition embodies much more than religious attitude and that the use of the concept is not limited to the human experience.

A recent definition of the concept explains that rituals are a selection of acts that are surplus to attain wanted ends on the technical side, but that within culture and society are viewed as fundamental. Such as societal and religious ceremonies, the way we salute others, pay respect and congratulate. It is also the case with political meetings that often perform ritual aims although it was arranged for reasonable intentions, such as focusing on group cohesion and affirming the leadership of the chair (Hofstede et al., 2010).

¹ Pertaining to a period from ancient history.

² The condition of being historically or chronologically misplaced.

Heroes

Since early times, heroes were used to provide explanations such as how humans discovered agriculture and ironmaking and other crafts, how main social, religious, and educational institutions were created, such as marriage, hierarchical systems, monarchies, shrines, and schools. Societies tend to cherish heroes and believe that they live among them spiritually as prophets or priests; these heroes become the theme of many rituals and religious events. In some African cultures, it is believed that the dead heroes always come back as spirits of guardians and protectors of their people (Jones, 2005).

Hofstede (2010) defined heroes are people, alive or dead, exciting, or factional, who have qualities that are profoundly valued in a culture and this manner fill in as models for conduct. Nowadays, and because of the mass media, the concept of a hero depends enormously on appearance and looks. According to him, all humans make their heroes, whether idolising their parents, older kin, siblings by seeing them as heroes and imitating them, or looking up to fictional characters such as Barbie, Batman and Snoopy in the United States, Asterix in France, or Ollie B. Bommel (Mr Bumble) in the Netherlands. Unlike Hofstede's definition, some scholars consider a hero as a mythological character, above man and under a god. Myth and the hero are crucial elements in popular culture. Heroes are manufacturers, with their remarkable achievements independent of their advantages, devoted to forming nations, communities, and cultures. Popular culture and its hero traditions are portrayals that rationally intersect, since both work simultaneously, one supplementing the other. The hero representation in the popular culture is more global than local, worldwide than narrow, shared than individual and meaningful than strict (Fishwick, 1975; Karki, 2016).

Symbols

According to Geertz (1973: 91), symbols are "any object, act, event, quality or relation which serves as a vehicle for a conception; the conception being the symbol's meaning". The conception conjures the vehicle or vice versa. In his quote, Geertz sees the conception as ideas, feelings, values, which are imported by the vehicle of the image or word or sound. He argues that a symbol is a model of behaviour and for life, because various items can be used as symbols and symbols can be utilised in various forms.

In the same vein, Wilhelm and White (1974) state that the essence of a symbol is inferred from and dictated by the individuals who use it, which means it is offered by human life forms upon

material things or occurrences that immediately become symbols. Moreover, the significance of a symbol cannot be found by a bare tactile assessment of its tangible appearance, even though its physical form is what allows it to be recorded in our experiences. Wilhelm and White also explain their definition by providing the following illustrations: no one can confirm the symbolic value of the phonetic sound "si" by hearing only, nor can anyone know the meaning of colour frequencies and what does it stand for (courage, cowardice, stop, go) because we perceive the true meaning of symbols by the intangible.

On another note, Nabofa (1994) considers symbols to be an unconcealed aspect of what is behind the direct notion. It is very common for a spectator to communicate his internal experience, display, religious beliefs, or conceptions by symbols. It should be recognised that a symbol is an utterance, and the utterance can be either written or spoken. Mythology, proverbs, and other cultural attributes have abiding symbols that still exist. Furthermore, Otite (1997) states that symbols are instruments, which are full of information and with propositions to adjust and enforce. At the point when decoded in context, either cultural or social, symbols are noticed to be based on implications of emotions and cognition. A symbol is a thought, a sign, a ritual, or an attitude design that remains as an external portrayal of an inward embodiment or unconscious experience.

Hofstede (2010) defines symbols as words, signs, photos, or items that convey a specific implication that is perceived merely by the individuals who share the same culture. In some cases, the symbols of one group are often imitated by other groups. Since they are globally used, the culture of symbols is evolving, where new symbols take the place of the old ones that vanish. While Udechukwu (2019) identified eight sorts of symbols, which any culture consists of; these sorts are animal symbols, ritual symbols, number symbols, royal symbols, ancestral symbols, cultural symbols, diagrammatical symbols, and gestural symbols.

Symbols are polysemantic attributes, which vary from their sensible form and can invoke thoughts in a complicated realism, including the entire human experience by being the apparent interpretation of culture, identity, and its religious and social behaviour (Womack, 2005). Symbols are the religion, art, literature and cultural expressions, language; they affect all human life, by being profoundly related to the socio-cultural context that created them.

Practices

Practices are shared ideas of how individuals regularly conduct in a culture, how do they behave and why do they behave in a certain manner (Frese, 2015). In Hofstede's point of view (2010), practices are driven by values, it is clearly stated in his works and the previous chart that practices are the visible aspect of non-material culture. The basis for cultural practices is formed by the other aspects the most important values.

To grasp the concept and the true meaning of cultural practices, societies adopt the idea of the expressive norm and shared behaviours (Shteynberg et al., 2009; Stephan and Uhlaner, 2010). The field of norms is very evolved in social studies. norms explain the way individuals think (common reality) and the manner they act, and they govern people's behaviours and attitudes (Shteynberg et al., 2009). Thus, they are linked to cultural practices based on the concept (Chiu et al., 2010). Learning of practices is frequently implied because practices are ordinarily construed from behaviour and standardising tension on behaviour prompts habitual activities; consequently, people are not generally mindful of norms (Johnson et al., 2006; Myers and Davids, 1993). Accordingly, the influence of practices may be more implicit than adjustments to value systems (Kahneman, 2003). Frese (2015) supports this view, asserting that norms emerge as both contributions to and outcomes of the progression of practices. Norms necessitate specific behaviours and attitudes, which, once consistently repeated and adopted as social routines, evolve into established practices. Thus, norms and practices are inherently interconnected, each reinforcing the other.

Cultural practices reflect qualities and convictions held by individuals from society for periods regularly spreading over time. Each social gathering on the planet has explicit customary social practices and convictions (Maluleke, 2012)

2.3. Cultural Imperialism

Cultural imperialism is defined as all the procedures that make a society part of the new world system and the controlling layers to make societies lured or sometimes coerced or even bought for the sake of changing social institutions or even supporting the supreme nexus of the system (Schiller, 1976). On the other side, Amin (1997) points that what he calls "a system of capitalists" administrating "intensified communications" aspires to be a "liberating or democratizing factor", but stress that the "observer who does not see Western life daily is always struck by the incredible brainwashing of the dominant media" (Amin, 1997: 17). Moreover, he

declares that any substance is different from a society to another due to the differences in the society itself and the problem that society is facing (Amin, 1997).

The cultural imperialism theory first appeared in the 70s, as a controversial matter amongst academics (Thussu, 2000; Christophers, 2007). Cultural imperialism theory gained traction as a result of cultural vandalism and damage, especially in countries of the third world, which was caused by the system's maltreatment. On the opposite side, some scholars back then claimed that, according to many factors, the theory was no longer applicable (Nelwan, 2012).

For example, Amazigh women in Algeria have skilfully leveraged globalisation's influence to promote their cultural heritage through social media. Their resilience and adaptability have enabled them to create and maintain spaces for cultural expression, preserving traditions in a manner that resonates with modern audiences (Pratt, 2015).

2.3.1. Cultural imperialism in Africa

Several studies underscore that globalisation entered Africa primarily through the mechanisms of slavery and colonialism, resulting in significant human and resource losses across the continent (Rodney, 1981; Emeagwali, 2004). Omekwu (2003) describes globalisation as a vehicle for cultural transmission across generations, with the influence of digital and information technology amplifying this process. This shift has positioned nations with advanced technological resources as dominant in cultural dissemination, often casting Africa in the role of a passive recipient (Ezema, 2010).

Globalisation's influence on cultural patterns presents both positive and negative dimensions, with the latter often impacting socioeconomically disadvantaged communities (Taptiani et al., 2024). This dual effect poses challenges for local cultures in preserving traditional values, practices, and customs (Liétor and Iñiguez, 2022). Negative impacts are observable in the gradual loss of local languages and traditions and the commoditization of culture, whereby cultural practices are commercialised, and foreign cultures are dominating. These processes can erode local identities and heritage, weakening young generations' connection to their cultural roots (Taptiani et al., 2024). Moreover, the influence of technology on socio-cultural dynamics is profound; as traditional norms and customs become less central, shifts in the cultural identity of ethnic groups occur (Tasruddin et al., 2022).

Despite these pressures, ethnic communities have adopted aspects of modernity to support the preservation of their cultural traditions. Mass media and information technology have become

tools for showcasing and celebrating local cultures, fostering a sense of cultural pride among the youth (Caropeboka et al., 2022). These platforms allow communities to innovate and safeguard indigenous knowledge, enabling locals to present their culture through community media, thereby creating spaces for the display of traditional skills and practices alongside modern media tools (Prasetyo Jati, 2022).

Ezema (2010) further elaborates on cultural imperialism, which can occur either as a forceful imposition of external culture or as a gradual, voluntary assimilation of foreign cultural norms. This influence has impacted African nations significantly, particularly in the economic sphere, where foreign-led privatization initiatives have transformed public services such as education, making them inaccessible to many due to prohibitive costs (Ya'u, 2004).

The impact of cultural imperialism on Africa has been profound, reshaping foundational elements of indigenous identity, including education, traditions, and languages. Colonial policies that imposed foreign cultures, languages, and values on African societies have led to cultural erosion (Wahab et al., 2012). For instance, the French colonial presence in parts of Africa promoted French language and norms, often deprioritising local languages, customs, and knowledge systems in favour of French culture.

In countries like the Democratic Republic of Congo and Senegal, French remains the official language despite the recognition of indigenous languages (Skattum, 2008). This ongoing use of the coloniser's language as the primary medium for political, educational, and social discourse underscores the lasting imprint of cultural imperialism, even post-independence. However, efforts to protect and promote local languages in countries such as the Democratic Republic of Congo, Malawi, Senegal, and South Africa represent an important resistance to cultural erosion, asserting the value of indigenous identity alongside the legacy of French influence (El Aissati, 2005).

North African countries exemplify resilience against cultural imperialism in the post-colonial era. In Algeria, for instance, the government emphasised an Arab identity in its national strategy, although French continued to be widely used. Algeria's constitution refrains from officially recognising French (Naylor, 2024), reflecting a partial rejection of colonial influence. Nonetheless, the distinct Amazigh identity was marginalised post-independence as part of a national unity strategy through Arabization policies. This marginalisation prompted the emergence of Amazigh movements advocating for linguistic rights and cultural recognition, asserting the integral role of Amazigh heritage within Algeria's national identity (Nanis, 2024).

The Berber Spring became a turning point in the Amazigh cultural resurgence, representing a broader political and social struggle to preserve Amazigh culture (Maddy-Weitzman, 2018). This movement opposed both the legacy of colonial assimilation and the state's Arabization policies, advocating for cultural diversity, and resisting the homogenizing forces that characterised both the colonial and post-colonial eras in Algeria. The movement emphasised the importance of recognising cultural plurality as essential to the nation's identity, establishing a legacy of resistance against external and internal forces of cultural dominance (Maddy-Weitzman, 2018).

2.4. Cultural Relativism

Boas (1887: 589) was the first to announce the notion of cultural relativism; he stated that "civilisation is not something absolute, but ... is relative, and ... our ideas and conceptions are true only so far as our civilisation goes". Since that time, relativism has been a debated topic in many domains. Explaining cultural relativism had to do with realism, which is the thought that the mind is the centre of all that is true and real. Therefore, linking realism to relativism indicates a reality beyond one's thoughts and beliefs (Marshall et al., 1994). So, cultural relativism is associated with respect and acceptance of others' differences, which relates to the critical context of culture and the understanding of values, beliefs, and practices of other people.

The world is full of cultures, and each culture relates its reality to a set of customs, beliefs, and practices. For example, Germany cancelled death penalty sentences, unlike the Chinese government; burial or cremation are the only ways to pay respect to a body in many countries, whereas in Tibet, it is thrown to vultures to eat it; polygamy is legal in all Arab countries but not in European ones. Cultural relativism states that "moral agents' behaviour" is determined based on what a culture accepts, that is to say, something is moral if it is accepted by a culture, and it is immoral if it is denied by a culture (Park, 2011). Hence, cultural acceptance is what makes a conduct righteous or not. Then, cultural relativism is a dogma or a moral code of societies for determining the nature of actions in that certain society (Schick and Vaughn, 2010; Rachels and Rachels, 2010).

From an opposed view, Pojman (2008) argues that since relativism holds that all actions with cultural approval are right, how can we measure the nature of the hideous crimes done by a serial killer? He furthermore states that although his actions are approved by a group of other serial killers, that does not make those crimes right or moral.

2.5. Ethnocentrism

Gumplowicz (1881) drew a comparison between ethnocentrism and concepts like egocentrism and anthropocentrism, highlighting how ethnic groups often regard themselves as superior to others. Sumner (1906) extended this view, describing ethnocentrism as an "egocentrism within an ethnic group," where each group sees itself as the central reference point, evaluating all other groups to itself. This internal cohesion and collective pride foster a sense of superiority that can manifest as self-centeredness toward outsiders. Herskovits (1972: 21) further describes ethnocentrism as the belief that one's way of life is preferable to any other, an outlook that stems from early enculturation. This inherent bias, whether explicitly expressed or not, can lead to prejudices, misjudgements, and ultimately, social conflict.

These theories provide insight into the complexities of cultural preservation and identity formation in countries with cultural minorities, highlighting the challenges these communities face in maintaining their traditions, languages, and practices while navigating dominant cultural narratives and systemic pressures for assimilation (Nayar, 2009).

2.6. Hofstede Cultural Dimensions

This section discusses Hofstede cultural dimensions, namely, power distance index, individualism vs collectivism, masculinity vs femininity, uncertainty avoidance index, long vs short orientation and indulgence vs restraint.

As reported by several scholars, the functionality of the notion of culture is to clarify differences and it relies upon having the option to unload it and recognise its elements because "Culture is too global a concept to be meaningful as an explanatory variable, however, and should be replaced by its constituents" (Van de Vijver and Leung, 1997: 3). That is to say, various factors ought not to be credited to differences in culture except if attributes of culture have been distinguished (Samiee and Jeong, 1994). Culture is a complex system that needs to be interpreted (Van Peurson, 1974); this complexity guides us to seek culture's dimensions. Using some cultural dimensions to find similarities and differences between cultures has a background in anthropology.

Some authors believe that diversity in culture is a result of distinctive answers to questions posed mainly to the same questions in different societies and under various circumstances. "As the existence of two sexes; the helplessness of infants; the need for satisfaction of the elementary

biological requirements such as food, warmth, and sex; the presence of individuals of different ages, appearances and other capacities" (Kluckhohn, 1962: 317-318).

Several attempts were made in the twentieth century to introduce cultural dimensions as a way of gathering differences and similarities in cultures. One of the earliest attempts was made by the sociologists Parsons and Shils (1951), who advised that five variables determine human behaviours. The first variable is affectivity (as in expressing emotion) versus affective neutrality (as in self-discipline); then is self-orientation versus collective-orientation, which deals with where is the attention focused; next is universalism (universal standards) versus particularism (bearing relationships in mind); follow by ascription (judging by identity) versus achievement (judging by actions); and finally, specificity (narrowing relations to certain domains) versus diffuseness (no previous limitations to relations). Parsons and Shils (1951) defended that these variables are found at the personal level, at the social level, and at the cultural level. Hofstede (2011), on the other hand, asserts that they did not consider that different factors could serve at different levels.

Another field study was done by Kluckhohn and Strodtbeck (1961) in which they recognised the following value orientations (previously mentioned) as human nature: the relationship between man and the natural environment, time adjustment, activity orientation, and the relationships among people. In his view, Hofstede (2011) also argues the efficacy of such a model by stating that it lacks some aspects as geographical limitations and missing empirical proofs.

One of the globally recognised and credited models that, according to Hofstede (2011), was empirically proven is Inkeles and Levinson (1969), through which they summed up sociological and anthropological studies concerning culture at the national level, interpreting "national character" as a model dealing with "personality type in a national society". What Hofstede named as dimensions; they labelled as standard analytic issues. From their literature review, they extracted three standard analytic issues, which are: relation to authority, the conception of self (including masculinity and femininity as concepts), and primary conflicts (how to deal with them).

Douglas (1973) suggested a two-dimensional model of seeing cultures. The first one is a group, including groups rather than individuals; the second one is a grid, to what degree rules control interactions. She believed that this model is related to cultural beliefs and social schemes as cookery, medicine, travelling, and history. Hofstede (2011) objects to her one-dimensional model, stating that it is overlapping but requires more explanation on the analytical and methodological level. In another research, Hall (1976) saw that culture should be divided based

on communication ways or what he called high and low context, in which the information was either explicit or implicit.

Although many scholars attempt to present the most appropriate dimension for culture, Hofstede's framework is the most widely used not only in one domain, but it is found in psychology, sociology, marketing, and management studies (Sondergaard, 1994; Steenkamp, 2001). In his study, Hofstede examined over 60,000 participants in 70 countries using 116,000 questions (Hofstede, 1988, 1991, 2001). He managed to identify five dimensions designated to ratios on each of the nations included in his study and to relate those dimensions to demographic, geographic, economic, and political aspects of a society. This was an incomparable character in his framework (Kale and Barnes, 1992). According to Smith et al. (1996), his model is inclusive, complete, and potent. Later in the 80s, Bond suggested a fifth dimension named "short vs long term orientation" to Hofstede's study (Hofstede and Bond, 1988). After two decades, Minkov collaborated with Hofstede and brought an additional sixth dimension labelled "indulgence vs restraint" (Hofstede et al., 2010). Hofstede's cultural dimensions will be used in this study, and each dimension in his model will be explored next in turn.

2.6.1 Individualism vs collectivism

Individualism reflects a mindset that prioritises the individual, valuing personal achievements and encouraging independent thought and behaviour (Arasaratnam, 2011). In highly individualistic cultures, the emphasis is on "self-concept," contrasting with collectivist societies, where social norms emphasise the importance of the group over the individual (Chen and Starosta, 2005: 51). Collectivist cultures integrate individuals from birth into cohesive social units, such as extended families or tightly knit communities, providing a strong sense of belonging and mutual support (Hofstede, 2011). In contrast, individualistic societies promote self-reliance, expecting each person to be responsible for their welfare. According to data from the Hofstede Centre, the United States ranks as one of the most individualistic societies, while Egypt scores among the lowest, illustrating stark cultural differences in how family and group importance are perceived (Agodzo, 2013).

In the context of this investigation on the Amazigh community, the collectivist nature of their society has a significant role in the preservation and transmission of cultural heritage (Wang, 2008). Amazigh culture places a high value on community cohesion, where traditions, values, and practices are passed down through generations within family and community structures. This collective approach to cultural preservation stands in contrast to the individualistic tendencies

observed in more Westernised contexts, which can challenge traditional community values (Brewer and Chen, 2007). Amazigh women, in particular, have a vital role in sustaining this collectivist culture, often acting as custodians of language, rituals, and customs that solidify group identity. Their collective efforts are not just acts of cultural preservation but also forms of resistance against the broader forces of individualism that accompany globalisation. Through creating a sense of community over individual gain, Amazigh women reinforce cultural resilience and contribute to a sense of shared identity that is essential to the continuity of Amazigh heritage in Algeria (Laghssais and Comins-Mingol, 2023).

2.6.2. Uncertainty avoidance

Uncertainty avoidance measures a culture's tolerance for ambiguity and unpredictability, examining the extent to which uncertainty provokes discomfort or threat (Hofstede, 1991; Chen and Starosta, 2005). Hofstede (2011) posits that in high uncertainty-avoidance cultures, individuals are conditioned to feel insecure in situations that lack structure or involve unexpected changes. Such cultures are typically characterised by rigid behavioural codes and laws, exhibiting low tolerance for deviation from established norms or unconventional views. Arasaratnam (2011) further elaborates that high uncertainty avoidance often aligns with traditional societies that prefer stable, established routines over change and innovation. For instance, Mexico's high uncertainty avoidance score, in contrast to that of the United States, indicates a cultural preference for stability and structured social norms (The Hofstede Centre, 2012; Agodzo, 2014).

In the context of this research on the Amazigh community, high uncertainty avoidance sheds light on the community's approach to preserving cultural norms and practices amidst external pressures, such as globalisation and modernisation (Stephan and Pathak, 2016). Traditional Amazigh communities, like other high uncertainty-avoidant cultures, often uphold strict adherence to established practices, valuing continuity and stability as key aspects of cultural resilience. Amazigh women play a pivotal role in maintaining these cultural norms, reinforcing structured practices, and guiding younger generations in ways that respect long-standing traditions. This cultural tendency aligns with the Amazigh community's emphasis on social cohesion and collective identity, elements that provide stability in uncertain social or political climates. Through their cultural practices, Amazigh women embody a collective commitment to safeguarding heritage, thus resisting the destabilising forces of cultural erosion and change.

2.6.3. Power distance index

According to Chen and Starosta (2005), the concept of power distance reflects the extent to which cultural adaptations address systemic injustices embedded in power distributions within relationships and institutional frameworks. It encompasses how societies navigate and respond to the consequences of power imbalances, including abuses in family, social, and managerial contexts (Soares et al., 2007). Hofstede's cultural dimensions study, which introduced the concept of power distance, identifies a fundamental gap that varies based on age, gender, status, and other hierarchical differences. This divide results in cultures that can be broadly classified as high or low power distance societies (Chen and Starosta, 2005). In high power distance societies, authority, rank, and social status hold immense value, often shaping individuals' interactions and expectations within both public and private spheres (Dainton and Zelle, 2019). In such settings, hierarchical structures are not merely tolerated but are often actively endorsed by both leaders and followers (Hofstede, 2011).

Hofstede's work underscores that power and inequality are inescapable elements of societal organisation, and that all societies exhibit forms of imbalance. However, these inequalities vary significantly in intensity in different societies. For example, studies comparing the power distance scores of Ghana and the United States indicate that Ghana scores higher than the U.S., suggesting that social rank and hierarchy play a more prominent role in Ghanaian society (Agodzo, 2014). This heightened emphasis on status in Ghana implies that relationships in Ghanaian communities and organisations are more likely to be defined by respect for rank and authority, in contrast to the more egalitarian tendencies of U.S. culture.

In this research on the dynamics of Amazigh communities, the effects of power distance are evident in both family structures and broader community interactions. Similar to high power distance societies, certain Algerian communities, particularly within Amazigh culture, exhibit a deep-rooted respect for elders and traditional authority figures (Charrad, 2001). This respect for hierarchy not only dictates family relationships but also influences cultural transmission processes. For instance, the role of elder women in preserving and transmitting cultural practices reflects a structured respect for age and experience, which reinforces traditional values within the community. Here, power distance manifests not merely in the form of control but also as a mechanism for cultural preservation, with authority figures acting as custodians of heritage

(Silverman, 2010). This research will explore the power dynamics of Amazigh communities and the effects of power distance on cultural preservation. Additionally, the study will look at how the power distance in communities intersect with gender norms, which will further shape how cultural knowledge and responsibilities are distributed.

2.6.4. Femininity vs masculinity

Adapting Hofstede's masculinity-femininity dimension on a societal scale, rather than an individual one, reveals that gender-based value distinctions hold significant implications across communities. Hofstede's study (2011) suggests that values traditionally associated with men, such as competitiveness, achievement, and success, contrast with values often linked to women, which are more nurturing, supportive, and empathetic. He characterises these contrasting sets of values as "masculinity" and "femininity," noting that in feminine cultures, both men and women may embrace caring and cooperative values, blurring rigid distinctions. However, in masculine cultures, the competitive and assertive values are dominant, yet they often create a perceived divide between men's and women's roles and values, where ambition and competition are seen as masculine and sensitivity and care as feminine (Hofstede et al., 1998).

Chen and Starosta (2005) further interpret this dimension as a gauge of stereotypical gender norms, measuring the extent to which masculine or feminine characteristics are emphasised in each society. In masculine cultures, men are typically encouraged to pursue ambition and competitiveness, while women often embody values of support, care, and duty, underscoring a clear delineation between roles (Dainton and Zelle, 2011). This separation is culturally ingrained and shapes both societal expectations and interpersonal dynamics. Hofstede's model identifies Japan, Australia, Venezuela, and the U.K. as examples of masculine societies, while Sweden, Norway, Denmark, Portugal, and Thailand exemplify feminine societies (Chen and Starosta, 2005).

In the context of this research, this dimension offers a useful lens to examine gender role expectations within Amazigh communities. This gender role of masculinity and femininity are important in this study, both masculine and feminine values coexist, yet they are nuanced by cultural traditions and expectations (Srite and Karahanna, 2006). For example, while women may embody the nurturing qualities characteristic of feminine cultures, their roles often extend beyond stereotypical bounds. In Amazigh society, women are keepers of cultural practices, actively contributing to the preservation of heritage and the transmission of cultural knowledge. This responsibility places them in a unique position where they simultaneously fulfil nurturing roles

within the family and authoritative roles within the community. The blending of these values reveals that, within Amazigh culture, gender roles are both defined and expanded, allowing women to embody values associated with both masculinity and femininity (Becker, 2006).

Moreover, the coexistence of these roles reflects a cultural fluidity in gender values, suggesting that while traditional gender roles may exist, they are adaptable and subject to change based on cultural needs (McRobbie, 2008). This interplay of masculinity and femininity supports a more dynamic understanding of gender in Amazigh culture, where community contributions and cultural responsibilities often transcend rigid gender distinctions. Through this framework, my research reveals that gendered values within the Amazigh community are multifaceted, underscoring both the nurturing and assertive roles that women hold, thereby contributing to a richer, more balanced social structure.

2.6.5. Long-term vs. short-term orientation

Hofstede's (2011) concept of long-term versus short-term orientation offers a speciality-relevant insightful lens for this research through which to examine cultural values and their influence on behaviours and attitudes in diverse societies. This dimension, identified as Confucian work dynamism by Harris Bond (1991), differentiates between cultures that emphasise perseverance, thrift, and respect for hierarchical relationships (long-term orientation) and those that prioritise values like respect for tradition, universal ethics, and social obligations (short-term orientation).

This distinction is relevant to understanding cultural dynamics within the communities investigated, especially regarding how traditional and future-focused values shape individual and group identities. For example, in long-term oriented societies such as China, Japan, and Germany (Agodzo, 2014), there is a focus on sustaining social structures over time, which may parallel certain traditional values within the cultural groups in this study. Conversely, the influence of short-term orientation, more prevalent in societies emphasising personal stability and respect for tradition, aligns with the tendencies in some communities to prioritise immediate social obligations and customary practices. This dual perspective is essential in exploring how cultural groups balance inherited traditions with evolving socio-cultural influences; a balance that profoundly impacts the preservation and adaptation of cultural heritage within a globalised context. Through the lens of Hofstede's dimension, this research can better analyse how cultural orientations inform the approaches to tradition and change within the communities in question,

specifically considering the implications for cultural continuity and transformation in the face of both internal values and external pressures.

2.6.6. Indulgence versus restraint

Hofstede's sixth cultural dimension, indulgence versus restraint, serves as a measure of a society's orientation toward happiness, freedom, and the fulfilment of basic human desires. Indulgent cultures encourage individuals to express and pursue enjoyment, valuing personal happiness, freedom, and a more spontaneous lifestyle (Xu and Schwarz, 2009). This dimension aligns closely with societal norms that promote self-expression, leisure, and an open attitude toward pleasure. In contrast, restrained cultures uphold strict social norms and laws, often emphasising self-discipline, duty, and a controlled approach to fulfilling desires (Baumeister and Juola Exline, 1999). Here, happiness is not necessarily pursued openly, as societal expectations prioritise order and restraint.

The distinction between indulgent and restrained societies is reflected in contrasting examples, such as the United States, which scores high in indulgence and thus promotes individual happiness and self-gratification, and China, where restraint is more valued, and social behaviours tend to follow structured regulations and established norms (Agodzo, 2011). These cultural orientations impact various aspects of life, from family structure to education and social practices, influencing how individuals in these societies perceive and pursue personal happiness.

In the context of this research, this dimension provides a useful framework for understanding how cultural attitudes towards indulgence and restraint affect the transmission and preservation of intangible cultural heritage. For instance, in societies with high restraint, traditional cultural practices may be maintained with greater strictness and continuity, as there is a societal emphasis on adherence to established norms (Cohen, 2001). This could be particularly relevant to communities striving to preserve cultural heritage under pressures of globalisation, as it could be the case in Amazigh communities, as the restrained approach may offer resilience against external influences that encourage rapid change or individual expression. Conversely, in more indulgent societies, cultural heritage might evolve more freely, reflecting an openness to adaptation and change. Thus, Hofstede's indulgence versus restraint dimension illuminates how cultural values surrounding happiness and social regulation influence the sustainability of cultural practices, a critical factor in this study's exploration of cultural identity and heritage within the framework of globalisation.

2.7. A reflection on Hofstede's Model

While Hofstede's cultural dimensions remain one of the most widely applied models in cross-cultural analysis, particularly within management, psychology, and communication studies, the framework has faced increasing critique in recent years. Nevertheless, some scholars have described the model as overly simplistic, potentially biased, and somewhat static (Williamson, 2002). McSweeney and Williamson (2002), for instance, argue that the model neglects key aspects of culture, contending that cultural dynamics are shaped not only by values but also by non-cultural factors such as social structures, economic conditions, and institutional influences. Similarly, Papamarcos et al. (2007) highlight that Hofstede tends to overlook the role of community and how its variations can shape cultural expressions. Bititci (2017) and Taras et al. (2016) have criticised the framework for its limited focus on cultural values. While this focus may offer insights into certain societal lifestyles and habits, it is seen as reductive, failing to account for the complexity and fluidity of lived cultural experiences.

A common thread among these critiques is that Hofstede's model equates culture too closely with nationality, thereby overlooking intercultural diversity, historical evolution, and the nuanced experiences of individuals and communities. This issue is particularly relevant in the Algerian context, where significant ethnic and regional distinctions, such as those between Arab and Amazigh populations, cannot be adequately represented through national cultural averages. As this thesis argues, culture in Algeria is more meaningfully understood through the lens of ethnic identity rather than national identity. This is not to deny the existence of an overarching Algerian culture, but rather to conceptualise it as a composite national identity encompassing the country's diverse ethnic groups.

From a methodological standpoint, recent literature challenges Hofstede's universalist and static definition of culture, suggesting that it reflects a predominantly Western, managerial worldview that may not translate effectively to non-Western or indigenous contexts (McSweeney, 2016; Minkov and Kaasa, 2021). Furthermore, Hofstede's original data were collected solely from IBM employees during the 1960s and 70s, raising concerns about the generalisability of the findings and their applicability to contexts such as rural Amazigh communities, where cultural dynamics have been historically shaped by colonial legacies, marginalisation, and oral heritage traditions.

Within this research, Hofstede's framework has not been adopted as a fixed explanatory model, but rather as a heuristic device to explore contrasts in value orientations. These contrasts serve to illuminate both intergroup (i.e. Arab as opposed to Amazigh) and intragroup (among Kabyle, Chaouia, Mzab, and Tuareg communities) cultural variations. Importantly, the application of the model to the Amazigh context was not treated as an a priori assumption; instead, its relevance emerged inductively from patterns observed in the primary data. These included interview accounts that consistently highlighted values such as collectivism, high uncertainty avoidance, and hierarchical patriarchal family structure, particularly in the experiences of Amazigh women. Other values, such as power index and short-term orientation aspects in the data obtained by cultural policy managers, as discussed in Chapters 6, 7, and 8. The deployment of Hofstede's framework was further supported by a range of scholarly works on Amazigh cultural and political dynamics, including those by Maddy-Weitzman, Sadiqi, and Gagliardi (Chapters 6 and 7), as well as Algerian policy scholars such as Kessab and Boukrouh (Chapter 5). This was complemented by an analysis of UNESCO frameworks and Algerian cultural policy documents. The multi-layered approach taken in this thesis supports its analytical lens and strengthens theoretical triangulation through the integration of interviews, literature, and document analysis, thereby contributing to a more holistic understanding of the research context.

Ultimately, this thesis employs Hofstede's framework, not to impose rigid cultural labels, but to explore how cultural values influence heritage transmission especially through gendered practices. By critically engaging with the model's limitations and complementing it with more flexible and context-sensitive conceptual tools, the study aims to offer a more nuanced and grounded understanding of culture and identity within Algeria.

2.8. Cultural Assimilation

Cultural assimilation refers to the process through which a group or a community is integrated into another dominant one. The characteristics of the dominant group are whether forced or imposed on the local community, and either intentionally or unintentionally applied. (Ballard, 2015). As Konya (2001) argues that this may be a result of a larger culture's ability to provide more opportunities in many domains, such as occupation, education, and services. In contrast, Hong (2021) claims that the assimilation process occurs when individuals and communities lose interest in preserving their heritage and cultural identity to fit into a larger society. Which contradicts the case of the Amazigh in Algeria.

The French policies adopted two methods to implement their “Frenchification” ideology: the soft assimilation applied by Jonnat, a French colonial administrator and politician, who presented a different position towards the Algerian cultural identity. At first, he fostered national and reform movements in Algeria, such as allowing Algerian intellectual elite to return to their homeland, introducing Arabic press in the country, and accepting the rise of Islamic reform movements. His policies aimed to develop the colony within a framework that respected both Arabic-Islamic and French cultural identities, which was implicitly a way of erasing cultural tensions between colonisers and colonised to facilitate the gradual acceptance of French rule and influence in the country (Ladjal and Bensaid, 2012).

The second method was the coercive strategy to achieve the French Algeria objective, when the General Governor Maurice Viollette took control over Algeria and started executing his plans and expanding them beyond accepting the duality of the Algerian French culture. His policies on cultural dominance sought to impose French identity and culture rather than coexistence. Firstly, imposing the French language as the official language in all official transactions, as he believed that Algeria could truly become French if the replacement of Arabic were applied in all domains. This positioning of language and culture as a tool of control and oppression is clear evidence of the cultural assimilation plan in Algeria during colonisation (Maamri, 2009). As this tool would facilitate the shift in fields as education, where Algerian children were schooled in French to integrate them into a French-administered society that would last for generations. Religion was also among the tools used to assimilate the local culture to the imposed one, as the French church encouraged missionary missions to convert Algerians to Christianity. These strategies of implementing the intangible cultural aspects such as language, religion, and traditions from the French culture to assimilate and replace the Algerian culture, aimed at not only governing Algeria but also to embed French identity into the very fabric of Algerian life (Ladjal and Bensaid, 2012).

The French cultural assimilation not only impacted the Arab culture in Algeria, but it also hindered the Amazigh culture. During the French rule, the French authorities perceived the Amazigh of the north of Algeria to be more “European” or “white”, a characterisation that significantly influenced how they were dealt with compared to Arab communities, as they had European “Caucasian” features and traits. On another hand, the French considered Amazigh to be “less Muslim” compared to the Arab communities, which encouraged the colonials to make the Amazigh better candidates for assimilation (Silverstein, 2002).

This misperception led the French to incorporate Amazigh individuals into positions of local power within communities as part of a broader framework to divide and control Algerian society. This distinction resulted in granting more privilege and authority position to the Amazigh as head of tribes. France aimed at creating tension between the Arabs and the Amazigh when they created the preferential relationship with the Amazigh communities, as an approach to weaken Algerian unity by driving a wedge between the Amazigh and Arab populations (Calvet, 2018).

The French colonial ideology to elevate one cultural group over the other created new dynamics between the two communities. While the purpose was to implement the strategy of “divide to conquer”, by dividing Arabs and Amazigh, this policy was ultimately short-lived and ironically worked in the opposite direction, creating greater contact and cultural exchange between them. This Arabo-Amazigh interaction resulted in a blending of Amazigh and Arab cultural identities. Ultimately the two groups developed a sense of unified Algerian identity under French rule. This blend of cultures helped in spreading a collective consciousness, which allowed the Amazigh to advocate for formal cultural recognition later (MacDonald, 2021). By the late nineteenth century, Amazigh communities began resisting French rule, joining Arab communities in organised protests and political movements (Yezza, 2013).

After the second World War, Algerian resistance to French rule increase and intensified, and led to a full-scale War of Independence that began in 1954. The independence war was marked by widespread violence and by thousands of Algerian martyrs. The liberation war demonstrated a unified push by both Arab and Amazigh groups for self-governance and independence, which was finally won in 1962 (El Aissati, 2001: 60).

Despite that the fight for independence did not initially aim for Amazigh cultural recognition, the shared struggle and fight against colonial oppression created a stronger sense of collective identity across Algeria’s diverse communities. The Amazigh and the Arabs fought side by side for the liberation of their country and for a unified independent Algerian state (Yezza, 2013).

The long struggle against French colonialisation contributed to embedding Amazigh culture and identity into the fabric of modern Algeria. This unified identity, however, faced new challenges after independence, as the newly independent Algerian government struggled with how to balance the dynamics of Arab and Amazigh identities in the national identity. Which eventually led to tensions that, over periods, escalated into violence, such as ‘the black Amazigh Spring’ in 1990, as the Amazigh groups navigated questions of identity, representation, and autonomy. Over time, the Algerian government offered reconciliation, leading to increased recognition of Amazigh

heritage within the national context. The outcomes of the independence war serve as a significant factor that partially explains why Amazigh identity, while still contested, is less politicised in Algeria than in neighbouring countries as Morocco, where Amazigh identity has maintained a stronger, more distinct presence (MacDonald, 2021). In Algeria, the shared struggles and experiences of colonial oppression helped in solidifying a unified national identity, allowing the Amazigh to later seek recognition for their cultural heritage within the broader Algerian context. The forced unification under colonial rule, therefore, contributed to the development of a collective identity that would be considered as a foundation for the Amazigh cultural movement in post-colonial Algeria (MacDonald, 2021).

2.9 Conclusion

In conclusion, this chapter has explored the multifaceted concept of culture, tracing its definitions and dimensions through various theoretical and disciplinary lenses. It highlighted the distinctions between material and non-material cultural aspects and their roles in shaping societal behaviours, values, and identities. The discussion of cultural imperialism illuminated the historical and ongoing tensions between dominant and marginalised cultures, with specific emphasis on the Algerian and Amazigh contexts. Theories of cultural relativism and ethnocentrism provided critical frameworks for understanding how cultural practices are judged and preserved within diverse societies, while Hofstede's cultural dimensions offered insights into the dynamics of values, power structures, and gender roles across cultures.

The chapter also dealt with the mechanisms of cultural assimilation, particularly during the French colonial era, and its enduring impact on Algeria's cultural landscape, emphasizing the resilience and resistance of the Amazigh people. Through integrating these perspectives, the chapter discussed the complexities of cultural identity and preservation in a globalised and historically contested environment. This foundation sets the stage for further exploration of how these cultural dynamics intersect with gender, heritage, and modern policy in subsequent chapters.

Chapter Three – Gender Dynamics in Amazigh Intangible Cultural Heritage

This chapter provides essential background on Algeria as a foundational context for understanding the Amazigh communities discussed throughout this study. It begins with an overview of Algeria's geography and ethnic diversity, followed by a brief historical and political account that traces the country's complex cultural evolution. This section discusses the interplay between Amazigh culture, Islam, and Arabization, analysing the challenges posed by linguistic and cultural shifts. Section 3.1 provides a comprehensive overview of Algeria's geographical, historical, linguistic, and political context, emphasising the Amazigh contribution to national identity. Section 3.2 outlines the characteristics of major Amazigh groups in Algeria, including the Chaouia, Kabyle, Mزاب, and Tuareg, exploring their unique cultural attributes and historical courses. Furthermore, it discusses the gendered dimensions of intangible cultural heritage (ICH), emphasising the central role of women in its preservation and transmission. Section 3.4 examines the challenges and opportunities faced by Amazigh communities in post-independence Algeria, from protests like the Berber Spring to contemporary efforts to integrate Tamazight into national frameworks. Finally, the Section examines the modern Amazigh identity and the ongoing struggle to preserve their heritage in a changing socio-political landscape, highlighting the community's resilience and pride in its cultural legacy. Together, these sections highlight the critical role of orality and cultural transmission in sustaining the Amazigh identity across generations.

3.1. Algeria and Amazigh

This section delves into aspects of the Algerian background, specifically culture, history, linguistic affiliation, and political life.

3.1.1. Geography and ethnicity

Algeria is a northern African country bordered by the Mediterranean Sea to the north, Niger, Mali, and Mauritania to the south, Morocco and Western Sahara to the west, and Tunisia and Libya to the east. It is the largest country in Africa and covers a total of 2,381,751 square kilometres (as shown in the map below).

Figure 3.1: Algeria's map

Source: Lichenological exploration of Algeria: Historical overview and annotated bibliography, 1799 – 2013. Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Nine-tenths of the country is composed of the six Saharan provinces, or as they are called locally, Wilayas, in the south of the country. Nevertheless, most of the nation's Wilayas are situated in the northern part, and 90 per cent of the population is settled there alongside the coastal and the hill areas (Brill, 1990). Algerian ethnicities are of mixed ancestry. The Algerians are antecedents of not only Arabic but also Amazigh, in addition to European descendants such as Spanish, French, Turkish and sub-Saharan. The culture in Algeria is a mixture of the different ethnicities of the country. There is a heterogeneity in music, architecture, food, and lifestyle, and some communities remain nomadic, such as the Tuareg and Gnawa³ (Nedjai, 2017).

³ The native inhabitants of North Africa and the Sahara Desert

3.1.2. History and religion

Algeria is the crossroads of four worlds: Mediterranean, Arab, Amazigh, and African. It is a melting pot for many ethnicities and cultures with a rich cultural heritage. Because of its location, the country has known many settlers along its millennia-long history, such as Carthaginians, Romans, and Vandals (Stora, 2004). The region was occupied by the Muslims in the early 8th century AD and freed by the Berber Revolt in 740 from the Islamic caliphate at that time. During the Ottoman period, Algeria became an important state in the Mediterranean Sea with its naval fleet, which led to many conflicts (Soucek, 2013). Those conflicts that eventually led to French colonialism. All these historical events have made the country vibrant with different cultures, dialects, and ethnicities. It is the largest country in Africa, home to 44 million⁴, of whom 99% are Muslims and the remaining 1% is composed of Christians, Jews and others.

3.1.3. Linguistic affiliation

The official language is Arabic, but it differs from the spoken one as a result of the number of ethnicities in the country and the long colonial history. The Algerian dialect is a combination of Arabic, French, Spanish, Amazigh, Turkish, and is influenced by English as well, since it is the global language (Baya Essayahi and Kerras, 2016). Due to colonisation and the influence of television after independence, French became the second language of the country, used by both the population and the state. Madani (1996) explains that television in Algeria has created many job opportunities for foreign production companies, which offer various programmes in French, American or European origin. The presence of the French language in Algeria is a result of 132 years of colonisation, and that should usually disappear with independence (Ibrahimi, 1997). This reality was shaped by the historical context of Algerian society, where a century of French language dominance in various domains, coupled with the coexistence of Arabic and French, significantly influenced linguistic practices. This prolonged exposure resulted in the preservation of the French language and its integration into the Algerian dialect, creating a unique linguistic landscape. (Belfarhi, 2019).

Tamazight, or the language of the Amazigh, is the native language of the country, spoken in the central parts of the Algerian territory, in the Kabylia⁵ in the middle of the country, the Atlas

⁴ <https://www.cia.gov/the-world-factbook/countries/algeria/#people-and-society>

⁵ It refers to the land of the tribes, situated within the Atlas Mountain range and bordering the Mediterranean Sea

Mountains area, and the desert, the Tuareg lands. Arabic remained the nation's first official language until 2002, when Amazigh was recognised as an official language and in 2016, when the state officially declared it in the constitution (Laidani, 2019). To conclude the language debate in Algeria, Maamri (2009) argued that the language spoken in the country is determined by the different national discourses and individuals' positions. For example, if there is a religious discourse, the Arabic language is the most used; if the discourse is purely political or even economic, experts tend to use French.

3.1.4. Political life

Algerian politics has known different stages since the country's independence in 1962 until this very day. Political parties are key actors in the process of democratisation in any country's political agenda. Before 1988, Algeria was a one-party government ruled by the Front de Libération Nationale (FLN)⁶ (Bouandel, 2003). After that, the decision-makers granted citizens the right to a multiparty system, as it seemed back then an important element for opening to the world, and as a tool for their political survival and that of their system (Ghanem-Yazbeck, 2018). This multiparty regime opened the door for many attempts to change the balance of power. For example, in 1991-1992, Front Islamique du salut⁷ grew to be so popular among the people that the government thought it would win most of the parliamentary seats in the elections; to prevent this, the Algerian military ceased the elections and effectively controlled the country (Ghanem-Yazbeck, 2018). These events led to what is called Algeria's civil war, or as the people named it, the dark decade⁸. Amidst that period, in the late 90s the decision-makers managed to reinstate constitutional processes regularly consisting in presidential, parliamentary, and local elections (Ibid). Algeria is not seen as only the largest country in Africa and the Arab world but also one of the few countries that has chosen stability over the Arabic Spring movement known in the MENA regions since 2011 (Ghanem-Yazbeck, 2018).

3.1.5. Amazigh name origin

The Amazigh identity is tribal, which means the Amazigh culture is not homogeneous. The customs and traditions are only determined by the law of the tribes, which are widespread

⁶ National liberation front

⁷ The Islamic front of salvation

⁸ The Algerian civil war

throughout North Africa. Those tribes are varied from one country to another with a plethora of diversity in terms of language, culture, and even physical characteristics (Colon, 2018).

The term "Berber" is taken from the Latin word *Barbarus* (barbarian), which the Romans used to describe the less developed and non-Latin tribes. The word itself demeans those tribes and puts forward a stereotype of their existence as savage, uncivilised and primitive people. According to Spicer (1980), they are a surviving and resilient population, and their capacities for survival depend on persistent ownership of land, preserving their language, culture, and ethnicity. Berbers use the terms *Tamazgha*⁹ and *Amazigh* to differentiate themselves from the cycle of brutality and wars that they have endured during the numerous conquests their lands have known over the centuries, such as the Phoenicians, Ottomans, Arabs, French, and Spanish (Ilahiane, 2006). *Amazigh* or *Imazighen* (plural) is the favoured term by most of them, as "the descendants of these peoples still speak variants of the language they call *Tamazight* and refer to themselves as *Imazighen*," or the "free men" (Harrison, 2015: 155). The etymology of the word *Amazigh* is different from one region to another; there is a phonetical change in the pronunciation of the word, for example, *Amazigh* in Algeria and Morocco, *Amajeg Air* (Niger), and *Amacheg* in Adrar (a city in southern Algeria) and sub-Saharan areas.

3.1.6. Tamazight language

Although *Tamazight* was never upgraded or officially seen as a standard language neither by kings of *Tamazgha* (Massinissa, Juba) nor by the *Amazigh* thinkers of that time such as St. Augustine, Tertullian, or Appule (Achab, 2001), nevertheless, there is an archaeological proof of rocks drawings in the decoded Berber calligraphy *Tifinagh*¹⁰ that is still used by *Amazigh* in present times (Ilahiane, 2006). Educational, scientific, and artistic forms in North Africa have adopted the *Tifinagh* corpus to teach and use *Tamazight*. The language itself is a branch of the Afro-Asiatic variety as seen in Figure 3.2 below. However, it holds a minimal bulk of Afro-Asiatic features and a broad level of Arabic borrowing (Kossmann, 2013). Berber tongue has always been considered to be a spoken rather than written language; it is spoken in many countries, taking many forms and dialects such as Moroccan (Riffian, Tarifit, Tachelhit), Algerian (Kabyle, Tachawit, and Mزاب Tamazight) (Merolla, 2020). There is also *Tamahaq*, which is the patois of the Tuareg in southern

⁹ The territory where the *Amazigh* have resided, maintaining their independence and freedom from external control.

¹⁰ Alphabetical system to write *Amazigh* languages.

Algeria, Niger, and Mali, alongside Tunisian Tamazight (in Tatawin, island of Djerba, Taoujout) and Egyptian in the oasis of Siwa (Achab, 2001).

Tamazight was officially recognised constitutionally in March 2016. The process began in 2002 and reached the legalisation after a decade, as stated in Article 212 (4) of the Algerian constitution "Tamazight as a National and Official Language".

The unpleasant events of 1980 were Amazigh students protesting the prohibition of a conference held by an Amazigh writer, "Mouloud Mammeri", and that had led to violence between the police and what was called the Kabyle movement to defend the Amazigh identity and rights, which was an important element in the recognition of Tamazight as a national and official language. The Amazigh language and all its variants are now one of the customary law languages. Kabyle, Chaouia, Mzab and Tuareg dialects do not have an adequate vocabulary that leads to a necessary, intensive, and effective legal language planning. As an attempt to reach this aim and fill the gap between the official languages of Algeria, an Amazigh-English dictionary edition has been published thanks to the initiative of the High Commission of Amazigh (Laidani,2019).

Figure 3.2: Reconciling archaeological and linguistic evidence for Berber prehistory 2018

Source: Blench (2012)

3.1.7 Amazigh, Islam, and Arabisation

Amazigh or as the meaning of their name the freemen, have strong connection with three important elements according to Chtatou (2020) the link between the land (Tammurt), the language (Tamazight) and the tribal system (ddm) is unbreakable. This link is what made the

Amazigh resist a history of invaders and preserve their culture in forms of oral and written forms from at least 10,000 BC (Llahaine, 2006).

El Aissati (2001) sees that Arabic is a vital element in religion in many countries of the so-called Arab world. It does not pose a serious threat to the native languages of any country, as we can see in Iran, Turkey, and Indonesia, where the religion did not change the official language of the state. However, according to him, to gain more territory in countries of the Maghreb, it is wise to reduce the Amazigh's authority, and that was the main issue for many Amazigh activists. Ahfir (2018) joins him in believing that there is a thin line between the spread of Islam and the imposition of Arabism, the former unfolded more than the latter over the world, unlike the North African countries, where Arabism had known its way all through the Maghreb. El Aissati (2001), in his article that dealt with the language shift as a part of identity and religion, poses an important question influenced by Yasmine (1997), who also dealt with the same topic. The question was whether the Amazigh should do their best to abandon their mother tongue to become better Muslims.

Ahfir (2018) explains that the difference between imposing and embracing Arabism is a resilience tool, mentioning that Algeria, for example, was a French colony where the French wanted to mould it into mini-France by using policies such as "divide and conquer", so as a reaction, the people embraced Arabic to defeat colonialism.

The language dialogue is certainly not new to the Maghreb countries. Studies like the one conducted by Bentahila and Davies (1992), where they surveyed Amazigh groups in Morocco to investigate the use of Tamazight, found that the new generation had almost completely lost the ability to speak it, and that they had no regret. This lack of regret is evident in their families' reaction to Tamazight. It is often said that "Berber will not help you to earn your daily bread", which reflects the perception that proficiency in the Berber language may not provide significant economic advantages. According to Bentahila and Davies (1992), this is "because it is not felt to affect identity, which is secured before and after the shift." This suggests that while language shifts occur, individuals maintain a stable sense of identity regardless of the language they use. (209-210).

El Aissati (2001) had come up with an eight-stage scale, as shown in the table below, that leads to a successful language shift if it is aimed to reinsert Tamazight as an official language in the Maghreb.

Table 3.1: The eight-stage guide for officials of a language

Stage 1	The community itself needs to recognise that it needs to promote and acknowledge that its language is endangered
Stage 2	The one that deals with mass media, with all its aspects, the television, the radio, and social media.
Stage 3	This stage is about the workforce, the official administrations, which are completely ignored
Stage 4	Emphasising the educational system and the formal way to add the language to the schools, which may create competition with the dominant language
Stage 5	Where the instruments and schooling programs that go along with the nation's educational system
Stage 6	The other side of family relationships that deals with the interaction between different generations, and provides the right atmosphere
Stage 7	The backbone of a language has to do with the familiar environment, which ensures the transmission through the generations.
Stage 8	Deals with the cultural and linguistic autonomy used by the media and the government.

Source: El Aissati (2001)

The table explains Language preservation in a multifaceted approach to ensure the survival and revitalisation of endangered languages, such as Berber or Tamazight. First, the community must acknowledge the language's endangerment and take ownership of its promotion. Mass media platforms, including television, radio, and social media, play a critical role in increasing

visibility and normalising their use in public life. Incorporating the language into administrative systems and workplaces further legitimises its importance. A key component is integrating the language into the educational system, providing formal instruction that competes with dominant languages. This effort must be supported by the development of educational materials and programs that align with national curricula (El Aissati, 2001). The home environment serves as the backbone of language transmission, fostering intergenerational interaction and creating a supportive atmosphere for daily use. Finally, cultural and linguistic autonomy in media and governance ensures the language's sustained presence and relevance in institutional and cultural contexts. This comprehensive strategy addresses both grassroots and systemic levels to preserve and promote endangered languages effectively (El Aissati, 2001).

Amazigh in the Maghreb did not achieve recognition peacefully; they had to obtain it by reclamations and demonstrations, such as the uprising events in the Moroccan Rif areas in 1958, and the Berber Spring in Algeria in 1980.

As result of these events countries in the Maghreb had introduced Amazigh in their schools and media platforms, such as Morocco, where the king Hassan II had launched different news bulletins in different Amazigh dialect in 1994, later then he announced the creation of the IRCAM, which is the royal institute of the Amazigh culture in Morocco (Chtatou, 2020).

3.2. The Amazigh

Historically, Berbers have inhabited North Africa in general and the Maghreb in particular as the first settlers of the territory. It is believed that their reign in North Africa dates back at least 10.000 BC (Ilahiane,2006). Berbers had established dispersed states from the time of the king of Numidia, Masinissa, until the Muslim conquest in the 7th century. As a result of the Arabization¹¹ movement, the Berber identity and governance had notably declined in the region. However, Berbers recovered some of the power they lost after the Fatimids'¹² withdrawal in the 11th century. After they regained their control over the territory, they founded the Almoravid¹³ and

¹¹ the process of growing Arab influence on non-Arab populations

¹² An Ismaili Shia caliphate that spanned a vast region of North Africa, stretching from the Red Sea in the east to the Atlantic Ocean in the west.

¹³ The term literally means "the one who ties" and figuratively refers to "the one who is fearless in battle." It describes an imperial Berber dynasty that ruled parts of the western Maghreb and Al-Andalus during the 11th century.

subsequently, Almohad¹⁴ dynasties (Choueiri, 2005). Although the Berbers are the pre-Arab inhabitants, they are considered a minority. They are mainly scattered across Algeria, Morocco, Tunisia, Libya, Mauritania, Niger, Mali, and Egypt, as the Table below shows.

Table 3.2: Berber population in North Africa

Country	Berber Population	Berber % of total population
Algeria	7,620,000	25
Libya	150,000	5
Mali	450,000	6
Morocco	29,347,000	37
Niger	650,000	10
Tunisia	200,000	3
Total	3. 8,417,000	-

Source: Cambridge Encyclopaedia

Algeria is the largest country in Africa, covering almost 2.4 million square kilometres of landscape diversity, with the north that is considered one-fifth of the area by its coastline, mountain chains and the Sahara that covers four-fifths of its total territory. Although the Algerian desert is the primary source of its economic and financial income, only 10 per cent of the population is found there due to many external and internal reasons. External reasons include a lack of security from border countries like Mali, Niger, and Chad. Internal reasons include the marginalisation of the Algerian south by the government in almost all aspects and sectors such as health, education, transportation, etc (Entelis and Naylor, 2019). The Algerian society is distinct in many aspects, such as religion, with Islam as the dominant religion in the country, where 99 per cent of the population are Muslims, with almost 100.000 Christians and 2.000 Jews (Worldatlas, 2019). Another aspect of that distinction is the linguistic attributes, such as the different dialects

¹⁴ The term means "the unifiers" and refers to a North African Berber Muslim movement and empire established in the 12th century, which encompassed North Africa and parts of southern Spain.

(Arabic, Tamazight, and French), the accents (East, West, North, South) and the set of habits and traditions that each community have (Arabs, Chaouia, Kabyle, Mzab, Tuareg).

According to statistics in 2016, the number of Berbers in Algeria ranges from 12 to 15 million¹⁵, with four major tribes: Chaouia, which can be found in the eastern region of the country, Kabyle in the centre, Mzab in the north of the Sahara, and Tuareg deep in the desert.

Figure 3. 1: Algeria's Amazigh population distribution

Source: Algeria interface. «La Peur des maquis» Dans *Courrier international*, Sainte-Geneviève (France)
Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

3.2.1. Chaouia

Chaouia is one of the major Amazigh tribes; they are found in Khenchela, Batna, Sétif, Souk Ahras, Tébessa, Oum El Bouaghi and in the Northern part of Biskra (Nedjai, 2017). Chaouia live on the east side of Algeria near the Aures¹⁶ (an extension of the Atlas Mountain range). The nature of the Aures is well secured by its geological borderlines. The northern line of the mountain forms the boundary of the massif, the high plateau from the south, and the ruins of Timgad¹⁷ from the sides, protecting the land from intruders' attacks such as Romans, Arabs, Turks, and French (Hilton-Simpson, 1922). According to Ibn Khaldoun (1856), the name Chaouia is derived from an Amazigh word for shepherd because of their lifestyle and economic system, which was based on irrigated agriculture and livestock. In another context, Nedjai (2017) states that the term Chaoui is derived from the Berber word 'Ich', which means "horn" and is a reference to the Numidian God Amon,

¹⁵ "Les Berbères en Afrique du Nord". Chaire pour le développement de la recherche sur la culture d'expression française en Amérique du Nord., Université Laval Québec, 2016.

¹⁶ an eastern prolongation of the Atlas Mountain System that lies to the east of the Saharan Atlas in north-eastern Algeria.

¹⁷ was a Roman city in the Aures Mountains of Algeria.

who is featured as a human with the horns of a ram. The social life in Chaouia's community is based on village councils known as "Harfiqt¹⁸" and "Arch¹⁹", which are the basic units of the society and are responsible for appointing people's jobs and duties (Ilahiane, 2006).

There are three main divisions of the population of Aures according to Guedjiba (2012): the rural-urban, the Berbeis, the Rophone-Arabophone²⁰ ethnic criteria, and finally the tribal identification. Following the large waves of rural exodus and high social mobility, the tribal system of the Chaoua broke down. Gaudry (1929) and Thiriez (1986) stated that the inhabitants of the Aures Mountains were semi-nomadic tribes accommodating to cold weather in winter and heat in summer. The language they use is a different dialect of Tamazight called Tachawit, which is the second largest Berber-dialect speaking group in Algeria after the Kabyles, with more than two million speakers (Nedjai, 2017), but one of the least studied varieties (Chaker, 1984). Furthermore, the Chaouia have cultural attributes to live by, as Nedjai (2017), as a choui himself, summarised them in the following point: to live a meaningful and honourable life, it is essential to be a person of respect, regardless of where you live or whom you live with. This involves respecting the differences of others and genuinely practising the principle found in our religion: "For you is your religion, and for me is my religion" (Quran, Surah Al-Kafirun, Verse 6).

The process of Arabisation was quick in Aures. While a few Chaouia attempted to assert their Amazigh identity, many others rejected the Berber movement on the grounds of regionalism. Unlike the Kabyle, the Chaouia did not consider themselves marginalised by the state in the formation of the nationalist project. The Chaouia had to erase the memory of colonialism and embrace the Arabism movement in their regions because they were the first Algerians to rebel and fight against France, which resulted in the repression and sieging of the Aures area. Quandt (1998) stated that this hatred towards the French colonisation had made the FLN ²¹ (Front de Libération Nationale, "National Liberation Front") leaders trust them and place them in the liberation army across all the ranks, which put them in intense contact with the Arabs. Boumediene's²² (1965-1978) glorified the Aures area for their sacrifices in the war against the French. Nevertheless, the Chaouia song was largely present through the themes of identity that

¹⁸ Amazigh word for clan

¹⁹ Amazigh word for tribe

²⁰ Berberophones is someone who can speak Berber (Amazigh) while Arabophones are the people who speak Arabic.

²¹ as the primary political and military organisation that led the struggle for Algeria's independence from French colonial rule

²² The second Algerian president

were always present through artists such as Markunda, Dihya, Mihoub, and Jermouni. Tamazight was introduced in the educational field through establishing the department of Tamazight in 2013 in the Aures area and a radio station in Arabic/Chaouia, alongside the noticeable rise of the cultural associations and public support for the Amazigh cultural heritage. Nowadays, one can clearly see attempts, though they are limited, of cultural production in Chaouia folklore, theatre, and linguistics.

3.2.2. Kabyle

The Kabyle traces go back to prehistory, as certified by its numerous archaeological discoveries like the lithic industry, engravings, and paintings on the caves (Adli, 2004). The first contact that the Kabyles had with the external world was with the Phoenicians, but because of the geographical isolation of the mountains, Kabylia remained inaccessible to the various invaders throughout history until 1857, when the French succeeded in occupying and crossing the mountains for the first time in history (Zayed, 1999). Epistemologically, the word Kabyle originates from the Arabic root "Kabila", which means tribe. Those tribes of the Kabyle people, known as the largest Amazigh group in Algeria, occupy Kabylia land, which extends from the metija plain²³ north, Oued el Kabir east and the soummam valley west, making Tizi ouzo²⁴ as their capital, and with small but dense areas in Bejaia, Bouira and Boumerdes as well (as it can be seen in Figure 3.3 below).

Figure 2.3: Chaouia and Kabyle distribution in Algeria

Source: Historical distribution of Chaouia and Kabyle in Algeria (1850-1950). Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

²³ is a plain extending along the outskirts of Algiers in northern Algeria

²⁴ Algerian district

Kabyle also constitute a large Amazigh group in France. Chaker (2003: 5) in his article entitled "Berber, a long-forgotten language of France" estimates 1,500,000 Amazigh in France alone, of whom two-thirds are Algerians. Since 1930, Paris has been a factory for the Kabyle song and the production of Kabyle music. Resulting in a dense productive network of Amazigh, which supported the cultural struggle to keep the identity alive, the Kabyle variety was reasonably well-documented, widely studied and written mainly in the Latin alphabet (Sayahi, 2014: 19).

The Kabyles were peasants who depended mainly on arboriculture (olive and fig trees) in their economic system, in addition to craft industries such as tapestry and pottery. Their political and social life was based on democratic communities, "Thaddart",²⁵ and the power to rule and decide was held by "Thajma't"²⁶ (Ilahiane, 2006). They mainly speak Kabyle in their districts, even though Arabic is the official language, Kabyle people favour their own language and promote it by music, art, and literature and preserve it by teaching it to the children from birth, imposing it in schools, and integrating it in the administrations. Among all the Amazigh, Kabylia is the region that has wholly retained and preserved its Amazigh dialect, Thaqbaylit, as a mother tongue (Mouhleub, 2005). Kabyle people usually only speak Thaqbaylit with their families and with each other and use it regularly even in the areas inhabited by Arabs as a resilient tool to protect their culture (Ibid).

3.2.3. Mzab

Known by the name Bano-Mzab or Mzab simply, they are an indigenous Amazigh group who inhabit the north Algerian Sahara near the Mzab valley after which they were named. The Mzab are followers of the Ibadi School²⁷. They are known for their creation of an irrigation system for palm trees, the technique is called "Foggara", which is now developed and used in almost 35 countries (Remini and Achour, 2012). Mozabites's economy depends on plantations and trade. They live in detached federations of seven small urban hamlets that flourished between the XI and XVII centuries, which are Beni Isguen, Ghardaïa, Melika, Bounoura, Elateuf, Guerrera, and Berriane, with Ghardaïa as their capital. On the political and social side, the community is governed by two republican assemblies, "El Halqa"²⁸, in which there are twelve religious representatives, "Izzaban", who control the civil and penal laws, and the other assembly, which gathers familiar

²⁵ A Kabyle word for villages

²⁶ A Kabyle word for an assembly

²⁷ Is an Islamic sect

²⁸ The Arabic word for the circle.

people responsible for administration and police work. Unlike other Amazigh groups, the Mzab are considered to be a very conservative society (Ilahiane, 2006). They speak “Tumzabt”, another Tamazight dialect. UNESCO considered Ghardaia as an essential tangible cultural heritage of humanity for conservation due to its planning (Cataldi et al., 1996).

The Ibadits/Mzab made the site a mixture of urban dimension and historical architecture, leaving the heritage iconic but straightforward. The Mzab architecture presents the Mozabit community's way of life and family structure. From the XII to the XIV century, the urbanisation process of the Mzab valley lasted three centuries and created five ksour²⁹ (plural of Ksar): El-Atteuf (1012), the first city that has inspired many architects, Bounoura (1046), Ghardaia (1048), Bani Isguen (1347) and Melika (1350). Each one of the castles has its own palm grove, a system of irrigation, and cemeteries (Diafat and Madani, 2019), as shown in Figure 3.4 below.

Figure 3.3: Bani Isguen castle plan, Ghardaia

Source: Mashary (2003) Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Unlike other Berber groups, the Tuareg are found in Algeria, but they can also be found in Tunisia, Mali, Niger, Libya, and Burkina Faso, as illustrated in Figure 3.5 below.

²⁹ Arabic word for Castles

Figure 3.5: Tuareg distribution in the south of Africa

Source: Shoup III, John A. (2011) Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

They inhabit the vast African Sahara and speak "Tamasheq"; they even call themselves "Kel Tamasheq"³⁰ after the language they speak, which also stands for the turbans or "Talgumust" the men wear (Shoup, 2011). Their population is generally estimated at 40,000 inhabitants (Perrin, 2014). The Tuareg social class system is divided into nobles, "Imajeghen," who possess camels and the right to own arms, vassals, "Imghad, Ineslemen, and Isherifen", servants, "Izeggaghen and Ineden", and enslaved people "Iklan". In modern days, this hierarchy system has ceased to operate (Ilhiane, 2006). Women have a very high status in the community as the Tuareg culture is considered matrilineal (Aven, 2007). Ilhiane (2006) states that the term "Tuareg" is a labelling term for the entire society because the Arabic background of the name dates to the word "Tawariq", which means "abandoned by God"; however, there is no objective evidence for the source of this information.

The culture of the Tuareg gave women a higher position and considerable independence, as exemplified by Queen Tin Hinan, who led the Tuareg in the 9th century. They represent a matriarchal society where females are granted freedom in most matters of life, such as choosing a life partner and managing domestic issues and business (Harris, 1996). According to Rasmussen

³⁰ The veiled people

(2005), Tuareg society is a blend of pre-Islamic and Islamic practices. Tuareg men were expected to travel in trade caravans and provide the family with essential living necessities; consequently, nomadic Tuareg women learned to read, write, and be responsible for both the household and the community.

The Tuareg's historical sources are derived from two primary sources. Firstly, the written documents and the historical work of Muslim notes on the city's Islamic ancient tradition from African nomadic tribes in Timbuktu, Agadez, and Sokoto. Secondly, the oral traditions transmitted by the Tuareg are conveyed in poetic form (Bernus and Cressier, 1992). Another aspect of the Tuareg cultural identity is their music, which holds high importance in social, political, and ceremonial contexts. It plays a pivotal role that some associated instrument or genre inspires festivals or events, for example, Tende³¹ (Schmidt, 2009). Music and poetry are verbal arts, and that explains why Tuareg music is primarily vocal. These vocal arts are highly regarded and respected due to their value in Tuareg life, having been developed over several centuries. One of the most famous musical genres is the Imzad, which is also believed to be a tool that inspires men to be courageous, and an amulet to protect them and guide them home safely. Card (1982: 577) elaborates on the Imzad significance: "Warriors in combat strove always to act courageously, lest their women deprive them of music: the prospect of silent fiddles on their return renewed their courage in the face of defeat."

3.3. Gender and Intangible Cultural Heritage

Many reflections about gendered views can be found in the field of culture; most dealing with topics related to cultural institutions, cultural professions, cultural attributes and aspects. However, women's role in general is less acknowledged and recognised. The aim of this section is to examine the concept of gender and intangible cultural heritage, as well as the role of women in cultural transmission. Thaalbi (1920) echoes Engels's (1884) view of the reproductive work of women in focusing on the family and the education of children by stating that "The woman is the guardian of the family, the conservator of society". Kabeer (2000) identifies the communal role of women, where women contribute to society but often receive no acknowledgement for their achievements. By stating that women are the guardians of society, Thaalbi refers to the fact that women are the active element in the transmission of traditions and practices within their

³¹ A traditional musical instrument similar to drums.

communities, which is what UNESCO now refers to as intangible cultural heritage (see Section 2 in Chapter 5).

Human rights principles should be informed by and aligned with cultural expressions and identity, emphasising the importance of recognising the dignity, value, and contributions of women to society and cultural development within any community (UNHR, 2012). International law clearly states that any form of discrimination is a violation of human rights. The 2003 convention eliminates all kinds of bias against women by requesting states to change the cultural and social aspects that prejudice the view of women, such as views that are influenced by the idea of superiority, inferiority or the cultural and social stereotypical perspectives of either of the sexes (Moghadam and Bagheritari, 2007).

Intangible cultural heritage (ICH) has been acknowledged as an important element in the preservation of cultural diversity in the world, since the Declaration on Cultural Diversity in 2001, and the Convention that followed in 2003 on the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage that was adopted at the thirty-second session of UNESCO's General Conference. The convention defined ICH as 'practices, representations and expressions, and knowledge and skills which are transmitted from generation to generation, and which provide communities and groups with a sense of identity and continuity'³². The 2003 UNESCO Convention on Intangible Cultural Heritage, Article 2, comprises:

- *“Oral expressions and traditions, including language as a vehicle of the intangible cultural heritage.*
- *Performing arts.*
- *Social practices, rituals, and festive events.*
- *Knowledge and practices concerning nature and the universe.*
- *Traditional craftsmanship and music*
- *Cultural spaces: places where population and traditional cultural activities occur in a concentrated manner.” (UNESCO, 2003)*

However, despite the clarification of the outlines of the ICH, the convention seems to be incomplete because it does not deal with the transmission process from a gendered view. To fully

³² Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Heritage, 2003.

understand the discussion, it is essential to consult the 1995 World Commission on Culture and Development report that stresses that “Women’s ingenuity, initiative and creativity in solving their daily problems of survival represented important local forms of organisation, association and self-help” (UNESCO, 2014, p. 51). Therefore, the international views regarding the role of women in the transmission of cultural heritage in their communities were highlighted prior to the 2003 Convention adaptation.

3.3.1. Women’s central role in the transmission of ICH

An International Symposium was held in Tehran in 1999 to discuss the role of women in transmitting ICH (UNESCO, 1999). After two years, UNESCO announced the outcome and the launching of a programme that admits and sheds light on women’s role in the transmission process (UNESCO, 1999). Gatrell (2004) argued that women are the pillar of children’s education, referring to the maintenance of the principles of upbringing a child, where in all societies women go through phases that follow certain traditions and principles. These traditions and principles are intergenerational forms of cultural heritage³³. These ruling points out women’s primary role in the safeguarding and transmission of ICH. The Symposium report stated that “women are also custodians of intangible cultural heritable which encompasses, among other forms, the performing arts including music, culinary and medicinal knowledge and the know-how for the creation of material culture”³⁴(UNESCO reports, 1999: 2). This is clear evidence to the dominance of women over men in the culture transmission process where men tasks are related to outside world, while women on the other hand, focus on the fundamental cell which is the family by passing traditions and customs that builds cultures all over the world.

UNESCO adopted the 2003 Convention as a result of the symposium without highlighting the prevalent role of women in the transmission of ICH. Even women’s achievements within the ICH field are still unrecognised and inconspicuous. Some societies depend on women’s role to keep existing. For example, in Nigeria, the continuity of the Gèlèdè ceremonies, practised and customs

³³ International Symposium on the role of women in transmission intangible culture heritage, Tehran 1999. URL: <https://ich.unesco.org/doc/src/00157-EN.pdf>, p.2.

³⁴ Ibid

by the Yoruba-Nago community, is guaranteed by the women and their practices. Women continue to be the main pillars in the preservation and transmission of ICH within their own community.

3.3.2. The transmission of heritage and cultural practices as opportunities for liberation

Women have found opportunities for empowerment through their role in transmitting intangible cultural heritage (ICH), despite often being overlooked in international policy discussions. To enable women to assume full authority in this domain, it is essential for society—especially men—to acknowledge their significant contributions and responsibilities in the preservation and transmission of ICH. By participating in the evolution of cultural traditions, women have gained social and personal advantages (Institut du Genre en Géopolitique, 2021).

Griswold and Murphy (2013) highlight the example of Pashtun women in Afghanistan, who use *landay*—a form of oral poetry—to voice their thoughts publicly and achieve social recognition, despite historically being excluded from the public sphere. In Iran, women have begun attending *Naqqali* performances, a traditional theatrical art form, despite previous restrictions. Women are now able to perform as storytellers for female audiences, enabling them to pursue valued careers in Persian culture and achieve a higher social standing (Beigi, 2021). Similarly, during World War II, women of the Malaka tribe in Indonesia adapted their cultural heritage to survive the threat of becoming "comfort women" for the Japanese army. They tattooed their bodies to signify marital status, which the invading forces respected. This painful yet life-saving tradition allowed these women to assert their agency and independence (Malay and Raha, 2019).

Cultural transmission through gender-specific practices is evident in Côte d'Ivoire, where falconry is passed down exclusively by men to men, while Mangoro pottery is transmitted by women to women (UNESCO, 2014:52). Culinary traditions also highlight the role of women as cultural transmitters. Eve-Marie Lavaud (2018) emphasises that cooking is deeply associated with femininity and motherhood, while Manuel Calvo (1982) notes that culinary skills are seen as inherently feminine, with some dishes exclusively prepared by women. This gendered division of culinary labour is not viewed as a sign of subordination but rather as a source of societal order and cultural continuity (Crenn, 2005; Institut du Genre en Géopolitique, 2021).

In the Middle East, Palestinian women engage in *Hiyake*, a ritual of storytelling that allows them to critique societal norms and build solidarity through shared experiences. Palestinian embroidery is another example, creating spaces for female interaction and fostering a sense of

community. This tradition also provides women with economic independence, as they produce and sell traditional crafts. A similar dynamic is observed in the Dao Tien ethnic group in Vietnam, where women earn income by selling handmade textiles to tourists, reinforcing the empowering potential of ICH practices (Institut du Genre en Géopolitique, 2021).

ICH transmission is not only a means of preserving culture but also a pathway for women's self-empowerment and economic independence. Making the gendered nature of ICH transmission more visible ensures its preservation and recognises women's indispensable role in sustaining cultural identity. In this context, without women's dedication to inheriting and passing on traditions, the intangible aspects of culture and identity within communities would face the risk of disappearance. Women's contributions are central to the survival and vitality of ICH.

3.4. Amazigh After the Independence

Some researchers, like Ahfir (2018), believed that the regime back then sought to target the Amazigh by launching only Arabic programs, which met with rejection among Amazigh activists in Kabylia³⁵. A significant event in 1980 was when the authorities banned Mouloud Mammeri from holding a conference about the Amazigh poetry. This event led to serious demonstrations across Amazigh areas where students protested, following the school boycott in 1994, and other forms of opposition.

According to Goodman (2004), if it were not for the law of the Arabization program that neglected the Amazigh identity and the demonstrations of the scholars at that time, the Berber Spring would not have happened, and this is what created a legacy for the Kabyle and the Amazigh in general and all across North Africa. These events had in favor the Amazigh case in the country where after years of struggling, the recognition had taken different dimensions such as Tamazight recognition as an official language in 2002, introducing Tamazight in cabled television channels in March 2009 and the opening to politics in 1989 by founding parties as the Rally for culture and democracy (Maddy-Weitzman, 2018). On the cultural side, many researchers still criticise the educational system in Algeria, where the children are taught a more Middle Eastern version of literature and history. They need to be taught about their ancestors in books. Furthermore, the Amazigh festive season is given little importance, such as the Amazigh New Year, which falls on

³⁵ A region located in north-central Algeria, situated between the Atlas Mountains and the Mediterranean Sea, encompassing areas such as Tizi Ouzou and Bejaia.

January 12th or, as it is called in Tamazight, “Yennayer”, is the most important event in the Amazigh calendar. This event is a celebration of King Shashnaq's triumph over the Pharaohs; it was only announced as a national holiday in 2018 (Ahfir, 2018). Finally, as quoted from Ahfir (2018), “not because Mexicans can speak Spanish, they consider themselves Spaniards”, identity is the only attribute that gives culture meaning.

3.5. Modern Amazigh: Preserving Heritage in a Changing World

After the independence in 1962, the newly formed Algerian authorities started to lay the basis of the country by deciding the internal and external policies of the country. In 1963, the first Algerian constitution stated that Arabic is the only official language of the state³⁶ (Algerian constitution, Article 5), as a reaction to the previous colonialism protocols, such as Algeria being a French colony by forbidding the Arabic language in all domains and refusing the Islamic religious aspects. As a result of the government’s negligence, the Berber society revolted against the regime by forming a political party by Ait Ahmed³⁷ called “Front des Forces Socialistes “(FFS)³⁸ (Attalah, 2019). The revolts against the government continued till 1980, when Berbers in Kabyle (Algiers, Tizi Ouzou district and its provinces) protested to demand recognition for the Berber identity, culture, and language after the ban of a conference held by Mouloud Mammeri³⁹. Berber activists went on a general strike to speak for their rights and their existence in the country. In 2001, disturbances and political demonstrations rose in Kabylia⁴⁰. This region is known as the Black Spring, where suppressive police measures met the Berber activists and protesters, leading to the death of almost 90 persons and where 5000 were injured (Oakes, 2008). The Berber Spring was a crucial event for the country’s incipient human rights for communities such as Berbers and non-Berbers (see chapter 7, section 2.2).

In 2002, the Algerian constitution finally included Tamazight as a national language as a result of the marches and protests of the Amazigh in the country. Currently, the Amazigh case is notably connected to a range of debated ideologies of identity boundaries, including language, place, and religion. It stands as a sensitive cultural and political issue in North Africa. By the 21st century, as

³⁶ Act number 5 in the Algerian constitution.

³⁷ Algerian politician

³⁸ Socialist Forces Front

³⁹ Algerian writer, anthropologist and linguist

⁴⁰ Is a cultural, natural and historical region in northern Algeria. It is part of the Tell Atlas mountains located at the edge of the Mediterranean Sea.

a shy attempt from the North African governments to recognise the Amazigh cultural and linguistic identity, and to open the door for discussion of the bare possibility of seeing Tamazight as an official and equal language to Arabic in their constitutions, teaching it in schools, and using it in public media. While Tamasheq (the language of the Tuareg) is the official language in Niger and Mali, the politicking of the Amazigh question is a continuous, feverish debate between Amazigh activists and the governments in North African countries.

“Mon identité, ma culture, n’est pas un dossier administratif que l’autorité légitime, établit, ouvre, et referme à sa convenance et auquel je n’a aurais qu’à me conformer. La culture est la création quotidienne d’une société libre” (Yacine, 1956).

In the above-mentioned quote, the writer states, "My identity, my culture is not an administrative document that the legitimated authority makes, opens, and closes according to its relevance, and all that I can do is to comply; culture is the daily creation of a liberated society" (Yacine, 1956). The Berber community has always been considered rebellious for their refusal to their marginalisation by their governments and for their pride in their culture, identity, and traditions that they see as a sacred legacy.

3.6. Conclusion

In conclusion, this chapter has demonstrated the profound significance of orality and intangible cultural heritage (ICH) in preserving and transmitting African and Amazigh cultural identities across generations. From the rich landscape of oral genres and traditions to the central role of women in cultural transmission, the study reveals how these practices sustain societal cohesion, cultural resilience, and individual empowerment. The challenges posed by colonisation, linguistic shifts, and political marginalization have been met with remarkable resilience by Amazigh communities, as seen in their artistic expressions, linguistic revitalization, and enduring cultural practices. The integration of Tamazight into national frameworks and the recognition of Amazigh heritage signify improvement toward cultural inclusivity. However, ongoing efforts are required to fully acknowledge and integrate these contributions within broader national and global discourses. Ultimately, the preservation of Amazigh and African oral traditions not only safeguards cultural diversity but also enriches the collective human experience.

Chapter Four - Methodology and Methods

This chapter provides a comprehensive explanation of the methodology and research design selected for this study, as well as the rationale underpinning these choices. First, the chapter presents the study's research question along with its core aims and objectives, research strategy, and foundational research philosophy. This introductory section establishes the theoretical and practical framework of the research, aligning it with its specific goals. Subsequently, the chapter examines the research design, emphasising the qualitative approach and the triangulation method used to enhance data validity and the depth of analysis. The following section introduces the sampling framework, detailing the criteria for participant selection, the sampling method, and the sample size. This structure ensures a robust and purpose-driven participant selection that aligns with the study's qualitative nature. The fourth section outlines the instruments used for data collection, which include semi-structured in-depth interviews, structured interviews, and document analysis, each selected to capture diverse aspects of the phenomenon under study. The fifth section then provides an in-depth account of the data analysis procedures, demonstrating how data is systematically interpreted. Finally, the chapter concludes with a discussion on ethical considerations, acknowledging the importance of maintaining ethical rigour in conducting qualitative research.

Heritage studies, as an academic field, began gaining prominence in the 1980s, emerging from a combination of socio-political and academic movements that re-evaluated perspectives on cultural legacy. These movements included post-colonialism, which introduced new voices into discourse on the past and encouraged a critical examination of the power structures governing access to and representation of heritage. Within academia, post-structuralist and post-modern critiques emerged, challenging traditional authority structure and advocating for broader inclusivity and diverse viewpoints within the heritage domain (Smith and Carman, 2009). These movements catalysed a shift in heritage studies from a previously overlooked area to a dynamic field of research.

The complexity of heritage, particularly cultural heritage, presents unique challenges in establishing the necessity of its preservation, calling for nuanced methodological approaches. Uzzell (2009: 327) emphasises that "Methodologies are important in Heritage Studies because they are the hand which guides us into the past from the present, showing us how to look and see.". The field's development as an interdisciplinary domain, with scholars drawn from

academic institutions and governmental organisations, resulted in methodologies adapted from various disciplines, including anthropology, archaeology, architecture, art history, psychology, sociology, and tourism (Smith and Carman, 2009). This interdisciplinary borrowing reflects the dynamic nature of heritage studies, which seeks to blend various perspectives to achieve a holistic understanding of cultural phenomena.

4.1 Aim, Objectives, and Research Questions

The aim of this research is to explore the critical role of Amazigh women in transmitting and preserving intangible cultural heritage (ICH) and to understand how Algerian governmental policies align with the preservation and promotion of this heritage. This study investigates the intersection of gender, culture, and policy within the socio-political framework of Algeria, focusing on the resilience of Amazigh women despite the adversities they face.

The objectives of this research are as follows:

1. Examine Algeria's cultural policies and their impact on Amazigh heritage preservation: This includes analysing the extent to which these policies support or hinder efforts to safeguard Amazigh ICH, with attention to the implementation and local adaptation of state policies.
2. Explore the influence of gender roles on Amazigh women's resilience and empowerment in heritage preservation: This objective seeks to understand how societal norms shape women's roles in their communities, either supporting or constraining their agency.
3. Identify strategies employed by Amazigh women to sustain and transmit ICH amidst socio-economic challenges: These strategies include communal initiatives, artisanal crafts, and oral traditions that help maintain cultural practices despite economic and social pressures.
4. Document the lived experiences and cultural practices of Amazigh women: Capturing their challenges and resilience provides an in-depth understanding of their contributions to cultural heritage preservation.

To address these aims and objectives, the research poses the following overarching question:

How do Amazigh women in Algeria navigate and contribute to the preservation and transformation of their cultural identity within the context of national and regional policies, socio-political challenges, and modernisation pressures? central main question is supported by the following sub-questions:

- How do Algeria's national policies on cultural heritage and identity impact Amazigh women's efforts to preserve intangible cultural heritage?
- In what ways do traditional gender roles and social norms influence the empowerment and resilience of Amazigh women in heritage preservation?
- How do Amazigh women navigate the tension between cultural preservation and modernisation within their communities?
- What strategies do Amazigh women employ to sustain and transmit intangible cultural heritage amidst socio-economic challenges and shifting national identities?
- How do the experiences and practices of Amazigh women in Algeria contribute to intangible culture preservation despite the adversities they face?

4.2. Research Philosophy

This section is devoted to examining the chosen philosophy behind this research. Social constructivism is chosen as the appropriate research paradigm. The social constructivism approach adopts the understanding that reality is a socially constructed, changing according to notions and the perspectives of individuals in society that built it. Therefore, the different perspectives of Amazigh women in the process of transmitting and preserving the ICH are of great importance to find answers for the research questions and to meet the different objectives of this study.

Guba and Lincoln define the research paradigm (1994: 105) as "the basic belief system or the worldview that guides the investigator not only in choices of methods but in ontologically and epistemologically fundamental ways". Accordingly, ontology is related to what is true, real, and the nature of that reality (Smith, 2012). Then, it refers to the role of Amazigh women in their already existing reality, which is the Amazigh culture.

Grounding this study's methodology are the philosophical positions of ontology and epistemology, which establish the underlying perspectives on reality and knowledge. Ontology concerns itself with the essence of reality, what exists and how it can be known (Snape and

Spencer, 2003; Crotty, 1998), while epistemology addresses the means through which knowledge is perceived and constructed. As Crotty (1998) notes, epistemology reflects the nature of knowledge acquisition. Cohen, Manion, and Morrison (2007) emphasise that it includes the foundational assumptions about knowledge's form, origin, and communicability.

This research aligns with a constructivist ontological stance, consistent with Cupchik's (2001) perspective that meaning is socially generated by both individuals and groups. This stance views reality not as a static, objective truth but as a dynamic construct shaped by social and cultural interactions. In the context of studying Amazigh intangible heritage and gender roles, constructivism supports the idea that heritage and cultural identity are not universally defined but evolve with the lived experiences, practices, and values of community members. Consequently, aspects of Amazigh culture, such as traditional practices and gender norms, reflect socially constructed realities that vary by region, social interaction, and individual perspective. Epistemology is concerned with the nature of knowledge and how it is obtained, that is to say, the interpretation of data gathered from the participants of the study and the different methods for collecting it (Chamberlain, 2015). As a result, using methods is about the way the researcher is seeking to know the reality. Table 4.1 below presents the basic research paradigm, including the suitable research paradigm chosen for the study.

Figure 4.1: Basic Beliefs of Alternative Inquiry Paradigms

Paradigm	Ontology <i>What is reality?</i>	Epistemology <i>How can I know reality?</i>	Theoretical Perspective <i>Which approach do you use to know something?</i>	Methodology <i>How do you go about finding out?</i>	Method <i>What techniques do you use to find out?</i>
Positivism	There is a single reality or truth (more realist).	Reality can be measured and hence the focus is on reliable and valid tools to obtain that.	Positivism Post-positivism	Experimental research Survey research	Usually quantitative, could include: Sampling Measurement and scaling Statistical analysis Questionnaire Focus group Interview
Constructivist / Interpretive	There is no single reality or truth. Reality is created by individuals in groups (less realist).	Therefore, reality needs to be interpreted. It is used to discover the underlying meaning of events and activities.	Interpretivism (reality needs to be interpreted) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Phenomenology • Symbolic interactionism • Hermeneutics Critical Inquiry Feminism	Ethnography Grounded Theory Phenomenological research Heuristic inquiry Action Research Discourse Analysis Feminist Standpoint research etc	Usually qualitative, could include: Qualitative interview Observation Participant Non participant Case study Life history Narrative Theme identification etc
Pragmatism	Reality is constantly renegotiated, debated, interpreted in light of its usefulness in new unpredictable situations.	The best method is one that solves problems. Finding out is the means, change is the underlying aim.	Deweyan pragmatism <i>Research through design</i>	Mixed methods Design-based research Action research	Combination of any of the above and more, such as data mining expert review, usability testing, physical prototype

Source: Guba and Lincoln, 1994, p. 109

The social constructivist paradigm underpins this study's examination of Amazigh cultural heritage and gender dynamics, emphasising that knowledge about social phenomena is not singular or fixed but is continuously constructed and shaped by individuals and communities. Constructivist theory, as a broad paradigm, holds that reality is comprised of multiple perspectives, with each person forming their own understanding of what is real. This paradigm implies that research findings emerge through collaboration between researchers and participants, leading to inherently subjective interpretations (Al-Saggaf, 2006). Within constructivism, two primary theories provide foundational insights: personal construct theory, which focuses on individual cognition, and social constructivist theory, which examines how social and cultural interactions shape shared understandings. This study adopts the latter, drawing on Berger and Luckmann's (1967) seminal work on social constructivism, which posits that reality is constructed collectively through social interactions, culture, language, and shared environmental contexts. According to Williamson (2002), social constructionists view people as jointly creating meaning, thereby constructing reality within a communal framework. In this way, the Amazigh culture, embedded in the practices and beliefs of the people who make up this society, reflects a shared, socially constructed reality.

On the epistemological level, this study adopts an interpretivist approach, acknowledging that knowledge is formed through subjective experiences and that individuals attribute unique meanings to their social practices, shaping their perception of reality (Constantino, 2008; Pascale, 2011). In this study, interpretivism provides a framework for understanding intangible heritage, identity, and gender as co-constructed realities shaped by the community rather than pre-existing objective truths. Through this interpretive lens, the study investigates how individuals within Amazigh communities define, understand, and communicate their cultural heritage and identity, viewing these as expressions of their lived experiences and social interactions. This combined constructivist and interpretivist approach offers a robust framework for interpreting the data, revealing the ways in which cultural identity, gender, and heritage are both created and sustained within the collective memory and daily practices of the Amazigh community.

4.3. Methodology and Research Design

Methodology, distinct from methods, provides the theoretical and systematic framework underlying research choices, encompassing research paradigms, models of inquiry, and a

spectrum of techniques, both qualitative and quantitative (Igwenagu, 2016). Unlike the methods, which focus on specific data collection and analysis tools, methodology offers a foundation for selecting the appropriate approaches for types of research (Irny and Rose, 2005). This study emphasises methodology as the foundation for guiding the research process, focusing on the alignment of theory with practice in a way that is both rigorous and relevant.

The research adopts a qualitative research approach with a triangulation data collection method. From the aims and objectives of the study, the qualitative research is applicable, the approach permits gender, cultural issues, such as female transmission and intangible cultural heritage, to be presented, understood and perceived in a better manner. The main method for the research involves locating women in different ethnic groups among the Amazigh groups in Algeria. These Amazigh women were chosen based on personal knowledge and acquaintances, as well as the guidance of colleagues and their kin.

Filippucci (2009) argues that cultural heritage research is inherently people-centred, focusing on the ways in which individuals and communities experience, interpret, and engage with their heritage. Qualitative methods are particularly suited for capturing these perspectives, motivations, and actions within the heritage process, as they allow researchers to record and analyse the views, attitudes, and behaviours of those involved. This is especially pertinent for the study of intangible heritage, which includes living traditions and practices that are integral to a community's cultural identity. Notably, intangible heritage gained formal recognition as a field of study following the 2003 UNESCO Convention, which urged member states to establish policies, monitoring institutions, and initiatives to support intangible heritage. This Convention emphasised community involvement, highlighting the importance of qualitative research in understanding the perspectives of those most directly connected to intangible cultural heritage.

To achieve a thorough understanding of this study's aims and objectives, a multi-method qualitative approach has been selected as the research strategy. According to Creswell and Clark (2007), this approach involves the concurrent use of two or more qualitative methods for data collection and analysis, in contrast to a mixed-method approach that integrates both qualitative and quantitative methodologies. Given this study's focus on cultural heritage and the central role of community perspectives, a qualitative methodology allows for the necessary depth and sensitivity in capturing the complex social and cultural dimensions involved.

Each component of this methodology serves a distinct purpose in achieving a nuanced understanding of the research topic. The multi-method approach, drawing on a triangulation strategy, integrates various qualitative techniques to ensure a well-rounded analysis. This approach not only strengthens the reliability of the data but also allows for a comprehensive exploration of the research questions from multiple angles. Triangulation is a particularly valuable strategy in qualitative research, as it enables cross verification of data by employing diverse sources and methods, thereby enhancing the study's validity. Through using semi-structured interviews and document analysis, this research achieves both depth and breadth, allowing for a well-rounded exploration of the cultural, social, and political dynamics at play.

This research's focus on qualitative methods is also aligned with recent research in heritage studies, which emphasises the importance of capturing community and individual perspectives, especially when dealing with intangible heritage. The qualitative approach allows for a more flexible, adaptive process, enabling the researcher to remain responsive to emerging insights throughout the research. Through this approach, the study aims to provide a layered understanding of the ways in which Amazigh women in Algeria navigate and contribute to their cultural identity amidst evolving national and regional policies, socio-political challenges, and pressures of modernisation.

4.3.1. Qualitative research

Marshall (1996) sets out a comparison between quantitative and qualitative research, stating that the former intends to validate a hypothesis that is established beforehand, the research is centred on deduction, and the researcher is objective and detached from their study. The outcome statistics require being general, valid and reliable for to tests. The latter on the other hand, is a passive holistic design to study convoluted phenomena, the researcher tends to be inductive to support the study with more significant data set, to create fresh hypotheses and to improve the understanding to an interesting phenomenon. Unlike quantitative method, the researcher is somehow subjective and attached to the study.

According to Anderson (2006), measurement and counting are the tools of a quantitative researcher, whereas describing a phenomenon and extracting its significance are the qualitative researcher's techniques. When comparing the samples in the qualitative method with the quantitative, it is noticed that it is smaller in size but richer and deeper in data. Because it not only seeks an explanation of the study of interest but also gives attention and precisely reflects

the opinions and feelings of the participants of the study. Another facet of comparison is the fact that the quantitative methods tend to be based upon correct numerical data statistics, which makes reality a universal law. By contrast, in qualitative research, the reality is flexible and dynamic; consequently, the results cannot be copied, which makes it broad and varied in the findings compared to the quantitative. Anderson (2006) further argues that the skills of the researcher decide the quality of the results.

The qualitative method contains various strengths that promote its use as a suitable approach for the study. Manning (1992) considers it optimum for investigating complicated issues in dynamic settings, and it provides a better understanding of subjects' perspectives. Moreover, qualitative research is flexible concerning research locations; it does not require monitored environments (Anderson, 2006). Above all, it facilitates the comprehension of thoroughly studied phenomena instead of the numerical and statistical analysis of a single attribute in it (Trochim, 2006).

Mason (2002:1) states, "Through qualitative research, we can explore a wide array of dimensions of the social world, including the texture and weave of everyday life, the understandings, experiences and imaginings of our research participants ...".

Flick (2002) believes that it has become difficult to give qualitative research a universal definition because it has become a respected and established approach, which guided him to provide three common aspects to be involved in the world "out there" instead of a laboratory. The first feature is examining the experiences lived by groups or individuals, whereas the second is examining the interaction and communication, and the third is analysing documents like music, films, texts, etc.

On the other hand, Mason (2002) notices that qualitative research cannot be "pigeon-holed" and abridged into common features, although she agrees with Flick's perspective in some common respects. She introduces qualitative research as an 'interpretivist' grounded approach because it presents the understanding, the experiences, and the constitution of the social world.

According to Denzin and Lincoln (2018: 9), "Qualitative research is a field of inquiry in its own right" and "crosscuts disciplines, fields and subject matter". They consider the qualitative researcher as a "bricoleur" in that he or she uses any materials and tools of his or her craft that are available and uses whatever methods and techniques to achieve the aim of the research.

This plan was previously critiqued by Bryman (2001), who views the researcher's subjectivity as an obstacle to his views on what is important. Secondly, there is a lack of transparency and difficulty in explaining the conclusions. Furthermore, unlike other scholars who consider this feature to be an advantage, he states, "Precisely because it is unstructured and often reliant upon the qualitative researcher's ingenuity, it is almost impossible to conduct a true replication" (Bryman 2001: 282).

To cover to some extent these issues this chapter attempts to explain in depth the reasons behind choosing certain methods, sampling technique, structuring interviews, and minimising limitations. The multi-method qualitative approach assists throughout the triangulation of methods, in overcoming issues of generalisation, reliability and validity. Which will be furthermore explained in the chapter.

4.4. Research Methods and Data Collection

This section of the research sheds light on the instruments used to obtain data for the study, these instruments are in-depth semi-structured interviews, participants' observation, and document analysis. In addition to the ethics that the research complies to. The rest of this section defines and explores each of the methods used in relation to the study aims and objectives.

Qualitative research often draws on multiple data sources to establish connections and confirm findings, utilising various sources to strengthen the study's validity. For this reason, combining document analysis with other qualitative methods, such as interviews, serves as an effective triangulation strategy, enhancing the research's validity and credibility (Eisner, 1991). O'Leary (2014: 244) emphasises that textual analysis deserves the same level of consideration as other data collection methods.

This study used both primary and secondary data collection methods. Primary data was gathered mainly through semi-structured, in-depth interviews, a technique recommended by Kvale (1996) as particularly effective in creating an environment where participants feel at ease and can freely share their insights. This approach allowed for an interactive and flexible exchange, encouraging participants to explore topics at greater depth. Additionally, field notes and observations were employed to capture contextual details and enrich the understanding of interview dynamics, providing critical insights for developing sampling frameworks and guiding questions (DeWALT and DeWALT, 2002).

Secondary data collection involved reviewing official documents and scholarly literature related to Algeria's cultural policies, UNESCO's conventions on intangible cultural heritage, and regional specifics of the Amazigh community. The background review helped establish a strong foundation, contextualising findings within existing frameworks discussed in later chapters. This approach also enabled cross-referencing interview data with documented policies, adding layers of credibility and reliability to the study.

4.4.1. Triangulation

Patton (1999) refers to Triangulation as a method in qualitative research that aims to develop an understanding of certain phenomena. The notion 'triangulation' in social studies refers to observing an issue of research from various sides. The history of triangulation traces back to 1959, where Campbell and Fiske established "the multi-trait, multi-method matrix" that was the starting point of triangulation (Flick et al., 2004).

Later, Denzin (1978) initially presented triangulation as a validation strategy. He recognised four modes; these modes are triangulation of data, investigator triangulation, triangulation of theories and the central concept of Denzin's "methodological triangulation".

The latter is used in this study; its aim is "to summarise, methodological triangulation involves a complex process of playing each method off against the other to maximise the validity of field efforts" (Denzin, 1978: 304).

Several scholars have reviewed Denzin's triangulation perspective. For example, Silverman (2010) stated that to obtain a total picture of certain phenomena, multiple research methods should be employed, and triangulation advocates should not refer to that because each method should be understood by its terms. Bloor (1997) agrees that each different methods require a specific investigation. Summing up all the critics, Fielding and Fielding (1986) state that the aim behind the combination of methods should be done carefully to add depth to the analysis of the research, not to find "objective truth". Blaikie (1991) further explains that in combining different research methods, scant attention is given to the individuals' method use.

In more of his recent works, Denzin and Lincon (1994) saw, thought out the critics, that triangulation is strategy leading more to the in-depth understanding of an investigated phenomena and less to an objective and valid interpretation. Therefore, triangulation is a strategy that explains the basis of knowledge and how to gain it not to give validation to research issues (Denzin and Lincon, 1994; Flick, 1992).

Using triangulation as a method has its merits; subsequently, Webb et al. (1966) stated that to eliminate and cancel the bias research finding, different methods must be used as a “multiple operationalism”, or as Denzin (1989: 244) asserts “, the flaws of one method are often the strengths of another”. Accordingly, to contribute to avoiding bias and subjectivity of one method, the use of triangulation is required (Lincoln and Denzin, 2003)

4.4.2. In-depth semi-structured interviews

Interviews are a flexible and informative data collection tool. Silverman (1997: 98) describes interviews as “active interactions between two or more people leading to a negotiated, contextually based result,” emphasising their dynamic nature. Similarly, Jones (1985) notes that interviews enable a deeper understanding of participants' perceptions and constructions of reality. According to Seidman (2013) and Kvale (2007), interviews are a structured, purposeful method of inquiry.

Interviews are particularly advantageous in exploring complex and abstract ideas. Sørensen (2009) argues that interviews facilitate engagement with intricate concepts, such as "heritage," in a way that fosters participants' awareness of its significance. In this study, the interviews are designed to achieve the research's primary aims and objectives by exploring how individuals contribute to the preservation and transmission of intangible heritage across generations.

To capture depth and flexibility, this research adopts an in-depth, semi-structured interview approach. Kvale (2007: 7) views the qualitative research interview as a “construction site for knowledge.” This approach allows the investigator to ask open-ended, prearranged questions (Ayres, 2008) while leaving room for participants to express their thoughts freely. Unlike structured interviews, the semi-structured format provides flexibility, as it relies on open questions without fixed responses, a guide interview, allowing participants to explore and elaborate on their answers (Creswell, 2012).

By posing semi structured questions, researchers encourage subjective and unbiased responses, in contrast to closed-ended questions that might restrict responses (Creswell, 2012; McNamara, 1999). Rubin and Rubin (2005) further argue that in-depth interviews foster a connection between interviewer and participant, enabling an open exchange of ideas. Follow-up questions, shaped around key words or themes from participants' responses, allow for deeper exploration, thus achieving richer insights.

The pursuit of depth in interviews aligns with the research's aim to gather valid and credible information from participants who possess "specialised knowledge" (O'Leary, 2014). Seidman (2013: 9) emphasises that "at the root of in-depth interviewing is an interest in understanding the lived experience of other people and the meaning they make of that experience." By seeking depth, the study draws on participants' unique insights, which are essential for answering the research questions.

As Rubin and Rubin (2005: 64) note, "Interviewees should be experienced and knowledgeable in the area you are interviewing about." An interview guide with twenty open-ended questions across five key topics structured the interview process:

- Traditions and habits in Amazigh culture.
- Female practices in society.
- Cultural influences on female Amazigh culture.
- Barriers and challenges for women in transmitting cultural heritage.
- Strategies to recognise and support women's roles in heritage creation.

Questions on traditions and habits were aimed at gauging participants' understanding of their cultural heritage. Gender-related questions examined participants' views on the significance of female practices and explored perceived barriers in cultural transmission. Finally, questions on cultural influences sought to highlight distinctive aspects of Amazigh culture and the role women play in preserving and shaping this heritage.

This semi-structured, open-ended approach provides a comprehensive understanding of the cultural dynamics surrounding Amazigh women, offering valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities they encounter in cultural preservation.

4.4.3. Structured interviews

This study incorporated structured interviews with four managers of cultural directorates, focusing on Algerian heritage policies related to intangible cultural heritage and gender dynamics. The decision to use a structured interview format was informed by the predictability and organisation this method offers, as structured interviews are designed to follow a set format that ensures consistency and focus (Gillham, 2005). Given the interviewees' managerial roles and the time constraints associated with their responsibilities, a structured approach

provided an efficient way to gather relevant insights without demanding extensive time commitments from participants. The data collected through these interviews proved to be well-aligned with the study's objectives, offering targeted information and themes on how heritage policies impact both intangible cultural heritage and gender dynamics within Algeria. The themes are as follows:

- Decentralisation and Regional Development in Algeria
- Cultural Hybridity and Colonial Influence
- Arabisation Policy and Its Consequences
- Cultural Marginalisation of Amazigh Communities
- Modernisation and Its Tensions with Local Culture
- Cultural Activism and Resistance by Amazigh Communities
- Role of National Policy in Cultural Development

4.4.4. Document analysis

One of the research methods is document analysis. According to Bowen (2009), Document analysis is viewed as an organised process for the assessment and examination of documents, both printed and electronic material. Like other analytical techniques in qualitative research, document analysis requires the analysis and interpretation of the data for the purpose of achieving significance, obtaining comprehension, and improving empirical information (Corbin and Strauss, 2008; Rapley, 2007).

The documents that are used in this method vary from one study to another. Among the examples of document analysis are manuals, background papers, brochures, press papers, organisational reports, and different public records. The latter two documents, those of organisational reports and public records, are of primary importance in this research. One of the method's merits is the low-cost manner of gaining authentic data for the research (Bowen, 2009).

Bryman (2012: 549) highlights that “The state is the source of a great deal of information of potential significance for social researchers”, and this was especially the case for detecting and examining data for intangible cultural heritage, which looks at the safeguarding of intangible heritage in Amazigh culture.

To analyse and contextualise UNESCO's interest in Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH) and the development of its 2003 Convention, this study will utilise comprehensive online resources, particularly the UNESDOC database. UNESDOC is a UNESCO digital repository containing over 350,000 documents dating back to 1945, which provides extensive material relevant to the organisation's evolving focus on ICH. For this research, an in-depth exploration of the database will be undertaken, targeting a variety of document types, including working papers, conference papers, and reports. Additionally, the search will include resolutions and decisions of the General Conference, publications endorsed by UNESCO, as well as Director-General speeches from 1970 onwards.

This exploration will also extend to materials that elucidate Algeria's engagement with ICH policies within UNESCO's framework. Algeria's role in the safeguarding and promotion of ICH is notably relevant, given the country's emphasis on heritage preservation in alignment with the 2003 UNESCO Convention. The analysis will examine Algeria's policy approaches concerning ICH, including legislative measures, funding allocations, and institutional support mechanisms aimed at preserving its rich and diverse cultural heritage. The study will particularly focus on Algerian initiatives that align with UNESCO's guidelines on ICH, assessing how national policies have been influenced by and contribute to the objectives set forth by UNESCO. Through this analysis, the study aims to capture a comprehensive view of UNESCO's influence on Algeria's heritage preservation framework, revealing how international conventions intersect with national policy efforts to safeguard cultural heritage in Algeria.

In qualitative studies, document analysis plays a central role in creating rich descriptions of phenomena or events (Stake, 1995; Yin, 1994). Merriam (1988) highlights the potential of diverse document types to aid researchers in uncovering meanings, broadening understanding, and generating insights relevant to the research inquiry. Additionally, Yin (2014) suggests that using documents is essential for corroborating and bolstering evidence obtained from other sources in case study research, further supporting the integrity of the findings.

4.5. Study Sample and Data Collection

This section describes what criteria were used to select the sample and what sampling methodology was used to select it, along with the sample size and details of data collection. Van den Broeck et al. (2013) defined the population of research as the target population that research intends to study. Because of the population size, it is unrealistic to recruit and deal

with the whole population; instead, researchers choose a sample to represent it. As Fink (2003: 1) states, “a sample is a proportion or subset of a larger group called a population...A good sample is a miniature version of the population of which it is a part, just like it, only smaller.”. A ‘sample’ is also a selected statistical representative group of a larger population (Acharya, 2013; Kamangar and Islami, 2013). To obtain a representative sample from the target population in quantitative research, many strategies are used (Kamangar and Islami, 2013). These strategies are referred to as sampling strategies, and these strategies depend on the type of research, the population attributes, and the level of significance (Majid, 2018).

4.5.1. Sample selection method and criteria

This study employs a non-probability purposive criterion sampling method, a widely accepted approach in qualitative research that focuses on selecting participants based on specific attributes rather than randomness (Trochim, 2006). As Marshall (1996) notes, while quantitative research seeks a representative population for generalisation, qualitative research prioritises capturing the sample’s reflection on phenomena of interest. Purposive sampling aligns with this objective by allowing researchers to identify individuals who possess specific characteristics relevant to the study. According to Klenke (2008), this method ensures an appropriate and targeted sample, enabling in-depth exploration of the research topic. Yin (2003) supports the application of non-probability sampling in qualitative research, emphasising that small sample sizes are not a limitation, as the focus is on real-life phenomena rather than statistical generalisations. The sample for this study was chosen based on four criteria: ethnicity, gender, role in society, and setting. Participants were all Algerian Amazigh women, mothers, or grandmothers, residing in regions historically associated with major Amazigh ethnic groups. These regions include Tizi Ouzou, which is home to the Kabyle, Batna, which is the land of the Chaouia, Ghardaia, which is home to the Mzab community, and Tamanrasset, which is predominantly inhabited by the Tuareg (for the numbers of participants by region see Table 4.1 below). This selection was made due to the scant attention given to Amazigh culture by both academic research and governmental or non-governmental organisations. Additionally, in a patriarchal society with a strong religious foundation, such as Algeria, the critical role of women in preserving and transmitting cultural traditions has often been overlooked (Salhi, 2010).

The participants were chosen for several reasons. First, they represent the largest Amazigh groups in Algeria, making the data both accessible and comprehensive. Second, mothers and grandmothers are cultural pillars within their communities, playing a central role in intergenerational cultural transmission and making them invaluable sources of information. Third, including diverse ethnicities ensures a holistic understanding of Amazigh culture as an umbrella term encompassing various minority groups. Fourth, each ethnic group has its own distinct cultural practices and traditions, necessitating an individualised approach to reflect their contributions while acknowledging their shared origins accurately. Finally, this research addresses a significant gap in Algerian academic discourse, where the role of women in cultural preservation and participation has not been adequately emphasised.

Participants were fully informed about the study's purpose, their voluntary participation, and their right to withdraw at any time (see information sheet in Appendix I). Measures were taken to safeguard their privacy and ensure anonymity if requested, and furthermore, informants consented orally to the interview. By selecting participants based on these rigorous criteria and adhering to ethical research practices, this study aims to provide an in-depth exploration of the role of Amazigh women in cultural preservation and transmission, offering valuable insights into an underrepresented aspect of Algeria's cultural heritage.

4.5.2. Sample size

This research acknowledges the ongoing debate among qualitative researchers regarding ideal sample sizes. Beitin (2012) notes that an appropriate sample size can range from 6 to 12 participants, depending on the study's aims and context. Marshall (1996) highlights that quantitative researchers often misunderstand the value of small sample sizes in qualitative research, arguing that the pursuit of generalisation should not be the aim of any well-designed study. Instead, qualitative research prioritises depth of analysis, where small samples can provide richer and more nuanced insights (Gerring, 2004). Unlike quantitative research, qualitative sample sizes cannot be calculated using a formula; instead, the optimal size is determined by the sufficiency to address the research question (Marshall, 1996).

Crouch and McKenzie (2006) emphasise the advantages of small sample sizes in qualitative research, noting that a smaller group allows researchers to develop stronger connections with participants, which in turn enhances the quality and validity of the findings. Davidson (2006) acknowledges the difficulty of defending the representativeness of a sample in non-probability

sampling. However, O'Leary (2014) argues that qualitative research often seeks a rich and detailed understanding that can be achieved through studying a few participants rather than many. Thus, a small sample is not inherently a limitation but a methodological strength in qualitative inquiry.

Mason (2010) further examines the factors influencing the determination of sample size in qualitative studies. He explains that sample size is shaped by several variables, including the objectives and aims of the research and the methods employed. The number of participants is often determined by the scope of the research questions and the insights required, with the sample size influencing the methods chosen for data collection and analysis.

In this study, the sample was carefully chosen to address the research objectives while considering practical constraints. The sample comprises 20 Algerian females from four major Amazigh groups: Chaouia, Kabyle, Mzab, and Tuareg. Five participants were selected from each group. Also, four cultural directories managers that represents different Amazigh regions, this composition allows for a balanced exploration of the cultural and social dynamics within each group while ensuring sufficient depth to answer the research questions effectively. The chosen sample reflects the study's focus on understanding the diverse cultural roles and contributions of women within the Amazigh community.

4.5.3. Describing the participants of this study

This section provides a detailed summary of the participants involved in the study. The research employed two distinct types of interviews to gather comprehensive data. First, structured interviews were conducted with four directory managers from different Amazigh regions, focusing on their roles in cultural management and the challenges they face in preserving regional heritage. Second, semi-structured interviews were carried out with twenty Amazigh women from four different locations (Table 4.1 below illustrates the participants). These interviews aimed to capture in-depth insights into their experiences, cultural practices, and perspectives on the preservation and transmission of Amazigh identity. This dual approach enabled the study to explore both institutional and personal dimensions of cultural heritage within the Amazigh community.

Table 4.1: Sample size and location (Amazigh women participants)

Cities	Batna	Ghardaia	Tamanrasset	Tizi-Ouezo
Participants	4	4	4	4
ethnicity	Chaouia	Mzab	Tuareg	Kabyle

The Amazigh women

The data collection involved 20 interviews with Amazigh women and four structured interviews with managers of cultural institutions. This blend of perspectives provided a holistic understanding of the complexities surrounding intangible cultural heritage in Amazigh communities. Conducted primarily in Arabic, the interviews were translated into English for analysis. In cases where participants only spoke Tamazight, their daughters or granddaughters assisted in real-time translation. This facilitated a natural flow of communication while ensuring cultural sensitivity.

The participants represent a diverse group of women aged 45 to 67, offering perspectives that span middle-aged to senior life stages. The majority are in their late 50s and 60s, reflecting mature individuals with extensive life experiences, while a smaller segment aged 60 and above provides valuable insights into senior perspectives, particularly in the realms of family traditions and cultural preservation. Professionally, participants come from varied backgrounds. Six participants are teachers or retired educators, highlighting their involvement in community-centric and educational roles. Several identify as housewives, emphasising their perspectives rooted in family life and cultural transmission. A smaller but distinct group comprises nomads, whose experiences reflect unique challenges related to preserving oral traditions and cultural identity amidst modernisation. One participant works in government sectors, offering policy-related perspectives, while additional roles include retired professionals, nurses, and individuals engaged in community-integrated activities, showcasing the group's broad social representation. Culturally, the participants predominantly identify as Amazigh, representing diverse ethnic groups, including Kabyle, Chaoui, and Tuareg. Kabyle participants, primarily from Tizi Ouzou, emphasise the importance of their linguistic and cultural heritage. Chaoui participants from Batna highlight their distinct linguistic traits and regional identity. Tuareg participants from Tamanrasset bring unique perspectives tied to nomadic traditions, oral

heritage, and traditional crafts. While most participants strongly align with Amazigh identities, some also identify with broader Arab Algerian or mixed heritage, reflecting Algeria’s complex cultural background. Across the group, there is a shared advocacy for the preservation of Tamazight and other regional languages, underscoring a strong sense of cultural pride. However, nuanced tensions exist between regional identities and the broader national narrative.

As all participants are women, their responses provide a focused lens on gendered roles in cultural preservation and family dynamics. Women emerge as cultural keepers, holding a pivotal role in preserving oral traditions, crafts, and intergenerational transmission of cultural values. Their contributions are central to community building and the continuity of cultural identity.

Regionally, participants come from diverse areas across Algeria, reflecting the country’s geographical and cultural diversity (see Table 4.2 below for participants' regional composition). From Tizi Ouzou, where Kabyle heritage and cultural activism are prominent, to Batna, where Chaoui identity intersects with industrialisation, and Ghardaia, with its Mزاب Valley traditions and inter-community dynamics, the responses reveal rich regional nuances. Participants from Tamanrasset provide insights into Tuareg nomadic culture and the challenges posed by modernisation and globalisation. The mix of urban and rural perspectives further enriches the narrative, offering varied views on cultural practices, preservation, and challenges. This demographic composition highlights the participants’ critical roles in shaping and sustaining Algeria’s rich cultural landscape, navigating the intersections of tradition, modernity, and regional diversity.

Table 4.2: Participants' regional composition

Location	Batna	Ghardaia	Tamanrasset	Tizi ouezo
participant	1	1	1	1
Duration of interview	45mn	40mn	35mn	40mn
Interview setting	Office	office	Office	Office

The cultural directors' managers

In the diverse cultural landscape of Algeria, professionals engaged in cultural management and preservation across various regions encounter unique challenges that require a nuanced understanding and sensitive approaches.

In Tizi Ouzou, a director tasked with decision-making and revising agreements must adeptly balance the imperative of cultural preservation with the forces of modernisation. This region is the home of Kabyle identity and Amazigh heritage, where the community places immense value on maintaining their distinct cultural practices and traditions. One of the central challenges is navigating language politics. The Tamazight language is a cornerstone of Amazigh culture, and ensuring its survival and promotion within educational, administrative, and cultural institutions is paramount. However, negotiating agreements that uphold Tamazight can be complex within a centralised state structure that has historically favoured Arabic, potentially leading to tensions. Additionally, the director is always mindful of political sensitivities, as Tizi Ouzou has been a focal point for activism advocating for Amazigh cultural rights. Managing relationships between local cultural institutions and national authorities involves addressing politically sensitive issues that could impact cultural projects.

In Batna, a duty manager responsible for supervising workers and site management faces challenges related to cultural diversity in the workforce. The region is home to both Chaoui Amazigh and Arab populations, leading to a blend of languages, work styles, and cultural expectations. These differences may result in communication barriers or workplace tensions that require careful management to foster a cohesive and collaborative environment. The duty manager must also address the tension between industrialisation and cultural integrity. As Batna is a semi-industrial region, integrating modern industrial practices can sometimes clash with local cultural values. Workers, particularly from Chaoui communities with strong ties to their heritage, may perceive modernisation efforts as threats to traditional ways of life. Furthermore, with ongoing urbanisation, preserving local customs within rapidly changing urban settings poses a challenge. Balancing operational efficiency with respect for cultural practices, including traditional social structures and religious observances, demands sensitivity and adaptability.

In Ghardaia, the director is also in charge of events that focus on cultural identity and community engagement and must navigate the complexities of religious and cultural conservatism. The region is deeply rooted in the Ibadi sect of Islam, which adheres to strict codes of conduct. Organising cultural events here involves understanding and respecting these social norms, as certain forms of cultural expression, such as specific types of music, dance, or modern art, may be considered inappropriate or conflicting with religious values. The organiser also faces the challenge of addressing inter-community conflicts. The Mزاب Valley, where Ghardaia is located, has experienced tensions between the Mزاب community (Amazigh, Ibadi Muslims) and Arab populations (often Sunni Muslims). Creating cultural events that are inclusive and acceptable to all groups requires careful consideration of historical grievances and social divides. Additionally, the organiser must work on maintaining tradition in a globalised world. Engaging the younger generation, who may be more attracted to modern or international forms of entertainment, involves finding a balance between innovation and the preservation of traditional cultural practices.

In Tamanrasset, the head of the department responsible for renovation and cultural preservation confronts the challenge of protecting traditional nomadic culture. This region is predominantly Tuareg, and their nomadic way of life is threatened by factors such as modernisation, desertification, and economic shifts. Renovation and preservation efforts must respect and reflect the nomadic traditions while accommodating practical needs like tourism development and modern infrastructure. The influence of globalisation and tourism presents a dual challenge. While tourism can provide economic benefits and increased visibility for Tuareg culture, it also risks commodifying and potentially diluting authentic cultural practices. Ensuring that preservation projects maintain the integrity of Tuareg culture rather than exploiting it for tourism is crucial. Moreover, the head of direction must contend with issues of cultural marginalisation. The Tuareg people have historically been underrepresented in national dialogues, and advocating for greater recognition and resources at the national level is essential. Preserving local autonomy in decision-making processes while seeking national support involves a delicate balance to ensure that cultural preservation efforts are practical and respectful of the community's needs.

Across these regions, professionals must employ culturally sensitive strategies that honour local traditions while navigating the complexities of modernisation, political dynamics, and social change. Their roles are critical in creating cultural preservation, promoting inclusive

community engagement, and ensuring that Algeria's rich cultural diversity is sustained for future generations.

Both the Amazigh women and the managers demonstrated familiarity with key concepts, including heritage, preservation, transmission, and identity, which facilitated discussions. Interviews with Amazigh women were conducted primarily in participants' homes, a choice they made for the familiarity and comfort it offered, helping them feel at ease and encouraging open, authentic exchanges. This setting also minimised scheduling challenges, with interviews typically held in the afternoon and evening to allow time for extended conversation.

The data collection phase lasted approximately six months, from June to December 2023. However, participant recruitment commenced in late 2021, with adjustments made as needed to address unforeseen events such as the COVID-19 pandemic and participant availability changes. These disruptions required a flexible approach to data collection, underscoring the importance of adaptive planning in qualitative research.

Ethical considerations were a core component of the data collection process. Participants were provided with informed consent forms, translated, when necessary, to ensure complete and full understanding of the study's aims, data usage, and their rights. Confidentiality and anonymity were rigorously maintained: pseudonyms were used for all participants, and identifying details were removed from the data records and final report.

4.5.4. Describing the document sample in this study

The preservation and promotion of intangible cultural heritage (ICH) rely on international frameworks and national policies that guided this document analysis of this research. In this part, the following are samples of documents analysed in chapter 5 and chapter 7.

Table 4.3: Sample of documents analysed

Documents Alignment	Documents titles
Global Frameworks by UNESCO	<p>Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage (2003): A foundational treaty establishing definitions, objectives, and measures for ICH preservation.</p> <p>UNESCO 2003 Convention Ethical Principles for Safeguarding ICH: Guidance on ethical considerations for respecting and safeguarding cultural heritage.</p> <p>Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity: Showcasing diverse cultural practices and expressions globally.</p> <p>List of Intangible Cultural Heritage in Need of Urgent Safeguarding: Highlighting cultural elements at risk and requiring immediate action.</p> <p>Recommendation on the Safeguarding of Traditional Culture and Folklore (1989): A precursor to the 2003 Convention, focusing on traditional cultural expressions.</p> <p>Proclamation of Masterpieces of the Oral and Intangible Heritage of Humanity (1997–2003): Recognising outstanding examples of intangible cultural heritage.</p>
	<p>Address by Koïchiro Matsuura (2006): Delivered during the first session of the Intergovernmental Committee for ICH Safeguarding in Algiers, emphasising Algeria’s role in implementing the 2003 Convention.</p>

<p>UNESCO and Algeria's Contributions to ICH</p>	<p>UNESDOC Materials Related to Algeria: Documentation of Algeria-specific cultural heritage initiatives.</p>
<p>Cultural Practices and Expressions in Algeria</p>	<p>Knowledge and Skills of the Water Measurers of the Foggaras (Touat and Tidikelt): Traditional irrigation techniques unique to Algerian communities.</p> <p>Rituals and Ceremonies of Sebeïba in Djanet: An annual festival fostering social cohesion and cultural identity.</p> <p>Practices and Knowledge Linked to the Imzad of the Tuareg Communities: Musical traditions shared across Algeria, Mali, and Niger.</p>
<p>Algerian National Policies on ICH</p>	<p>Law No. 98-04 (June 15, 1998): Legislation concerning the protection of cultural heritage in Algeria.</p> <p>Executive Decree No. 03-325 (October 15, 2003): Establishing procedures for storing intangible cultural heritage in the National Data Bank.</p>
<p>Algeria and Amazigh policies</p>	<p>Plans from the High Commission for Amazighity (HCA)</p> <p>Reports on Arabization Policies Post-Independence</p> <p>Reports on Women's Role in Amazigh Culture</p> <p>Studies on French Colonial Impact</p>

4.6. Data Analysis

The initial feature of analysing qualitative data centres around coding and categorising the information collected, then organising it into themes. As Miles and Huberman (1994: 12) describe data analysis as a non-linear process, as shown in Figure 4.2 below, that is continuous, iterative, and cyclical, with stages that occur concurrently, alternately, or are repeated throughout the analysis. The reason for this choice is the flexibility it offers in managing data by providing a comprehensive, in-depth account of the data (Braun and Clarke, 2006; King, 2004).

Figure 4.2: Process of analysing data

Source: Miles and Huberman (1994)

In the context of this study, thematic analysis was chosen and used, as it is the process of defining patterns in qualitative research. Braun and Clarke (2006) argue that it offers core skills that are valuable for carrying out analysis. Furthermore, thematic analysis depends on stages shown in Figure 4.3 below, which facilitate the process of dealing with quantitative data such as familiarisation, coding, generating themes, reviewing the emerged themes, and forming reports (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

Figure 4.3: Six-phase framework for doing a thematic analysis

Source: Braun and Clarke (2006)

It is essential to comprehend the extensive data obtained and to identify the patterns because as Patton (2002), argues it is through this process data significance is derived. The data for this study is gathered from interviews and document analysis which requires the use of themes to organise and develop the initial data to comprehensive findings.

In this investigation, Microsoft Excel version 2307 (released in September 2023) (Microsoft, 2024) was utilised to analyse qualitative and quantitative data. Although primarily designed as spreadsheet software, Microsoft Excel is highly flexible and capable of supporting a wide range of research tasks. Its ability to handle large datasets makes it particularly effective for storing and managing both qualitative and quantitative data efficiently (Brookfield, 2021). While primarily associated with numerical data, Excel offers valuable features for qualitative data analysis (Brookfield, 2021). For instance, after transcribing qualitative data, researchers can use Excel to create tables summarising codes or themes (see Appendix VI and VII). The filter function can then isolate data linked to specific themes, facilitating targeted analysis and interpretation. Additionally, conditional formatting allows for colour-coding of text related to themes, enabling quick identification of keywords and patterns (Brookfield, 2021). Excel also provides flexibility in importing data, with tab-delimited files being particularly advantageous for storing and transferring data (Meyer and Avery, 2009). This format allows researchers to organise different interviews on separate tabs within the same file for ease of access and comparison. To analyse the data collected from interviews, the following steps were

undertaken: Organising Data: Responses were arranged into rows, with columns categorising participant attributes such as age, occupation, responses, and themes. Coding Data: A column for "Codes" or "Themes" was added, descriptive codes were assigned to summarise content, and colour-coding was used to highlight similar themes. Sorting and Filtering: The filter function was used to view data points associated with specific codes or themes. Frequency Analysis: The occurrences of codes or themes were counted using Excel's tools. Text Analysis: Keywords were identified using Excel's search features. Summarising Data: Themes and patterns were documented in separate sheets for further analysis. It is important to acknowledge that no software, regardless of its sophistication or cost, can independently analyse qualitative data. The analytical process relies fundamentally on the researcher's interpretation, critical thinking, and ability to discern meaningful patterns (Eliot, 2011).

In the data preparation phase, the researcher familiarising themselves with the data is a key factor in the analysis. In this phase, the researcher is required to engage deeply with the data, becoming thoroughly acquainted by reading through it many times while making preliminary analytical notes and observations and listening to any audio-recorded material at least once, if applicable (Braun and Clarke, 2006). In this study, the interviews were transcribed in Word format and translated from Arabic to English, as the interviews were conducted in Arabic, similar to the documents related to the Algerian policies on culture and Amazigh. The transcripts and translated versions were read through and analysed initially to develop a thorough grasp of the data and findings.

The second phase of coding, as described by Rubin and Rubin (2005), is the organisation and labelling of the emerged concepts, themes, and events, systematically to facilitate the retrieval and analysis of all data units referring to the same subject across interviews. The pictures below illustrate the coding process, and the codes created from both interviews conducted. Braun and Clarke (2006) add that coding is more than a method for reducing data; it is also an analytical process in which codes reflect both the explicit meaning and underlying concepts within the data. The data from the interviews and the fieldnotes related to concepts and understanding of the beliefs, perceptions, experiences, and knowledge of Amazigh women, which required an interpretivist analysis to elicit the meanings and non-direct statements from which specific themes in this research emerged.

4.6.1. Generating themes

A theme is defined by Braun and Clarke (2013: 2-3) as “a coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question”. Themes significantly help with the process of finalising the findings and the discussion. This section deals with the themes generated from the community interviews. In order to best support the development of the findings’ narrative, a detailed table giving the themes generated and their respective codes can be found in chapter 6, section 3.

The initial themes were deduced by reading through the data, and then codes were created from the data under each theme. I worked on the sub-themes and their relevance in an inductive manner, attempting to capture the implicit meaning of statements and analyse them. Braun and Clarke (2013) advise researchers to adopt this technique in their analysis journey by stating that conducting a thorough analysis of each theme requires the researcher to delve deeply into the essence of the data, articulating a comprehensive understanding of each theme. This process involves the researcher questioning, "What narrative does this theme convey?" and "How does this theme integrate into the broader storyline of the data?" Such reflection aids in uncovering the core message of each theme and constructing a concise, impactful, and descriptive label that accurately encapsulates its significance.

After identifying the general themes and subthemes and interview fragments, the data was exported to a Microsoft Excel sheet as shown below, which created an organised set of information easy to process and report on. This process was very beneficial for visualising the data themes of the study. An example of the exported Excel file for the interviews with Amazigh women can be seen in Appendix IV. At the same time, Appendix V has an example of the exported Excel file from the data collected in interviews with managers.

In the process of reviewing themes, as outlined by Braun and Clarke (2013), the researcher ensured that each theme aligned effectively with the coded extracts and the entire dataset. This step involved reflecting on whether the themes convey a coherent, compelling narrative about the data, defining each theme's nature and understanding the relationships among them. At this point, modifications and adjustments are necessary, such as merging themes that have the same concept or idea as “Collective Practices and Communal Solidarity Among Amazigh Women”. For example, in chapter 7, the themes of Arabisation and Cultural Assimilation were merged under Cultural Hybridity (see section 2). It was also necessary to divide themes, as in

chapter 6, where Amazigh women's adversities were divided into three sections: hardship of life, patriarchal kinship, and access to education (see sections 6.4.1, 6.4.2, 6.4.3, and 6.4.4). In this research, the intertwining complexity of codes reflects the nuanced nature of Amazigh identity. For instance, being Amazigh once signified marginalisation, particularly before the governmental initiatives to promote and recognise Amazigh identity in political and social discourse in Algeria, such as recognising Tamazight language in 2002 and its application in 2016 (chapter 5 section 4).

Defining and naming themes requires a focused analysis of each pattern. The analysis starts by attempting to answer what this pattern means or implies, which facilitates the process of naming themes, as the name will encapsulate the significance of the theme. The final stage of writing up is a fundamental part of the analysis. According to Braun and Clarke (2013), this involves linking together the narrative with illustrative data extracts to create a cohesive, persuasive story that situates the findings within existing literature, which can be seen in Chapters 6, 7 and 8 of the thesis.

Writing up entails mapping and interpreting themes by integrating field notes, interviews, and if applicable photographs. Once all data is organised into themes and subthemes, the analysis shifts into the comparative phase, building a narrative that presents qualitative data comprehensively. This method demands precise focus to unify all components, from the questions of the research to link to the theoretical framework and results discussion.

4.7. Research Quality and Ethics

This section outlines the established guidelines implemented to ensure the research meets both quality standards and ethical requirements. It addresses two key questions: How is research quality maintained in this thesis? What ethical principles have been adhered to? These questions are explored in detail in the subsequent subsections.

The final steps in this chapter address data analysis and ethical considerations. Data analysis is presented as a systematic yet interpretative process, wherein data is meticulously organised and examined to reveal thematic patterns. Ethical considerations are also acknowledged as a foundational aspect of this research, given the significance of cultural sensitivity and respect in engaging with community-based heritage issues. These ethical principles guide the study to ensure that it respects the cultural values and perspectives of all participants involved.

In order to validate the integrity of this research, the thesis complied with the ethical application guidelines of the University of the West of Scotland. As Stake (2000: 447) declares, “qualitative researchers are guests in the private spaces of the world. Their manners should be good and their code of ethics strict”. Those strict codes protect the participants and prioritise their welfare, ensuring that an explanation of the research and its purpose will be provided to the participants. The safety of the participants can be assured not only by protecting their confidentiality but also by ensuring that they are treated with respect for their needs and feelings (Polkinghorne, 2005). It is vital that the participants know that they are volunteering in the study, and they can withdraw anytime they feel uncomfortable, refuse to answer specific questions during the interview as they wish, or are unwilling to continue. They will be informed that they are recorded to give their consent and sign a form or refuse to. The participants will also be informed that the gathered data as part of this research will be protected securely, in accordance with the Data Protection Act 2018⁴¹. To meet these requirements, the data collected, and its analysis should be transparent to researchers who may review them and use them as a part of their studies (Polkinghorne, 2005).

Ensuring validity and reliability is essential for upholding the rigour and credibility of qualitative research. These concepts are particularly significant in studies exploring complex and nuanced phenomena, such as intangible cultural heritage and the role of Amazigh women in its preservation. Through adopting robust strategies to address both validity and reliability, this research aims to produce findings that are meaningful and credible.

Patton (2001) underscores the importance of these factors in every stage of qualitative research, from design to analysis and evaluation. This perspective resonates with the foundational question posed by Lincoln and Guba (1985, p. 290): "How can an inquirer persuade their audience that the findings of a study are credible and worthy of attention?" By addressing this question, this study seeks to ensure that its methodology and outcomes are both methodologically sound and academically compelling.

Validity has been addressed through measures enhancing internal and external validity. Internal validity was achieved by aligning research methods with objectives, employing semi-structured interviews to explore the lived experiences of Amazigh women, and structured interviews with cultural managers to collect policy-related insights. Braun and Clarke’s (2006)

thematic analysis provided a systematic approach to identifying themes, while triangulation—integrating interviews and document analysis bolstered the credibility of findings. Although qualitative research emphasises depth over generalizability, external validity was strengthened by sampling participants from four major Amazigh groups, offering a diverse representation of regional and cultural contexts (Palinkas et al., 2013). Construct validity was ensured by grounding the study in established theoretical frameworks (Waterman, 2013), aligning interview questions with research objectives, and employing Excel for systematic data organisation and interpretation.

In quantitative research, reliability is primarily defined as the capacity to replicate both the processes and the results with precision. However, this definition is less applicable to qualitative research due to its diverse paradigms and epistemological foundations, which emphasise context and subjectivity over replication (Leung, 2015). Despite its quantitative origins, the concept of reliability is relevant across all research methodologies. In qualitative research, reliability is better understood as the overall quality of the study. A well-designed qualitative study can provide valuable insights, helping to clarify and deepen understanding of situations that might otherwise remain ambiguous or complex (Eisner, 1991, p. 58).

In this study, reliability was ensured through consistent data collection methods, including semi-structured and structured interviews. The methodology was thoroughly documented, detailing participant selection, data collection, and analysis procedures to enable replicability. Reflexivity and the systematic use of Excel for coding and theme development minimised subjectivity. Additionally, triangulation and member checking strengthened the study's reliability by cross-verifying data from multiple sources and engaging participants in validating the findings.

4.8. Conclusion

In summary, this chapter outlines the methodological framework employed in this qualitative study, which adopts a constructivist approach to gain a nuanced understanding of Amazigh women's lived experiences and struggles through data triangulation involving interviews, field notes, reflexivity, and document analysis. The study aims to provide a comprehensive interpretation of reality. The study used non-probability sampling techniques to select informants, ensuring diversity to enrich findings. The thematic analysis approach, as outlined by Braun and Clarke, guided the organisation and analysis of the fieldwork data, systematically moving from initial coding to thematic development, which supports the final write-up and discussion necessary to answer the research questions.

In conclusion, the methodological framework outlined in this chapter is designed to address the unique requirements of heritage studies, which often involve complex social, cultural, and political dynamics. The multi-method qualitative approach, grounded in a socio-critical paradigm, provides an effective means for exploring the nuanced dimensions of intangible cultural heritage. By integrating multiple data sources and employing a triangulation strategy, this study aims to provide a comprehensive, nuanced analysis that contributes to a deeper understanding of cultural preservation and identity within the contemporary Algerian context. This chapter, therefore, lays the groundwork for the research, presenting a methodological foundation that aligns with the study's objectives, theoretical framework, and the broader field of heritage studies.

The data collection process for this study combined a rigorous and adaptive approach to capture diverse insights into intangible cultural heritage within Amazigh communities. By incorporating semi-structured interviews and a review of secondary resources, the study achieved a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the subject. An ethical, participant-centred approach was maintained throughout, ensuring that data collection not only upheld academic rigour but also respected the personal and cultural sensitivities of participants. This thorough data collection framework enabled the study to offer significant, culturally embedded insights into the roles, perceptions, and challenges of intangible heritage preservation in Algeria.

Chapter Five - Safeguarding Intangible Cultural Heritage: UNESCO's Framework and Algeria's Multifaceted Commitment to Preservation, Policy Evolution, and Cultural Diversity

Cultural heritage is a vital element in connecting generations, encapsulating a nation's identity, culture, and historical narrative. In the Algerian context, it is critical to prioritise the protection of the cultural diversity and the preservation of the cultural heritage in all its forms. The focus of this study is the promotion and safeguarding of Amazigh intangible cultural heritage (ICH) and the role of women in this endeavour. Algeria has linked national policies with international frameworks to safeguard Algerian ICH, as a member of the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO), the nation is working on preserving all forms of ICH such as oral traditions, performing arts, rituals, and traditional knowledge.

This chapter explores the link between UNESCO's evolving ICH policies and Algeria's national strategies. It highlights Algeria's proactive approach in ratifying the 2003 UNESCO Convention, its legislative efforts to protect heritage, and its challenges in implementing these policies effectively. This investigation of the Algerian cultural policies and initiatives aims at exploring the protection and the promotion of Algeria's cultural richness. Ultimately, to also shed light on Algeria's ongoing journey to preserve its heritage amid globalisation and modern pressures.

5.1. UNESCO and Intangible Cultural Heritage

This chapter explores the background of the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO), focusing on its evolving approach to safeguarding cultural heritage, particularly the transition from policies addressing folklore to those concerning intangible cultural heritage (ICH). It examines the key recommendations, conventions, and proclamations that have shaped the global framework for ICH preservation. Algeria, a member state actively involved in implementing UNESCO's ICH policies, serves as a significant example in this discussion. With a diverse cultural landscape encompassing various intangible traditions, Algeria has leveraged UNESCO's frameworks to safeguard its heritage. Through initiatives like the 2003 Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage and the cultural policies of the states, Algeria has implemented measures to identify, document, and promote its rich cultural practices, aligning national efforts with international priorities (Kessab, 2008). This section

dives into these global and local efforts, highlighting their interconnectedness and impact on the preservation of cultural diversity.

5.1.1. UNESCO's background

The United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO), like many global institutions, was established in the aftermath of severe wars with the goal of creating a culture of peace among nations. Its foundation was initiated at a conference in London in November 1945, attended by representatives from 44 nations (UNESCO, 1945). The organisation officially came into existence on November 16, 1945, and began its operations on November 4, 1946 (UNESCO, 1945).

The preamble of UNESCO's constitution emphasises its mission to spread culture and educate humanity in the principles of justice, liberty, and peace, stating that such efforts are "indispensable to the dignity of man and constitute a sacred duty which all the nations must fulfil in a spirit of mutual assistance and concern" (UNESCO, 1945:2). The organisation is headquartered at Place de Fontenoy, Paris, and operates through a vast network, including 22 National Offices, 11 Regional Bureaux, 27 Cluster Offices covering 113 Member States, and 4 Liaison Offices. Despite its extensive reach, Seeger (2015: 132) describes UNESCO as a large and complex institution that is often overextended and under-resourced.

From its inception, the conservation and promotion of cultural heritage have been central to UNESCO's mission, as articulated in Article 1, Paragraph 2 of its constitution. This article highlights the importance of "assuring the conservation and protection of the world's inheritance of books, works of art, and monuments of history and science, and recommending to the nations concerned the necessary international conventions" (UNESCO, 1945). While cultural heritage was a foundational concern, its most significant recognition came with the adoption of the World Heritage Convention in 1972. This landmark convention introduced three key principles: first, it asserted that certain properties possess universal value and must be preserved; second, it defined heritage primarily in terms of material, immovable assets, excluding intangible heritage; and third, it distinguished between natural and cultural heritage, despite the differences in managing these domains (Batisse and Bolla, 2005). However, as Lixinski (2013: 11) notes, "The fact that the World Heritage Convention neglected an important part of cultural heritage was considered from its adoption a shortcoming of international regimes focusing on protection of cultural heritage." This omission, particularly regarding intangible heritage, led to the development of new frameworks

and concepts for heritage management, broadening the scope of international efforts to safeguard cultural heritage in its diverse forms.

5.2. UNESCO and Folklore Policies

The legal framework for the protection of intangible cultural heritage (ICH), historically referred to as folklore, is a relatively modern development. The emergence of international treaties and laws in this area can be traced back to the 1950s (Kurin, 2004). Early efforts to legislate and promote the safeguarding of cultural identity began in Japan, which introduced national patrimony laws in the post-World War I era. These measures were driven by the loss of many ancient royal traditions (Jong, 2003; Kurin, 2004). The preservation of cultural properties also gained attention as part of broader efforts to combat trafficking and destruction. Early regulations such as the Hague Conventions (1899–1907) focused on the prevention of pillaging, while later agreements, including the 1954 Hague Convention for the Protection of Cultural Property in the Event of Armed Conflict, emphasised that harm to cultural property represents a loss for all of humanity (UNESCO, 1954). The 1954 Convention was the first international legal instrument to formally introduce the concept of "cultural property" into international law.

Recognizing that cultural property has suffered grave damage during recent armed conflicts and that, by reason of the developments in the technique of warfare, it is in increasing danger of destruction.

Being convinced that damage to cultural property belonging to any people whatsoever means damage to the cultural heritage of all mankind, since each people makes its contribution to the culture of the world;

Considering that the preservation of the cultural heritage is of great importance for all peoples of the world and that it is important that this heritage should receive international protection;

Guided by the principles concerning the protection of cultural property during armed conflict, as established in the Conventions of The Hague of 1899 and of 1907 and in the Washington Pact of 15 April 1935;

Being of the opinion that such protection cannot be effective unless both national and international measures have been taken to organise it in time of peace,

*Being determined to take all possible steps to protect cultural property,*⁴²

While folklore was initially categorised as part of cultural property, its conceptual evolution was significant in shaping the modern understanding of ICH. As Bortolotto (2007: 21) explains, “the reflection on what was formerly known as ‘folklore’ by UNESCO was an important stage in the shift toward the idea of intangible heritage.” According to her, UNESCO's engagement with folklore can be divided into two distinct phases. These phases represent a transition from an archivist approach —focused on documentation and preservation— to a process-oriented approach inspired by Japan's early practices of safeguarding intangible heritage. The first phase of UNESCO's folklore policy began in the 1970s, marking a pivotal shift in international discourse on cultural heritage.

The subsequent sections of this chapter will present a detailed timeline tracing the evolution of intangible cultural heritage policies and the legal frameworks supporting them, from the 1970s to the present day, to provide a comprehensive understanding of their development.

5.2.1. The first folklore policy (1973–1979)

By the early 1970s, global conventions and policies began expanding their scope to encompass broader aspects of heritage protection. A notable milestone was the 1972 World Heritage Convention, which aimed to safeguard the world's natural and cultural heritage, focusing essentially on immovable assets such as monuments, buildings, and sites. However, this treaty excluded intangible and movable heritage, prompting criticism for its narrow definition of heritage (Blakely, 2014). Many nations expressed concerns over the treaty's inability to address the broader dimensions of cultural heritage.

The period between 1972 and 1979 marked a turning point for the preservation of intangible cultural heritage (ICH), with significant progress both within and beyond UNESCO's frameworks. This era occurred with the "nation-building" phase for many newly independent states, which sought to revive and present their cultural identities as a testament to their sovereignty. Examples of this cultural revival include events like the National Cultural Festival in Libreville (1974), the World Festival of Black African Art in Lagos (1977), and academic initiatives such as the Nordic Institute's 1975 investigation into the relationship between copyright and folklore (Sherkin, 2001).

⁴² Convention for the Protection of Cultural Property in the Event of Armed Conflict (1954).

In April 1973, Bolivia's Ministry of Foreign Affairs formally proposed an international treaty to protect "folk properties and culture". This proposal, submitted to UNESCO's intergovernmental copyright committee, led to a study titled "Desirability of Providing Protection for Folklore at the International Level" (UNESDOC, 1977), accredited in December 1975. By November 1976, at a conference in Nairobi, UNESCO launched its first formal ICH program, focusing on preserving nations' lifestyles, traditions, and cultural identities.

In July 1977, UNESCO convened a committee of experts, including lawyers and folklorists, in Tunis to address the challenges facing ICH, including its definition, identification, conservation, preservation, and exploitation. The UNESCO emphasised the need for interdisciplinary examination under its sole auspices to address these issues comprehensively (UNESCO, 1977; Sherkin, 2001). Subsequently, in May 1978, the UNESCO, and the World Intellectual Property Organisation (WIPO) reached an agreement to collaborate on safeguarding ICH. WIPO would handle issues related to copyright and intellectual property, while UNESCO would focus on folklore preservation within a global framework. This partnership culminated in a 1979 convention, although disagreements over the division of responsibilities created stagnation in ICH development during the subsequent decade (Sherkin, 2001).

In August 1979, UNESCO distributed a "Questionnaire on the Protection of Folklore" to member states to identify challenges in ICH preservation. The survey aimed to develop solutions for cultural issues and guide applicable measures for safeguarding folklore. Responses from 71 nations informed the definition of folklore presented at the 1982 Committee of Experts meeting (UNESCO, 1982).

5.2.2. The UNESCO 1980s intangible heritage policy

The 1980s marked significant advancements in the recognition of intangible heritage. At the Mexico City Convention (1982), intangible heritage was officially defined as encompassing "both tangible and intangible works through which the creativity of people finds expression: languages, rites, beliefs, historic places and monuments, literature, works of art, archives, and libraries" (UNESCO, 1982b). Delegates highlighted the importance of intangible elements, emphasizing that buildings and monuments should not dominate heritage discussions. In response, UNESCO established the Committee of Experts on the Safeguarding of Folklore, which included a section dedicated to "Non-Physical Heritage" (Bouchenaki, 2004). This committee

prioritised urgent measures to protect ICH as a critical component of humanity's cultural legacy (UNESCO, 1983). By its second meeting in 1985, the committee deliberated on whether a formal recommendation or convention would be more effective. While some argued that a recommendation would offer flexibility, UNESCO saw it as a foundational step for future developments (UNESCO, 1985, 1987). In 1989, UNESCO adopted the Recommendation on the Safeguarding of Traditional Culture and Folklore, encouraging member states to implement legislative measures and submit reports on their actions. Despite positive feedback, the recommendation faced criticism for its non-binding nature and limited coverage of ICH elements (McCann et al., 2001). Additionally, Park (2013) noted the tendency to treat ICH as an object for public dissemination rather than a dynamic form requiring generational transmission. Nevertheless, the recommendation laid the groundwork for future ICH conventions, which was later highlighted in the 2003 Convention (Blake, 2017).

5.2.3. The UNESCO 1990s intangible heritage policy

The 1990s brought further refinement to ICH policy. In 1992, UNESCO evaluated its cultural activities from the previous two decades, leading to the adoption of the term "Intangible Cultural Heritage" (Aikawa, 2001). A year later, consultations were held to explore new perspectives on ICH, resulting in two key decisions: to pursue innovative safeguarding programs and to launch pilot projects in regions such as China, Niger, Mexico, Tunisia, and Eastern Europe (UNESCO, 1993b). While these efforts raised awareness about the urgency of safeguarding ICH, the scattered nature of ICH elements highlighted the need for a more structured approach to address aspects such as languages, oral traditions, rituals, and performing arts (UNESCO, 1993). A significant breakthrough occurred in 1993, when Ambassador Sang-Seek Park of South Korea proposed the "Living Cultural Properties" system, modelled after practices in Japan, Thailand, and the Philippines. This system identified specific cultural traditions and supported their transmission through governmental laws, ensuring their continuity across generations (Stefano, 2019). The concept of living cultural properties significantly advanced the recognition of communities as active agents in safeguarding ICH, emphasizing the dynamic and evolving nature of cultural heritage. This chronological exploration of ICH policies at UNESCO highlights the gradual evolution from focusing solely on tangible heritage to a comprehensive framework for safeguarding intangible elements. These

efforts emphasise on the importance of adapting heritage policies to address the dynamic, living aspects of culture while ensuring their transmission and preservation for future generations.

5.2.4. The UNESCO 2001 proclamation of the masterpieces of the oral and intangible heritage of humanity

In May 2001, UNESCO headquarters witnessed the initial proclamation of the masterpieces of oral and intangible cultural heritage. According to UNESCO (2001), this proclamation was the outcome of over two decades of dedicated efforts by pioneers and activists committed to safeguarding and preserving traditional cultures. The initiative underscored the urgency of addressing the vulnerabilities of intangible heritage, which had faced significant threats over the years.

The proclamation highlighted that intangible cultural heritage (ICH) was endangered due to various factors, including cultural homogenisation driven by globalisation, armed conflicts, the pressures of tourism and industrialisation, rural-to-urban migration, and environmental degradation (UNESCO 2001). Many cultural traditions were being lost, forgotten, or destroyed, often due to the deaths of practitioners during conflicts or the economic and environmental challenges that forced communities to abandon their legacy. In response, UNESCO outlined three primary objectives: raising awareness about the importance of ICH and its safeguarding, implementing administrative measures to evaluate and protect it, and promoting the active participation of traditional cultures and their custodians (UNESCO, 2006).

To identify and proclaim ICH attributes, UNESCO appointed a jury of eight members tasked with evaluating nominations. These nominations were assessed under two categories: cultural spaces and forms of traditional cultural expression. The criteria for selection required nominees to:

- Demonstrate exceptional value as masterpieces of "human creative genius."
- Establish deep cultural roots within the traditions or historical identity of their communities.
- Reinforce the cultural identity of the communities concerned.
- Exhibit excellence in skill and technical quality.
- Serve as living testimonies of cultural traditions at risk of disappearance (Stefano, 2019).

The proclamation was a milestone in the preservation of ICH, receiving positive recognition for its efforts. Nas (2002: 139) remarked that the initiative was "important ... in that it explicitly

recognises the value of the collective memory of peoples and the inventory of human cultural phenomena." However, critics raised concerns about some limitations of the proclamation. Alivizatou (2007) and Park (2013) argued that the use of the term "masterpiece" implied a hierarchy among cultural heritages, suggesting that certain traditions were deemed less valuable than others. Moreover, the selection process faced challenges due to differing interpretations of culture and its attributes between governments, the public, and cultural custodians (Kurin, 2002).

Financial constraints were another area of critique. Hafstein (2009) noted that the proclamation lacked sufficient financial resources to support preservation efforts, which weakened its overall impact. Despite these criticisms, UNESCO's then Director-General, Koïchiro Matsuura, defended the initiative, asserting that it had been successful in raising global awareness and emphasizing the value of ICH. Matsuura described ICH as "fragile heritage" that required significant attention to prevent its loss and disappearance (UNESCO, 2006).

5.2.5. The UNESCO 2003 convention for the safeguarding of intangible cultural heritage

Following the limitations of the Proclamation of the Masterpieces of Intangible Cultural Heritage, UNESCO sought to advance the safeguarding of intangible cultural heritage (ICH) by developing the 2003 Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage. This marked a significant step forward in addressing the gaps identified in the earlier proclamation.

In February 2000, UNESCO conducted a comprehensive survey among its member states to gather insights into the definitions and inventories of intangible cultural heritage (UNESCO, 2001). The survey aimed to document the diverse elements that constitute cultural heritage, including tangible materials, personal possessions, and intangible attributes. Building on these efforts, a subsequent meeting held in March 2001 in Turin consolidated the collected data and worked towards formulating a universal definition of ICH. UNESCO's working definition emphasised the dynamic and evolving nature of ICH, stating:

"People's learned processes along with the knowledge, skills, and creativity that inform and are developed by them, the products they create and the resources, spaces, and other aspects of the social and natural context necessary to their sustainability; these processes provide living communities with a sense of continuity with previous generations and are important to cultural

identity, as well as to the safeguarding of cultural diversity and creativity of humanity” (UNESCO, 2002).

After extensive deliberation, a report authored by Janet Blake, Preliminary Study on the *“Advisability of Regulating Internationally”*, through a *“New Standard-Setting Instrument, the Protection of Traditional Culture and Folklore”*, was submitted to UNESCO’s General Conference for review in 2001. This document supported the decision to establish an international convention to address the safeguarding of ICH (UNESCO, 2002).

The next significant milestone occurred in January 2002, when a meeting in Rio de Janeiro formally announced the year as the United Nations International Year for Cultural Heritage. This declaration underscored the importance of prioritizing ICH as a central theme. During the meeting, participants worked on drafting the first version of the convention, drawing from the model used for the 1972 convention (UNESCO, 2002). A key focus was refining the definition of ICH to make it both inclusive and accessible. As noted by Zanten (2004: 38), the initial definitions were deemed *“too academic”* for practical use. The final definition adopted was:

“For the purposes of the present Convention, intangible cultural heritage means the practices and representations – together with their necessary knowledge, skills, instruments, objects, artifacts, and places – that are recognised as such by communities and individuals and are consistent with universally accepted principles of human rights, equity, sustainability, and mutual respect between cultural communities. This heritage is constantly recreated by communities in response to their environment and historical conditions of existence and provides them with a sense of continuity and identity, thus promoting cultural diversity and the creativity of humankind”. (UNESCO, 2002)

Based on this definition, UNESCO identified key subcategories of ICH, which include:

- Oral expressions,
- Performing arts,
- Social practices, rituals, and festive events, and
- Knowledge and practices concerning nature (UNESCO, 2002).

These foundational steps laid the groundwork for the 2003 Convention, emphasizing the importance of ICH in fostering cultural diversity and human creativity while ensuring its preservation for future generations.

5.3. Algeria and the UNESCO ICH Policies

An analysis of UNESCO documents on Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH) reveals that Algeria's commitment to safeguarding its intangible cultural heritage began as early as the establishment of the 2003 UNESCO Convention. Algeria underscored its dedication to cultural preservation by becoming the first state to ratify the Convention⁴³ on March 15, 2004⁴⁴, marking a significant milestone in its efforts to protect and promote its rich intangible cultural heritage. Algeria's rich and diverse cultural heritage played a pivotal role in its decision to adopt UNESCO's cultural safeguarding policies. The country's unique cultural landscape highlighted the pressing need to address long-standing community demands for recognition and preservation of their heritage. Reflecting this commitment, Algeria's profile with UNESCO includes seven World Heritage Sites under protection and eleven intangible cultural heritage practices and traditions prioritised for safeguarding.⁴⁵ The country's cultural landscape has been significantly influenced by a series of political, economic, and legal reformations that have promoted cultural expression and heritage preservation. In 1989, political and economic developments offered transformative and constitutional changes, including the 1990 Law on Associations Law 90-31, which allowed the creation of civil organisations and associations. This law facilitated the fast-paced growth of organisations, reaching nearly 110,000 by 2016, and by the 15th of January 2012 it was updated by Law 12-06 to further enhance civic participation in creating and participating in civil, educational, environmental, and cultural work (Bennacer, 2014). These recent developments were underpinned by constitutional measures and official article designed to safeguard cultural heritage. The article 45 of the 2016 Constitution declares the citizen's right to culture and the role of the state in protecting both tangible and intangible heritage⁴⁶ (The national official journal of Algeria, 2016).

⁴³ <https://ich.unesco.org/en/state/algeria-DZ?info=periodic-reporting>

⁴⁴ <https://treaties.un.org/pages/showDetails.aspx?objid=080000028006656f>

⁴⁵ <https://www.unesco.org/en/countries/dz>

⁴⁶ <https://www.joradp.dz/har/consti.htm>

The 1998 Cultural Heritage Law (Law 98-04) marked a significant step in Algeria's efforts to establish a structured and comprehensive framework for heritage preservation. Consisting of over 100 articles, this law laid the foundation for safeguarding both tangible and intangible cultural heritage (ICH) (Ministry of Culture and Arts, 1998). Article 67 specifically defined ICH as encompassing *“social representations, knowledge, skills, and techniques founded on tradition, representing cultural belonging and elements of national identity.”* It further expanded on the domains of ICH, highlighting Algeria's rich and diverse cultural landscape.

The national ICH was described as including various forms of music, traditional songs, and rhythms, alongside modern genres such as Rai and Pop music, as well as theatre, dance, religious rituals, cuisine, oral traditions, folktales, legends, riddles, and proverbs (Ministry of Culture and Arts, 1998). This comprehensive documentation underscored the multifaceted nature of Algerian cultural heritage and reflected the state's intention to protect and promote it. In addition to identifying the elements of ICH to be safeguarded, Articles 68 and 69 outlined measures for its preservation. These provisions aimed to ensure the systematic safeguarding of ICH within a policy framework. However, despite the law's scope, it is notable that out of more than 100 articles, only three specifically addressed intangible heritage. This limited focus indicates that while ICH was recognised as a critical component of Algeria's cultural and national identity, its prioritisation within broader heritage policies remained insufficient. Effective initiatives for the collection, documentation, and digitalisation of ICH were not comprehensively developed under this law, leaving a gap in the preservation of Algeria's intangible heritage. The adoption of the 2003 UNESCO Convention for the Safeguarding of Intangible Cultural Heritage addressed this gap by providing a global framework for protecting ICH. Algeria's ratification of the convention reinforced its commitment to preserving ICH and inspired the development of additional legal measures and regulations. One such measure was Executive Decree 03-325 of 2003, which detailed procedures for identifying and recording ICH in a national database. This decree established protocols for regional departments of culture, emphasizing the need for coordination among institutions, associations, and individuals (Ministry of Culture and Arts, 2003). It also provided guidelines for documenting ICH attributes, ensuring that this vital aspect of Algerian cultural identity would be systematically documented and accessible for future generations.

These developments demonstrate Algeria's evolving approach to ICH preservation, reflecting a growing recognition of its importance as a cornerstone of national identity. However, the challenges associated with integrating ICH into policy frameworks and allocating adequate

resources highlight the need for sustained and focused efforts to ensure the effective safeguarding and promotion of Algeria's intangible cultural heritage (Ministry of Culture and Arts, 2003).

5.3.1. Amazigh cultural practices and knowledge in Algeria within the UNESCO safeguarding framework

The UNESCO's ICH policies highlight the importance of ethnic and local culture traditions, in the context of Algeria, the cultural heritage of the Tuareg communities embodies rich traditions that serve as markers of identity, history, and communal bonds. Among these traditions, Imzad music and the Sebeïba ritual stand out as profound examples of intangible cultural heritage. These practices, deeply rooted in Tuareg society, emphasise the strong link between art, identity, and community. Both traditions, recognised by UNESCO as intangible cultural heritage of humanity, not only celebrate Tuareg identity but also emphasise the importance of safeguarding these practices as national heritage treasures (UNESCO, 2013a; UNESCO, 2013b).

Imzad Music and its cultural significance

Imzad music, a revered traditional art form, is integral to the cultural heritage of the Tuareg communities in Algeria, Mali, and Niger. At the heart of this practice is the Imzad, a single-stringed bowed instrument exclusively played by women, highlighting their unique role in the musical traditions of the Tuareg (Ozah, 2021). Imzad music seamlessly blends instrumental melodies with poetic expression, often performed during ceremonial gatherings in Tuareg camps. These performances narrate and celebrate the adventures and heroic deeds of past figures through poetic or heroic songs composed and recited by Tuareg men. The collective participation of both men and women, who contribute high-pitched tones and cries, enriches the melodic structure, and reinforces communal bonds (UNESCO, 2013a).

This musical tradition is more than mere performance; it acts as a vital mechanism for the transmission and preservation of Tuareg heritage. It encapsulates the cultural values, history, and identity of the Tuareg, fostering continuity across generations. Recognizing its cultural significance and vulnerability, the UNESCO inscribed Imzad music on the Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity during the eighth session of the Intergovernmental Committee in

2013. This designation underscores the global importance of safeguarding such practices, ensuring their sustainability and promotion within and beyond the Tuareg communities⁴⁷.

The Sebeïba ritual in Djanet oasis

The Sebeïba ritual, a significant cultural tradition of the Tuareg community, is practiced in the oasis of Djanet in the Algerian Sahara. This ten-day celebration begins in the first month of the Islamic lunar calendar and culminates in vibrant displays of cultural pride and social unity. The ritual involves a spirited competition known as Timoulawine, held on the ninth day, where male dancers and female singers compete for the honour of representing their respective communities. On the tenth day, which coincides with the tenth day of the lunar month, participants gather at a site called “Loghya,” located between the villages. Dressed in elaborate war costumes, the male dancers, or “tikemsine” in Tamahaq (a Tuareg Tamazight dialect), parade to showcase their costume and weapons in a symbolic performance of Tuareg heritage and identity. The women sing traditional songs to the rhythm of tambourines, adding depth and harmony to the display. The Sebeïba ritual serves not only as a celebration of Tuareg cultural identity but also as a medium for creating social cohesion by performing community rivalries in an artistic manner. The transmission of knowledge about the ritual is deeply embedded in Tuareg society, with older generations teaching younger members about its practices. Local artisans contribute by crafting and maintaining the distinctive costumes, weapons, and instruments essential to the event (CNRPAH, 2014). Recognizing its cultural significance and the need for preservation, UNESCO inscribed the Sebeïba ritual on the Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity during its ninth Intergovernmental Committee session in 2014. This inclusion underscores the ritual's importance as a living testament to the resilience and creativity of Tuareg's traditions (UNESCO, 2013b).

Imzad music and the Sebeïba ritual stand as timeless testaments to the cultural richness and resilience of the Tuareg communities. These traditions transcend mere artistic expression; they serve as witnesses for preserving historical narratives, cultural values, and communal identity. Through the creation of intergenerational transmission and engaging local artisans, these practices

⁴⁷ <https://ich.unesco.org/en/state/algeria-DZ?info=elements-on-the-lists>

remain deeply embedded in Tuareg society, offering a sense of continuity amid the pressures of modernisation and globalisation (UNESCO, 2013a; UNESCO, 2013b).

5.4. An Overview on the Algerian Culture Ministry and the Cultural Policies

The Algerian Ministry of Culture (MOC) serves as the primary authority responsible for formulating and implementing national cultural policies. It comprises various directorates and sectoral departments that support the minister, who is an elected official, in overseeing and coordinating cultural activities and events across the country. Through the minister's directives, cultural organisations align their operations with the MOC's strategic framework, ensuring its implementation at both national and regional levels, as illustrated in the accompanying Figure 5.1 below (Boukrouh and Kessab, 2010).

Figure 5.1: Organisation of the Ministry of Culture (MOC)

Source: Boukrouh and Kessab (2010).

The Ministry of Culture in Algeria engages in inter-ministerial and intergovernmental cooperation; however, according to Boukrouh and Kessab (2010), these collaborations remain insufficient. For example, in cultural preservation, the Ministry of Culture works with the Ministries of Interior, National Defence, and Tourism to combat heritage trafficking. However, communication and coordination within these initiatives is often lacking. This is evidenced by the continued trafficking of tangible heritage across borders, an issue that remains inadequately addressed. Similarly, efforts to digitise intangible cultural heritage (ICH) have been slow, despite Algeria's ratification of the UNESCO 2003 Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage and the adoption of national legislation for ICH protection (Law 04-98).

Since gaining independence in 1962, Algeria's cultural policies have been profoundly shaped by the urgent need to construct a unified national identity after decades of colonial rule. In the post-independence years, efforts were focused on reclaiming Algerian heritage and culture. This process predominantly highlighted the Arab-Islamic attributes shared by much of the population while dismissing the cultural contributions of other ethnic groups, such as the Amazigh (Berber), from national identity discourses.

During President Houari Boumediene's tenure in the 1970s, a "cultural revolution" sought to reinforce an authentic Algerian identity. Boumediene emphasised the promotion of traditional arts, literature, and the Arabic language within a broader Arabisation framework. His policies aimed to eradicate the lingering French cultural influence and establish an Arabic-Algerian identity through reforms in education and cultural promotion (Ruedy, 1992).

Despite these efforts, Algeria faces ongoing challenges in managing and equitably distributing cultural resources across its vast and geographically diverse territory. The remoteness of many governorates (wilayas) from the capital, Algiers, has hindered comprehensive cultural coverage. Algiers, benefiting as the capital, hosts most national cultural events and activities, leading to significant regional disparities. Recognizing this imbalance, policymakers have prioritised decentralisation to redistribute cultural resources and empower regional cultural representation (Boukrouh and Kessab, 2010).

One of the key steps toward decentralisation came in October 1974, when an inter-ministerial jury proposed the experimental establishment of Directorates of Culture and Information in three major governorates: Algiers, Oran, and Constantine. These experimental directorates were later extended nationwide in July 1992 and officially formalised as the current Directorates of Culture in 1994 (Boukrouh and Kessab, 2010). These directorates were tasked with supporting local

cultural activities, managing regional heritage sites, and providing the administrative infrastructure to facilitate provincial cultural expression.

To further promote regional identities, the government implemented a range of local cultural festivals that celebrate regional arts and heritage. Events such as the Amazigh Cultural Festival, the Tuareg Music and Songs Festival in Tamanrasset, and the Local Festival for Kabyle Music and Songs in Tizi Ouzou have been designed to support local cultural expression and foster pride in regional identities (Boukrouh and Kessab, 2010).

Although these decentralisation policies represent progressive steps, their impact has been uneven. Algiers continues to command a disproportionate share of national funding and institutional support, leaving many other regions constrained by limited resources and funding. These disparities hinder the sustainability and scope of cultural initiatives in less advantaged areas (Kessab, 2008). Consequently, while decentralisation has fostered regional cultural expression in some areas, significant gaps remain in achieving equitable support for cultural development across the country.

5.4.1. Changes in the cultural policies

Since gaining independence in 1962, Algeria has engaged in cultural legislative efforts to regulate its cultural sector. These initiatives were driven not only by the need to manage the frameworks inherited from colonial France but also by the ideological importance of culture in defining the identity and vision of the newly independent Algerian state. A key milestone in this process was Decree 96-21 of January 8, 1966, which focused on the organisation of Algerian theatre. This decree was pivotal in enabling the nationalisation of the former Algiers Opera House and the establishment of the Algerian National Theatre (TNA). The creation of the TNA marked a significant shift, reflecting the state's commitment to a socialist and centralised cultural policy. This institution became a cornerstone of cultural development and a tool for political hegemony, emphasizing the role of culture in reinforcing state authority.

Since this foundational initiative, Algeria's approach to cultural legislation has evolved, varying in intensity based on historical and political contexts. The legislative history of Algeria's cultural sector can be divided into three distinct periods, each characterised by specific priorities and challenges (Kessab, 2013).

The first period, spanning from independence in 1962 to 1988, witnessed limited legislative and regulatory activity in the cultural sector. This era was defined by Algeria's socialist framework, which prioritised state control and the dominance of ruling authorities over cultural structures and organisations. Policies implemented during this time primarily focused on establishing statutes and organisational frameworks for public cultural institutions, particularly those related to cinema. However, the decade culminated in significant upheaval, with violent riots, including the events of the "Black Spring" and the "Black Decade" marking the decline of socialism and paving the way for political pluralism and economic liberalisation (Kessab, 2013).

The second period, extending from 1988 to 2001, was characterised by a marked pause in cultural legislation and regulation. This stagnation coincided with the suspension of the electoral process in 1992, following a coup d'état against President Chadli Bendjedid, and the onset of violent Islamic riots during the 1990s (*Sueur, 2014*). These events were further compounded by a severe economic downturn and an escalating security crisis, which paralysed the Ministry of Culture's activities. By 1991, public funding for cultural institutions had ceased, with government resources redirected toward a select few artistic projects of political significance. Major cultural institutions, including the Algerian National Theatre and the Regional Theatres in Oran and Constantine, were forced to close their doors, remaining shut down until the early 2000s, when they gradually reopened (Kessab, 2013).

The third period, beginning in the early 2000s, was marked by gradual improvements in Algeria's economic and security conditions, leading to a revival of the Ministry of Culture. Under the leadership of a newly appointed Minister of Culture, who remained in office until 2013, the ministry underwent significant transformation. From 2003 onward, the Ministry of Culture benefited from an increasing budget (as shown in Figure 5.2 below), which enabled it to utilise cultural legislation and regulation as instruments for restructuring the sector and establishing a strategic vision. This era was characterised by an intensive period of legislative and regulatory activity, during which numerous critical texts and decrees were ratified and published in the official state bulletin. These measures reshaped Algeria's cultural and artistic landscape, transforming the sector and aligning it with the evolving priorities of the state. (Kessab, 2013).

This progression reflects the dynamic relationship between Algeria's cultural policy and its broader socio-political and economic realities, highlighting the central role of legislative and regulatory frameworks in shaping the nation's cultural identity and infrastructure.

Figure 5.2: The budget of the Ministry of culture (2003-2012) (Unit: Million dollars)

Source: Kessab (2008)

This financial increase enabled the initiation of several projects within the cultural sector, including the launching of new agencies and organisations as well as the organisation of cultural events. These developments required the adoption of a wide array of legal texts to provide these initiatives with the necessary legal and structural frameworks. According to Kessab (2012: 3) this study identified “548 critical legislative and regulatory texts related to the cultural sector, enacted between 2002 and 2012”. However, the total number is likely to exceed 1,000 when accounting for administrative measures such as the appointments and dismissals of Ministry of Culture staff and board members of cultural organisations of “the 548 texts identified during this period, 297 are ministerial orders⁴⁸, 119 are inter-ministerial orders, 130 are decrees⁴⁹, one is an ordinance⁵⁰,

⁴⁸ A ministerial or inter-ministerial order is a directive, either general or specific, issued by one or multiple government ministers.

⁴⁹ A decree is an executive decision, also of general or specific application, issued by either the President of the Republic or the Prime Minister, acting within their regulatory authority.

⁵⁰ An ordinance is a legal instrument enacted by the government to address matters typically governed by existing legislation. The government can issue ordinances only when authorised by parliament. Although ordinances take effect upon their promulgation and are treated as regulations, they gain full legislative authority only after being ratified by parliament within a specified timeframe.

and one is a law”. Kessab (2012: 3). The number of legislative and regulatory text from 2005 to 2012 are detailed in Table 5.1 below.

Table 5.1: Legislative and regulatory acts related to cultural sector Published from 2002 to 2002 in Algeria

Year	Ministerial order	Inter-ministerial order	Decrees	Ordinances	Laws	Total
2012	33	24	19	0	0	76
2011	52	9	14	0	1	76
2010	49	12	12	0	0	73
2009	32	16	19	0	0	67
2008	41	7	16	0	0	64
2007	20	9	14	0	0	43
2006	30	15	5	0	0	50
2005	27	10	19	-	0	56
2004	4	12	2	0	0	18
2003	5	1	9	1	0	16
2002	4	4	1	0	0	9
Total	297	119	130	1	1	548

Source: Kessab (2008)

5.4.2 Cultural policies within the Amazigh societies

Decentralisation policies in Algeria have had a profound impact on Amazigh regions, such as the Kabyle, Chaouia, and Tuareg areas. These policies have provided these communities with a framework to preserve and promote their cultural heritage within the broader national discourse, addressing to some extent the historical marginalisation of these ethnic groups. By creating opportunities for cultural expression and recognition, decentralisation has enabled the Amazigh people to sustain their music, traditions, practices, crafts, and language while sharing them with a wider audience.

One significant avenue for this cultural promotion has been the establishment of regional festivals and cultural exchange events. As noted by Boukrouh and Kessab (2010: 31), various local festivals have been instrumental in celebrating Amazigh culture, including “the Local Cultural Festival for Kabyle Music and Songs, the Local Festival for Tuareg Music and Songs, the Local Festival for Chaoui Music and Songs, the Local Festival for Mizabi Music and Songs”, and the Local Festival for Amazigh Music and Songs in Tamanrasset. Furthermore, inter-governorate cultural exchange weeks, such as the Cultural Week of Ghardaïa in Tizi-Ouzou, have become annual traditions, fostering a sense of unity and shared cultural appreciation across regions (Boukrouh and Kessab, 2010). In addition to these festivals, numerous associations dedicated to promoting regional cultures have emerged, actively participating in various cultural events and initiatives (Kessab, 2008). These organisations play a crucial role in preserving and showcasing Amazigh cultural practices and expressions. For instance, the Kabyle region has become a hub for several prominent events focused on Amazigh culture, including the Amazigh Heritage Festival, the Amazigh Poetry Festival, and the Amazigh Theatre Festival (Kessab, 2008). These events not only celebrate the richness of Amazigh traditions but also provide platforms for dialogue and exchange, reinforcing the cultural identity and pride of these communities.

Through these measures, decentralisation has contributed to elevating the visibility and significance of Amazigh culture within Algeria. While challenges remain in achieving full equity and representation, these policies have offered a critical pathway for the recognition and preservation of Amazigh heritage as an integral part of the nation's cultural landscape.

5.4.3. Challenges in policy implementation and cultural preservation

Algerian cultural policies, while ambitious in scope, continue to face significant challenges in the practical implementation of resource allocation and the decentralisation of cultural activities. Efforts to address the centralised nature of these policies are often hampered by disparities in funding and infrastructure between urban centres and remote areas (Satterthwaite and Tacoli, 2003). Limited financial support restricts access to cultural programs in less-developed regions, reducing opportunities to promote and sustain cultural practices and expressions in these areas.

One of the key challenges within the realm of heritage is the underdeveloped discourse on intangible cultural heritage (ICH). While tangible heritage, such as monuments, historical sites, and physical artifacts, has received substantial attention in both research and policy, ICH remains underrepresented in Algeria's cultural agenda. As Eichler (2020) emphasises, ICH is one of the most

vulnerable aspects of cultural heritage, requiring urgent attention. A review of Kessab's works (2008, 2010, 2012) highlights this gap, showing that governmental articles and regulations predominantly focus on tangible cultural aspects, such as cinema, theatre, reading, and historical sites, while ICH remains inadequately addressed. As shown in Figure 5.3 below the disproportion of tangible and intangible heritage within legislative work, tangible heritage represents 4/6 (including: Cinema, Museums, Theatre, and Heritage) while Intangible cultural heritage 2/6 (includes: reading, and possibly parts of Heritage such as oral traditions, folklore, or ICH practices). This omission presents a significant challenge to the preservation of heritage in general, and ethnic cultures in particular, as many of these rely heavily on intangible practices for their continuity.

Figure 5.3: Allocation of Resources in Algerian Cultural Policies

Source: by Author (2024)

The Amazigh culture, for instance, relies on oral transmission to sustain its practices, skills, and traditions. This dependence on non-written forms of heritage makes it particularly vulnerable to neglect if sufficient measures for ICH protection and promotion are not established. The absence of robust policies in this area risks the erosion of vital cultural attributes that define ethnic identities and their transmission to future generations.

Additionally, the tension between tradition and modernity further complicates Algeria's cultural landscape, particularly in relation to the Amazigh community. In an era of globalisation and the increasing influence of contemporary cultural expressions, Algerian policies face the challenge of balancing the preservation of local heritage with the acceptance of modernity. This dynamic is especially evident in the Amazigh regions, where cultural preservation efforts often contend with pressures to adopt modern lifestyles and norms (for more on this see Chapter 7 section 4).

The Berber Spring of 1980 marked a turning point in the struggle for cultural recognition, as the Amazigh community's demands for formal acknowledgment of their heritage sparked significant political and social movements. This pivotal moment led to a shift in Algerian cultural policies, fostering the inclusion of Amazigh identity in the broader national narrative (Maddy-Weitzman, 2015). The events of the Berber Spring underscored the importance of preserving ethnic cultures within a modern national framework, laying the groundwork for policies that now seek to integrate the Amazigh heritage into Algeria's cultural identity.

Despite these advancements, challenges persist. Effective strategies to address funding inequalities, ensure broader access to cultural programs, and prioritise ICH protection are essential for the sustainability of Algeria's diverse cultural heritage. Moreover, a nuanced approach is required to balance the interplay of tradition and modernity, ensuring that local identities are preserved while engaging with the broader currents of globalisation. Only through such comprehensive measures can Algeria truly support the diverse cultural expressions that define its rich national narrative.

5.4.4. Women within policy context

In Algeria, women play a pivotal role in the transmission and preservation of cultural heritage, a reality that is implicitly acknowledged but not consistently formalised within the country's cultural policy frameworks. This role is particularly prominent within Amazigh communities, where women act as cultural custodians, sustaining traditions through their practices in language, crafts, and oral storytelling (Laghssais and Comins- Mingol, 2023). Despite their indispensable contributions to the preservation of intangible cultural heritage (ICH), Algeria's cultural policies often overlook the significance of women's roles, leaving their contributions under-recognised in

official narratives (see chapter 5 section 4.4). Nevertheless, their efforts are essential to maintaining the continuity of Algeria's diverse cultural identity.

The intersection of policy and women's involvement in cultural preservation is complex. While government initiatives in this area remain limited, non-governmental efforts occasionally step in to fill the gap. For example, certain NGOs focus on supporting cultural preservation and empowering women through community-based projects, particularly in rural and regional contexts (Haider, 2009). These initiatives often enable women to preserve traditional crafts, sustain linguistic heritage, and contribute to local economies. However, in Algeria, the scarcity of such organisations is a notable challenge, particularly when compared to neighbouring countries like Morocco. For instance, Morocco's "Voice of the Amazigh Woman"⁵¹ is a prominent organisation that leads cultural and social initiatives aimed at improving women's lives and fostering cultural preservation. In Algeria, the absence of similar NGOs exacerbates the challenges faced by Amazigh women, as both governmental and non-governmental support for their cultural roles remains minimal.

Despite these limitations, women in Algeria continue to serve as the backbone of cultural preservation, particularly in the safeguarding of ICH. Their contributions are not only cultural but also economic, as many traditional crafts and practices form the basis of local livelihoods. The informal yet vital role women play highlights the urgent need for policies and initiatives that formally recognise and support their contributions (see chapter 7 section 8).

5.5. Conclusion

Algeria's commitment to preserving its intangible cultural heritage shows a profound recognition of its cultural diversity as a cornerstone of national identity. From being the first state to ratify the 2003 UNESCO Convention to developing comprehensive legislative frameworks like the 1998 Cultural Heritage Law and Executive Decree 03-325, the country has shown a dedication to safeguarding its rich culture.

While this chapter has outlined Algeria's evolving commitment to UNESCO frameworks and detailed the national policy efforts toward ICH preservation, the analysis reveals a gap between institutional intentions and lived realities. Cultural legislation has largely emphasised tangible heritage and top-down initiatives, often overlooking the informal, community-based, and

⁵¹ <https://imsli.org.ma/new>

gendered dimensions of heritage preservation, particularly in marginalised communities like the Amazigh. Women's central role in sustaining oral traditions, crafts, and intergenerational knowledge has not been sufficiently reflected in formal policy, and structural inequalities persist in how resources and support are distributed across regions. For these reasons, policy analysis has not been a primary focus of the following chapters. Instead, this study centres on the everyday realities and cultural agency of Amazigh women, whose voices, practices, and narratives offer a grassroots perspective on cultural resilience and empowerment. By shifting focus from institutional discourse to lived experience, the research aims to highlight how intangible cultural heritage is preserved and reshaped through local engagement—often in ways that exceed or bypass the limits of official policy.

Chapter Six - The Paradox of Amazigh Intangible Heritage: Women's Role in Preserving and Transforming Cultural Identity

This chapter aims firstly to explore the diverse adversities and challenges facing Amazigh women in Algeria such as the hardship of rural life and patriarchal relations. The participants in this study, many of whom have strong ties to traditional lifestyles and cultural practices, reveal insights, share experiences, and express their opinions about. In this chapter that investigates, in an intersectional manner, the role of gender, cultural marginalisation, and socio-economic limitations in Amazigh women lives. Secondly this section explores the empowerment these women create through their participations in their intangible heritage and through preserving it. Analysing their resilience through safeguarding the intangible cultural attribute such as traditions, rituals, language, and orality. To contextualise these practices, and give sense of the research's findings, the following section begins with an overview of oral traditions and intangible cultural heritage in Africa and North Africa, with a focus on the Amazigh cultural landscape. It also presents a codebook for the interviews conducted to provide an anchoring point to the data discussed in the chapter.

6.1. Africa and Orality

Oral genres, styles, and performance have been the primary means of communication, acculturation, entertainment, and societal admiration, given the fact that literacy was common in most African societies (Gregsens, 1977; Gérard, 1981). The few but significant possessions that enslaved African people brought to the new world (America) were their cognitive and performative African oral skills and traditions.

The public recitation of pedigrees and praises of the rulers by highly skilled poets and public speakers was one of the important roles of the oral genres all over the continent (Gunner, 2004). The diverse array of oral genres that coexisted with music dance instruments events and even religion empowered the social, political, and the spiritual existence in Africa. Furthermore, orality in Africa took another path in blending culture with politics, as the *ubwiiiru* in the Rwandan culture that talk about a dynastic ritual code that the historians Rwabukumba and Kagame have

turned into a written record and a part of a broader historical narrative in the Rwandan culture (Feierman, 1995; Rwabukumba and Mudandagizi, 1974).

In the west, in Nigeria specifically the oriki was a poetic praise vehicle for both powerful and ordinary Nigerians that blended their past with the present according to Barber (1991: 76) “the crossing from the world of the dead to the world of the living, making the past present again”, and poems that intertwined personal and public history (Barber 1991). Furthermore, Finnegan (1970) argues that the African orality was a bridge between past and present but also the way to the future. As she stated, “long and rigorous period of apprenticeship” by young members of the families of poets ensured mastery of existing poems and of the “vocabulary, imagery and subject-matter which formed the traditional basis of any future composition” (Finnegan, 1970: 89).

The abundance of the expressive African forms that have been made is observed by its exploitation by colonisers and abusive power holders (Gunner, 2008). Another role of the oral genres was the forming of the memory banks of the societies, which is considered a mirror to formalise memory of the past and to make the past comprehensible and accessible. As Derive (1995) has argued, the multiplicity of oral forms is not solely the “distinctive sign” of a certain social condition, but also a potential vehicle of striving pressure and transforming social conditions and power relations. Using a recognised art form to complain, to express, to protest and to hope for change is an important medium for those without power.

The African records and products of culture make clear vision of orality, as it is far from being amorphous and preliterate communal cultural attribute, waiting for redemption and development by manifestations of modernity (Gunner, 2008). Orality is ever-changing presence that is challenging, interacting, and producing a completely different and modern kind of cultural equilibrium on the African continent (Benveniste and Moran, 1962; Voloshinov and Bakhtin, 1986). The African oral performance genres show sharpened skills of expressive art to fit the ambience of a specific culture produced by the societies themselves. Those societies that had for centuries suffered from by internecine wars, by slavery, by disease and by poverty (Gunner, 2008).

6.2. Oral tradition of Amazigh and North Africa

The colloquial–classical system has been always challenged by the inhabitants of North Africa. The historiographer Ibn Khaldun (1332–1406) recorded lengthy examples of the oral epics about the sera (biography) of Beni Hilal tribes in the three volumes of his book which is titled *Muqaddimah* (Prolegomena). He states that “Most contemporary scholars... disapprove of these

types [of poems] when they hear them, and refuse to consider them poetry ... They believe that ... they are [linguistically] incorrect and lack vowel endings...”, he furthermore argues, “Vowel endings have nothing to do with eloquence” (iii: 4, 12–80). In the same vein, Maunier (1926) affirms that “folklore is local not national” and any attempt to mould it in a larger frame will make it something different. Webber (2008) confirms that belittling the oral over the written form and the regional dialect over the classic language of either Arabic or Amazigh led to notable consequences on preserving forms of oral culture as it was regarded as not worthy.

Orality in the Amazigh language is changing fast in North Africa mainly because of the increasing presence of illiteracy and media nowadays (Merolla, 2005). Despite the socio-political position of the Amazigh as being marginalised, an explosion of form and content in all cultural expressions has occurred lately (Lafkioui, 2008). As a result of the language recognition and induction of the new educational system and the cultural projects of the state, the Amazigh identity is being constructed and the Amazigh group identity is now being reconstructed, and in this process, orality is a pivotal element. Cultural attributes such as oral poems and tales embody the traditional values and traditions that had carefully been preserved and transmitted through generations for centuries in North Africa (Ibid). These values and traditions present the aesthetical facets and genres of the Amazigh culture. Cultural studies show that Amazigh groups such as, Kabyle, Chaouia, and Riffian (in Morocco) create and affirm folktales that are the reflection of their worlds and their reality (Bounfour, 1999, 2005, 2013; Kossmann, 2000).

Amazigh oral genres are always innovating and challenging all the critics. As an example, is the Amazigh poem, and it is the resilience of the Amazigh as a group, composed by Si Mohand ou Mhand a strophe of nine verses in the Kabyle dialect from second half of the 19th century. As Lahlou (2017) as cited in Merolla (2020) explains that the emergence of such poem can be the result of the disruption and confusion brought about by colonisation. For the poet using the mother tongue is a way of rebellion and resilience. Many western Europeans were interested in Amazigh studies because they have considered the Amazigh as fertile, exotic, more “authentic”, and that was more challenging in several aspects, on the other hand others studied Amazigh to determine the origins of the people or for unintimidated political purposes (Henri Basset, 1887).

The Amazigh genres are much more than just resilience mediums, those folktales, legends songs, and more, are a witness of a culture that knew how to preserve and transmit its roots to generations ahead. Some examples of those genres are mentioned next.

6.2.1. Tales or legends

Tales or folktales tend to be vague in time and setting, despite the fact that Arabic tales took place in Baghdad during the age of Haroun al-Rashid or a Persian city. In North African tales, all logic is dropped and the boundaries between animals, humans, the supernatural, and the natural does not exist. Humans may talk to the sea, to animals or even ogres. Traveling from the natural and supernatural, waking and sleeping, even life and death occurs unquestionably.

The females' characters in the tales are often educated and having a purpose in the story seeking a spouse, a missing parent, or revenge (Webber, 2008). The characters travel to exotic lands, where the stories develop, and the events occur. The most famous Arabic tale, one thousand and one night, tells the story of a girl named Shahrazad and the prince Shahryar, and is a collection of many stories that the cinema nowadays adapted such as "Aladdin and the magical lamp", "Sinbad the sailor" and more.

The stories are told orally by men or women and are sometimes read aloud to entertain others while embroidering or putting henna, weaving, mending fishing nets. In the past, women who are storytellers might live in the home of their patrons, as a source of entertainment for their families and the children. The narratives are divided into tales, legends, and contest and epics. Legends, as an example in the North African oral tales can be believed to certain degrees, they contain references to supernatural creatures and elements, and the characters varies between the brave, the holy, the foolish, the coward, the wise and so on (Webber, 2008). The tales take a religious form as well to teach the children and to advice the adults; stories of "awliya"⁵², or for Jews, "tsaddiqim" and for Coptic Christians, "quadding" (holy ones), and their deeds in life. The tales describe even their deaths and the afterlife sometimes a way to encourage the people to believe and hold on in communal crisis (1994).

6.2.2. Politesse

Is a central North African oral conversational genre that is usually delivered according to the right place, right time, in an appropriate manner. The simple way of saying good morning or good night goes through a process of personalising that depends on the context and the listener. For example, when a beggar asks for money and the person wants to refuse his demand, she/he

⁵² A term used to describe men who sincerely love and worship God or are known for performing miracles.

responds by “may God provide”. This same expression can be used in different contexts such as parents regarding the health and success of their children (Webber, 2008).

Even when insulting someone North Africans use a different kind of speech, as Daumas (1864) stated in his book to say to a person that she/he is sloppy eater you can say “From the rate at which you are making that goat disappear, one would think that while living it gored you.”. Daumas also collected fifty ways and expression to wish a person well in Algerian Arabic as well as many creative phrases to pray to someone with recovery, or to comfort them when a loved one dies, when someone loses money, marries, has a child, or brings good news (Webber, 2008).

6.2.3. Songs

Rhymed prose pieces or poems are put to a spectrum of melodies and tunes taking into consideration regional and personal preference. Tuareg poetry in Ahaggar (amazigh) is recited but mostly sung accompanied with a musical instrument that can be drum, violin, guitar or Tuareg instrument such as imzad or tende. Among other Amazigh groups a flute might be used (the Jurqra of the Kabyles) and the nonprofessional women’s sing in private (Abu-Lughod, 1986), unless it is a traditional wedding. Amazigh women sing while weaving, grinding wheat, spinning, sewing and cooking. They have songs and rituals to God to make it rain in the dry times. In parts of North Africa, Algeria and Tunisia, these rituals and songs are playful adaptations of Punic human sacrifices to the goddess Tanit (the rain Punic goddess) (Webber, 2008).

The songs tend to be also religious when they talk about Prophets lives or other important Islamic or Christian figures, constructing an authoritative, “realistic and lived religions, a very lively aspect of the textual tradition. As an example, the Coptic Christians in Egypt have re-established the art of hymns about the Christ, the church, and the saints sung in homes and at family gatherings”. These examples manifest the importance of investigation in the North African religious traditions as lived traditions that have been constructed and transmitted orally (Webber, 2008).

Amazigh music is a developing art, several Amazigh artists have promoted their culture through their music such as Idir’s a Vava Inouva “My little father” in 1973, which is widely credited as the first song of the Kabyle music to reach popularity outside of North Africa (Nidel, 2005). Tinariwen, a group of Tuareg singer that have introduced a new feature of their native music, the group even represented Algeria in the 2010 football world cup that took place in South Africa (Perry, 2010).

6.2.4. Lullabies

As anywhere in the world, lullabies can be any songs that appeal to the singer mostly to the loved ones. North African lullabies specifically focus on the mother's relationship with her children. As an example, lullabies for girls show the tender and supportive relationship between a mother and her daughter, the future of the little girl growing up, the womanly skills that she will acquire as a grown up. Meanwhile, for the boys the lullabies show what is expected from him when he grows up and how his mom will be proud of him and what he has achieved. Those lullabies are nursery songs to put the babies to sleep and to calm them as toddlers (Webber, 2008). One of the most famous lullabies in Algeria is the French lullaby 'frere Jacques' (the brother jack).

6.2.5. Coded speech

The small artistic techniques such as metaphors, naming practices, use of diminutives, and coded languages are essential to the foundations of orature or the orality, but also embroider everyday speech and conversational genres such as, riddles, proverbs, and jokes.

Basset (1920) acknowledged the women and children artistic speech, paying attention to the Kabyles women who can speak without being understood by their men using a certain type of speech that only them can decode (Webber, 2008). The use of diminutives in north Africa has a deep relationship between the Amazigh language and the Arabic as well. Arabic is known by its excessive use of diminutives in an artistic way of everyday speech. Jouin (1957) utilises the Moroccan example of a diminutive where bint (girl) to bnita (little girl) to banutta (little, little girl) or, alternatively in Algeria where benti (my daughter) and bneyti (my little daughter) the pattern differs from place to place, but the concept is one and widespread.

6.2.6. Children's rhymes and games

Children rhymes and games such as, clapping, naming, or counting using fingers, rhymes are also used for learning to walk, in losing the first tooth. The fingers games are varied, and they have many purposes educational as teaching kids to count, cultural stories about the different sizes of the fingers and for fun such as tickling games where the armpit becomes the cave for a little mouse creeping up the child's arm to tickle her/him. The rhyming game varies in languages as well as content it can be sung or told in Arabic, Amazigh or even French. Creative pet names are often related to the family Arab or Berber world history and familial relationships (Webber, 2008).

6.3. Patterns of Meaning in Amazigh Women’s Testimonies

Table 6.1 below provides a structured overview of the themes and corresponding codes that emerged from the community interviews conducted with Amazigh women across various Amazigh regions in Algeria. The thematic analysis was guided by an inductive coding process, allowing recurring concepts, expressions, and shared cultural experiences to surface organically from the participants’ narratives (chapter 4 section 6). The table reflects the complex intersections of gender, culture, tradition, and resilience, encapsulating how Amazigh women navigate and negotiate their roles within heritage preservation and community life. Each theme is supported by a set of codes that illustrate the nuanced dimensions of cultural identity, patriarchy, socio-economic adversity, and intergenerational transmission. These categories not only offer analytical clarity but also serve as the foundation for deeper discussion subsequently in the chapter.

Table 6.1: Community interviews themes and codes

Themes generated	Codes
Role of Amazigh Women in Preserving Cultural Identity	<i>Cultural Custodianship</i> <i>Heritage Preservation</i> <i>Transmission of Cultural Knowledge</i> <i>Identity Expression</i> <i>Traditional Practices as Identity</i>
Challenges and Adversities Facing Amazigh Women	<i>Gender Discrimination</i> <i>Marginalisation as Minorities</i> <i>Socioeconomic Limitations</i> <i>Patriarchal Constraints</i> <i>Access to Resources</i> <i>Daily Hardships</i>
Resilience and Empowerment Amidst Adversity	<i>Transforming Challenges into Strength</i> <i>Heritage as Resilience</i> <i>Self-Empowerment through Culture</i> <i>Identity Assertion</i> <i>Adaptation and Agency</i>

	<i>Empowerment through Intangible Heritage</i>
Cultural Transmission Through Handicrafts and Traditional Practices	<i>Handicrafts as Heritage</i> <i>Economic Support through Crafting</i> <i>Generational Knowledge Transfer</i> <i>Women’s Roles in Cultural Continuity</i> <i>Crafting as Identity Expression</i> <i>Community Bonding through Crafts</i>
Impact of Patriarchal Kinship and Gender Norms	<i>Patriarchal Authority</i> <i>Gender-Based Expectations</i> <i>Traditional Marriage Roles</i> <i>Limited Autonomy</i> <i>Family and Social Pressures</i> <i>Male Dominance in Decision-Making</i>
Collective Practices and Communal Solidarity Among Amazigh Women	<i>Women Supporting Women</i> <i>Community Solidarity</i> <i>Collective Empowerment</i> <i>Traditions of Mutual Aid</i> <i>Sisterhood and Collaboration</i> <i>Crafting as Shared Experience</i>
Education and the Intergenerational Transfer of Cultural Values	<i>Educational Aspirations for Girls</i> <i>Barriers to Education</i> <i>Hope for New Generations</i> <i>Cultural Values in Education</i> <i>Generational Knowledge Transfer</i> <i>Parenting for Empowerment</i>
Language, Orality, and Cultural Resilience	<i>Language as Identity</i> <i>Oral Traditions</i> <i>Storytelling and Proverbs</i> <i>Language as Resistance</i> <i>Mother Tongue Preservation</i> <i>Cultural Identity in Language</i>

<p>Traditions and Rituals as Symbols of Cultural Identity</p>	<p><i>Wedding Traditions</i></p> <p><i>Rituals of Heritage</i></p> <p><i>Cultural Celebrations</i></p> <p><i>Community Festivals</i></p> <p><i>Traditional Gatherings</i></p> <p><i>Shared Cultural Memory</i></p>
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6.4. Amazigh Women Challenges and Adversities

Most of the Amazigh women interviewed, were women who lived rural lives or nomadic lives, even those who were educated and had jobs were linked to tribes and family members that are living to this day either in old cottages in the mountains or in tents in the desert. According to Gagliardi (2021, p. 1) “a significant number of Amazigh women face multiple forms of discrimination – as women, as minorities and as non-elites within their community”. It is evidenced in the data collected that Amazigh women encounter daily struggles, not only for being a part of a marginalised group but also as being females in their society. These struggles, as seen in the data collected from the interviews and the observations of the researcher, can be categorised into three types: firstly, gender discrimination in various aspects of life as education whereas females of all ages are discouraged from pursuing education, since “women’s place is the kitchen” as one of the informants stated. Secondly, the fact that they are minority members expose them to being marginalised and excluded from accessing resources as nomadic women. Thirdly, Amazigh women within their own communities have a limited influence in the decision-making process.

During one of the interviews, I noticed that some Amazigh women interpret their struggles as faith in God. They see any inconvenience as destiny, and few of them would argue that it is a lack of opportunities on a political or social level. Amazigh women prefer to accept life and continue in their customs, taking care of the house, and the kids, cooking, and engaging in handicrafts that for them are not a source of financial stability, crafts are a normal part of their life and the way they express their deep-rooted culture. During an interview with S48, I asked about crafting.

F: Do you think a woman can make a business in making carpets?

S48: From where I came a woman can make the carpets, but unfortunately, she can never be the one who owns the business or presents it, in Mzab communities, especially in rural areas.

Mzab society is one of the most preservative Amazigh groups in Algeria, women there are barely seen performing any kind of labour activities, and from my observations, I have come to notice that all women working in the area are not Mzab. From interviewing the women, they clearly stated *“Our girls do not work they do not even finish their education; we make sure they can read and write and that is all...”*. In the rest of this section, the following adversities of Amazigh women’s lives will be discussed: hardship of rural life, access to education, patriarchal kinships, and divorce and shame.

6.4.1. Hardship of rural life

In this stage, I will define the rural life of the interviewees as was described to me, due to the different settings of the sample I will divide this part into two kinds of lifestyles the first will cover the rural life in the mountains and the second will deal with the nomadic and desert life.

Because of the rural setting and the similar life patterns within the sample, there is notable consistency. Take for instance interviewee B53-V1, a woman in her 50s who lives in the mountains. As she describes, she rises early morning to release the chickens to roam freely for a while. Following this, she prepares breakfast for herself and her family and then attends to household chores. Afterwards, she heads out to the fields with her sheep to allow them to graze. Upon returning home, she tends to the animals and prepares lunch. These tasks are strenuous and demanding, as evidenced by an incident where one of the sheep inadvertently injured her foot three times.

Despite the challenges, she diligently cares for and breeds her animals, so her husband can sell them when Eid⁵³ arrives. This serves as a means of generating income for the family. In the same context interview M47-V2 narrates that she goes to the market to purchase essentials such as oil, sugar, tea, tomatoes, potatoes, onions, and meat, ensuring the household's needs are met. In the afternoon, she dedicates roughly 2 to 3 hours to crafting her wool items. As the sunsets

⁵³ Eid Adha which is a Muslim holy feast where they sacrifice livestock.

(Maghrib prayer⁵⁴) approaches, she tends to her animals, and prepares, and shares dinner with her family. Despite the hardship she endures she dedicates time, spending her afternoons weaving clothes to contribute to the family's financials, her husband and sons sell her handicrafts in their shops. This shows how little women are acknowledged for their efforts and treated as workers who will not get promoted.

T48-V3 talked about her daily routine, in the morning she wakes up at 6 am and goes out to the small farm they have to feed her hens, then milk the cow to get fresh milk for her family's breakfast, she expresses how important is for her husband to find the breakfast ready when he is up, by saying *"... It is the most sacred meal of the day for him"*, then she wakes the kids up for school. In the afternoon she sits and has some free time to knit, her kids love the way she customises their gloves and hats in winter, she states that her daughters learnt knitting at a young age, and they help her in doing so when asked if the boys are interested in that too, she laughed and said, *"it is a woman's job..."*. The relationship between gender and handicrafts is always floating in almost all the interviews, except if the work needs more force such as leather or iron handicrafts. It is impressive how women are seen and treated: on one hand fragile and weak to do physical activities, and on another responsible and mighty in handling things that are overwhelming for them. R58-N1 expresses that through narrating her day plan by mentioning that her boys and girls used to have turns in shepherding, which was progressive but at the same time double standard. Where in many families as described by the interviewees, girls do house chores and boys are responsible for the outside ones, but in the previously mentioned story girls help even with outside shores while boys do not help in the houses. Another example of that is mentioned by T48-V3 where she talked about olive harvesting stating that *"all the women of the village get together and pick the olives to make the oil... it reminds me of my grandmother and how she used to take me with her to play in the fields and celebrate Twiza⁵⁵"*. The contradiction of being fragile or tough, of being responsible or responsible of, is what makes Amazigh women powerful and resilient.

⁵⁴ Maghrib prayer, one of the five daily Islamic prayers, when the sunsets.

⁵⁵ Twiza is a charity event where the Amazigh (Kabyle) women of a village get all together and make a feast to share with all the people with no regards to the wealth or the status.

The interviews were conducted during summer time, rural Amazigh women during summer time have a great amount of work and responsibilities because, in their traditions, they should work in summer to rest in winter, it is exemplified by them through a famous folktale as one of the interviewees recounts “ *in one of the cold winter nights an ant hears someone knocking on her door, when she opened it was a grasshopper asking her for food because he spends all his summer singing in fields and did not keep any food supply for the cold windy days*”. The comparison made in the story explains how women are the planners and mainly responsible for the house, whether it is for food or other supplies, it is evidence that women hold full responsibility in case of any misfortune, they even tend to see them as good or bad omens.

S56-V4 narrates a story of one of her sisters in law, “*The night she gave birth it was hard for them and she struggled a lot to deliver*” At the end of the story she clearly said, “*My brother was newly married, his wife helped a lot in the process because she was taught by her mother, her face is a good news carrier*⁵⁶, “*she is a good omen, the baby was a boy*” the interviewee adds laughing. The story illustrates the struggles that women have and the way they are multitasking in their communities, they must improvise and help in everything from the normal house shore to the complicated tasks, such as medical emergencies that require not only knowledge but practice. Another important observation is the way the interviewee stated that the sister-in-law is a good omen, which is a common belief in society because she was a new member, she will be in a way responsible for the good or the bad events that will happen until she lives with them for few months.

Vyse (1997) describes Superstition as an aspect of human nature, embedded within our neuronal mainframe. Superstitions are not deviant behaviour or finite to traditional cultures, specific races, religions, or nationalities, nor are related to a person’s intelligence, or educational level. Superstitions are widely spread in the Amazigh traditional societies with no regard to their members’ education, race, or intellect. As the previous statement by the informant links women’s presence to a good or a bad outcome, which is based on random circumstance and an illogical judgment, the outcome would have happened even if the new bride is not present, but for these societies is the most comfortable way they can justify events and overcome hardship and confusion.

⁵⁶ An Algerian expression that literary translates to goodness face, which means a person with brings good news and a source of optimism.

Another observation was made based on the same story related to the gender of the baby, it is always and still nowadays, unfortunately, believed that women are responsible for the baby's wrong gender, in rural places, women are mostly not educated, nor well informed and they still face problems because of this belief. De Beauvoir (1949) argues that in a way women are producers who have no control over the product. A55-V5 narrates the story that she has four daughters and that was her husband's reason to remarry, which she strongly disagreed on and preferred to leave, she clearly expressed her opinion *" I was happy with my girls, girls are gentle and obedient, I cannot accept to be in a marriage that does not have respects for me, he kept saying he wants a boy to carry his name like girls don't carry their father's names..."*, the interviewee is a strong opinionated women, living in a small rural area as a single mother of four is hard and expensive. She is one of the few women who saw tradition and beliefs differently, and that had caused her, her marriage, but she sees it as one of the few choices she got in her life and one of the few times she was not blamed or ashamed by her family.

The rural lifestyle is harsh, and the struggles and the daily tasks are exhausting and non-ending, but some life utilities make living in the mountains bearable and manageable, whereas the nomadic lifestyle is challenging due to its unpredictability and reliance on natural resources, for instance due to elements such as rigorous weather conditions, and the inaccessibility to healthcare and education. Moreover, Griswold (2012), explains the necessity to insert protection measures to preserve their heritage and way of life from the pressure exerted on them due to differences in culture and lifestyle. As modern industrial societies emerged, the cultural disparity intensified resulting in a subordinate status for nomadic peoples within their societies.

T46-N2 is a nomad who has never had the chance to go to school, see a doctor or live in a house, she narrates about her childhood and how she struggled in her life doing basic things, her daily routine was not hard because cleaning and washing as they rarely have access to water, it was the fact of moving around to find a place with water, she states *" we were always on a treasure hunt"* she laughs *"we could look for a place with flat ground and water access and that was hard, my father used to have his tricks to find the place that has water"*. The need to be always on the move made the needs of their lives become more and more each day, L55-N3 talked about the way they used to leave places to either get close to the city sometimes to get some essentials or to a place where they can get enough water made her feel that she belongs nowhere, *"getting used to a place and then leaving without knowing whether you will see it again or not is so hard, it was hard for me and my siblings and now for my kids"*. The feeling of belonging is important to

the Amazigh, for Amazigh women land is a mother they are the farmers because of their knowledge of soil, they are vets for their knowledge of livestock, and they are impressive botanists for their knowledge of herbs and their medical features. D67-N4 is an old nomad lady with a long experience of making herbal remedies for her family and even the people who knew her, used to travel kilometres to get her advice or a paste for an injury. D67-N4 recounts tales of women who had issues during pregnancy and how she used to provide the right herbs for them. Those stories do not only show how extraordinary Amazigh women are, but also how they hold on to their responsibilities and fulfil their duties and missions as they call it.

F: how do feel about your life and responsibilities?

L55-N3: "I always feel that I am on a mission, and I must be always ready for anything. I remember the time of sandstorms I had to protect my siblings and hide them when my mom got sick, I was responsible for everything in the house, when my father is not around, I do his shoes".

Their way of opening up and talking about their lives opens doors for other discussions, such as the role of government in all of this, a second-degree citizen⁵⁷ as they are called in Algeria. Education, health care, and water are life essentials, but these nomads see them as a luxury that they are unable to afford and get because of their lifestyle, which in a different context is not right as witnessed by one of the interviewees, when it is a time of elections, they are easily found even in the deep desert.

The discussion with the nomads was a different kind of interaction, these people live a humble life with almost nothing to offer, and a lot to ask from the stakeholders such as the priority in ensuring their livestock or in governmental benefits which at least offer compensation for the marginalisation and the neglect they are facing. One of the interviewees (T46-N2) talked about charity convoys that some people organised and brought, she said *"I felt like we are refugees in our own country or we live in two different countries"*, they were very thankful for the people who have this spirit, which is a hard journey as described by one of the Associations' members *"we travel kilometres and kilometres to find them and to keep track of the families we already know so we help them again"*. These nomads see the aid and charity convoys as a sent from God seeing

⁵⁷ An expression often used in Algeria to describe a person whose rights are treated as less important than those of other people because of its origins, sex, work, or the region where he/she lives in.

their kids playing with the toys brought to them and finally getting shoes on their feet as painful it was but comforting. As D67-N4 said that “who creates us will never forget us” and this was a sign of the strong belief and faith they have even in the hardest times. This very faith they have is rooted in all of them even women despite their hard lives as S56-V4 expressed her feeling of neglect it is something “written” for her, and she accepted it. When she was asked about women's needs, she said:

F: how do you get the things you need as a woman?

S56-V4: it depends, sometimes when the men go to the city, they get what we ask of them, and you know men they get what is in front of them sometimes they do not bother looking for it and just say it they didn't find it...but what we can do it is our destiny all is written.

F: Do you ask them to take you along?

S56-V4: I tried but my husband says that it is expensive and not convenient, and if I go, I have to take the kids, he thinks it is lighter for him to be alone.

F: Why is it not convenient?

S56-V4: he goes to crowded places, and he has to pay attention to us, you know how men think.

The way she described a normal scene in life is evidence of how women are treated and seen, she did not express that as something wrong or bothering her, “you know how men think” is an expression that she believes in, that it is justified and normal. Assuming that women are a burden is embedded in nomad women's conscience by literally saying “lighter” to describe his journey alone as if his family accompanying him will make him restrained and not at ease.

The belief that everything is written and already destined for them, is not proof of how religious they are, but is a way of life and their survival method. Acceptance and coexistence or what they call “*Kisma w Nassib*” is a term they repeated all along their interviews which translates to one's luck and fortune, and that does not mean that a person is lucky or fortunate by money or material things, on the contrary this is about the intangible things that a person got fortunate to have whether it is health, marriage, kids and so on.

6.4.2. Access to education

Access to education is a crucial concern within the rural and southern areas context among the Amazigh. Several reasons contribute to the limited access of women and girls to education, as well as the high dropout rates. According to findings from the fieldwork, 13 out of 20 informants disclosed that during their upbringing, they were deprived of the opportunity to attend formal schooling due to the prevailing societal belief that it was shameful for girls to pursue education among boys. As M58-V6 expresses

F: Did you attend school?

M58-V6: No. My father was against it, schools brought shame for girls, to go there and be in same place with boys is shameful. For me and a lot of the girls in my generation and my older sisters as well. Only the boys went to school.

F: Did your brothers attend school?

M58-V6: Yes, they went and one of them has a university degree.

F: You did not say that you want to go to school just as your brother did?

M58-V6: No. I was scared to say this to my father, and because I was not the only one in the village who did not go, I was scared to be the only one who objected... even if I did, I knew he would not accept.

The fact that some families believe that mixed classrooms are not appropriate for their girls, led to classes where there is a separation in the same classrooms, for example, they would make two lines for girls and two for boys with a big gap between them or even making classes which are all of one gender. The problem with this is that girls were not allowed to study subjects such as human anatomy which relates to body parts or music or even to practice any sport because it is “shameful” and “men’s only”. So, in places where it was allowed for girls to study, they would have a different curriculum. In one of the interviews with Mzab Amazigh, it was clearly said by the interviewees that “*we don’t have girls that go to school beyond elementary*” because if the girls pursue their education will ruin their reputation and their family image in the village. This image of women and family image has always been discussed and highlighted as a woman is the

showcase of the family which puts a great deal of pressure on women and makes their mistakes seen as a crime and that leads to many problems.

In a discussion with S58-C1 asking whether they have female teachers, she answered *“All the female teachers are not Mzab they come from other cities from the north”*, which is considered as an honouring gesture for their women, one of the interviewees talked about her father’s views and she stated that he used to tell her *“you are a queen in your house”*, a patriarchal view of how women should be and behave to be seen as decent or “queen”. This problem with education has led to aggravation in their societies, the contradiction between not allowing girls to go to school or not seeking further education and the need for female teachers or doctors, is causing issues in the work market, housing, and medical practice (Naili and Dahmani, 2023). Women are prohibited from having any interaction with other males outside of family relations even if it is a doctor. In an interview with a female doctor in Mzab city (Ghardaia), L62-C2 talked about how she was called only when it was urgent and there was no other solution, *“their women are not to be revealed to anyone even strange women”*. On the other hand, Mzab women whom it was very hard to interview justify this as protection and endearment, *“you only hide what is precious”* as S55-C3 declares.

Other informants relate the issue of accessing education to poverty, one of the interviewees mentioned that there was no point in studying if she was not going to work eventually and be the breadwinner in the house, her brother was the one who had to go to school to find a proper job and supports the rest of the family. She furthermore adds that girls will get married, and their husbands will support them, so there is no need in insisting to go to school or having a job. Therefore, they rather ensure the boys *“become the financial provider of the family and hence investment in their education is prioritised”* (Laghssais and Comins Mingol 2021, p. 7).

This point could be seen as practical due to their limited resources, while talking to Amazigh women who themselves agree, M58-V6 stated that if she has the means to enrol one of her kids to school it will be a boy because *“he will be the provider eventually”*, she does not believe that it is a type of favouritism, and if it was she clearly said *“I am favouring my daughter to be around me and being provided for”*. As it is seen by some Amazigh women, men are responsible for financial support whereas women are not. This belief carries several contradictions as in many cases women are the real provider of their crafts, their contribution to plantations, and livestock wellbeing, and men are the one that deals with the third party whether it is a buyer or investor.

Denying girls their right to education and considering it a type of protection reflects a deep-rooted belief that Amazigh see it as a tradition and their way of existing, they make the roles and the society rules and live by them. These traditions are not imposed on anyone anymore, but they are still practised and respected.

6.4.3. Patriarchal kinships

This section deals with patriarchal kinship which is linked to several aspects of the relationship between women and men. This relates to male dominance and how it limits women's fulfilment and pressures them in what Comis Mingol (2016) describes as the idealisation of the notion of a good mother and virtuous woman in a manipulative way, for her, it is illogical to talk about gendered approach without discussing the equality between the gender in terms of education and healthcare, especially in the context of the villagers and the nomads.

First, dealing with the issue in a social aspect such as the societal pressures faced by rural Amazigh women and girls in their daily lives. As Laghssais (2021) describes, gender is a social construct, governed by codes of honour and shame in society. Through these notions, women become not only controlled by their families but also prohibited from many conducts and activities that are considered inappropriate, from a young age the girls become the property of their families, and they continue being so until they are the property of their husbands. In an interview with M58-V6 she genuinely talked about how being married at a young age has been hard for her and about her expectations as a child, she described *"I was thinking it is a game"* She laughed and continued *"I was dressed only for the party but they left me in a new house with new people and that was scary at first, but later on, I got used to it and there was no big difference between my life before and after"*, the fact that she felt that her existence in two different places, different families, different environments is the same, means that she felt that she makes no difference in the family or the society. Another notion that was brought to light talking to the interviewees was body purity which in the whole Algerian context is a big issue, girls are always kept under close watch in case she does anything that may bring shame and dishonour to their family which will lead to in many cases to crime "honour killings"⁵⁸.

This kind of pressure in applying the codes of honour makes girls submissive to male authority, not only in action but also in thought. For example, the girls and women who chose a different life

⁵⁸ A crime committed against women her male family member (s), to "bury" their dishonouring behaviour.

and rejected the norms of their societies are seen as a bad influence and bad women, the problem is that women from the same society support this claim and teach it to their girls. L62-C2's little daughter was talking about dreaming of playing football and her mother told her that if she ever did that she would be like X (a girl in the family) who was considered a bad influence and a source of troubles because of her choices, she furthermore adds *"If she had a man in her life, he would have controlled her impulsive character"*. The statements were not only strong but harsh, the way a woman would believe that other women's choices are wrong just because they were different is a male construct opinion, which was embedded so deep in the interviewee's mind she believed in it, and she is teaching it to her daughters. Another observation made from the statement is the need for male power, authority, or existence to "adjust" whatever is considered wrong or inaccurate, may not align with contemporary perspectives, but continues to persist due to its deep roots in societal norms and longstanding traditions.

Many Informants reported that social pressure persists throughout the lives of girls from their childhood until the time they get married. From the analysis of data collected, it is possible to divide or categorise girls' life cycle into three phases: the first phase is childhood (pre-marriage) where the girls are monitored by their mothers following their fathers or other cases their brothers' guidance, interviewee N58-C4 described a scene of her childhood where she wanted to play outside when she was 11 years old and she was rejected by her father because she is no longer a child, *"you are a grown woman, you should learn women things, playing is for kids"*, this scene was seen as normal as she has described it to be as eye-opening it was for the way male dominates the Amazigh some groups of the Amazigh, her father decided that she has grown up and she cannot go outside and there is no one who would interfere to change this decision, even her mother.

This leads to the following stage which is adolescence (supposed to get married), where girls face the stress of having to marry⁵⁹ before getting older which is 19\20, most girls get married by the age of 15 which is illegal by law, families tend to not register the marriage till the girl reaches minimum legal age which is 18 in Algeria⁶⁰. The pressure of this period drives girls to start doubting their beauty, their sense of responsibility, and the way they are seen in their societies because girls marry in a traditional way, such as distant family members or the suggestions of the women in the

⁵⁹ <https://webarchive.archive.unhcr.org/20230518175800/https://www.refworld.org/docid/540430a44.html>

⁶⁰ <https://www.prb.org/resources/child-marriage-in-the-middle-east-and-north-africa/>

village. M55 describes her marriage stating *“All of my sisters got married before I did, even the youngest ones”*, to her this was concerning as she continued talking *“Maybe because I was the least beautiful of them”* The pressure does not come only from their expectations or their interpretation for matters but also from their family members where males start asking why she is not married yet, to the girls it is embarrassing because they have no answer. In the last stage following the marriage, women’s existence transforms from the responsibility of their families to their husbands’, where they have several expectations from women for example submissiveness, delivering babies (especially boys), working hard in the household, tending to livestock and the land, acceptance of the new life with the in-laws. When marrying, man has the power and the right to make conditions for the woman he is about to marry, the conditions usually are related to her beauty, age, family, origins, and placement in society. As interviewee T63-C5 was married to someone who was 25 years older than her,

F: Did you marry for love?

T63-C5: laughs.... No, you see we used to get married and after that, if we are lucky enough, we may find love.

F: How did you meet your husband?

T63-C5: He was my relative and he was older than me by 25 years, my father saw that he was convenient as he was wealthy and could provide for me.

F: How old were you?

T63-C5: I was 16 years old but thank God we had a good life together and he was kind to me, I still remember him to this day.

Men usually prefer younger women, in some cases they specifically ask for a young and uneducated woman, whereas girls are not likely to ask for anything or make conditions of their own. In these societies as it is believed in and usually repeated by the interviewees *“the only flaw a man can have, is an empty pocket”*, as above mentioned by the interviewee T63-C5 her father agreed on her husband because he was wealthy. As superficial as it seems it was a way that a family can guarantee that their daughters will at least have a decent life among all the other things they were deprived of. After the marriage, women are expected to deliver babies, most of the women are usually asked whether they are pregnant or not, which is not only embarrassing but also stressful. In interviewing K63-C6, she talked about her experience where she had health

concerns that prevented her from having kids the first few years of her marriage, and that caused problems in her marriage, where the husband wanted children. Now she has 5 children with grandkids, and she stated that *“the amount of pressure I had almost led to my divorce, few who cared about my health because I was seen as mainly a birthing machine”*.

The pressure by males is not only performed when there are no children but also even worse when the new-born is a girl as previously talked about in this chapter section 6.1.1, when a girl is born, the family starts to plan for the next baby and pray for a boy. When North African countries converted to Islam, many practices and beliefs cease to exist as burying their dead with jewellery and weapons (Ouachi, n.d), or mummifying the corpse of their leaders (weeks, 2015), but somehow problematic beliefs such as having girls instead of boys still exist. Which has led to a demographical problem with an increased rate of birth in these areas as the need for a boy to carry the family name and lineage is all that matters.

Male dominance contributes to the forming of a patriarchal system, imposing submissive roles on women. However, these same roles give men certain privileges which serves them. Therefore, they do not think of challenging reality or changing it, because they benefit from it. As Eltahawy (2019) describes it *“This world is run by men for the benefit of men [...] men challenged other men for power to secure a share of that power for themselves, not for equality and justice for all”* (Eltahawy 2019, p. 100-134).

For example, when a woman marries, the authority over her transfers from her father to her husband and this is proof that power is held by the stronger and most fortunate party in this case the male authority. The patriarchy is not seen only in practices but also in terminology as T46-N2 was talking about her father and she said *“his word never drops to the ground”* which is a literal translation that whatever he says will happen no matter what. This expression is only used to describe men’s speech, another expression used to describe a promise is *“a man’s word”* and this is even used by women, where the word *“man”* is not replaced because it is culturally rooted in their minds that only men honour their commitments. This same expression is used in *“forced marriages”* when a girl does not approve of a certain person, her father, brother or even sometimes uncle says *“I already gave my word”* as a sign that it is final.

In some cultures, which bias to a gender is practised and believed in can lead to what is called cultural violence. Galtung (1969), states that cultural violence does not always relate directly to direct violence, but it legitimises the superiority of one gender or race over the other. This patriarchal mentality is prevalent in Amazigh cultural traditions. This mentality denies women the

right to make their own choices and puts them always under the guardianship of their male relatives. Such a mentality driven and supported by cultural beliefs and expressions are examples of cultural violence that empower men's voices and grant them authority over women. The triangle of domination, power, and conservatism establishes a sense of inferiority amongst women, which equally leads to oppression that was noticed during the interviews while talking about divorce.

6.4.4. Divorce and shame

As religiously and logically divorce is an option that frees women from oppression, violence, and other issues, socially is considered as a shameful deed. Divorce in Amazigh societies (especially in villages) is related always to women and their failure whether in the marriage industry or delivering babies: *"a woman must have patience for her husband"* that what is usually said and believed in. K56-C7 recalled a problem in her marriage and talked about how she maintained her family's stability by being patient and wise, *"my role as a wife is to treat my man as if he were one of the children, children often say and do illogical things"*, this statement justifies what a man do but never give the right to the women for getting a divorce or act defensively, the fact that women themselves believes in this illustrates the impact that the social norms leaves in people's minds.

The interviewee furthermore adds *"if we were as reckless as the girls of the new generation, we will be divorced... it takes patience"*, though it is logical to be the wise one in the relationship and make an effort to work it out, it is also a form of pressure that the society and traditions impose on women. The other point of the statement is considering the new generation reckless for what is a right, which in a different context as women who moved to big cities are seeing differently as a form of liberation and opinion. The contradiction of the same tradition in different locations and lifestyle illuminates the fact that shame and what is called *"ayb"*⁶¹ is related to the environment that women live in, and to their attachment to the traditions and culture itself. Ferguson and Eyre (2000) believe that a common sustained belief in Amazigh societies relates to gender roles and stereotypes, implying that women and girls tend to be *"more interpersonally sensitive"*. Accordingly, they are perceived to be more vulnerable to losing love and more relying on other's approval. This vulnerability in women tends to weaken their sense of logic and free will, where they choose to be accepted socially and liked.

⁶¹ Is an Arabic word to describe shame, but it has many meanings associated to social norms and traditions.

When the informants were asked about their perception of shame and how it shapes their lives, they were divided into two groups, the first group believes that people can never run away from their origins and traditions, and everyone who does this is a person who has no legacy or land, they even go further to express that as a form of treason to the ethnicity and their nation as one interviewee described it by a proverb often used in the Amazigh society *“li maando kbir ma ando tad bit”* which translates to *“the ones who do not have elderly do not have wisdom,”* and this expresses the idea that following the traditions and the practices of the previous generation is considered as a way of respect and appreciation to the ancestors. Interviewee B57-C8 said that *“once you see the concept of shame from a different perception you will understand that it is an educational way and the only method the ancestors managed to make rules that societies had to obey”*. She further adds, *“If I did not know that it is shameful to enter a room without knocking for example or putting my feet in front of the face of others, I would be still doing this, and it would be not good”*.

Three of the interviewees reported that they do not accept the idea of shame in their lives anymore nor do they use it to influence their girls, this group consisted of women who left the villages and changed their lifestyle. As one of the interviewees narrates how her grandmother was very strict when it came to traditions and beliefs, *“in my grandmother’s house it was not allowed to talk when the elderly are talking even if you had something to say or defend yourself from something, this has affected my personality deeply and I will never do this to my children or grandchildren”*, these women who rose in face of traditions, chose to see life differently. One interviewee who works in crafting bags and cultural items as illustrated in the statement below, expressed her disregard for shaming working women.

A59-C9: I am proud of my crafts and happy that I can do a job that I enjoy love and that gets me money, I don’t wait for anyone’s help and that is enough for me, I believe that shame is when you believe working or choosing a life you like as shame.

Historically due to the association of patriarchy with public spaces, which were considered as male domains, women being present in such spaces was often regarded as shameful. According to the concept that Sadiqi (2021) had coined *feminizing public spaces*, women can be found and seen in public spaces. But in some Amazigh societies, this idea of feminizing the public spaces is

not accepted, Mزاب, the most conservative society amongst the Amazigh, still does not allow their women to go out or work. As observed women are rarely seen outside and they avoid other people even females who are foreigners, women are always covered by “Hayek” a long white piece of fabric that covers everything except one eye they call it “bo awina” which means eye and refers to the only thing visible when wearing this traditional piece.

Unlike the Tuareg society which women are the authoritative gender, they choose to not work and let men provide for them but at the same time they have access to everything they want, T60 talked about her life “*I do not work but I have a livestock that was a part of my dowry, I brought a shepherd as a worker*”, Tuareg women are more powerful in the society because of their cultural norms and traditions, women have complete freedom and they see the divorced woman as a free one. Unlike all other Amazigh women, Tuareg men cover their faces whereas women do not, women own houses and livestock and bring workers to care for their wealth, while interviewing K56-C7 she stated that “*I am proud of my ethnicity and traditions, in my society, I have the right to live as I want*”, being a part of a culture that encourages equality between the genders makes women’s living conditions better and allows them to openly respect and protect cultural norms and traditions. Despite that, most Tuareg participants lived in rural desert areas with very low access to water and hard life conditions, All the Tuareg informants played a musical instrument whether it was Imzad⁶² or Tende⁶³, they all had the right to choose a partner and their own opinion to share.

Location is not related to the oppression practised on women, it is the mentality that oppresses women and holds them back, while it is justified that cultural norms and traditions are an ancient method for societies to spread respect, virtue, politeness, and organisation before any legal system or religion exist. It is also suggested by Ellemers (2018) that traditional female roles are related to undermining social status and prioritising interpersonal submission rather than dominance, which suggests that in traditional cultures, the roles designated to women are often perceived as inferior or less valued compared to those allocated to men. These roles commonly refer to behaviours or responsibilities that prioritise submission to men or obedience to social norms and traditions rather than taking leadership positions. For example, traditional gender roles expected from women are nurturing, providing, and prioritising care, and conserving

⁶² a single string bowed instrument used only by the Tuareg women.

⁶³ Is a musical instrument, made and played by Tuareg women similar to a drum.

relationships within the family or community, whilst men are expected to take leadership roles, make decisions, and be assertive. These roles and expectations lead to gender inequalities, reinforcement of traditional gender norms, male dominance, and oppression.

6.5. Amazigh Women Building Resilience Amidst Adversity

Although Amazigh women face numerous adversities talked about in section, they show resilience and perseverance to hold on to their culture and identity, they shape their adversities into opportunities for empowerment both internally and externally. This second part of the chapter explores Amazigh women aspirations, ambitions, and resilience, the participants of this study stood in face of the challenges and the adversities to preserve their traditions and lifestyles. Aspiration is defined by Kosec et al., (2018, 7-8) as “individuals’ goals for the future”.

Aspirations aims at several domains in life such as financial, educational, or social aspects, it is generated internally to hold hope and practice the strong will these women have in themselves to pursue their goals. Such hopes are tied to the surroundings and the circumstances in which Amazigh women found themselves in. For Amazigh women in Algeria the adversities mentioned and explored in the previous section are a central source of motivation and inspiration for change and empowerment, for themselves, their families, and their communities. From interviews conducted, three notable areas manifest hope and aspiration for the participants, hope in the new generation, women supporting women, traditions as witness for their efforts.

6.5.1. Hope in the future: new generations’ aspiration

The participants who had children 9 out of 20 expressed that their aspirations for a better future and a full recognition for their rights as an ethnic group lie with their children. For example, these participants did not have the chance to go to school themselves, they aspire that their girls specifically have the opportunity to do so and to pursue a high educational degree. While discussing with A55-C5 concerning her ambitions and hope for ethnic rural women, she answered that *“I wish for many things, to live a proper life, raise my children in a way where there is no shame or blame, I want my girls to go to school and have a proper job with good salary, I don’t want them to live the same life I did...”*

The interviewee talked about how hard she worked, the amount of *“misiriya”* (misery) she suffered and the challenges she faced to raise the kids, so they do not have to go through the

struggles she did. Another H57-C10 who has three children, all daughters, she talked proudly about her eldest daughter who have a job and works in a decent place as she stated “*she was my lifeboat, she is responsible for her other sisters’ education, she helps with the bills and everything. I have invested a lot on her...*”. In her statement, the interviewee felt like raising kids and educating them is an investment because they will return “the favour” back, girls, especially, are being put into a mould of if you succeed it is a win for the whole family, if you fail you will deal with the consequences alone. Although the pressure on the females is intense, as the interviewee described her daughter as a lifeboat, but it gives hope for females living same conditions, these expectations open door for girls to learn and work. As another interviewee talked about her mother encouraging her to study to save herself and she did get an MA degree, she is now helping her entire family and her own.

Thirteen of the interviewees also expresses hope in their daughters continuing their education, because they are making their dreams true, B53-V1 said my girls now enrolling me in literacy classes so she can learn to read and write, she furthermore explains that she could of never learn how to write her name if she did not teach her daughters. Most of the rural areas interviewees hope that their daughters and granddaughters have a better life, be empowered to claim their own identity and be their own savers, the “traditional upbringing is not bad” stated by K56-C7 “but is does not suit in this modern way, we raise children to be proud of their own identity and ethnicity but we have to see them develop it, it is scary for girls to be locked in...”. the statement aimed to encourage ethnic people to accept the changes and adopt new ways in protecting identity, the globalisation is not only a threat that the ethnic groups scare, it also can be a mean of salvation for their culture.

6.5.2. Women empowering women

In the context of Amazigh women, it can be seen that, the stereotypical image of them being *illiterate* and *passive beneficiaries*, and *reductionists* leads to a failure in their recognition and contributions in many aspects of their lives. Laghssais and Comins Mingol (2021, p. 8) argues that “the underlying mentality of the victimiser and furthermore reduces women to passive objects rather than active agents” which is another struggle Amazigh women undergo while they are fighting to be acknowledged and heard. Amazigh women unconsciously decline this view of being reductionists through self-empowerment, agency, and resilience on a personal and collective level.

As this part of the thesis explores Amazigh women collective efforts as mean in collective resilience and agency while sharing their experiences within communities that still protect traditions and values as collective practices that promote their local culture. In Algeria, Amazigh women are considered proud gatekeepers of their shared heritage and strong collective bond which creates undeniable mutual recognition between them. This reflects in a notable effect where women work together to empower one another while preserving their heritage.

Amazigh women demonstrate empowerment in various ways within their professional domains, particularly through crafts and traditional practices. For instance, they actively support one another in the learning process, creating a sense of community and shared growth. As these crafts and practices are deeply rooted in collective cultural heritage, they are transmitted across generations, with mothers passing their knowledge and skills to their daughters. In this way, women play a crucial role in preserving and safeguarding their cultural identity and heritage through the crafts and practices they engage in.

Sisterhood as it is called among Amazigh women is a crucial factor in their lives, they lift each other out of adversity and struggles as the strong women in the community perform crafting inspire other women whether in the same villages or other near villages to work together to and share initiatives in order to empower their families and communities. As M47-V2 said:

F: How do you know these crafts?

M47-V2: we learn ourselves from each other. Some cases the elderly women in the village start teaching the young girls and it continued with us through generation, for example my village is small, everyone knows everyone, and we are from the same tribe family member and distant family members, so we know each other. For example, when I learnt crafting, my grandmother said we need to preserve traditions and costumes of our tribe. Our women keep these alive by continuing to perform these crafts that we learnt from our ancestors, with the new trends and lifestyles these crafts always are innovating but we keep the knowledge and the essence living.

F: Do women help each other here in the village?

M47-V2: yes. Women help each other to weave big things, even the young girls from near villages come to learn. Our girls as well sometimes they have interest in other crafts so women in other villages teach them. We always welcome other women to learn and they do the same, it is a pride to teach about your heritage and learn also.

This support is also noticed in other aspects, such as transportation, helping with resources, M47-V2 illustrated the importance of these bonds and relations.

M47-V2: The neighbours are very important. In good times as well in bad ones, we check on each other, we collect help when one of us is struggling, my daughters' schools are a little far, so our neighbour usually takes them with his daughters, if there are a financial issues people of the village gather and collect the money needed to help them.

F: What about women supporting other women?

M47-V2: we have these traditions that when a woman is sick or mourning someone's death, we send food for weeks, so she does not cook, we keep an eye on her children. when women give birth, we celebrate her and the new-born we cook traditional food, I used to keep my neighbours children in my house so she does not worry about feeding and taking care of them, we even spend nights with her so she can get some rest while we take care of the baby. At our weddings and events, you find all the community helping. It's our responsibility as we have been passed these practices and this culture from our parents to keep it alive and transmit it to our children.

In other cases, women financially support the education of other girls through their crafts, one of the interviewees talked about her works in jewellery making in her village, describing that other women buy and advertise for her work to other women, in return she had an idea to help other girls in buying school stationary and books, *"I have been lucky to have this craft to help my family, so why not other girls, sometimes my neighbours need books and school stationary I get for them as I do with my girls, we also do charity works among us so if we have things that our children no longer need we donate them to others .."*

This solidarity spirit among women fortifies their works in crafting not only because it offers a financial stability but also communal support, adding to that it promotes their intangible heritage through adopting these practices in many facets. The traditional practices for these Amazigh women are not a mean of preserving culture only but also a mean of women empowerment and resilience that could lead to social change (Virkama,2006).

6.5.3. Traditions for aspiration, resilience, empowerment

Amazigh women are the gatekeepers for the culture in north Africa, they are also the primary figures in the Amazigh traditions and culture preservation. As Becker (2006) describe Amazigh

women as artists, she believes that they create the heritage not only they preserve it, which is the case for Amazigh women in Algeria. The themes in Amazigh arts and practices are centred around femininity and motherhood, for example, women weave carpets using motifs that express life, and fertility.

Amazigh women use the loom in their daily weaving activities, this tool is used by women in the production of traditional items, but it symbolises the idea of women being the creators of traditions and heritage. *“Women have the power of life over a textile, and when a weaver finishes it, she cuts it from the loom and the textile is said to die. This personification of the textile underlines women’s reproductive and creative powers and, by equating textiles with humans passing through the life cycle, reinforces women’s roles in the propagation of Amazigh identity.”* (Becker 2006, p. 44). Becker’s quote describes thoroughly how women used tools to express themselves in their communities and how the knowledge of the practices is perceived by them.

6.6. Empowerment Through Craft: How Amazigh Women Express Identity and Resilience

In this part the focus is on the role of Amazigh women handicrafts as tools of individual or collective use for empowerment, that contributes to their family’s and community’s thriving. The sample of participants interviewed during the fieldwork were diverse as some have their own small projects or initiatives and others who practice this tradition as a hobby.

Amazigh women are attached to handicrafts, historically crafting was an essential part of their daily lives, it has been a financial source through time for Amazigh women, especially those who live in rural areas or have a nomadic lifestyle. Many Amazigh women in the Tuareg still live a nomadic life which makes crafting a fulfilment for their needs, they create carpets, blankets, bags tents and other life essential items. As one of the Tuareg interviewees talked about an item called *“Qirbaa”* they use in summer to keep water cold, the nomadic lifestyle is based on moving so the domestic appliances are not needed, that results in them improvising to create items that suit their lives.

The Amazigh that moved to villages due to policies established by the French colony, as discussed in chapter seven, were encouraged to have a sedentary life, to fit in the civilised French colony and abandon their primitive lifestyles. Yet the Amazigh women despite this change in their lifestyles they retained the knowledge of the practices, and the skills to preserve their heritage and create a new version of their traditional items. Because arts and crafts express cultural identity and symbolise womanhood (Becker 2006).

Although the sedentary lifestyle is less stressful and more stable for Amazigh women, this new lifestyle has created a new social category of women such as women who are widowed or divorced. In the nomadic life women who lost a partner go back to the big family whereas rural women sometimes end up living alone with their children, as an interviewee recounted about her neighbour who is a 65-year-old widow *“she was struggling a lot alone with the children, but she started to weave winters capes, gloves and hats and that helped her financially ...”*. Despite that intangible heritage mitigates women from being autonomous, but the skills and the practices in some cases save lives and promote self-growth and empowerment. Arts and crafts can be identified as a powerful sign of resilience and agency for women who are facing struggles and adversities, using cultural skills and knowledge to better their lives and improve their communities.

The hidden side of the crafting experience that Amazigh women share is the social role of the process, when women gather around and talk about their adversities, share poems and proverbs, sing together, learn about other women’s wellbeing. Creating a social construct of a healthy environment that women support each other and grow self-esteem and confidence. This causes the crafting whether it is weaving, leather production, or even making couscous, to be considered an important tool in communities’ solidarity and prosperity.

6.7. Amazigh Women and The Fabric of Tradition: Weddings, Rituals, and Collective memory

Weddings are celebratory occasions representing a significant part of the social and cultural practice within a community. They lie within the scope of Article 2.2, section (c) “social practices, rituals and festive events of UNESCO's Intangible Cultural Heritage Convention of 2003”. Weddings are celebrations that highlight the deep value that these gatherings hold as they provide several cultural attributes in the shape of various customs, traditions, they are embedded in the core of a specific community or culture. This part will briefly describe the practices, rituals and traditions performed during collective gathering such as weddings in the Amazigh culture as described by the participants in the spirit of preserving their heritage and culture.

These collective weddings are in fact an attempt to help the poor people in the community and lower the costs for these celebrations to get married, due to the nature of the rural areas and their economical background, it gives the opportunity to spread happiness and joy among members of the society and sharing the collective memories. These events go beyond celebrating the folkloric aspects of weddings, serving instead as opportunities to unite the community and

foster discussions on important local issues, such as education and child marriages. Additionally, they provide a platform for local small-scale vendors to showcase and sell their products, while also creating space for artists and performers to share their talents through activities like dancing, music, culinary arts, and storytelling. As the interviewees described what is shared between the different Amazigh groups, the weddings last up to three days, the groom's party ceremony is named *Tamyra* or *tissulya* (wedding), the bride also have her own party called *asa n ighmi* (bachelorette party) at her parent's house. the night of the wedding the bride does Henna for her hands and feet starting from the right hand then the left as a symbol of good and righteous things, the bridesmaids also get Henna tattoos in simples forms while signing folk songs and rhythms, after that the elderly women braid her hair and cover it with a paste made of rose, Henna and clovers. They dress her in white fabrics as a sign for purity and innocence. The groom sends his male family members "*imslan*" to bring the bride to her new home in a ceremony called "*imngfn*" when the bride leaves her home her family usually breaks a jar made of clay that symbolise good omen, some Amazigh groups receive the bride by dispersing rice as prosperity sign.

These rituals are profoundly linked to the Amazigh culture, which is shared among the four investigated groups, as one interviewee declared "we enjoy making the day of the wedding memorial, we make the bride feel cared for and important, it is only the day of the wedding women feel special...". the interviewee appreciated her heritage and culture and described it in a way that traditions make women feel cared for and special, the rituals gives them the sense of belonging yet at the same time, "only on wedding days women feel special" expresses the hardship these women endure during their lives, and their need to be recognised, it shows that Amazigh women are supporting each other in important events in life and they share generosity, empathy and solidarity.

Many interviewees mentioned other practices such as "*Twiza*" that requires collective services, for example during harvest and construction of community buildings or other activities that helps the community. "*Twiza*" refers to a collective spirit that encourages all healthy and able members of the community to actively participate in chores that improve and develop their environment.

Amazigh women teach their children the traditional concepts of their identity and encourage them to take part in it, as one interviewee described "children learn with practice, my son was shy, he did not talk in public, but from our traditions and the events that he participated in he learnt

to be more social and have an opinion...". Amazigh women not only upbringing and raise future generations, but they also contribute to building up character and encouraging new generations in participating in their heritage and embrace their identity, as Adichie (2019) argues, "*the danger of the single-story*" makes Amazigh women at risk of falling victims to the idea of them being illiterate and ignorant rural women, which leads to denying them from recognition in their own communities. Amazigh women's aspirations and resilience will move them toward empowerment despite their adversities, marginalisation, and vulnerability. As Adichie (2019) believes, it is a responsibility to look beyond the single sided stories about local cultures ethnic groups and ethnic women.

6.8. Resilience Expressed: The Role of Language and Orality in Amazigh Women Empowerment

As discussed in chapter seven, Standard Arabic is the primary language in formal and professional settings, including political offices, business organisations, religious institutions, legal environments, and the media. It serves as the standard language for written knowledge (Sadiqi 2007). Despite the recent reforms in Algeria, Tamazight is still absent in the official use in many domains in the country, which makes Arabic the language of the public domains. Tamazight on the other hand, has started to be taught in schools and used officially in recent times, and mostly it is still underseen and other forms such as its written version. The first environment of Tamazight is the private sphere (home) where mainly it is used to transmit oral literature, folk stories, and traditions (Sadiqi 2003). As Sadiqi believes, the context of Tamazight has promoted the language to have a noticeably feminine connotation:

"As a language of cultural identity, home, the family, village affiliation, intimacy, traditions, orality, and nostalgia to a remote past, Berber perpetuates attributes that are considered female in the Moroccan culture." (Sadiqi, 2013:59).

Similarly in Algeria, where the Amazigh women carry the responsibility of preserving language and the culture, Algerian Amazigh women as other north African Amazigh, are the gatekeepers of their heritage and identity as Hoffman (2006, p. 147) stated "while urban men are primarily responsible for the campaign to bring Tamazight to the forefront of public consciousness, rural women are the ones who preserve and keep alive the language within their own communities".

The use of language for Amazigh women is a tool of empowerment, they are the active producers of linguistic and cultural traditions, as Sadiqi (2003) argues, although the government and society may have put ineffective efforts to improve the status of women related to social power and patriarchal, Amazigh women are, nonetheless, key negotiators in the language politics. Regardless of their backgrounds, they use language and oral traditions to shape their groups and, safeguard their cultural practices. Illustrating this a participant explained how Amazigh women can communicate among “we don’t need to use words sometimes; eyes can be very powerful in transmitting a message”. Body language is seen as a language itself when women want to share something without words.

Orality of Amazigh women is a significant factor in Tamazight’s survival, as they use the language in their household, with their children, and recounting folk stories, proverbs, songs, and family and cultural histories. As Tamazight is not the formal language of instruction in formal schooling, despite adding it to the education system, it makes Amazigh women responsible to transmit Amazigh knowledge using their mother tongue to future generations (Ennaji,2005).

This responsibility as stated by an interviewee “was never a man’s task, only women, I don’t remember my father talking in Tamazight to us after we left the village, only my mother was encouraging us to learn it and practice it...”, women take pride in preserving their identity attributes as , B57-C8 continued “I am doing the same with my children, although I am married to an Arab, but I remember my mother and her teaching she even keeps insisting on my children to talk Tamazight to her”. Amazigh women are guardians of culture, and they contribute to sustaining Amazigh artistic and cultural heritage through their practices and traditions such as textiles, music, poetry, and dance (Becker 2013). Moreover, Amazigh women are creative and innovative as they infuse artistic crafts with their oral traditions and transmit it through generation.

For example, women give Tamazight names to many patterns in their textiles works and pass them on to their daughters and granddaughters. The names differ according to the environment the weaver perceives, a deep connection between the women and their surroundings or the natural world (Eggert, 2017). As illustrated in the pictures below, Amazigh women insert the famous Amazigh pattern in most of their crafts as symbol of pride of their identity and ethnicity, they also insert motifs of birds in pottery and textile as a symbol of female freedom and liberty. Amazigh culture is illustrative, using animal and plant symbols in one of the most expressive forms as birds like Swallows, which are very common in the area, represent family and collectivism as they travel in flocks protecting each other. The use of the intangible in making the tangible allows

them to express their emotions and gives them a sense of rebellion on the patriarchal system and social norms imposed on them (Magdi and Ibrahim 2023). The patterns and motifs vary in meaning, for example some Tamazight names have a multitude of use and different significance for different artists and families.

Figure 6.1: Patterns in Amazigh crafts

Source: pictures taken by the author

Similarly to other form of intangible heritage such as songs and dances, they act as a tool of empowerment to Amazigh women, in a society where women have limited freedom in speech the oral heritage is used as a mean of opposition to injustice and marginalisation, most of these cultural attributes were never written, they were transmitted orally over generations (Becker 2006), which proves the position of women in preserving heritage. Intangible heritage in relation to Amazigh women is a way of life and survival, preserving it does not necessarily mean safeguarding a cultural identity, it may refer to the long history of women fighting for their rights and advocating for a better one for the new generations.

Amazigh women accomplish this through their competence in oral literature and traditional skills passed down orally through the generations. In some cases where society silenced oral female genres and works, as Sadiqi in her investigation on Moroccan women’s contribution to oral literature, she declares that “‘unofficial’ voices that circulate as ‘anonymous’ literature in the community without being officially recognised” (Sadiqi 2003, p.13). However, this manifested in a surprising resilience effect for these silenced women, for her women without notable social

authority and recognition, i.e., power positions, have less social constraints on their voices which gives them more room for self-expression without being seen as a threat. (Sadiqi 2003).

Storytelling is another tool for elderly women empowerment as described by Sadiqi (2003) they prove and retain their social value, through storytelling when they feel their status being taken by younger women who can bear children. They entertain their audience, often younger children, through suspenseful unfinished stories. As an interviewee talked about her mother “even if I tell a story my kids still prefer their grandmother telling it, they say she makes it more interesting and intriguing to listen to using old vocabulary and proverbs...”, from the interviewee’s quote it is noticeable that Amazigh women have the skills and knowledge to keep the listeners intrigued. Language also is a pivotal element in the process of storytelling, “they exhibit powerful thinking, memory and skilful use of psychological knowledge of human nature” (Sadiqi 2003, p.17).

The stories are female empowering they mostly contain themes that reference and challenge the patriarchal society, and traditional norms with mainly female protagonists using their intelligence to triumph over their male counterparts who are illustrated in the shape of monsters or villains (Sadiqi 2003). In many traditional stories provided by the participants such as the cow of the orphans, Loudja the daughter of the sultan, and the Oudaa and her seven brothers, the females triumph over the monster, the unjust of their families, the hardship of their society. These stories reflect on the lives and the environment of Amazigh women, their victory in the end of the stories mirrors their hope, dreams, and aspirations.

Orality is used by Amazigh women in negotiating social power through their knowledge of traditional skills, such as midwifery, herbal remedies, carpet weaving, *henna* art, and cooking are all essential part of society’s thriving and culture continuity as discussed in chapter three. These important skills are mastered and passed down through the generations only by women who maximise their value by keeping secrecy of the mastery of these skills, in one of the interviews a participant was asked to share a recipe, she jokingly states “the secret is not in the recipe, it is in the way that it was made” which refers to the fact that Amazigh women believe that traditions and practices are more than rigid guidelines, they have a background full of emotions and experience when it comes to ICH practices which empower them and allow them to express. As Sadiqi believes, “the acquisition of traditional skills is an opportunity for girls and women to experience typically female sensations that give women authority in all-women gatherings and ‘hidden’ power in society at large” (Sadiqi 2003:14).

In conclusion, traditions and beliefs are what make a culture live and evolve nevertheless, they have a different side that holds people back and forces them to accept ideas that seem in a modern setting unreal or problematic. Intangible culture might be a reason for the survival and existence of all civilisations, it is also a legacy that all cultures must protect but it can also restrain societies from evolving and adopting an unbiased perspective for women's role.

6.9 Conclusion

Despite the many adversities discussed in the previous chapter manifesting in the hardship of Amazigh women's lives, the patriarchal society the problems in accessing education, they show resilience and perseverance through embracing their identity and preserving it, creating agency from their struggles, and aspiring to embrace a better future for the next generations. Amazigh women have managed to turn their internal and external challenges into opportunities, and their oppression into empowerment.

Following from this chapter's focus on the governmental policies concerning the Amazigh, ICH and role of women in culture, the next chapter provides a link between adversity, empowerment and national efforts and initiatives.

Chapter Seven - Navigating Cultural Heritage and National Identity: The Role of Amazigh Women and Regional Leaders in Algeria's Decentralisation and Cultural Policy

The second chapter presenting the findings from the structured interviews conducted with four authority figures in the culture domains in Algeria. The interviews conducted across the regions of Tizi Ouzou, Batna, Ghardaia, and Tamanrasset provide valuable insight into the intersection of cultural dynamics and professional roles within Algeria's diverse cultural background.

This part of the analysis focuses on how individuals in leadership and management positions navigate the challenges through different lenses. In the context of policy, these interviews express the tension between national governance and regional autonomy that accommodates diversity in same country, particularly in regions where cultural and linguistic preservation is key to local identity such as Amazigh communities.

Algeria's centralised governance⁶⁴ structure, which promotes a unified national identity, often contrasts with the desires of regions such as Kabyle and Mزاب for more recognition and protection of their unique cultural heritages. On the other hand, Amazigh regions show resilience as individuals and communities by working to preserve their cultural identities in the face of economic and social pressures. In order to achieve the preservation of the Amazigh heritage, managers in these regions demonstrate resilience by adapting to both national policies and local expectations, ensuring the continuation of cultural traditions while also engaging with modernisation. These adaptive strategies reflect a deeper resilience embedded within Algeria's cultural landscape.

⁶⁴ Centralised governance refers to a system where most decision-making power is concentrated in the hands of the national or central government. Where local or regional authorities have limited autonomy or control over policies and decisions that affect their areas (Fiveable, n.d.).

Table 7.1: Territorial Organisation/ Decentralisation and Local Governance in the MENA Region, 2010.

Country	Provincial Level	District Level	Local Level
Algeria	58 provinces, <i>wilayas</i>	553 districts/constituencies <i>(da'iras)</i>	1,541 municipalities (communes)
Governance	The council of nation People's national Assembly	People district Assembly	People municipality Assembly

7.1. Algeria's Decentralisation Policy

Algeria's approach to decentralisation in terms of different domains such as, culture, education, and others, has been characterised by a cautious, gradual process in implementing what is called “directories” which refers to departments or administrations in different cities (Wilaya) responsible for different jurisdictions in order to reform balance, as each directories is responsible of a certain sector which allows citizens to bring up their concerns, additionally this regional development aims to maintain national unity and stability (Bergh, 2017).

The changes of reforming the administrative map have involved the decentralisation of responsibilities from central government authorities to regional, provincial, and local authorities as shown in Table 7.1 above. In 2019 the government have increased the number of provincial districts from 48 to 58 as an attempt to broaden the decentralisation process in the country by encouraging local governance, improving administrative efficiency, and supporting regional development, as stated in the law number 19-12 in the official journal of the Algerian government on the 11th of December 2019⁶⁵. However, these changes, have been balanced with measures that effectively enhance the oversight and authority of centrally appointed officials such as government representatives in their domains. A salient example of these changes is noticed in the increased power granted to provincial governors or as called “Walis” in 2005, where there was a shift in the

⁶⁵ <https://www.joradp.dz/FTP/jo-francais/2021/F2021022.pdf>

role of the *wilaya* from being primarily a local governance unit to a deconcentrated functioning administrative district (Bergh, 2010). Ultimately, the change in the administrative policies reflects a dual approach, where in some areas the local governance is encouraged, yet a significant control is retained by the central government through enhanced supervisory roles.

Historically the Algerian government maintained strong control over political and economic decision-making, especially after the period of the black decade in the 90s and the black spring, “Tafsut Imazighen”, which were among the darkest times of the nation’s history (as explained in the literature review chapter 3 section 4), and the recent social movements, particularly the Hirak protests, have in ways imposed a policy for greater decentralisation process that supports regional autonomy and equitable development.

In response to the people’s demands, the Algerian government under President Abdelmadjid Tebboune has introduced policies aiming in addressing regional disparities, particularly at the economic level in the disadvantaged areas in the south of the country and the Kabyle region, while still maintaining a centralised political framework. The key element in these intensified policies is to focus on key policy changes have focused on a system of investments and economic development dedicated to the underdeveloped regions aiming to address longstanding concerns related to regional inequalities (world bank, 2024). For example, economic policies targeting the southern regions including economic perks to minimise the sense of marginalisation in these areas communities.

7.2. Cultural Hybridity in Algeria

One of the most controversial concepts in postcolonial theory is hybridity. Cultural hybridity is defined as a duality between the coloniser and the colonised, and eastern and western culture. In his examination, the theorist Bhabha argues that (1994) due to the relation of colonisation between the two parties in conflict, where oppressor introduces parts of his culture to the oppressed (“as a part of civilising the uncivilised in imperialism”) and the natives presenting their culture to the coloniser, this interaction results in creating what is called “the third space of enunciation”, which emerges where a two cultures with their the beliefs, values and systems mix (Bhabha, 1994). With this concept, Bhabha (1994) refers to a hybrid space that allows for communication. It is a conceptual realm and transitional zone that puts colonial power norms and values into questioning, while allowing a space for creating hybrid identities and cultural changes

without imposing a dominant culture or identity. He, furthermore, employed hybridity to shed light on the contradictions in the colonial speech of power, that is to say, that the concept of hybridity eliminates the belief of an original culture which leads to challenging the colonial claim of possessing a superior culture (Bhabha, 1994).

7.2.1. Cultural hybridity during the French colonialisation

Bellocchi (2009, p.72) states that it *“Becomes the moment in which the discourse of colonial authority loses its univocal grip on meaning and finds itself open to the trace of the language of the other, enabling the critic to trace complex movements of disarming alterity in the colonial text”*. The assertion of Bellocchi, concerning the colonial authority losing grip, was absent in the participants answers as they were explaining how Amazigh culture had been influenced by the French colonialisation in some of the life aspects. Furthermore, some participants were using French in their answers, as one interviewee stated, *“unfortunately I couldn’t find an equivalent in Arabic or n Tamazight”*, which does not refer to the fact that the Arabic or Amazigh vocabulary lacks words but the habit of inserting French words since the colonial times.

Hybridity in the Algerian society is not seen only in the language, but also in other aspects of culture such as cuisine where many of the Algerian food habits are linked to the French (croissant, pain au chocolate). The concept of hybridity and its effects on the Algerian culture in general and the Amazigh especially Kabyle, was spotted in many answers as the following:

F: Do you think that preserving cultural events and festivals in one of the government’s concerns?

I: Actually, we do receive support to celebrate special event in Amazigh culture such as Yennayer ...and we do organise gathering at the level of the directorate, people attend and we do celebrate... a lot of the community member make jokes about that we should also make events in Christmas time... which we all see that is not part of our traditions and culture but a lot of people actually celebrate...”

In the previous passage the interviewee (RK) sees that celebrating a foreign cultural event as an intercultural aspect of the colonial period of the country. Nevertheless, it is also a form of resistance and opposition that local culture had to endure during those times, when from two

culture clashes a new one will be born. As the Kabyle interviewee stated that *“they had to learn the language to understand, they had to understand to live”*. Muñoz- Larrondo agrees with the idea that colonial culture fails to *“replicate itself in a monolithic and homogeneous manner”* in the colonies, so they end up *“creating an alienated colonised from its true self and identity”* (2008, p.15).

The French occupation had applied an “assimilationist ideology”⁶⁶ on the indigenous people as the Amazigh and people in rural areas (Mabrouh and Mgharfaoui, 2017). The French started convincing them with improving their life conditions by constructing railroads, facilitating goods transfers and currency value as well as their health or what the French called ‘mise en valeur’ of the colonies⁶⁷, which later resulted in the sacrifice of their way of life, culture, and values. The French saw that the African cultures need to be modified in a way that comply with the principles of the French government. Hence, the African colonies were turned into experimental grounds for French policies and served as sites of negotiation and conflict between the colonisers and the colonised, where the French kept altering and redefining the notion of the African potential and the ability to civilise them (Conklin, 2000). Returning the Algerian context, the French have considered Algeria their own and acted upon that in the way they were imposing policies and changes whether in the administrative domains or the society. Megglé (1931), in his book *“L’Algérie Terres Françaises”* claims that *“l’Algérie est Française”*, i.e., “Algeria is French”, he stated:

“Elle est fière de l’être, comme la France, dont elle est le prolongement à travers la Méditerranée...”

Which translates to “Algeria is proud to be like France, it is an extension to France across the Mediterranean” (As cited in Gosnell, 2002, p.13). It is clearly noticeable, from a colonial perspective that France considered the Algerian territory as a part of its own beyond its borders, which amplifies that the extension covers culture, language, values, and identity. This claim carries an underlying tone of a dangerous colonial ideology that works to erase the identity of the colony and aspire to impose its own. It also carries a direct threat to the cultural continuity of the Algerian culture and its local ethnicities. Maunier (1935, p.168) *“Le nom même d’Algérie est l’oeuvre des Français: Les Français ont nommé, ont créé l’Algérie, quelques mois même après la reddition*

⁶⁶The term "assimilationist" describes an individual, policy, or ideology that promotes or endorses assimilation—the process of integrating one cultural group into another, typically the dominant or mainstream culture.

⁶⁷ A French expression meaning bringing the best out of something.

d'Alger", this translates to "The name of Algeria was given by the French, they named and created Algeria, just few months after Algiers surrendered". Algeria, therefore, was a cavity that allowed colonial desires to be coercively implemented.

In summary, the French colonialism of Algeria significantly threatened the existence of the local cultures, as the Amazigh culture. The French occupation ideologies between 1830 and 1962 impacted the cultural identity of Algeria profoundly leading to cultural erosion by marginalising and suppressing the local cultures. This marginalisation and suppression were summarised by firstly, imposing the French language and neglecting Algeria's main languages where the official language of the administrations, education and even public life was the French, meanwhile Arabic and Tamazight were excluded and prohibited. Secondly, implementing French history and values, introducing the French culture as superior and civilised which was a form of cultural assimilation policy aiming to replace the local culture (Bouherar et al., 2021). Thirdly suppressing cultural practices and labelling them as primitive such as local religious practices and traditional gathering. Fourthly, land possessing where the French distributed the fertile lands of the Amazigh (Kabyle and Chaouia) to the European settlers leading to urban migration which affected the Amazigh's social fabric and style of life and resulted in diluting the cultural practices and the traditional customs. Despite all the deliberate efforts to erase the Amazigh culture in the form of cultural assimilation and suppression, by the marginalisation of traditional practices by imposing French language and cultural norms, and the threat towards the continuity of Amazigh heritage, yet the Amazigh with their resilience and resistance managed to preserve their cultural identity, language, and traditions. However, the colonial legacy, its cultural dominance, and its institutionalised oppression of local cultures, created enduring challenges in reviving and promoting Amazigh language and culture after independence.

7.2.2. Towards Arabisation in post-colonial era

The notion of the "civilizing mission" as defined by Harrison (2019), was a selfish and disgraceful religious and ethnocentric blend, embroiled in the colonial past where "*the end justifies the means*", i.e., the destructive ideology of the colonials was a justification for violent conquest. This ideology led to local cultures being threatened to disappear, in Algeria for example, the fight was to make a collective national identity that confronts the consequences of the occupation that lasted decades.

On July 1962 Algeria got its independence, after a seven-year struggle against the French colonialism. The country was facing pressing issues on all levels, which required a reform for the nation's institutions and a revitalisation for the Algerian identity. The Algerian nationals initiated the process of Arabisation to break ties with the occupation that lasted 132 years and form an independent nation with its own identity and culture. This decision has significant consequences on the country and the people. The radical change in the country administrative, economic, and the educational system and subsequently all aspects of life.

Algeria's pursue for identity require firstly restoring the national language as stated in the third article in the Algerian constitution "*Arabic is the official and the national language of the country*" (Algerian constitution, Article 3, 1963), which was facing critical drawbacks due to the occupation ideology of making Algeria French. Although the people had developed their own colloquial language, which is a mix of Arabic, French and other languages. Classic Arabic was not commonly used nor taught, leaving most of the ordinary people unable to write in Arabic. Whereas the educated elite were bilingual more adaptive to any language. However, it was a daring move to shift to the use of Arabic as the primary language of instructions and communication, especially given the challenging conditions of lacking resources for even providing a basic educational program. The newly liberated Algeria despite the challenges saw the reform of language as a step towards reclaiming its cultural and linguistic identity. As discussed in the interviews most of the interviewees saw that the risk facing the local culture is a result of the Arabisation policy that was adopted in the country. In the next passage an interviewee explains how some policies effected their regions when asked about the government efforts in terms of preserving Amazigh cultural heritage.

I: Things changed now I can say it is much better than before where the focus was on implementing the Arabic identity into the people to resist against the French occupation.....things are going to the better, people start getting over the colonial hard times and focusing on their culture and appreciating it.

Arabisation is the English translation, in Arabic "*taarib*" which refers to turning into an Arab or speaking Arabic (Balla et.al, 2017; Khalid, 2018). Or as cited by Dekhir (2013, p.25) "*the extensive use of Arabic in all domains of life: political, social, and cultural i.e., it refers to the promotion of Arabic as a medium of interaction in public and private sectors.*"

The Algerian government started a process of “language planning” or “language reform” as a first step in the restoring of the cultural identity of the country. This process was intervention to radically change the language used in the community and the official institutions (Benrabah, 2005), started by a political and administrative activity or ‘status planning’ where the language is designed to serve specific communal or societal sectors such as: education, and mass media. The stakeholders assigned that Arabic is the main language in all educational institutions and the official language for national television. Then, ‘corpus planning’ in which the language is assigned to form grammar, spelling, and develop new orthographies, and that had led to the way Algerian dialect or “*Darija*” is spoken in terms of lexical borrowing, standardisation, and diglossia. After that, the process of acquisition planning to ensure Arabic is being spread and fostered. An interviewee illustrated the importance given to teaching Arabic stating that “*most of my teachers in high school were from the middle east, I remember that my Arabic teachers was Iraqi, and my philosophy teacher was Syrian*”. The efforts done to implement Arabic were substantial, the government had allocated financial undertakings and human resources to popularise Arabic. Lastly, Prestige planning by creating positive attitude towards learning Arabic, and promoting the language as an identity marker and a pride (Benrabah, 2005).

After the independence, Algeria had a great interest in reclaiming its Arab and Muslim identity which was the opposite of the imposed French identity. Extensive efforts were made to eradicate the coloniser’s language and replace it. According to Benrabah (2007), is “the language policy implemented to displace French altogether” (p.194) and replace it with “classical Arabic; the language of the Quran and the essence of Arab Islamic identity, which entails choosing monolingualism over Arabic-French bilingualism” (Bossut, 2016, p.20). Nationalist in the country were convinced that preserving the language leads to preserving the culture and the identity. Undoubtedly, language is a powerful tool, the Algerian president Houari Boumediene, who was half Amazigh himself, was the biggest advocate for restoring the Algerian identity and erasing all the French remnants, he argued that an independence without a national identity is “in vain, our personality incomplete, and our entity a body without a soul.” (As cited Mostari, 2004, p. 26).

An interviewee gave a very interesting example as he argues that “*even the street in the capital Algiers were changed to Arabic names and the panels were written in Arabic*”. Where in fact in Algiers, places are named after Algerian martyrs, among these are Place Bugeaud, rue D’Isly, and rue Michelet which became respectively Sahet Chouhada’, rue Larbi Ben Mhidi and rue Didouche Mourad (Bekkai, 2015). This indicates the measures and the fierce promotion to the Arabisation

policy by nationalists, political figures and even presidents who believed in building an Arabo-Islamic Algerian identity and that entailed laws and guidelines to institute Arabic in all public spheres, and initiated projects in public domains such as environment, government, and education. The following is a sample of the Arabisation policy laws in the country where it is noticed that the government focus was on only promoting Arabic. Moving forward to the 90s where Algeria was going through several political issues after the death of Houari Boumediene and Chadli Bendjedid taking over. In that epoch, the country was under two different political arrays, an Islamic influenced current that favoured Islamic teaching, "*Shari'a*" laws, and the implementation of the Arabisation project, whereas the second one is a Francophonic opposing with the first in its secular democracy, advocacy of modernism, and adherence to the French culture (Saidouni, 2021).

As it is noticed from the above-mentioned discussions, in both periods of the Algerian identity restoration history, the Amazigh part is missing. The focus was on revitalising Arabic and officialise its use in the country, whereas the absence of the Tamazight, the Amazigh culture and identity is a reflection of the history of their marginalisation and the ongoing struggle for recognition and inclusion within the national framework.

Especially following President Bendjedid's statement of recognition of Algeria's "Arabness", as a reaction to criticism, he disclosed "Algerians are Berbers Arabised by Islam," (Saidouni, 2021, p. 232). This claim in many ways omits the Amazigh identity from the cultural map of Algeria. The Socialist Forces Front party (FFS) which was created in 1963, declared their complete opposition to the central government and their rejection to its Arabisation policies. The tension between the government and the Amazigh was uprising, the authorities had imposed oppressive measures against Amazigh culture and language, such as ending the Circle of Berber Studies at Algiers University in 1971, as well as making possession of Berber dictionaries and flags a criminal offense. The Amazigh on the other side started to protest especially after the cancellation of Mouloud Mammeri's lecture. Mouloud Mammeri is a Kabyle Amazigh writer and activist who was granted permission by the Minister Taleb Ibrahimi to re-establish the Chair of Berber Studies at Algiers University after being banned by Ben Bella's administration in 1962 (Benrabah, 2007). The lecture was supposed to be on the Kabyle folk literature. The cancellation was a trigger for riots and manifestations among the Kabyle, however, the government repressed activists and adopted measures against them which resulted in chaos and what is known by the black spring in 1980, that ended in arrests and deaths among the protestors.

The country was in a very critical state after the Amazigh protests for recognition, the collapse of oil prices in the 80s and the economic instability, people started to raise and oppose the policies and the stakeholders. As it was seen, the one-party system was not effective and was dictatorial, which compelled the president to follow people's demands and undertake political changes such as ending the hegemony of one political party and the recognition of party pluralism (Dris, 2022). The Arabisation policy in post-colonial Algeria emerged as a pivotal response to French colonial dominance, aiming to reclaim Algeria's Arab and Islamic identity. However, while efforts to displace French influence and promote Arabic were extensive, they came at the expense of the Amazigh culture and language, which were marginalised and suppressed. The Algerian government, driven by nationalist motives, instituted radical language reforms in education, administration, and public spaces to reinforce the Arabic identity (Chaker, 2001). Yet, as seen in the protests and uprisings of the Amazigh people, this policy led to significant social tensions. The exclusion of the Amazigh identity from the national discourse sparked resistance, as exemplified by the events of the Black Spring in 1980. Ultimately, Algeria's quest for a unified national identity was marked by a complex interplay of Arabisation, political reform, and cultural conflict, highlighting the ongoing struggle for recognition and inclusion in all aspect of the country's diverse heritage.

7.3. Cultural Marginalisation

Modood and Khattab (2016) stated that individuals take an essential part in forming ethnic groups and serve as the fundamental components of their ethnic groups. Hence, it is important to examine and understand individual identities, including their origins, culture, values, language, and traditions, which are markers of their ethnicity. So, neglecting any element of the ethnicity markers of any minority can be a threat to the whole ethnic identity, and that leads to marginalising those societies and their culture. Culture marginalisation affect ethnic groups deeply making them feel less important and not recognised by their own country, in Algeria the Amazigh language (Tamazight) was relegated, when Arabic was announced to be the first official language of the country, and implementing Arabisation policies threatened the continuity of their cultural practices (Benrabah, 2007). Arabic was used and enforced in schools, government, and public life, while Tamazight was excluded from educational curricula, official documents, and the media. The following Table 7.2 represent a survey done to examine the decreased number of Tamazight teachers in different Algerian cities.

Table 7.2: Fluctuations in the number of Tamazight teachers across various cities in Algeria from 1995/96 to 2007

Districts	1995/1996	1996/1997	1997/1998	2000	2002	2007
Algiers	8	10	-	-	3	0
Batna	9	8	-	-	0	21
El Bayed	1	-	-	-	0	0
Ghardaia	12	-	-	-	-	1
Illizi	3	-	-	-	0	0
Khenchela	6	-	-	-	-	1
Setif	3	-	-	8	-	5

As shown in Table, the inconsistent presence of teachers reflects the cultural marginalisation of Tamazight. The reason for choosing these regions, is that most of the inhabitants are Amazigh and speak Tamazight such as, Batna, Setif, Ghardaia and Khenchela, there has been a notable reduction in Tamazight teacher numbers, and in some cases, a complete absence by 2007. According to Tiziri, (2018), the decline in teachers number suggests a pattern of underinvestment in education concerning Tamazight, due to the state's historical reservation to fully embrace the linguistic and cultural Amazigh side. The data presents fluctuations of teacher numbers across various provinces in Algeria highlighting a broader issue, which is the neglect of Tamazight within the country's education system. For years, Tamazight and its associated dialects were marginalised in favour of the Arabic national identity, particularly in regions where the Amazigh population is significant, such as Ghardaia and Batna. The cultural marginalisation also menaced the local Amazigh traditions and festivals, such as Yennayer (Amazigh New Year), that were not officially recognised, as other Arabic or even universal events are, as official holidays in the country until 2018. One of the interviewees stated that it is contradictory that people were given a paid leave on the 1st of May as international workers day, but not the 12th of January which is the new Amazigh year celebrations.

7.3.1. Cultural marginalisation in the south

The Mزاب society is an Ibadi sect of Islam, distinct from both Sunni and Shia branches. They mainly live in the M'زاب Valley, a region in the northern Sahara. Mزاب, who are both Ibadis and Amazigh, have maintained and preserved their cohesive religious and cultural identity for centuries through all the changes the country went through. As described by the Mزاب interviewee "our heritage is famous for their unique architecture, strict community organisation, and religious conservatism". However, their ethnic traits and differences such as, religious difference, costumes, and traditions, have contributed to their marginalisation. As Sunna is the dominant sect in the country, Ibadism is regarded as a minority sect, often overlooked and forgotten. On the other side Tuareg as well, a nomadic Amazigh group and inhabit the vast Sahara Desert, struggled to maintain their independence and cultural identity in the face of modern state boundaries and centralisation efforts.

Tuareg, known for their distinctive culture, music, language (Tamasheq), nomadic way of life, and cultural traditions are facing for risk of modernisation and centralisation because of their nomadic social structure and pastoral economy⁶⁸. Tuareg culture, known for its oral traditions, music, and artisan crafts, has been suppressed by the promotion of the Arab-Islamic cultural attributes, and their traditional practices such as nomadic pastoralism and desert trade have been undermined by state policies aimed at integrating the region into the national economy.

The cultural and political marginalisation of the Amazigh in Algeria is evidence on the complexities of nation-building in a diverse, and a testament on a multi-ethnic society. The complexity in Algeria had roots from colonial era, that have resulted in a French colonial legacy, post-colonial legacy and a restored Algerian identity that had gone through phases to be a wholesome Algerian identity (Mortimer, 2010). Despite the efforts done to include Amazigh culture in all the nation's aspects, the struggle for recognition and inclusion remains a central issue in Algeria's ongoing efforts to navigate its national identity, one that reflects the diversity of its people and their historical legacies.

⁶⁸ A pastoral economy refers to an economic system that is primarily based on livestock herding and the raising of grazing animals, such as cattle, sheep, goats, and camels. This type of economy is common in nomadic or semi-nomadic societies.

7.4. Modernisation and Local Culture

One of the most important aspects discussed in the interviews is the tension between modernisation and the preservation of local cultures. The relationship between globalisation and cultural diversity is a complex one. Whereas globalisation can in a way expand intercultural interaction, broaden cultural diversity, and provide a better understanding for cultures and their differences, modernisation also generates cultural dominance in certain areas and among certain groups; for example, in the Algerian context the use of French is declining because of the dominance of English (Parinduri et al., 2020). Participants explained that modernisation is a threat to cultural heritage. Local culture and heritage are jeopardised due to the younger generation's lack of awareness and interest in preserving it (Suharyanto and Wiflihani, 2024). While the youngsters are concerned with trends and social media rather than their own culture and identity, the heritage and culture are disappearing from the daily life and routine of the people. As stated by an interviewee *“in a world where everyone wants to fit in with others no one wants to be seen as old fashioned and out dated”* and he goes further to explain that even the adults are slowly moving towards abandoning what was once an identity marker, for example most of the interviewees talked about “Kchabia”, which is a male traditional Algerian outfit very known to Mزاب society and their economy, is now being seen as old fashion and only used among elderly people.

Interviewees said that to overcome this challenge in particular, young people must develop an appreciation for their cultural heritage and actively engage in its preservation. Similarly, in Tamanrasset, the head of directorate faces the challenge of managing renovation projects while preserving the traditional Tuareg nomadic way of life. In the few past years, the Algerian desert have known an explosion in the number of tourists and travellers from all around the world that had resulted in putting the region increasingly under the pressures of globalisation and tourism. Despite that, it brings economic benefits to the region and the country but also threaten to commodify and alter the authenticity of Tuareg customs. As an interviewee had stated *“Tuareg are shy and reserved community, being in the spotlight of strangers is new to them as they have always been closing on themselves”*, it is noticed while visiting the families that their kids hide and only peek from time to time, even in main cities of Tamanrasset people are avoiding contact with strangers unless they are asked for help.

On the other side, in Tizi Ouzou, a region known for its strong Kabyle identity, the interviewee's responsibility involves not just administrative leadership but the navigation of politically sensitive issues around language and cultural rights. As per the past two decades, the Kabyle people have been advocating for the recognition of the Tamazight language and cultural autonomy in Algeria. Here we can see that modernisation in any country gives their people the power to put pressure on the stakeholders and policy makers to align with their national identity and reflect on their community values. One of the interviewees explained the relation between political pressure, modernisation, and cultural heritage by retelling stories from the 1980's black spring in the country, where he acknowledged the role of modernisation and its aspects as freedom of speech in promoting the Kabyle heritage. The interviewee, furthermore, illustrated that *"without the free speech, the freedom of journalism, the policy makers would not listen and made changes that after years of negotiating were completed on paper as well as in practice"*.

The technological and informational advancements have driven globalisation and modernisation, to significantly change contemporary societies in terms of connectivity, transportation, education, economy, even cultural diffusion. However, it has threatened local culture and heritage and created tension between modernity and tradition (Suharyanto and Wiflihani, 2024). The solution to this cultural dilemma is firstly, balancing between the modern development framework and cultural preservation, secondly embracing the benefits of the modernisation, and safeguarding the culture. Thirdly, accepting to coexist by adapting to modernity while preserving the deeply rooted traditions and unique ethnic identities. And finally, getting support from both the government and the concerned communities to safeguard and preserve local cultures (Suharyanto and Wiflihani, 2024).

7.5. Cultural Activism and Resistance

Despite the challenges facing Algeria's ethnic groups, these local cultures have shown resilience through cultural activism and resistance. In Tizi Ouzou, land of the Kabyle, for example, the Kabyle people have long been advocating for Amazigh rights and fighting for recognition from the government. In the riots of the Berber Spring in 1980, activists and supporters of the Amazigh identity recovery protested demanding their cultural and linguistic rights. With the support of organisations that promotes Amazigh cultural heritage and its protection, Kabyle culture is one of the most dominant Amazigh cultures despite the Arabic culture influence in Algeria (Boudhane, 2017). The interviewee states that in Kabylia "the society is well structured and organised, where

we promote our culture to generation ahead, we help of sometimes governmental organisation or even community organisations... we are one hand to carry out our legacy and keep it alive, it is the mission of people not only the government". This statement presents resilience and motivation for the Amazigh, they feel responsible for their own heritage with or without the government, same is case when reading the answer of interviewee when asked about whether they receive support, he answered *"it is not the case with support or financial aid, when people support their own culture it never dies, and when they give up on it nothing can save it..."* .

In Ghardaia, the Mزاب community has similarly engaged in efforts to protect its cultural and religious practices. Cultural events, religious festivals, and the preservation of Mزاب architecture such as their historical castles, are central to maintaining their identity in the face of national pressures and neglect in some cases. Tuareg in the Sahara facing challenges in preserving their nomadic lifestyle from the impact of modernisation and tourism, maintain control over their traditions and values, promoting it and celebrating its authenticity by presenting in festivals, introducing their traditions to tourists and trying to make an impact on foreigners, as stated by an interviewee *"in the beginning we thought tourism will ruin our land and make us look like we are primitive but we were surprised by the amount of people interested in our traditions and customs... now we are working on protecting our culture through introducing it to others and presenting it as we think it is"*.

Despite the South Amazigh efforts, they remain underrepresented in the political and cultural system, and their demands for greater autonomy and cultural recognition continue to be dismissed. Whereas the Algerian states prioritisation of a unified Arab-Islamic identity, the Amazigh and their cultural aspirations find themselves minoritised as result to monism as they fight for a pluralism culture that preserves and promotes their identities in a rapidly changing nation. In terms of objectives, the overall perspective within the Amazigh movement is that the progress made in the process of cultural recognition does not fulfil the needs and aspirations of this indigenous, ethnic minority spread across North Africa.

The achievements are considered insufficient and inadequate, considering the longstanding resistance, resilience, and efforts of Amazigh men and women, who have ensured the survival of their language and culture through centuries and throughout a vast region as Algeria extending from the Mediterranean to the Sahara. Moreover, these accomplishments do not fully address or rectify the linguistic and cultural destruction, discrimination, and inequality that have resulted from centuries of exclusion and forced assimilation imposed by foreign colonial powers seeking to

erase the history of the nation, and post-colonial ideologies seeking to unify the nation under one monism view.

7.6. The Role of National Policy in Regional Cultural Development

Historically, the Amazigh have confronted notable struggles in Algeria due to policies emphasizing and favouring Arab identity and Arabisation. Following Algeria’s independence in 1962, the government adopted a strong nationalist agenda that prioritised the ideology of the Arabisation and focused on the Arabic culture and language, often at the cost of Amazigh identity. This affected the national identity and led to the partial erosion of Amazigh cultural practices, languages, and traditional governance structures (Youcef,2020). As a result, to the French colonialism and post-colonial policies the cultural landscape in Algeria was complex and unequal, where the Amazigh felt neglected and excluded from the national narrative.

Few decades ago, national policies in Algeria started to shift towards greater recognition of the Amazigh identity. Starting with the language recognition in 2002, where Tamazight was acknowledged as a national language. The legal language acknowledgement was a significant milestone that reflected a growing awareness of the urgent need to embrace Algeria’s cultural diversity (Roberts, 2003). This first step was a foundation for promoting and including Amazigh culture within the educational system, economic development, and political representation. Starting with the role of national policy in education which was integrating Tamazight and aspects of the Amazigh culture in schoolbooks, national curriculum and scholar events created a sense of pride and awareness among younger generations and encouraged them to value their diverse identity, as it is presented in Table 3 below the number of Tamazight teachers and learners has been increasing from 2010.

Table 7.3: Number of Tamazight teachers from 2010/11 to 2012/13

Scholar year	2010-2011	2011-2012	2012-2013
Learners	213075	225210	234690
Teachers	1330	1427	1654

Source: Hamdan and Kessar 2023, Language Policy and Planning in Algeria: Case Study of Berber Language Planning

In 2017, the Ministry of Higher Education and the High Commission for Amazigh declared that the total number of the enrolled learners in Tamazight course in three educational levels primary, middle, and secondary schools reached 600,000, as a response to the 2016 officialisation of the language, and the number of the provinces teaching Tamazight rose to 38 (Hamdan and Kessar, 2023). By the school year 2019-2020, the Secretary General of the Commission, Professor Hashemi Assad, announced that the total number of Amazigh teaching classes reached 15.000 allocated in 44 provinces. Due to the efforts and measures adopted by the government teaching and learning Tamazight will be mandatory in the next 10/20 years (Hamdan and Kessar, 2023).

These recent educational reforms aiming at spreading the Amazigh culture among the youth begun to cultivate a sense of identity among them, however, the efficiency of these initiatives depends on professional training for teachers and on available educational materials in Tamazight. The Algerian government is intensifying its efforts and declaring the opening two new translation departments from Tamazight to other languages in 2022 at the universities of Bejaia and Tizi Ouzou. Other efforts including the Linguistic Atlas including areas where Tamazight is spoken in Algeria, the UNESCO a list of Algerian languages including different varieties of Tamazight (Aoumeur, 2023). On the 1st of April 2022 the 25th International Book Fair of Algeria (SILA) had presented 27 new Amazigh titles and an online Amazigh newspaper (Algeria Press Service, 2022).

On the cultural level, the authorities have initiated projects aiming to protect and promote Amazigh heritage and culture, such as supporting Amazigh events like the Amazigh New Year (Yennayer) and other cultural festivities that celebrate Amazigh traditions (Becker, 2016). As well as supporting local traditions and practices such as the Mزاب agricultural techniques, the Tuareg musical traditions and the local governance systems in Amazigh tribe the "Djemaa" council (Harmon,2014). Moving to the economic development, where national policies also promoted cultural tourism as an attempt to reach sustainable economic initiatives that focus on Amazigh heritage. This step can create economic opportunities while preserving cultural traditions as the interviewees declared, the tourism in the Amazigh areas opened doors for commerce and personal development for creative individuals as jewellery makers, leather production, and many other crafts (Bernasek,2008).

These initiatives involved local Amazigh communities in the process of decision-making and ensured that cultural tourism respects and reflects their identities (Wasela, 2023). Moreover, promoting regional development in areas as Tizi Ouzo, Ghardaia, and Tamnasset will lead to investments in the field of healthcare and security and that will reduce disparities and foster

economic and social growth while respecting cultural identities. However, these national development projects and processes must consider the fact that adopting such measurements should not commodify Amazigh culture for profit only but instead prioritise the preservation of traditional practices and community well-being. Finally, national policies are working on providing the proper political representation of the Amazigh to ensure that their voices are included in political decision-making and their demands concerning effective policies that support their cultural preservation are met (Kruse III, 2013). Recent movements advocating for greater representation and autonomy for the Amazigh in Algeria reflect a growing demand for recognition and respect. However, political tensions between the central government and Amazigh activists often complicate these efforts, making it essential for policymakers to engage constructively with Amazigh representatives (Jabi, 2011).

These policies and measurements reflect a growing acknowledgment and recognition for the importance of Amazigh culture in the dialogue of Algeria's national identity and regional development strategies (Aïtel, 2014). The ongoing efforts aim to promote adequate social and economic development, fair political representation, and a full validation of this major part of the Algerian cultural legacy, while preserving and protecting the Amazigh cultural heritage.

The impact of national policy in the field of local cultures development, particularly concerning the Amazigh in Algeria, is a diverse dilemma that covers social, economic, and political dimensions (Zoubir and Amirah-Fernández, 2008). National policies directly influence the preservation and promotion of cultural identities, especially for marginalised ethnic groups as the Amazigh, who historically have faced many struggles in their cultural heritage recognition within a dominated Arab national narrative and identity in post-colonial Algeria. These national policies serve as a framework for cultural revitalisation and sustainability. For example, cultural policies that emphasise the importance of social capital⁶⁹ in the Amazigh culture refers to the societal networks, relationships, shared values, and norms that promotes cooperation and collective action within the Amazigh society, it also represents the sense of belonging and mutual understanding that individuals from the same cultural group build and develop to maintain their cultural continuity and resilience (Kirmayer et al., 2009). The social capital values enhance community cohesion and cultural vitality among the Amazigh.

⁶⁹ Social capital refers to the networks, relationships, and norms of trust and reciprocity that enable individuals and groups to work collaboratively and achieve collective goals.

Edwards et al. (2003), argues that social capital is reflected through the strong community and family bonds, shared language, similarly to the case of the Amazigh people in Algeria, as the collective efforts to maintain and revitalise their cultural practices despite historical marginalisation. These societal efforts dedicated to preserve their culture, revitalise it and resist all the pressures in dismissing it, is a clear example on how social capital helps sustain their unique cultural identity and help with its continuity. Axelsson et al. (2013) stresses the importance of cultural vitality and identity and highlight that they are crucial indicators of successful cultural policies, which support the sense of belonging and participation among marginalised culture. This is particularly relevant in Algeria, where the Amazigh identity have been previously overshadowed by Arabisation policies. To reach a sustainable cultural diversity and inclusion it is vital to recognise and incorporate the local cultures as the Amazigh into the national narrative (Kruse III, 2013). The interviewees' answers support this statement in terms of the difference that was noticed after recognising Tamazight as an official language in the country, and the effect of this recognition was the first step in the process of revitalising and promoting the Amazigh culture as a whole.

The vitality of the Amazigh culture was one of the reasons for its continuity, the traditions, crafts and practices on one side are indicators of cultural heritage but at the same time are vital for economic development in regions such as Kabylia (Tizi Ouzo), where communities depend fully on traditional crafting and the practices knowledge for their incomes. Yang et al. (2018) supports this idea of culture and heritage significance in the context of developing countries, as their survey on the Pakistani hand crafts show how it serves as a national income, which we can relate to the Algerian context where Amazigh crafts in a way are a source of financial support to the country.

The interconnection between national and regional policies is also fundamental in shaping cultural identities. In the Algerian context, the historical and socio-political landscape has significantly influenced the Amazigh's struggle for recognition and rights. Perret (2014) stated that the governance of cultural policies in Algeria must take into consideration the unique aspects of socio-cultural dynamics of the Amazigh and their groups. The distinguished aspects of each Amazigh group create an array of differences in policies and actions (Crawford and Hoffman, 2000). The Amazigh of the south mostly known for their conservative lifestyle and modest manners in which as stated by an interviewee "if the same policies were to be adopted in Tizi Ouzo and Ghardaia that may lead to conflicts and misunderstandings, you cannot implement a

policy that put a woman in a more privileged place than a man in Ghardaia because of the social norms there...". This statement illustrates the complexity in policy implantation whereas every group has its own values and norms. However, as Zamorano (2017) states, the comparative analysis of cultural policies in different regions presents a middle ground on how sub-state actors can influence cultural governance and identity formation. Therefore, empowering local governance structures in different Amazigh regions can lead to more effective relevant cultural policies, this approach influences not only regional cultural development but also strengthens national unity by embracing diversity.

In summary, Algerian national policies can shape regional cultural development, particularly for Amazigh culture that have been struggling for recognition. The promotion of cultural diversity, the support of traditional practices in many aspects, including financial and institutional, and the empowerment of local governance and decentralisation of the authorities leads to building national policies that facilitate a thriving environment for the diverse Amazigh groups and maintain an inclusive and sustainable cultural landscape of the country. This, in turn, enhances social cohesion and contributes to the overall development of the Amazigh region.

7.6.1. Challenges facing national policy and development in Algeria regarding the Amazigh

The Algerian policies and development procedures related to the Amazigh culture and identity still face several significant challenges, despite the notable progress in recent years. These challenges can be summarised in language standardisation, cultural preservation, economic hardships, and bureaucratic issues. One major issue to the government policy development is the language standardisation, noting that of Tamazight has several regional dialects, this diversity in the linguistic field complicates the process of creating a unified written language for education and official use. Despite that, Tamazight was recognised as an official language in 2016 and started to be implemented in all educational levels (Laidani,2019). However, its use in the national education system is inconsistent, and the distribution of the resources is still limited to certain areas and many regions lack trained teachers and resources (Chaker, 2001).

The cultural preservation is another pressing issue, as modernisation and rapid urbanism is threatening traditional Amazigh practices and languages. The younger generation increasingly prefers English or French, because of the uprise of the social media and globalisation which creates a raising concern about cultural erosion. Furthermore, fully embracing Amazigh identity on a political level is facing a resistance from different sides, such as the Arab Nationals and religious

conservatives (believing in the superiority of Arabic) which creates a limited representation for Amazigh demands in national policymaking (Maddy-Weitzman, 2018). Centralisation is another challenge: several Amazigh regions are being excluded in political decisions and their autonomy and ability to manage local affairs is dismissed, which has resulted in economic disparities, as Amazigh-majority regions like Kabyle in the villages and the chaouia in Aurès mountains are often isolated comparing to urban areas (Mechiat,2022). They are facing lack of job opportunities, facilities and resources which causes aggravation among local populations. This aggravation creates social tension between different ethnic groups, and fuels resentment between Arab and Amazigh communities such as the Ghardaia riots in 2013 between Mزاب and Arabs (Hadj-Moussa, 2023). The favouritism of a group over the others sometimes worsens these tensions, complicating the efforts to reach a unified national identity.

On another level the bureaucratic obstacles delay the procedures of promoting Amazigh language and culture. For example, although the language was officialised years ago, it is still slow due to the administrative limitations and, as described by some interviewees, insufficient funding for cultural initiatives. Additionally, the media representation on one side remains scant, with limited platforms consistently broadcasting in Tamazight (Dhehbiya,2023), which hinders broader cultural outreach, and the constitutional gaps regarding the practical implications of Tamazight's official status on the other side. All these challenges make it a real struggle to fully acknowledge the Amazigh identity and provide the required consistent enforcement in government and public life.

The solution of these challenges is in tackling the issues in terms of a national identity framework, concentrating all efforts to ensure that Amazigh voices are heard in decision-making processes and their demands are met, also to enhance investment in fields of education and facilities, and to promote cultural pride while establishing national unity. In an increasingly modernizing society and a culturally diverse country, the Amazigh culture risks further marginalisation if further sustained commitments were not made.

7.7. Women's Right for Recognition

The female pursuit for historical acknowledgment in Algeria manifests through the use of cultural heritage, such as the traditional costume. During the Algerian 2019 movement or as called

in the country “*Hirak*⁷⁰” Algerian women manifesting in the streets wore the Algerian “*Hayek*” a one-piece white cloth that covers the entire body and face, to express their identity and belonging. This attire was a symbol of resistance during the war of independence, where women hid their faces in its large white scarf to oppose the French policies of cultural erosion as discussed in chapter three section 4. On Independence Day, pictures of Algerian women wearing this symbolic piece was widely seen on social media, expressing women's resistance (Ourahmoune and El Jurdi, 2023). Women continued to challenge the authorities when they declared that the Amazigh flag was illegal and arrested protesters who displayed it. In response, women were out in the streets wearing traditional Amazigh dresses and jewellery, asserting their Amazigh heritage as a big part of the Algerian identity while also carrying the Algerian flag as a form of resistance (Ourahmoune and El Jurdi, 2023).

A recurring theme in all the females’ interviews in chapter six, and in the interviews of this chapter was the reference to the “*moudjahidates*” or what is translated to “*female freedom fighters*” during the colonial era. While investigating figures of female resilience and strength, notable characters appear such as Djemila Bouhired, Hassiba Ben Bouali, and Djamilia Boupacha who took up arms and faced torture and unjust persecution under French occupation between 1954 and 1962. The women considered their participation in the “*Hirak*” as a continuation of the legacy of rebel Algerian women who fought for independence and earned respect from both men and women (Ourahmoune and El Jurdi, 2023). Algerian women are respected for their bravery and their achievements in preserving the nation and the culture. Throughout the war of independence, women were foundational pillars of the Algerian society. Many of them lost their husbands and became widows yet chose not to remarry to raise their children, handling both maternal and paternal responsibilities. Regardless of their ethnic or educational background, all were filled with pride in being descendants of resilient women capable of anything to support their families as the Amazigh women and their resilience as discussed in chapter six.

⁷⁰ The *Hirak* movement in Algeria refers to a series of mass protests that began on February 22, 2019, sparked by widespread discontent over then-President Abdelaziz Bouteflika’s announcement to run for a fifth term despite his declining health. The movement quickly evolved into a broader demand for systemic political change, targeting corruption, the dominance of the military in politics, and the lack of transparency in governance.

Women who do not belong to the “Feminist Square” ⁷¹are proud of the traditional opinion of women as guardians and protectors of cultural values, traditions, and caretakers of the family. This internal heroic view of femininity reflects on sacrifices embedded in Algerian women during the colonial era (Ourahmoune and El Jurdi, 2023). Their struggle was not merely a fight for equal rights as citizens, but also a fight for the nation’s survival. Part of the women who participated in the “*Hirak*” sought delegitimizing feminist demands and aiming to validate their demands for gender equality by remembering the long history of women’s resilience and invoking images of the “*moudjahidates*” who scarified their lives during the independence and the women who died in the black decade’s violent events specially towards women (Ourahmoune and El Jurdi, 2023). The struggles for recognition faced by Algerian women encompass the political policies alongside the cultural side of male authority as Hobson's (2003) asserted that to understand the recognition struggles it is required to have insights into cultural gender frameworks.

It is important to understand these cultural frameworks within the socio-historical context that creates them. To clarify and explore the complexities of post-colonial contexts, the emphasis must be on encompassing different contexts and examining them on their different merits to avoid homogenizing women's struggles, because each context has distinct socio-historical aspects that shape gender ideologies and cultural frameworks (Ourahmoune and El Jurdi, 2023). Amazigh women’s context differs significantly from Arabic women’s context, for example rural Amazigh women living in villages live under the rule of male authority without having the chance to challenge it, rural women in general cannot access the justice system to fix legal matters such as inheritance or divorce. The socio-cultural norms prevent them from their rights and impose an ideology of accepting men’s opinions and decisions.

The cultural framing of gender in Algerian society is shaped by cultural practices and Family Code, both presents and mitigates pathways for recognition struggles (Laaredj-Campbell, 2015). The interaction between feminist demands and established gender frameworks makes it complicated to adopt efforts for recognition and creates a controversial space surrounding women’s right. While social movements limiting women’s rights may be characterised as nonviolent and progressive, yet the reality reveals that the apparent advancement of women's

⁷¹ been used metaphorically in recent feminist discourse to represent inclusive spaces where feminist ideas, activism, and intersectionality converge.

rights often comes at a cost (Ourahmoune and El Jurdi, 2023). This dynamic leads to a scant application of women's roles, where their contributions are acknowledged only in theory.

In the analysis of the Algerian policies concerning women's rights, a set of law and regulations were notable, these laws point to a proof of efforts the Algerian government is adopting to change the conditions of women in society and in politics (Ourahmoune and El Jurdi, 2023). According to the changes made to the Algerian Constitution in March 2016, Article 36 states that the government is committed to adopt efforts and measurement to promote equality between genders in the job market (El Amine, 2024). This also covers an encouragement for women to advance and integrate into leadership roles within public institutions and private companies.

The acknowledgment of women's contributions and rights in Algeria is inserted in the country's legal framework, which labels them as crucial parts in the economic and social development process. This framework focuses on the principles of equality and non-discrimination between women and men. For example, Articles 37 and 40 of the Constitution guarantee these rights, ensuring that women access the employment field and that they are protected against discrimination (Ait Aoudia, 2024). As the law 90-11, ratified on August 21, 1990, protects working women by guaranteeing they receive equal pay and fair working conditions, consequently securing their right to equal salaries compare to men's salaries (Nemar, 2010). Moreover, the authorities' attempt to improve the law related to ownership and equality by enacting articles to fortify women position in this matter, as the Article 674 of the civil code states that Algerian women have the legal right to own and manage property independently. This indicates Algeria's commitment to promote and empower women. Remarkably the government-initiated programs to job creation and entrepreneurship which resulted in positive outcomes (Dendougui et al., 2024). In the period of 2019/2021, the National Microcredit Management Agency (ANGEM) issued significant loans for women's small businesses and innovations. The loans going to women were estimated to be 64% of the government budget for small businesses (Benzidane and Boudraf, 2021).

This decision acted as a reflection of the Algerian government support to change the society perceptions and attitudes towards women, as women can be entrepreneurs and contribute to every aspect in life. The Algerian society uses the expression "*your place is in the kitchen*" as a slogan of patriarchy and male authority, whereas a women's place can be anywhere she decides to be, this expression is diminishing for women and their abilities. With the change evoked by the government policies especially in the period of Abdelaziz Bouteflika, and the laws upholding the principle of gender equality (Zeraoulia, 2023). While women have made gain in representation

within elected bodies and government, there is a notable contradiction in their presence and their aspirations for greater involvement and impact (Entelis and Naylor, 2019).

7.8. Conclusion

In conclusion, French occupation in Algeria had a profound and detrimental impact on the local Amazigh culture, as it systematically attempted to erase and replace the indigenous cultural identity. The colonial period between 1830 and 1962 was marked by the imposition of the French language, the exclusion of Arabic and Tamazight from public and formal domains, and the promotion of French culture and values as superior. This cultural assimilation policy extended beyond language, affecting local religious practices, social gatherings, and land distribution, which in turn threatened the Amazigh way of life and diminished traditional customs. Despite these efforts at cultural suppression, the Amazigh people exhibited remarkable resilience, managing to preserve significant aspects of their identity, language, and traditions. However, the colonial legacy has left lasting challenges, and the struggle to fully revive and promote Amazigh culture and language.

Chapter Eight - Discussion

In recent years, Algerian government policies had a significant role in recognizing and supporting Amazigh cultural heritage, yet the impact on the empowerment of Amazigh women, particularly in cultural preservation efforts, remains complex and paradoxical as shown in the previous two chapters. The recognition of Tamazight as a national language in 2002, followed by its application in 2016 (Laidani, 2019), symbolised a daring step toward embracing Amazigh identity as an integral part of Algeria's national narrative. While these initiatives affirm the government's intent to address cultural diversity, the reality for Amazigh women reflects an ongoing struggle against both structural and societal barriers that limit their roles in intangible heritage preservation and social participation. For Amazigh women, cultural preservation is deeply personal, embodying in the tangible artifacts of their heritage, as discussed in chapter 6 section 6, and in the intangible cultural heritage that defines their community's identity, values, and traditions as for instance as discussed in chapter 6 section 5.2, 5.3 and 6.7.

Amazigh women manifest an enduring commitment to their roles as cultural guardians, yet they often face challenges and adversities such as limited access to resources and educational opportunities. These limitations put at risk their ability to engage fully in cultural initiatives and obstruct their presence in decision-making processes. In Amazigh rural regions, deep rooted social norms further complicate their participation, limiting women to traditional roles and frequently marginalizing their contributions to cultural preservation. This situation persists even within an evolving legal landscape that seeks gender equality but, in practice, offers insufficient support for the personal and societal challenges faced by Amazigh women.

As they confront these obstacles, many Amazigh women actively advocate for greater recognition of their cultural contributions. They seek inclusion in programs and initiatives designed to protect intangible heritage, emphasizing on the need for policies to value their perspectives and empower them as leaders in preserving Amazigh traditions. This section examines how the current framework affects Amazigh women's efforts in cultural preservation and highlights the broader implications for inclusive policy-making that genuinely values and uplifts their roles as custodians of Algeria's rich and diverse heritage. Furthermore, the chapter provide a link between chapter six and seven and underpinned by research findings, it focuses on discussing the empowerment of Amazigh women through advocating for solution for their adversities and improving policies concerning them.

8.1. The Effect of Government Policies on the Empowerment of Amazigh Women and Their Ability to Participate in Cultural Preservation

Algeria government policies have a significant influence in empowering Amazigh culture and more specifically, empowering the Amazigh women and their roles in local culture preservation. The recognition of Tamazight as a national language in 2002 was a daring move in acknowledging the Amazigh as part of the Algerian identity, furthermore the government elevated its status in 2016 (Laidani,2019), marking a pivotal shift towards adopting new policies concerning the Amazigh culture. However, the implementation of these policies remains inconsistent and limited. Amazigh women express the will to engage actively in cultural preservation efforts and to participate in the Amazigh identity recovery process, yet they face systematic barriers and social adversities such as limited access to resources and educational opportunities that obstruct their participation.

As stated by Ourahmoune and el Jurdi (2023), Algerian women's courage and ability to preserve the nation are highly respected within society, yet despite the dedication Algerian women show in protecting the culture and traditions they encounter several difficulties. In local culture as the Amazigh groups, women are more vulnerable to challenges in many aspects, in this context, Amazigh women struggle in obtaining funding for cultural initiatives, these challenges manifest on the systematic side. Additionally, in terms of social norms that prevent women from being actively involved in the process, as mentioned in chapter six, the adversities that Amazigh women endure affect their personal life and social roles in their communities. Gaining recognition as leaders in cultural events is a struggle, as mentioned by K56-C7 "women are best at what they do, if they do it in their houses" which justifies the nature of societies that dictate women's' roles as "housewives". In the same position women believe that they are overlooked in their societies and need to be recognised for their efforts and participation in their culture, as one of interviewee stated, "Despite our contributions to preserving our culture, we often find ourselves overlooked in decision-making processes."

8.1.2. Legal framework and gender equality

The legal framework governing women's rights in Algeria discussed in chapter 5 section 4.4 and chapter 7 section 8 has encountered several changes through time, nevertheless it is often scant and insufficient in addressing the specific challenges faced by different women ethnicities,

more specifically Amazigh women. Although the Algerian constitution proclaims gender equality, the reality on the ground reveals persistent gender inequalities (Porrás-Gómez, 2022). The real state of the laws related to family and personal status often follows the traditional gender roles and social norms, limiting women's autonomy in critical areas such as marriage and inheritance⁷² (Gray, 2009). On a cultural level, the intersection of gender and cultural identity complicates the fight for rights (Bond, 2003), because individuals often face overlapping systems of oppression or discrimination that are tied to both their gender and their cultural background, and the different cultural ethnicities in the country entail different measures and regulations to cover all the diversity in the cultural landscape (De Zwart, 2005).

Despite the government's attempts to enhance female representation, the participation of women in political life remains limited. In Algeria, the rate of female delegates rarely exceeds 25% (in 2021 was 22.5%)⁷³, a figure that reflects different statistics in other north African countries like Tunisia and Morocco (FIDH, 2021). Whereas in these countries there have been notable advancements, such as Morocco's current government containing seven women ministers, and similarly in Tunisia with a woman as the head of government and ten female ministers out of twenty-four. Yet, female participation and representation remains unchanged in Algeria. Many Algerian women, especially Amazigh women who are barely integrated in the dialogue of decision making, argued that this lack of representation is frustrating, as B57-C8 expressed: "We have voices, but they often go unheard in decision-making processes. We wish to have women in places that influence change." (...).

The change that Amazigh women aspire for can promote progress in women's rights. Political representation on one side reflects on broader societal attitudes that change the perception of women in ethnic groups and motivate other women to be ambitious. For example, restricting women to roles that are stereotypical in fields like culture and health, while positions typically held by men, such as finance and justice, are still predominantly male-dominated (Bishu and Headley, 2020). The "Gender Gap" report from the World Economic Forum declared that, despite the development in fields of education and employment, women's participation in the national

⁷² Algerian report, Sarah Chellal and Zouhour Ouamara, October 2021, forthcoming.

⁷³ <https://www.fidh.org/fr/themes/defenseurs-des-droits-humains/algerie-zoom-sur-le-hirak>

economy remains at 16%, compared to 75% for men. This difference reflects the structural inequalities that persist in the workforce.

Many women, especially those living in rural areas as the Amazigh, oversee the domestic responsibilities while also contributing significantly to agriculture as many interviewees mentioned in chapter 6, they are the financial providers in their families, and, moreover, they even assist in the process of crafting for their families' businesses. In fact, Amazigh women are the backbone of their families and societies, they work tirelessly without wages or acknowledgement, yet they have look after their children and husbands. M47-V2 living in a rural area said, "We take care of our families, their livestock, and many responsibilities, but our work often goes unnoticed and underappreciated."

Whilst the Algerian state invests heavily in social services through initiatives such as free education and healthcare (Brégain, 2016), aiming to improve women's living conditions, the outcome is yet to be determined as systemic barriers continue to hinder their empowerment and access to equal rights. The government had adopted Programs designed to improve facilities (electrification, water supply, and housing) and had enhanced access to public services for women and girls. Yet, poverty and marginalisation are significant issues that limit women's empowerment and recognition, particularly for ethnic women living in patriarchal households, they face several challenges in obtaining the adequate resources and support as it was shown in chapter 6.

In conclusion, while the Algerian government has made progress in creating a legal framework that advocate for gender equality, the lived experiences of many women, especially Amazigh, reflect the opposite. Amazigh women, in particular, face a dual struggle against both patriarchal norms within their communities and the broader societal expectations imposed by the national policies. This ongoing struggle for recognition promotes feelings of frustration and marginalisation in Amazigh women, yet it fuels a determination to resist and fight for their rights and a better equitable future. The quest for gender equality within ethnic groups in Algeria requires continued advocacy and engagement to ensure that the voices of all women, especially those from marginalised communities, are heard and respected.

One of the significant research objectives in this study includes analysing Female's dynamics in the transmission of intangible cultural heritage in Amazigh culture and examining how can governmental initiatives in Algeria better interact with Amazigh women, their communities, and their unique cultural heritage. To achieve this, it is essential that the government develop programs in partnership with Amazigh women, rather than only for them. This collaborative approach would

ensure that Amazigh women's voices are heard, and their insights are integrated into the management and decision-making processes (Gagliardi, 2018). By empowering Amazigh women and integrating them to strategies and collaborations, they will encourage their community to engage in programs and cultural institutions and gain a better understanding of what these women expect from such initiatives and how best to serve their communities in a relevant manner. Furthermore, the evaluation of Amazigh community engagement programs can provide valuable insights into how future initiatives can be structured to better support Amazigh women and Amazigh culture (Laghssais and Comins- Mingol, 2023). It is essential that these programs tackle the specific needs and aspirations of women, thereby facilitating their active participation in preserving and promoting their cultural heritage.

8.2. Cultural Identity Empowering Amazigh Women

The profound link between cultural heritage, identity, and empowerment is significant for Amazigh women. This research investigates the way these women perceive themselves as guardians of their cultural heritage, emphasizing their vital role in shaping both their communities and their national identity (Laghssais and Comins- Mingol, 2023). Amazigh women relate their reflections on their culture and identity with a sense of pride and responsibility. Many interviewees express how their connection to cultural heritage influences their self-perception and community roles. S58-C4 remarked, *"We are the heart of our culture. By preserving our traditions, we ensure that our children know who they are and where they come from"*.

The findings on this research reveal that Amazigh women are not just passive participants in cultural preservation; they actively engage in the process. They understand that their identities are intertwined and linked to their ability to maintain and transmit cultural heritage (Evangelista 2003), particularly intangible cultural heritage. As noted in the literature review, intangible heritage is best preserved by those who practice it and transmit it (Ruggles and Silverman, 2009). Amazigh women are positioned to carry forward their traditions, having inherited the required knowledge that shapes their understanding of cultural significance. For example, the importance of traditional crafts and practices is embedded as a means of connection to their culture and history. Non-Amazigh individuals would find it challenging to replicate the art and designs and to save the meanings rooted in these crafts, as they lack the Amazigh cultural context that enrich these choices. This awareness inspires Amazigh women and fuel their passion to participate in

community cultural engagement programs, ensuring that they contribute to the preservation of their cultural past, promote their culture in the present and protect it for the future (Boudraa and Krause,2021).

Their commitment to and participation in cultural preservation is also a form of empowerment and resilience, allowing them to preserve their identities in an era of modernisation. By participating in cultural events and small community teaching programs as discussed in chapter 6, they seek to teach younger generations about the significance of their heritage. They believe that by passing down their knowledge and skills, they are preserving their culture and empowering future generations to embrace their identities fully. The Amazigh women empowerment journey is full of adversities and challenges. Women often face gender inequality, societal expectations and traditional norms that can limit their opportunities. Yet, through their resilience and determination, they are challenging their societies and changing their roles within their communities. They are not merely maintaining traditions; they are claiming their rights as women and cultural leaders and showing that cultural identity and empowerment are deeply interconnected (Sadiqi, 2003).

In conclusion, Amazigh women's cultural practices, expressions and traditions highlight their identity and link them to their heritage and community which empower them to participate in their culture's continuity. Amazigh women activism in preserving cultural heritage and in some cases advocating for female's rights reflect a broader narrative of resilience and empowerment.

8.3. Cultural Heritage Guardians: How Amazigh Women Preserve Heritage amidst Globalisation

Cultural practices among Amazigh women as discussed in chapter six, serve as an important expressive tool of their identity and heritage in Algeria. Traditional crafts, storytelling, music, and rituals are not merely forms of artistic expression; they are powerful acts of resilience against cultural assimilation (Bronner,1998). In a society where globalisation threatens local cultures and identities (Trichopoulou, 2012), Amazigh women's role in transmitting cultural practices to younger generations ensures the continuity of their heritage and culture. This transmission is pivotal, as it empowers women in maintaining their cultural identity and claiming their presence and significance in their communities.

For example, the complex patterns in Amazigh textiles crafts, see illustration 1 in section 6.8 figure 6.1, carry deep cultural meanings and stories that connect women to their ancestors as

discussed in chapter six. Interviewee code stated, *“When I weave, I’m not just making a carpet; I’m sharing my ancestors’ stories and preserving our identity.”* Such statements reflect the deep connection between Amazigh women and their cultural heritage, illustrating how traditional crafts and the knowledge are infused with personal narratives. This connection is important for maintaining a sense of belonging and identity in an increasingly globalised world (Andayani, 2020).

As Algeria continues to struggle with the challenges and the impact imposed by modernisation and globalisation (Katumo et al., 2023), it becomes increasingly important to safeguard the intangible cultural values of the Amazigh people. Community engagement initiatives should cover all cultural events, activities, and projects that provide enhanced learning experiences for younger generations (Gootman, and Eccles, 2002). These initiatives are crucial for guaranteeing that future generations keep a connection to their cultural identity and heritage. By making the Amazigh women active and involved in the design and execution of these programs, cultural institutions can spread the sense of belonging and pride among community members.

In the field of cultural heritage studies, it is important to recognise the profound links between the preservation of cultural heritage and the cultural identity of Amazigh communities in Algeria. This understanding presents significant implications for how policymakers, researchers, and cultural organisations approach the safeguarding of heritage (Aïtel, 2014). Involving Amazigh women in discussions about cultural preservation, opens the door for institutions to address the challenges and opportunities presented by the need to preserve both tangible and intangible cultural heritage.

The insights collected from this research highlight the importance of recognizing the agency and resilience Amazigh women show in their cultural practices. Although, they come cross historical and current challenges, these women are not passive participants; they actively shape their cultural narratives and assert their roles as custodians of their heritage. Essentially, the sustainability of cultural heritage in Algeria depends on the empowerment of Amazigh women and on the support provided for them to take ownership of their cultural identity and heritage (Macdonald, 2021). Collaborative efforts and creating inclusive spaces for these women, will contribute to a comprehensive understanding of their heritage and empower them in their ongoing journey for recognition and equality.

Moreover, the role of educational institutions and cultural organisations is another factor in the process of preserving heritage. As discussed in chapter six, girls in rural Amazigh areas experience hardship in accessing schools. The need to prioritise educational access for Amazigh

girls and provide better scholarly opportunities will change the reality for many Amazigh families (Laghssais and Comins- Mingol, 2023). Adopting a supportive environment for female empowerment, spreading community awareness that challenge traditional beliefs about women's roles (e.g. that they should not get a proper education), and creating a cultural understanding that values and recognises the contributions of women in Amazigh societies, will encourage women to overcome the adversities and evolve (Mosedale,2005). The conservative societies can collaborate with local organisations to design and implement programs that resonate with the community values and practices while adapting to the modern times.

8.3.1. Activism through cultural engagement

One of the forms Amazigh women in Algeria advocate for their right to be acknowledged through cultural engagement which is an essential platform in highlighting their significant contributions to their culture and their society. Integrating local communities in heritage preservation guarantees that cultural practices and traditions are preserved and protected across generations (Brown, 2019). Events such as the Amazigh Cultural Week provide a venue for women to exhibit their artistic talents and to facilitate discussions on broader societal issues that affect their lives. These cultural gatherings promote solidarity among women as discussed in chapter six, and create opportunities for networking, advocacy, and collective action. Women's participation in these events, to assert their cultural identities and to push policymakers to recognise their cultural heritage within the larger national framework.

In recent times, the widespread of social media has had a notable impact on empowering Amazigh women to promote their cultural practices and raise awareness about their rights. Social media platforms create a space, via online campaigns, forums and other avenues, for women to share their personal stories, connect with compatible individuals, and mobilise support for their causes and needs can become, as Kumari (2024) highlighted, a potential for women to express themselves and fight for their rights. These digital platforms on one hand encourage them to have voices, and on the other hand allow them to create supportive networks that have no geographical boundaries. Similar to other women, Amazigh women express their opinions, talk about their situations, and share their experiences online. They contribute to a growing movement that aims to challenge stereotypes and promote the rich diversity of Amazigh culture.

Findings from this research alongside to other literature hints at how community engagement in Algeria can support women empowerment by focusing on the management of cultural policies

aimed at preserving intangible cultural identity. The Algerian policies and laws protecting and displaying tangible and intangible cultural heritage such as handicrafts and the knowledge and practices of crafting, created initiatives and opportunities for empowering women to share their intangible heritage knowledge with others in structured environments, yet these are still regarded as insufficient and limited (Boukhalkal and Touhami, 2024). Amazigh women are facing challenges in being integrated directly to the initiatives and are overlooked in the process of intangible heritage preservation.

The importance of developing cultural community activities cannot be overstated. Such initiatives and activities promote cultural ideals and integrate them into broader engagement programs (Skounti, 2010). Amazigh women feel a profound sense of responsibility to protect their cultural heritage, a sense echoed by Yang (2018) in relation to rural women globally. These women are aware of the significance of their roles and identity and are prepared to face the challenge, trusting their cultural expertise and the rich traditions they embody. This illustrates the necessity of integrating Amazigh women's voices into discussions about cultural preservation strategies and procedures through truly involving them in community engagement and cultural initiatives. While the suggestions of empowering Amazigh women in policies related to cultural engagement are ratified, policy makers, cultural institutions, and community leaders are subsidizing their practical recognition and the value of these women's contributions.

The cultural engagement through Amazigh women's participation enriches the cultural landscape of the country, preserves the heritage, and empowers women to take ownership of their narratives creating a sentiment of pride in identity.

8.3.2 Balancing tradition and modernity

A significant aspect in the experiences of Amazigh women in Algeria is the complex relation between tradition and modernity (Smith, 2004). As Amazigh women aim to preserve their rich cultural heritage, simultaneously, they quest to adapt to modern societal changes. The act of balancing is evident in how they engage with traditional practices while embracing contemporary challenges and opportunities that can improve their socio-economic status. For example, in rural areas, many Amazigh women are increasingly participating in social workshops and cultural programs that mix the traditional skills with modern techniques. Consequently, they participate enhancing their financial independence and provide an income for their families as discussed in chapter six (see section 6 and 8).

Amazigh women focus on traditional crafting such as weaving, pottery, and embroidery. In one of the social workshops held in the Kabyle region, a group of women came together to learn modern weaving techniques using new machines while preserving traditional patterns unique to the Amazigh culture. T48-V3, explained this dual commitment, stating, “I want to preserve our traditions, but I also want a better future for my children. I am sure we can do both”. This statement reflects a broader aspiration among many Amazigh women who understand that preserving their cultural identity does not prevent them from pursuing progress and innovation in these modern times.

The Algerian government admits the need for economic sustainability in the Amazigh areas, thus it has implemented certain cultural programs and development plans to promote both economic growth and to preserve cultural heritage (Silverstein, 2017). These plans are vital in rural regions inhabited by Amazigh communities, which require investment to improve their local economies. For example, the establishment of cultural tourism initiatives in the Saharan regions (as mentioned in Chapter 6) seeks to exhibit the unique crafts and traditions of the Tuareg people, encouraging visitors to experience the Amazigh culture first-hand. Making facilities to travel to the south and promoting traditional food, music, planning trips with official but local guides. In the recent years, the Algerian Sahara and the Tuareg people have experienced a significant shift from being closed societies to a more global integration (Keenan, 2004). These initiatives create more job opportunities while reinforcing the cultural significance of Amazigh heritage. Furthermore, these efforts of blending traditions with modernity serve as a reminder for new generations that practicing traditions and preserving culture does not necessarily mean living in the past, it also helps with improving the present and aspiring for a better future (Ahearn, 2014). For example, the annual Amazigh New Year celebrations, “*Yennayer*”, include fairs, music, and traditional performances. These celebrations are platforms for Amazigh women to present their crafts, such as handwoven carpets, silver jewellery, and other traditional attributes, while also teaching the younger generations about their cultural significance which is more important than the item.

In this context, some of the Amazigh area have been allocated with budgets and investment opportunities, in sectors such as tourism, education, and cultural preservation (Boukrouh and Kessab, 2010). This strategy aims at investing in modern technology to promote the heritage, for instance by organising cultural events where the participants can explain the skills and practices with short clips and slides. This use of technology empowers women in introducing their culture and preserve it, both traditionally and contemporarily. However, from the perspective of some

Amazigh women, the excessive influence of globalisation creates a threat to the survival of cultural heritage. Several women express concerns that unmonitored globalisation could overshadow the traditional practices, leading to diminishing their cultural identity as B57-C8 believes *“the way social media influence people and children, to be heritage as old fashioned, as traditional clothing, certain practices and believes...”*. They believe that properly managing the relation between globalisation and cultural preservation is important for maintaining the skills and practices of their communities. For example, several participants voiced their fears during the interviews asserting that foreign influences are dominating all aspects of their traditional life, so their practices and identity is at risk of fading away. As interviewee code pointed, *“If we do not protect our cultural heritage, then the entire identity of our community may fade away.”* This statement echoes Wilson (1999) findings that emphasise the importance of community agency in preserving cultural heritage.

Another aspect of modernisation is noted in the tension between the older and younger generations of Amazigh women, while the younger women choose or in some cases got the opportunity to pursue educational degrees, certain women for the old generation believe that it might lead them away from traditional roles as caretakers of cultural heritage (Inglehart and Baker, 2000). Older Amazigh women find themselves debating this issue, as cultural expectations dictate that the younger generation should preserve the traditions and customs and pass it down through generations. Which makes it contradictory as in similar cases women who have lived under certain social and cultural norms and expectations that limited their autonomy, should react differently as they were resisting these norms and expectations. However, the data collected shows the resilience in the young generation, as several interviewees were able to do both, be educated and break from traditional role while at the same time preserve and pass down cultural heritage. The new generational despite the awareness, however, is still facing adversities within their communities.

The aspiration within Amazigh women remains strong despite these challenges, they are committed to spread the importance of intergenerational transmission of cultural knowledge, intangible cultural heritage (Smith, 2015), ensuring that the richness of their culture is maintained. Smith (2015) highlights the effect of community engagement programs and gatherings as discussed in this section previously, a smaller model community engagement can be made by Amazigh mothers and their children. Involving younger generation in the process aims to promote community engagement programs and linking tradition with modernity. In addition to workshops

that focuses on the skills and practices, storytelling sessions where elder women recount folktales and historical narratives are pivotal in preserving the oral traditions of the Amazigh culture. These sessions act both as educational and cultural events, allowing younger generations to connect with their heritage in a meaningful manner. Such initiatives promote a deeper understanding of the values, traditions, and history that shape their identity as Amazigh people.

In conclusion, the experiences of Amazigh women in Algeria illustrates the complexity between tradition and modernity. As they manage the challenges of preserving their cultural heritage in rapid changing time, these women demonstrate remarkable resilience and adaptability. Amazigh women aspire for environments that support both cultural preservation and economic empowerment. While the Amazigh society focus on ensuring that their rich traditions continue to thrive through time, it yet fails to acknowledge Amazigh women 's value and their contribution to preserving their cultural identities and practices against many changes. Amazigh women ensure that these practices are understood, respected and passed down. Participant code used an Algerian proverb to explain "it is okey to love the new, but do not forget the old", which is a summary of the issue with modernity and tradition, embracing modern ways of life is valuable, however, forgetting about traditions and cultural heritage risks losing essential parts of identity and continuity.

8.4. The Resilience and Challenges of Amazigh Women in Algeria amidst Gender Inequality

The complexity of the social norms and expectations in Amazigh women's lives is a central factor that these women struggle to face and overcome. They navigate various societal pressures that interfere in and shape their daily experiences, often forced by inherited gender norms that have significantly constrained their autonomy. As argued by Laghssais (2021), gender is a social construct controlled by the rigid social system of honour and shame, which poses strict limitations on women's attitudes and choices. Girls from a young age, are viewed as the property of their families, transitioning from paternal control to that of their husbands after marriage. This perspective was directly illustrated by one interviewee who described her marriage, reflecting on her childhood innocence with a mix of nostalgia and resignation: "I thought it is a kind of games or a party... where they dressed me and left me in another house with new people... I was so scared at first... she laughs" D67-N4. Her experience carries an intensive sense of displacement, where the change in familiar and social environments made her feel merely as a participant in her life, rather than an active agent.

Marriage in local culture carries several connotations such as the concept of "body purity" which further complicates the understanding for these women in relation to the society. The need to maintain women's honour and reputation reflects on how their lives are managed, they are constantly under surveillance and guard, with any wrong perceived attitudes or actions that would lead potentially to dangerous repercussions, including the tragic phenomenon of "honour killings."⁷⁴

This gender-oriented pressure creates an environment which considers that submission to male authority is the norm, not just through actions but also through deep rooted beliefs. Amazigh women who dare to challenge societal norms and beliefs are labelled as bad influences; interestingly, these judgments frequently come from other "obedient" women who have submitted to patriarchal norms. For example, in chapter six, an interviewee shared her experience when her daughter expressed a desire to play football, she did not receive encouragement, on the contrary her mother warned her that pursuing such interests would link her to a female relative known to be a bad influence, continuing the damaging cycle of judgement that encourages the restrictive gender norms and diminish any hope for challenging them.

The striking reality is that choices and approval on marriage are made with an emphasis on financial stability rather than love or compatibility, leading to a sense of powerlessness among women. They become embroiled in a system where their value is measured against their ability to bear children, particularly sons as discussed in chapter 6 section 4.1. The societal obsession with lineage is exemplified in the undue pressure women face to produce male heirs, often leading to distress when a girl is born.

This pervasive culture of patriarchy creates an environment where women are marginalised and deprived of agency. As Eltahawy (2019) strongly believes, the structures of power and privilege tend to benefit men, perpetuating a cycle of control and subservience. The transition of authority from fathers to husbands is representative of how deeply ingrained these gender dynamics are, often viewed as unchangeable truths than women cannot challenge or object to. Women internalise this oppression to the extent that even their language reflects patriarchal values. As shown in Chapter 6, participant T46-N2 described her father's authority, stating, "His word never drops to the ground," a phrase that symbolises the weight given to male opinions. Such

⁷⁴ Honour killings refer to the practice where individuals, typically women or girls, are murdered by their own family members because they are perceived to have brought dishonour or shame to the family or community

expressions reinforce the belief that men's voices are paramount, while women's experiences and perspectives are considered nonessential.

This cultural environment has profound implications for the mental and emotional well-being of Amazigh women. The societal endorsement of male superiority, coupled with a lack of avenues for self-expression, creates a space that carries cultural violence. Galtung (1969) describes that cultural violence justifies the oppression of one gender over another, a phenomenon that clearly promotes the sentiment of inequality in Amazigh communities where cultural traditions reinforce male dominance. Women face societal and cultural barriers that limit their opportunities and diminish their self-worth. As result many Amazigh women assert that their contributions to cultural heritage preservation is the only escape from the male dominance area. They consider that the intangible heritage their own, a space where gendered role vanishes, women hold on the traditions and the heritage to express themselves and tell stories. Yet their contributions and efforts are overseen in their societies, as S55-C3 stated, "Despite our contributions to preserving our culture, we often find ourselves overlooked in both recognition and decision-making processes.". This sentiment illustrates the broader struggle for recognition within their communities. Women often feel demoted to the background of their societies, performing vital roles yet lacking acknowledgment as leaders in their culture preservation. The societal tendency to view women primarily as "housewives" further diminishes their visibility and contributions.

In terms of the legal framework surrounding women's rights in Algeria, although there have been significant strides towards gender equality, the reality remains clearly different. The legal structures often reflect traditional gender roles, limiting women's autonomy in critical areas such as marriage and inheritance (Gray,2009). The intersection of gender and cultural identity complicates the fight for rights, as different ethnicities within Algeria face unique measures and regulations that fail to address the diversity of cultural experiences. While some advancements have been made, such as promoting female representation in government, the practical application of these changes remains inconsistent, particularly for Amazigh women (Charrad, 2001).

The systemic barriers faced by Amazigh women highlight the need for continued advocacy for gender equality and cultural recognition. These women engage in a dual struggle against both patriarchal norms within their communities and the broader societal expectations imposed by national policies. Their ongoing quest for recognition and empowerment underscores the importance of inclusive dialogues that elevate the voices of all women, especially those from

marginalised communities. Ultimately, the experiences of Amazigh women reveal a profound determination to one hand resist oppression and fight for their rights, contributing to the broader narrative of women's empowerment in Algeria. On the other hand, face the societal and cultural expectation forced on them by either patriarchy, or culture settings.

In summary, the intersection of gender, culture, and societal expectations significantly influences the lives of Amazigh women in Algeria. Their experiences illuminate the complexities of navigating a world that often seeks to define their identities and roles in restrictive terms. As they continue to advocate for their rights and cultural heritage, it is essential to recognise their resilience and the vital contributions they make to their communities. Empowering Amazigh women to challenge the norms that bind them is not just a matter of justice but also a crucial step towards preserving the rich tapestry of Algeria's cultural landscape.

8.5. Empowering Amazigh Women Through Education: A Pathway to Cultural Preservation and Social Change

Education acts as a pivotal role in empowering Amazigh women by challenging imposed societal norms and facilitating asserting their rights. Several initiatives aimed at increasing educational opportunities for girls in rural areas are emerging within the community, despite the barriers to access them. These communal programs focus on raising awareness about the value of educating girls and promoting literacy in Amazigh areas, and for Tamazight, the traditional language of the Amazigh (Laaredj-Campbell, 2015). These initiatives on one hand emphasise the importance of education in rural societies, and on the other work to promote a sense of pride in cultural identity among young girls despite the adversity. Education is a means for both Amazigh women personal growth and Amazigh culture continuity.

The empowerment gained through education enables Amazigh women to actively engage in cultural preservation efforts and advocate for their rights. Many Amazigh women who challenged the social norms and are educated express a strong will to serve as role models for younger generations, demonstrating that education can lead to greater agency and the ability to implement changes within their communities. This strong will reflects a broader awareness of how education can transform not just individual lives but also communal identities. Women participating in educational programs gain knowledge and reshape the narrative surrounding women's roles in society (Laaredj-Campbell, 2015).

Central to this discussion is the recognition that Amazigh women exist within a unique socio-cultural context that profoundly influences their daily lives, aspirations, and challenges. Many interviewees shared their experiences of living in rural and nomadic settings, where traditional roles are both expected and enforced. These societal norms often prioritise domestic responsibilities over educational and professional ambitions, significantly limiting opportunities for self-advancement (Maranto et al., 2019). Interviews revealed a common narrative among women who, despite their hard work and dedication to family and community, find their contributions undervalued and unrecognised. The emotional burden of this inequity leads to feelings of frustration, yet it strengthens the will for change and greater recognition.

In this context, education emerges as a motivator and an agent of change for empowerment (Laaredj-Campbell, 2015). The findings indicate that access to education is often at risk by the dominance of societal beliefs that prioritise boys' education as vital for future financial stability. This systemic undervaluation of female education creates a cycle of dependence, wherein women remain trapped in traditional roles and are deprived of the tools necessary to advocate for their rights. However, there is a rising awareness among Amazigh women about the transformative power of education (Laaredj-Campbell, 2015). Many express that pursuing education is not merely a personal goal but a means to challenge societal norms and assert their identities.

This intersection between education, empowerment, and cultural preservation is critical. Women recognise that education fortifies them and carries essential skills to navigate the complexities of modern life, while also enabling them to uphold and transmit their cultural heritage. In this way, education is more than an academic pursuit; it is a pathway to reclaiming agency, building resilience, and ensuring the continuity of Amazigh identity in an evolving societal landscape. The Amazigh community can look forward to a new generation that is knowledgeable and committed to preserving their rich cultural heritage amidst the pressures of modernisation, social norms, and patriarchal systems, if they invest in the education of girls and women.

8.6. Conclusion

In summary, this research has illuminated the complicated and multifaceted experiences of Amazigh women in Algeria, highlighting the profound link between education, cultural heritage, gender roles, and the ongoing quest for empowerment. At the core of this investigation lies the recognition of the unique socio-cultural context that shapes the lives of these women, influencing their aspirations, challenges, and the ways in which they navigate societal expectations. Through

qualitative interviews and a thorough examination of the Algerian culture policies, this study has provided a platform for the voices of Amazigh women, underscoring their resilience and agency in the face of adversity.

Education emerges as a pivotal factor in empowering Amazigh women, enabling them to challenge imposed gender norms and advocate for their rights. While access to education remains a barrier, community-based initiatives and governmental policies are making strides in promoting literacy and raising awareness about the importance of girls' education. Empowered through education, many Amazigh women are not only participating in cultural preservation efforts but also positioning themselves as role models for future generations. This highlights a significant shift in the cultural narrative, as women increasingly recognise education as a vital pathway to greater agency and the continuity of their cultural heritage. Moreover, the cultural significance of gender roles within Amazigh society cannot be dismissed. The traditional expectations placed upon women often confine them to roles as caretakers and homemakers, leading to feelings of frustration and marginalisation. Yet, the interviews revealed a growing consciousness among Amazigh women regarding their rights and potential and presented a myriad of governmental policies and challenges concerning culture recognition. Many expressed a desire to break free from the constraints of societal norms, seeking greater autonomy and recognition for their contributions. This desire highlights a shift in cultural dynamics, as women assert their agency and challenge the status quo.

The findings of this research also underscore the importance of addressing systemic barriers that inhibit the empowerment of Amazigh women. Legal frameworks, while evolving, often fall short in addressing the specific challenges faced by women from diverse ethnic backgrounds. The lack of representation in decision-making processes and the pervasive influence of patriarchal norms continue to impede progress. However, the commitment of Amazigh women to cultural preservation and their advocacy for their rights reflect a determination to overcome these obstacles and foster positive change.

In conclusion, the empowerment of Amazigh women in Algeria is not merely a matter of addressing immediate challenges but also involves recognizing their integral role in cultural preservation and social change. This study advocates for continued efforts to enhance educational opportunities, promote intangible cultural heritage, and involve women in decision-making processes. By amplifying the voices of Amazigh women and supporting their aspirations, a contribution to a more equitable society that values and honours the rich cultural tapestry of the

Amazigh community will emerge. As the journey toward recognition and empowerment continues, it is essential to create collaborative efforts that celebrate the contributions of Amazigh women and ensure that their cultural heritage thrives for generations to come.

Chapter Nine - Conclusion

This chapter summarises the conclusions derived from analysing data related to the preservation and empowerment roles held by Amazigh women in Algeria, focusing on how these insights can influence future cultural policies and initiatives. The findings highlight the crucial role of Amazigh women as cultural guardians and community leaders, especially in rural regions where they have a pivotal part in sustaining Algeria's intangible cultural heritage. This chapter further examines how targeted community and governmental engagement policies and programs can be designed to empower Amazigh women as active collaborators in preserving their heritage, aligning with global practices on community-driven cultural conservation (Smith, 2006; Graham and Howard, 2008).

Drawing from the research, several practical implications are identified for developing cultural programs that place Amazigh women at the forefront of cultural preservation initiatives. Specifically, the chapter advocates for creating and implementing community engagement programs that not only support heritage conservation but also provide socio-economic benefits to the women involved (chapter 9 section 7). In line with studies that recognise the need for community-based strategies in heritage conservation (Smith and Akagawa, 2018), these programs could empower Amazigh women through involvement them in cultural project design, skill-building workshops, and entrepreneurial opportunities that enable them to leverage their unique knowledge and practices as assets within the broader Algerian cultural landscape.

Ultimately, this chapter underscores the importance of creating inclusive, cultural approaches that recognise Amazigh women as essential stakeholders in Algeria's heritage conservation. By embracing strategies that blend empowerment with cultural preservation, Algeria can take initiatives toward ensuring that its rich Amazigh heritage continues to flourish amidst modernisation pressures. These initiatives align with global heritage preservation standards, such as those proposed by UNESCO, which stress the role of community involvement in safeguarding cultural heritage (UNESCO, 2003). In doing so, Algeria not only strengthens its cultural diversity but also empowers a historically marginalised demographic to actively shape and sustain their cultural identity.

9.1. Aim and Objectives of the Thesis

The aim of this study was to explore how Algerian government policies, social and cultural barriers, and the national recognition of the Amazigh identity influence the empowerment of Amazigh women in their roles as guardians and transmitters of intangible cultural heritage. To accomplish this, the study explored in Chapter six, the impact of Algerian government policies on the Amazigh cultural heritage and empowerment of Algerian women, in particular, Amazigh women, within the sphere of heritage preservation. This included analysing the scope, implementation, and limitations of policies supporting Amazigh culture, with a particular focus on their practical outcomes for women's empowerment. By examining case studies across different Amazigh regions, in chapter 3 section 2, this study shows regional disparities in policy concerning Amazigh culture and support for women's heritage preservation efforts.

The study also identified in Chapter five the social, cultural, and structural barriers that hinder Amazigh women's active participation in preserving and transmitting their intangible heritage. It investigated the role of social norms and expectations, gender roles, and community structures that limit these women's agency in the realm of cultural preservation. Additionally, it explored in chapter five to seven, structural challenges, such as economic disparities and resource allocation, which further restrict Amazigh women's participation in cultural preservation across both rural and urban settings.

Furthermore, the thesis has highlighted how Amazigh women use cultural intangible heritage to assert their roles as guardians of cultural heritage within Algeria's national identity framework. This includes documenting various forms of cultural activism, such as participation in cultural festivals, traditional crafts, and grassroots movements that are aimed at preserving cultural heritage. It also assesses the effectiveness of these efforts in challenging cultural erosion and promoting the recognition of Amazigh identity within Algeria's broader national framework.

9.2. Answering the Research Questions

This section briefly addresses the core research questions that directed this study, by synthesising the findings presented in chapter five, six, and seven. By systematically exploring each question and connecting it to the study's theoretical framework with the empirical data.

How do Algeria's national policies on cultural heritage and identity impact Amazigh women's efforts to preserve intangible cultural heritage?

Algeria's approach to a unified national identity, prioritising Arab-Islamic traditions over minority cultures like the Amazigh, aligns with studies examining how centralised governance affects ethnic diversity and cultures, i.e., this thesis analysis of Algerian policy aligns with studies examining centralised governance. In research by Eriksen (2010) and Barth (1998) it is notable that national policies emphasizing a dominant culture such as the Arabic culture in Algeria often lead to marginalisation of minority identities. Algeria's policies reflect Hofstede's Power Distance Dimension, as explained in chapter 2 section 6, as high power-distance societies (Arab) tend to support centralised governance, where dominant cultural narratives in a way suppress regional ethnic identities. This can be seen in Algeria's Arabisation policies, which, despite recent progress such as in acknowledging the Amazigh language, often restricted formal recognition of the Amazigh culture within national institutions like schools and media.

Through adapting theories of Cultural Assimilation and Erosion, as explain in chapter 7 section 7.2.1, 7.2.2 and 7.7.1, it is highlighted that the effects of such policies on minority cultures challenge their preservation and their continuity for example, during the French colonialisation, the French policies attempted to assimilate the Amazigh culture. During colonial era the French adopted another ideology to "modify" the Amazigh culture and reshape it in a way that serves their interests, the ethnocentric ideology that threatened the heritage of the Amazigh, through promoting that the French culture is superior and it has some similarities with theirs or as called "Berber myth". Later, Arabisation policies in the post-colonial era in Algeria, work to dilute this myth and challenge it through prioritizing the Arabic culture. Amazigh face significant adversities in maintaining their culture in Algeria yet their culture is still living and evolving because of the resilience they showed particularly Amazigh women's resilience.

While Berry (1997) and Assmann (2010) believe that cultural erosion is a gradual process where dominant culture overshadows and attempts to replace traditional practices of minority groups. In the Algerian context, Arabisation policies have marginalised Amazigh traditions, language, and cultural practices. These policies despite being a mean to recover a national identity and unify the country, served also as an imposed initiatives to diminish the Amazigh culture, these policies created a sentiment of resent for a long time in the country and have led to serious outcomes. While these policies aimed to integrate all citizens into a single Arab-Islamic identity,

they risk erasing Amazigh heritage by diminishing the use of Tamazight in public settings and minimizing ethnic representation in national narratives. The dominance of Arabic culture in the country led to intensifying the traditional rule among the Amazigh groups as they build their own society norms which fostered a cultural paradox for Amazigh women.

For Amazigh women, this cultural erosion presented a difficult challenge. In studies by Nagata (1974) and Titon (2009) on heritage preservation in minority cultures, they illustrated how women emerge as key agents in protecting intangible heritage through grassroots initiatives and how do they sustain it. Equally, this thesis findings show that as central Algerian policy often fails to fully represent Amazigh culture, Amazigh women adopt preservationist roles, sharing traditions within families and communities. They achieve this through oral storytelling, crafts, language teaching, and local festivals, embodying what Bhabha (1994) refers to as “hybridity” in cultural resistance, this cultural theory emphasis on adaptation to the environment surrounding the local culture. By preserving customs in informal, often private, spaces, the women in this study ensure cultural continuity, counteracting the assimilative pressures of centralised governance.

This foundational activism echoes Anderson’s (1983) theory of “imagined communities,” as Amazigh women create a collective identity, as mentioned in chapter 2 section 2.6.1 as shown in section 6.2.2, that strengthens their community’s resilience against cultural erosion.

Sadiqi (2011) and Ennaji (2005) similarly declared that women’s roles in cultural sustainability and preservation is significantly important within North African societies. Despite the restrictive policies, Amazigh women use their daily domestic and communal roles to preserve cultural identity and pass it to the next generation, exhibiting their resilience in a high power-distance context that often limits their formal representation.

In summary, Algeria’s approach to national identity has implications for the preservation of minority cultures, as the Amazigh, placing indirect pressure on Amazigh communities, especially, women, to creatively sustain and protect their heritage. Through communal cultural activism and informal transmission, Amazigh women ensure that their heritage endure while balancing the effects of a dominant national narrative that often overlooks their identity.

In what ways do traditional gender roles and social norms shape Amazigh women's empowerment and resilience in heritage preservation?

Traditional roles in Amazigh communities dictate women's responsibility in the process of heritage preservation, a dynamic shown in this thesis (see chapter five) that aligns with studies on gendered heritage transmission within indigenous societies. Research by Clark (2003), Whittington (2021) and Wei et al. (2024) on traditional societies present that women's roles as heritage guardians emerge from environments where established gender norms position men in external roles such as economic roles and women within the domestic sphere. In many indigenous traditional communities, as the Amazigh groups, this gendered division aligns with Hofstede's Masculinity vs Femininity Dimension, as shown in chapter 2 section 6.4, where "feminine" values convey in aspects such as family welfare, cultural transmission, and nurturing are their responsibility. This cultural organisation within societies positions women as homemakers, yet it empowers them as guardians of collective memory, tradition, and social continuity.

The Paradox of Cultural Erosion and Resilience described by Bui et al. (2020) and Tapsell and Woods (2008) highlight how traditional practices adapt in response to external pressures and influence while sustaining their traditions and acting a source of resilience and identity preservation, also noted by Palmater (2011) research on indigenous identity preservation. The findings in this study shows how, similar to other indigenous groups facing modernisation, Amazigh women have challenged cultural erosion by revitalizing their roles. For example, as shows in chapter 6 section 8, in practices central to Amazigh heritage such as practicing marriage rituals and storytelling, women incorporate economic perks by promoting shows and festivals for local markets or tourism, which leads to blending tradition with modern relevance. This process alters heritage into an adaptable, empowering element that serves in both providing economic support in the community and to the nation, and that reinforces cultural continuity.

In line with Sahlins' (1999) and Bhabha's (1994) concepts of cultural hybridity and resilience, Amazigh women navigate their roles in ways that allow both tradition and adaptation to coexist. They work to engage younger generations through modern forms of practice, adjusting aesthetic styles or storytelling formats to resonate with modern tastes. This form of transmission involves adaptation, adding to what Di Pietro, Guglielmetti Mugion, and Renzi (2018) describe. They viewed that cultural knowledge is not static but living, evolving asset which women actively pass for future generations.

Finally, Amazigh women's dual responsibility as homemakers and heritage keepers delivers a nuanced framework of empowerment through cultural continuity. The previous studies on indigenous and rural societies suggested that where tradition intersects with economic and social adaptation, it allows and supports cultural resilience amid modernisation pressures. This study shows how Amazigh women uphold their community's identity by transforming their traditional roles into empowering and economically viable functions, ensuring the survival and relevance of Amazigh heritage.

How do Amazigh women navigate the tension between cultural preservation and modernisation within their communities?

The impact of modernisation on cultural continuity has been a topic of significant value, particularly regarding how traditional societies manage the preservation of intangible heritage amid rapidly social changes. Studies on indigenous cultural resilience, such as those by Fleming and Ledogar (2008) and Kirmayer et al. (2011) reveal that modernisation frequently brings both risks and opportunities for communities like the Amazigh, where cultural identity and heritage are closely link to daily practices and social structures. As this study has shown, Amazigh women embody the duality of this link and balance the cultural preservation with adaptability. This is a dynamic that Shils (1981) and Bhabha (1994) have described as a hybrid cultural existence, where traditional societies navigate a space of negotiation and adaptation rather than assimilation.

Applying Hofstede's Uncertainty Avoidance Dimension to these dynamics show that high uncertainty avoidance societies tend to prioritise and aim to stability and continuity, often resulting in a collective effort to maintain cultural practices. The Amazigh women, with their high preference for cultural preservation, use innovative approaches to safeguard traditions while making them accessible to young audiences in a modern setting, as shown in chapter 6 section 6.8. Triandis (1999) and Vandello and Cohen (1999) on their study on individualism and collectivism noted similar adaptive measures among collectivist societies such as this study found for the Amazigh participants, where the blend of heritage practices with new influences creates a form of "cultural recontextualisation." This concept is notable among Amazigh women, for example, they adapt the traditional attire, stories, music and crafts with contemporary aesthetics. Amazigh symbols and designs for jewellery, for instance were a tradition and tribal, in recent time more women refer to them as vintage and aesthetics new style (see chapter 6 section 6.4). The

process of making these symbols and practices of identity attractive to younger generations helped preserve and protect intangible heritage in a rapidly evolving social landscape.

In this process, Cultural Assimilation Theory provides insights into the challenges minority groups face while interacting with a dominant culture. According to Berry (2001) and Padilla and Perez (2003), assimilation often leads to the erosion of cultural creativity and uniqueness, as individuals adopt the practices of the larger society or global settings (see chapter 7 section 7 and 8) Yet, studies on cultural resilience among indigenous groups, such as those by Merlan (2009) study on Indigeneity Global and Local, suggests that community-centred strategies can achieve balance in this issue. This study shows similar strategies used by Amazigh women under the modernity pressures, ensuring that traditions evolve in a way that is meaningful within their own cultural framework by emphasizing family and community as the spotlight of heritage transmission. This approach aligns with McIntyre (2003) and Krieg's (2016) findings of cultural continuity and reclaiming identity among indigenous women, which emphasised the role of the communal engagement in resilience, particularly where heritage faces the threat of cultural erosion.

In studies on modernisation in indigenous societies, Appadurai (1996) and Venn and Featherstone (2006) emphasised that modernisation can sometimes serve as a "cultural trigger," enabling ethnic societies to selectively integrate aspects of global culture to strengthen, rather than erase, their identity. This study shows how Amazigh women's engagement with modern tools like social media to promote their language and customs, as shown in chapter 6 section 5.2, chapter 7 section 8 and chapter 8 section 3.1, proves Throsby's (2001) notion of "cultural capital," where communities adapt external resources to sustain and elevate their cultural assets in different domains. Amazigh women transformed the heritage preservation process into an interactive dynamic process that resonates with younger generations, counteracting the homogenizing pressures of globalisation.

In conclusion, this study highlight how Amazigh women adopt the approach of modernisation as a resource for sustaining their cultural heritage rather than a force of erosion. This model of resilience that allows heritage to evolve through a combination of cultural continuity and selective adaptation, encourages Amazigh identity to thrive. It focuses also on how women in collectivist societies can navigate cultural paradoxes, ensuring that heritage remains relevant and accessible to future generations.

What strategies do Amazigh women employ to sustain and transmit intangible cultural heritage amidst socio-economic challenges and shifting national identities?

Amazigh women's efforts to reach a balanced economic need alongside preserving cultural heritage align with broader findings in studies on heritage preservation in economically less advantaged communities. Previous research on the transmission of intangible cultural heritage, especially within collectivist societies, points out how cultural practices are adapted to modern economic landscapes, a concept explored by scholars such as Smith and Akagawa (2009), who noted that intangible cultural heritage remains resilient when it is integrated into the community's economic structure, rather than being isolated from it. Their findings resonate with findings in this study (e.g., see chapter 6 sections 5,6, and 7) that show how Amazigh women incorporate heritage into their economic activities, preserving cultural identity through cultural intangible heritage attributes, while simultaneously creating income opportunities.

Studies on Cultural Erosion Theory on the other hand suggest that economic adversities, blend with the nuances of modernity, lead to the gradual erosion of traditional practices in indigenous communities, as documented by Graham and Howard (2008). These scholars believed that economic pressures and urban migration can draw younger generations away from traditional practices. This resonates with the challenges facing Amazigh women, where younger generations are increasingly influenced by the global cultures. However, in line with the findings of Spence et al. (2016) on cultural resilience, findings in this study show, for example in chapter 6 section 5, that Amazigh women adopt strategies that blend economic and cultural goals to ensure continuity and adaptability such as voluntary social gathering to teach and learn the traditional practices and promoting for rituals and events in social media. The strategies Amazigh women adopt facing cultural erosion varies according to the Amazigh groups, for example in Ghardaia, Mzab women culturally engage in events in households with other women only (see chapter 6 section 5.2, and 5.3), whereas Tuareg women have more freedom to impact on their societies in and out of the household (see chapter 3 section 2 and 3), all these initiatives by Amazigh women have the same aim of fighting cultural erosion.

Hofstede's Collectivism vs. Individualism Dimension similarly provides a framework observed in cross-cultural studies on heritage transmission within collectivist communities, such as Hsu et al. (2017), who found that collectivist communities tend to prioritise cultural preservation through

family and communal engagement. In the case of Amazigh women, this collectivist procedure of protecting and promoting heritage is seen in their strategies to pass on cultural knowledge by embedding these practices within the family unit (e.g., see chapter 6 section 5. Section 6.5.2 and 6.7). These findings align with findings from De Vita, Ragozino, and Simeone (2015), who underscore the importance of cultural transmission through daily family activities and communal responsibility, which is the case for Amazigh communities where women are main actors in the process. Together, these studies and theories fortifies the way Amazigh approach parallels with global findings that demonstrate resilience through cultural and economic adaptation.

Amazigh women's focus on family-based transmission and the integration of cultural practices into local settings which echo with wider academic insights into how economically constrained communities strategically preserve their cultural identities. These bodies of research provide a valuable context for understanding the role of intangible heritage preservation as a dynamic and adaptable process, one that is essential for the cultural continuity of indigenous and minority communities.

How do the experiences, and practices of Amazigh women in Algeria contribute to intangible culture preservation despite the adversities they face?

The experiences, and practices of Amazigh women in Algeria are essential in preserving intangible cultural heritage, particularly as they face and resist several adversities, such as traditional norms, social expectation, gender roles which align with Hofstede's Masculinity vs. Femininity Dimension, as seen at different points in the findings chapter 9 and chapter 2 such as section 2.6.4. Through cultural actions, Amazigh women contribute actively to the continuity of their cultural traditions, language, and social norms, adopting resilience in the face of historical and contemporary challenges, such as marginalisation, linguistic suppression, and socioeconomic barriers (Ahearn, 2014).

This study's findings show how Amazigh women contribute to intangible cultural preservation through a myriad of cultural practices embedded in community solidarity (Goodman, 2005). For example, they participate in traditional collective events such as Twiza or traditional weddings (discussed in chapter six section 6.4.1 and section 6.7), which emphasises communal efforts, support, and collaboration. Through engaging in teaching these practices, they transmit meaning and value of empathy, generosity, and social cohesion to younger generations, ensuring that these

intangible aspects of Amazigh culture remain existent within the community (Brett and Fentress, 1997). Through the concept of cultural capital, in Bourdieu's theory (1977), these practices represent a form of social capital that combine community members and their efforts strengthening cultural resilience.

The concept of cultural relativism allows Amazigh women's crafts knowledge, orality, and traditions to be seen as complex expressions of their cultural identity rather than as "primitive" practices. These cultural attributes serve as vessels of cultural memory, enabling women to preserve and adapt cultural symbols, styles, and narratives in a way that would protect their legacy.

Despite the historical and cultural barriers imposed by linguistic and social marginalisation, this study shows how Amazigh women's efforts have helped reframe cultural preservation as a dynamic, living process rather than a static tradition. Their actions align with the theory of cultural hybridisation in the way that traditional cultural practices blend with modern influences without losing their value. For example, initiatives that integrate modernity to traditional practices, like weaving machines and products used in drying animal leather, demonstrate how Amazigh women adapt modernity to their needs, creating a bridge between heritage and modernity (Ahearn, 2014). The theoretical frameworks of cultural relativism, cultural capital, and cultural hybridisation highlight the depth of Amazigh women contributions, illustrating that preserving heritage is both a personal and collective responsibility significant in sustaining Amazigh identity.

9.3 Contributions of Policy

This study's contribution is to provide meaningful insights centred on the role of Amazigh women in Algeria for policy, including in the areas of heritage preservation, community empowerment, and education. The thesis also provides insights for future research. The study highlights how Amazigh women balance heritage preservation with the modern demands of their communities and offers practical contributions and implications for Algeria's cultural contexts.

9.3.1. Implications for heritage preservation policy

The findings present how vital it is for Algerian policy frameworks to prioritise community-based approaches to heritage conservation. Including Amazigh women and local communities directly in decision-making processes, can promote a more inclusive and diverse cultural identity. As recommended by UNESCO's safeguarding principles, cultural policies that integrate traditional practices within modern economic frameworks, such as sustainable tourism or craft markets,

create economic opportunities while protecting cultural heritage (UNESCO, 2003). In Algeria, this means regionally tailored policies that empower women and other local community to preserve Amazigh traditions in ways that are socially and economically sustainable (Ahearn, 2001; Bhabha, 1994).

9.3.2. Implications for gender and community empowerment

The study highlights that, Amazigh women through their roles as cultural guardians, are powerful drivers of both cultural continuity and economic stability in their communities. Programs that support women in traditional skills, like crafting knowledge and skill, or orality such as storytelling, contribute not only to heritage preservation but also to financial independence and social recognition; this aligns with broader gender equality goals (Sadiqi, 2003; Maddy-Weitzman, 2011). Practically, this might involve creating cooperatives or organizing regional festivals where Amazigh heritage can be shared and protected. These programs give women new economic power while preserving the heritage that is essential to their cultural identity (Ennaji, 2014).

9.3.3. Implications for education and cultural transmission

The research seeks reforms on the educational level to embrace Algeria's diverse cultural identity, advocating for the integration of Amazigh language, history, and customs within the national curriculum. Including these elements in school programs would help younger generations appreciate Algeria's rich cultural diversity, contributing to a stronger sense of collective identity and continuity (Hoffman, 2008; Ennaji and Sadiqi, 2011). Collaboration with local communities to develop educational resources that reflect and promote the Amazigh heritage, such as storytelling, crafts, and oral traditions could make cultural education more engaging and meaningful for students.

9.3.4. Implications for future research and theory development

This study advocates for improved theories of cultural preservation, particularly by presenting how communities facing modernisation pressures can adapt rather than assimilate. For instance, while Cultural Assimilation Theory suggests that minority groups often submit to dominant cultures, Amazigh women challenge this by emphasizing heritage through community led transmission practices (Barth, 1969; Maddy-Weitzman, 2011). The findings also support Hofstede's

Power Distance and Uncertainty Avoidance dimensions by illustrating how centralised governance and cultural resistance shape Algeria's cultural dynamics (Hofstede, 1980; Schwartz, 1999). Future research could further explore these themes in other ethnic minority communities, examining how adaptation rather than assimilation serves as a preservation strategy in diverse global contexts.

In conclusion, the study suggests that through community centred policy and practical engagement, Amazigh women can continue to serve as empowered guardians of cultural heritage. Their technics in blending economic sustainability with cultural authenticity provide an example of resilient approach to heritage preservation, offering insights for Algeria and similar ethnic communities in their efforts to maintain cultural diversity amidst modernisation.

In alignment with UNESCO's 2003 Convention for the Safeguarding of Intangible Cultural Heritage, which emphasises community participation and the recognition of local knowledge, this study highlights the urgent need for Algeria to embed such global principles into its national cultural policy. The research demonstrates that Amazigh women are central to the preservation of ICH, yet they remain underrepresented in formal heritage governance. To bridge this gap, the state should implement policies that institutionalise women's participation through local cultural councils, integrate Amazigh oral traditions and crafts into school curricula, and fund regional economic initiatives such as cooperatives and festivals, that are rooted in women's heritage practices. These measures would operationalise UNESCO's recommendations within the Algerian context, creating a heritage policy model that is both inclusive and culturally sustainable.

9.4. Research's Original Contribution to Existing Literature

This study's contribution is to provide meaningful insights centred on the role of Amazigh women in Algeria for policy, including in the areas of heritage preservation, community empowerment, and education. The thesis also provides insights for future research. The study highlights how Amazigh women balance heritage preservation with the modern demands of their communities and offers practical contributions and implications for Algeria's cultural contexts.

The significant themes of this thesis are addressed in the two main findings chapters: chapter six titled *The Paradox of Amazigh Intangible Heritage: Women's Role in Preserving and Transforming Cultural Identity*; chapter seven titled *Navigating Cultural Heritage and National Identity: The Role of Amazigh Women and Regional Leaders in Algeria's Decentralisation and Cultural Policy*. Within these chapter, the key ideas for this study are developed with the findings

contributing to a broader academic discourse on various concepts and theoretical frameworks. These discourses focused on culture and heritage, Amazigh women empowerment, and national policies studies underpinned by seminal works of authors such as Geertz, Goffman, Smith, Golding, Hall, Sadiqi, Ennaji, and Maddy-Weitzman. This thesis adds to several key discourses within heritage, gender, and ethnic studies through situating its contribution within discussions on UNESCO's intangible heritage, gender theories, and empowerment policies.

The literature in heritage studies navigates the significance of empowerment as a resource associated with cultural heritage preservation, and its strong link to the politics of recognition. While certain cultural groups are acknowledged for their achievements and contributions to society, other marginalised groups face neglect and adversities that threaten their culture. Women in marginalised groups are voiceless and overseen in terms of policies and acknowledgement, which leads to their suppression and imposing traditional norms that limits their opportunities and autonomy.

This research contributes a detailed amount of data related to intangible cultural heritage in Amazigh regions in Algeria, through interviewing Amazigh women and sharing their experiences and stories. Furthermore, it focusses on providing research findings that are unique and offers original contributions to existing academic knowledge related to marginalised women in North Africa and their empowerment journey through practicing cultural heritage as a tool to express themselves and to preserve them.

This study also contributes to the understanding of intangible cultural heritage preservation by examining the essential role of Amazigh women in Algeria. In a nation with a complex history of centralisation, colonisation, and cultural marginalisation, the study offers insights into how Algerian Amazigh women navigate these challenges to preserve their cultural identity while simultaneously advocating for social and economic empowerment. It also shows Amazigh women's core processes of sustaining and adapting heritage, revealing their ability to create resilience-based strategies that blend tradition with the pressures of modernity. As a result of this, the study contributes to a broader discourse on heritage preservation, gendered agency, and indigenous resilience.

The study reveals that cultural preservation among Algerian Amazigh women extends beyond mere conservation. In fact, it is an active process that incorporates socio-economic adaptation, community empowerment, and generational knowledge transfer (De Vita, Ragozino, and Simeone, 2015).

Finally, this thesis highlights the empowering role of heritage for women within indigenous communities. Drawing on feminist perspectives and theories of cultural resilience (Gunnestad, 2006), the research shows how Amazigh women's involvement in heritage preservation contributes to broader feminist movements in North Africa. In ethnic communities, such as the Amazigh in Algeria social life is dominated by male authority. The study sheds light on the unique ways that Amazigh women overcome the patriarchal system and protect cultural memory and heritage. This study navigates the tension between national governance and local autonomy to keep their heritage alive. Moreover, it underscores the lack of academic work concerning Amazigh in Algeria compared to Morocco, Tunisia, or Libya, and as such fills an important gap in knowledge.

In its entirety, this study expands existing scholarship of intangible heritage preservation, and indigenous women empowerment by presenting a nuanced model of heritage as a lived, adaptive process. It emphasises the role of local Amazigh women in cultural preservation, a perspective often underrepresented in both heritage studies and feminist scholarship in Algeria. This contribution is significant and important that adds understanding of how ethnic women participate culturally, socially and in some cases economically in sustaining their identities amidst modern pressures, traditional norms, and patriarchy, and it offers practical implications for cultural policy in Algeria. In doing so, the study advocates for a participatory approach to heritage that respects the agency of those Amazigh women in their community, aligning with global frameworks like UNESCO's emphasis on living intangible heritage and cultural sustainability (UNESCO, 2003).

9.5. Personal Reflection on the Research

Reflecting on this study, the role of Amazigh women in Algeria emerges as both inspiring and complex. They are, in many ways, key actors in a rich cultural heritage landscape, living at the intersection of tradition and modernity, facing adversities and challenges that limits their opportunities. This research highlights the complex yet unique blend of resilience and innovation, through navigating the pressures of modernisation while preserving their identity. A balance that is as challenging as it is empowering as Maddy-Weitzman (2011) stressed.

The study also reflects on how community and family hold central roles in heritage preservation. Hofstede's Collectivism Dimension is particularly evident in how Amazigh women involve family members, especially younger generations, in cultural practices. Furthermore, the dimension of femininity and masculinity is distinctive in this study, while Amazigh women are held

responsible for the protection and transmission of the intangible cultural heritage, men are controlling the narrative and limiting them to the traditional role in their societies.

Women on the other hand, creating and carry a shared, family centred experience around intangible heritage attributes such as storytelling, weaving, and other traditions, they foster a sense of pride and continuity that counterbalances the individualism often promoted in modern Algerian society (Hofstede, 1980). This intergenerational collaboration created by women is not just about cultural transmission but about building identity and resilience, a practice that echoes UNESCO's emphasis on the importance of family and community in safeguarding intangible cultural heritage (UNESCO, 2003).

One of the most impactful key points from this study is the resilience of Amazigh women in the face of a central government that often emphasises a unified national identity, sometimes at the cost of both female and minority representation. In navigating these constraints, these women embody Hofstede's Power Distance Dimension, highlighting how individuals within high power-distance societies negotiate autonomy within restrictive systems (Hofstede, 1980). Amazigh women's determination to pass on their language, customs, and beliefs even when national policies may not fully recognise them is a testament to their strength and agency. Through oral transmission, community events, and crafts, they craft a narrative of pride and endurance, ensuring that their heritage remains visible, valued, and vibrant.

On the final reflection on this study, it becomes clear that the preservation of Amazigh culture depends not only on policy shifts or academic recognition but on the quiet, consistent efforts of the women within these communities. Their role is an inspiring reminder that true cultural preservation is as much about adaptation as it is about tradition, as much about resilience as it is about legacy. This study contributes a vital perspective to the field of cultural preservation, affirming that heritage is not just an artifact of the past but a living, breathing testament to community strength and identity in the face of change.

9.6. Limitation of the Study

This section provides a detailed overview of the various methodological and contextual limitations encountered in conducting this study on the Amazigh communities in Algeria. Research involving culturally distinct and remote populations often faces unique challenges, and this study was no exception. The limitations addressed in this section cover aspects of sample size, logistical

and cultural accessibility, and academic resources. Additionally, the COVID-19 pandemic introduced unexpected obstacles to data collection, impacting participants' availability and willingness to engage. Furthermore, as an external Arab researcher, navigating cultural sensitivities and linguistic nuances was paramount in interacting with the Amazigh communities, especially given traditional gender norms and a history of marginalisation. To overcome these constraints, various strategic approaches were employed to promote participant engagement and thus gather meaningful data, while ensuring methodological rigor. This reflection on limitations not only highlights the difficulties of fieldwork within unique cultural contexts but also points out to the importance of adaptive methodologies in qualitative research.

The limited sample size in the closed-ended interviews posed challenges for coding and thematic analysis, as the volume of responses required considerable time and effort to process into meaningful insights. Participants often expressed hesitation in engaging fully with the study due to the personal and sensitive nature of the topics discussed, likely influenced by traditional norms in their communities. Interviews conducted in participants' households were sometimes shaped by the presence of family members, potentially limiting the depth and openness of responses. Geographic and cultural barriers further compounded these issues, particularly in rural and remote southern regions where extended travel times exceeding 10 hours by road were often required. Access to culturally traditional villages frequently necessitated introductions from residents, adding layers of complexity to the process. The COVID-19 pandemic exacerbated these logistical challenges, introducing health concerns and restrictions that led to frequent rescheduling of interviews, disrupting timelines, and requiring continuous adaptations to ensure participant availability.

To address these challenges, the researcher prioritised adaptability and rapport-building, creating a comfortable environment for participants to share their experiences openly. This included flexibility in scheduling, adjusting locations, and tailoring timings to meet participants' needs. Observational techniques and note-taking complemented the interviews, allowing for a richer and more nuanced understanding of the cultural and social phenomena under study. Triangulation, as highlighted by Flick (2002) and Denzin and Lincoln (2018), served as a nuanced approach to refine perspectives, while Creswell's (2009) emphasis on qualitative validity underscored the importance of thorough accuracy checks to ensure reliability. Stake's (1995) perspective further reinforced the importance of clarifying extraneous influences to maintain the integrity of findings.

Despite these limitations, the study's adaptive strategies enabled the collection of meaningful insights into the resilience and cultural practices of the Amazigh women. Through combining flexible approaches, observational methods, and triangulated data collection, the research successfully navigated the inherent complexities of qualitative inquiry, offering valuable contributions to understanding culturally nuanced contexts. These strategies underscore the importance of resilience and innovation in overcoming research challenges, particularly in studies addressing ethnic communities and sensitive socio-cultural dynamics.

Academic limitations

Another significant limitation of this research was the accessibility of academic literature specific to the Amazigh in Algeria, especially gender aspects, and particularly in English. Much of the relevant studies available were primarily in French or Arabic, necessitating an extensive process of translation, which proved both time-consuming and demanding in terms of accuracy. Translating these works required careful attention to linguistic nuances, as critical terminology and cultural concepts do not always have direct equivalents in English. As a result, the relativeness of studies focusing specifically on the Algerian Amazigh context led the researcher to seek related research from other North African countries, such as Morocco and Libya. While this literature provided valuable insights, its applicability to Algeria was sometimes limited by contextual differences, emphasizing the need for future studies directly addressing Algeria's unique cultural and socio-political landscape.

Cultural sensitivity

The nature of cultural dynamics of the Amazigh communities, particularly in regions like Ghardaia, Mزاب group, presented notable challenges during data collection. Accessing and interviewing women in these areas posed some difficulties due to traditional norms governing gender roles and external interactions. Initially, the data gathered was shaped by participants' adherence to social expectations, resulting in responses that were often cautious or aligned with the norms and values upheld by their families and communities. Additionally, some participants expressed intimidation about being recorded, which further impacted the depth and openness of the data collected.

Stating the positionality in the investigation, aims at acknowledging the situating perspectives, values, and beliefs in relation to the research process. In the context of this study, stating positionality allows me to identify, construct and critique my role in this research (Manohar et al., 2017), as an Arabic outsider female to the Amazigh culture, I observed that participants were initially hesitant and reserved in their responses, likely due to my position as both an outsider and an Arab woman. This initial hesitancy affected how freely interviewees expressed themselves, with many choosing to respond in a manner that felt modest and restrained. On several occasions, language presented an additional layer of complexity; some participants spoke primarily in Tamazight, necessitating translation into Arabic. Which was addressed by seeking translations from the participants families, and my own Amazigh colleagues (who spoke Arabic).

For these reasons the research adopted technics to overcome this challenge, as Nagasawa et al. (2023) underscored the role of nonverbal cues in influencing social interactions, suggesting that nonverbal behaviours such as nodding, maintaining neutral facial expressions, smiling, and demonstrating understanding are instrumental in encouraging participants' openness. Additionally, Lindlof and Taylor (2002) emphasise the importance of customizing interview approaches to align with individual differences in personality and mindset. Tailoring the approach based on the unique characteristics of each participant helps to build rapport and foster an environment that encourages sincere responses, thereby enhancing the quality of the collected data. Building rapport with the participants is crucial in the interviews. Through rapport-building, researchers create a positive relationship with participants (Abbe and Brandon, 2013; Gabbert et al., 2020), consequently, obtaining more information, and in some cases suggesting other participants as a gesture of help.

Funding limitations

Due to the scholarship period ending, a significant portion of travel expenses and logistical costs were ultimately self-funded by the researcher. This personal financial undertaking sometimes necessitated adjustments to the data collection timeline, as resources had to be allocated thoughtfully to accommodate multiple field visits and extended stays where necessary. Consequently, scheduling delays occasionally arose, particularly when interviews or site visits required travel to remote areas, which further stretched available funds. This financial limitation highlighted the challenge of sustaining in-depth field research over time and influenced the pacing

and scope of data collection. However, taking account of this, the researcher planned and prioritised each phase within the constraints of self-funding in order to make sure all the relevant data was collected in a robust and systematic manner.

Generalizability

This investigation is conducted within the unique socio-political and cultural context of Algeria, particularly its policies on national identity, and minority recognition. As a result, the findings may not be entirely generalizable to Amazigh populations in different settings in the country or other North African countries, such as Morocco, Tunisia, or Libya, where political and cultural dynamics differ. Despite the fact that the study's findings may resonate across borders, future comparative studies across the Maghreb could provide broader insights into how different national policies impact Amazigh cultural preservation. However, as shown in section 9.3 and 9.4, this study fills a gap in knowledge by producing understanding on ICH and gender dynamics within policies, it promotes cultural heritage material / non-material and acknowledges minority groups efforts in protecting and reproducing it across time and generations.

9.7. Recommendations

Considering the significant role that cultural heritage has in preserving national identity, this section offers targeted recommendations aimed at strengthening the preservation and transmission of Algeria's intangible cultural heritage (ICH), particularly within Amazigh communities by women. These recommendations address critical areas, including improved access to resources and data, increased research funding, recognition of women's central role in heritage preservation, educational initiatives, and the empowerment of local communities through decentralisation. Implementing these strategies can help ensure that Algeria's rich cultural heritage is both protected and dynamically engaged with by future generations. Through embracing a collaborative, inclusive approach, these recommendations underscore the importance of acknowledging local perspectives and facilitating regional autonomy, creating a framework for sustainable heritage preservation that respects the unique characteristics of each Amazigh community.

Facilitate Access to national resources and data on ethnic groups

To support research on Algeria's ethnic groups, it is essential to enhance accessibility to comprehensive national records, policies, and statistical data that include demographic, cultural, and socio-economic information. This could involve digitising national archives and policy documents and making them available through academic platforms and public records offices as (ministry of culture and arts, 1998). Through providing researchers access to reliable and up to date data on ethnic groups, particularly those from remote or traditionally underrepresented areas, this can ensure a richer, data-informed understanding of the unique characteristics and challenges these communities face. To implement these suggestions, national and regional government bodies, in collaboration with research institutions, could develop centralised digital databases that facilitate public access to relevant information (Arzberger et al., 2024). Establishing open access policies for declassified government data, along with guidelines for ethical use, would further empower researchers to approach these communities with informed perspectives.

Allocate targeted funding to support research in intangible cultural heritage

To encourage academic investigations into Algeria's intangible cultural heritage, it is recommended that dedicated research funding be allocated specifically for this purpose. Such funding could be used to support fieldwork, data collection, and the development of local partnerships, particularly in regions where the preservation of cultural heritage is at risk due to socio-economic pressures or modernisation. Providing financial incentives can motivate scholars to conduct in-depth studies on intangible heritage areas, such as oral traditions, local arts, language preservation, and community rituals, that might otherwise go unexplored (Omer, 2021). To integrate these suggestions, academic institutions and governmental research agencies could establish grant programs focusing on Algerian intangible cultural heritage, with eligibility criteria encouraging cross-disciplinary and community-engaged projects. Additionally, prioritizing funding for research led by or involving local scholars would further support culturally relevant insights and help build research capacity within Algerian communities themselves (Dickeson, 2021). This approach fosters a collaborative environment that values local perspectives and enhances the global knowledge base on Algeria's rich cultural tapestry.

Acknowledge and strengthen the role of women as guardians of intangible cultural heritage (ICH)

Women have a critical role as the primary guardians of intangible cultural heritage (ICH) in Amazigh regions, ensuring the continuity of cultural practices, traditions, and knowledge across generations. Recognizing and formally acknowledging this contribution is essential to preserving ICH over time. Policies focused on ICH preservation should explicitly incorporate women's perspectives, expertise, and cultural contributions into decision-making processes (Whittington, 2021). This could include ensuring that women are equally represented in local councils and cultural committees alongside men. Acknowledging women as key contributors in the preservation process not only strengthens cultural identity but also promotes gender equity within the community context. To implement these measures governmental bodies and cultural organisations could establish gender-equal mandates for local authorities, particularly those involved in heritage preservation (Björkdahl and Somun-Krupalija, 2020). This would help facilitate balanced representation and include women in strategic decisions affecting cultural preservation, community planning, and heritage transmission initiatives.

Create opportunities for women to promote intangible cultural heritage through education and community engagement

To empower women in preserving and promoting ICH, it is crucial to create opportunities for them to actively share cultural knowledge and practices (Bhattacharya, 2014). Initiatives could include professional roles in teaching cultural practices, such as traditional crafts, languages, and music, and organizing women-only cultural events in regions where traditional norms may otherwise limit women's public engagement. These efforts not only preserve intangible heritage but also enable women to pass on their knowledge and inspire younger generations to engage with and uphold their heritage. Educational institutions and cultural centres could collaborate to offer training and employment opportunities for women as instructors or community educators in the arts, crafts, language, and oral traditions specific to the Amazigh culture (Toole and Louis, 2014). Hosting women-only workshops, festivals, and community gatherings would provide a safe space for women to freely express and transmit cultural practices, especially in communities where mixed-gender events may pose challenges.

Prioritise and support girls' education in rural areas as a foundation for cultural continuity

Empowering young girls through education is fundamental for creating long-term engagement in cultural heritage preservation. Prioritizing education for girls in rural and remote Amazigh regions would help them develop the skills, confidence, and opportunities to sustain and advocate for ICH (Laghssais and Comins- Mingol, 2023). By addressing barriers to education such as lack of transportation, catering, and access to appropriate learning environments. Policymakers can create supportive conditions for girls to embrace and promote their heritage. Furthermore, Local Government can provide resources such as transportation, meal programs, and culturally inclusive safe learning environments to encourage school attendance among young girls. Scholarships and community support initiatives can further motivate girls to pursue education and, in turn, build a solid foundation for their active participation in the preservation of intangible cultural heritage.

Promote decentralisation to empower local autonomy and strengthen cultural identity

Decentralising governance to give regions more autonomy can have a profound impact on cultural preservation by enabling communities to make decisions that reflect their specific cultural values, practices, and priorities (Cheema and Rondinelli, 2007). Autonomy allows regions to develop appropriate heritage policies that value local traditions while aligning with broader national goals. Decentralisation validates the distinct identities of different regions and enables them to take ownership of their heritage, ensuring that cultural preservation is responsive to the unique characteristics of each community. To implement this recommendation, national and regional governments could prioritise policies that decentralise decision-making powers to local authorities, particularly in cultural and heritage domains. Funding and resources should be allocated directly to regional councils, allowing for local investment in cultural projects and initiatives (Grodach and Loukaitou-Sideris, 2007). To enhance regional autonomy further, platforms for inter-regional exchange could be established, where communities can share best practices in heritage preservation, creating a sense of unity while celebrating regional diversity. This approach would promote a more inclusive and representative preservation of intangible cultural heritage across the country.

In conclusion the recommendations provided underscore the multifaceted strategies necessary for effective cultural heritage preservation within Algeria. Strengthening access to resources, enhancing research support, empowering women, prioritizing girls' education, and promoting regional autonomy are essential procedures toward fostering a more inclusive and sustainable cultural preservation model. Adopting these measures, Algeria can enrich its approach to heritage management and ensure that intangible cultural practices and knowledge are not only safeguarded but also actively shared and celebrated. This comprehensive, community-focused approach aligns with the broader goals of cultural continuity, enhancing the resilience and visibility of Algeria's heritage on both a national and international scale.

9.8. Conclusion

In conclusion, this section has explored the multi-layered challenges faced in researching the socio-cultural realities of the Amazigh communities in Algeria, underscoring the criticality of adaptability and strategic approaches in qualitative studies. The limitations ranging from logistical difficulties and sample constraints to cultural sensitivities and the availability of academic resources posed significant demands on data collection and analysis. Each obstacle necessitated careful consideration and the implementation of tailored strategies to enhance data accuracy and participant comfort. The reliance on adaptive interviewing techniques, rapport-building, and the triangulation of observation and notes helped mitigate some of the challenges, facilitating a deeper understanding of the Amazigh cultural landscape. Despite the barriers, the findings provide valuable insights into Amazigh women resilience and cultural preservation, illustrating the necessity for detailed, contextually aware research approaches in studies of marginalised groups. The limitations acknowledged here serve as a foundation for future work to expand upon and deepen research within the cultural and political complexities of the North African region.

Appendices

Appendix I

Participant Information Sheet

Amazigh Intangible Cultural Heritage: A qualitative exploration of gender and the role of women in the preservation and transmission of traditional cultures in Algeria

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

What is the purpose of this study?

This research study has the purpose of exploring Amazigh culture as a traditional Algerian culture and identify the challenges faced by the Amazigh women in terms of preserving and transmitting cultural intangible heritage such as the traditions, the cultural events, food, and music. In addition, it exposes the importance of intangible heritage (traditions, practices, food, music, stories, and proverbs) in Amazigh culture and investigating the government efforts concerning the promotion and the protection of the intangible cultural heritage. Finally yet importantly, a further research purpose is contributing in protecting and giving importance to the culture of minorities against the lack of consideration from the government and from the scholars as well.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to take part in this study because you are the head of the cultural directions in one of these wilayas Batna, Tizi ouezo, Ghardia, or Tamanrasset.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. If you decide to take part you can answer the questions you want to and refuse those that you may not like and you are free to withdraw at any time during the interview without giving a reason.

Appendix II

School of Education & Social Sciences
Paisley Campus

Consent form

Title of the research project: *The safeguarding of the Amazigh intangible cultural heritage: exploring women's efforts in preserving and transmitting Amazigh intangible cultural heritage in Algeria nowadays*

Name of the researcher: Fatima Zohra ZINAI

- 1- I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above project and the researcher has answered any queries to my satisfaction.
- 2- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the project at any time, without having to give a reason and without any consequences.
- 3- I understand that I am going to:
 - a- Participate in an interview (around 45 minutes).
 - b- Be audio-recorded during the interview.
- 4- I understand that any information recorded in the investigation will remain confidential and no information that identifies me will be made publicly available.
- 5- I consent to being a participant in the project

Appendix III

26/01/2023

Dear RESCHED1 Fatima Zinai,

Your application 20900: Amazigh Intangible Cultural Heritage: A qualitative exploration of gender and the role of women in the preservation and transmission of traditional cultures in Algeria, submission reference 15961, has been approved, with conditions, by the Education and Social Sciences SEC. The reviewers have raised some comments that need to be addressed. Can you please work with your supervisor to address these **BEFORE** you proceed with data collection.

Title	Comment
Principal Investigator	Please use your title.
Supervisor/Director of Studies	Just state 'Education and Social Sciences'.
Where will the proposed research take place?	Can you briefly clarify who these individuals are and what they do?
Where will the proposed research take place?	Sample size?
Where will the proposed research take place?	Can you say briefly why these cities were selected?
How will the costs of the study be met?	This includes fieldwork costs?

Appendix IV

Examining the challenges facing non-Algerian employees in Algerian private and state-owned oil and gas organisations regarding team performance and social integration

Zinai Fatima Zohra

Interview

You are being asked to participate in a research project that aims to investigate the role of Amazigh women, in preserving and transmitting the intangible cultural heritage and the role of the heritage associations in promoting and protecting the intangible heritage in Algeria.

As a part of this project, a series of semi-structured in-depth interviews is being conducted with a twenty Amazigh women aged 45 and above from different Amazigh ethnicity (Chaouia, Kabyle, Mzab and Tuareg).

As such, I would like to include you in these interviews. The interview will take no more than 45 minutes and all information gathered will be anonymised and treated as strictly confidential, following compliance with required Data Protection legislation.

In order to secure an interview, I am happy to be completely flexible in the choice of date and time for the interview and will be sending you full briefing material in advance. This will be recorded, with your full agreement and consent.

Thank you in advance, and kind regards.

Interview schedule

Section one: Opening questions.

Q1. What do you do in life?

Appendix V

interview

This interview is a part of a research project being undertaken by Zinai Fatima Zohra, who is a PhD research student in the School of Education and Social Sciences at the University of the West of Scotland. This research project is concerned with the role of Amazigh women in transmitting and preserving intangible cultural heritage and the role of the heritage associations in protecting and promoting it. This project depends a great deal on the responses of people like yourself. To this end, we are approaching you with this questionnaire and requesting your kind cooperation in completing this as fully as you can.

All information given by you shall not be used for any purpose other than that of our research and it is completely anonymous and will be treated in the strictest confidence.

Section one: (Identifying personal information) please tick the appropriate box.

Q1. Are you

Male

Female

Other

Prefer not to say

Q2. Which age group describes you?

From 18 to 29

From 30 to 39

Appendix VI

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N
3	culture and ethnicity	I have to say I am firstly proud too. be Algerian in the first place, being a Kabyle is another pride that I carry	kaoye tran anything else but since I grow up, I am both proud to be an Amazigh as much as I am to be an Algerian	I love my ethnicity and culture and I would like for it to stay a long time even after I am gone.	I think very highly of my culture as an Amazigh firstly and then as a Kabyle,	as a Chaouia i feel that being algerian is important because we eventually all have same nationality	having roots in the atlas mountains, it means a lot to me, Tachaouit is a heritage and identity	pride, i do feel proud about my ethnicity but at the same time I love my country and every ethnicity it has	links you your roots and land, my ethnicity is not only important but it reflects everything i do in my daily life	my city and my people, i didn't know what is outside until i moved to another city, so Ghardaia is all what i knew	from time to time, i am proud of my ethnicity and the way i was raised, i love nothing like i love my land	i love Ghardaia , my land my roots my house i feel safe in ways i can't change that for anything, he explain, my home is all what i saw and what i felt i belong to, my ancestors land	heritage and i would never is here and everyone i care about. my land and roots are planted here.
4	importance of culture and history	that we guarantee that it is not lost nor forgotten	it was important not only to me but also to the entire people there we had to know to tell people who visited the area and asked about places and events or the names behind the streets and roads/ it wasn't in the books we had in school or in the educational curriculums it was something that is transmitted by telling and hearing.	From alders telling me what happened and then we had history classes in the school where they talk generally about the country's culture and history, where there's a really few details and information on the Amazigh as culture and a big part of the country's history.	all the history I have now about my culture region is from my father, he was a huge fan of history he was a teacher so did that for his entire life and thanks to him I got information and knowledge about my culture.	landscapes you can see where it was planned the war of independence, i am glad that some part of my ethnicity is taught in schools/ the origins and the history of amazigh is not that presented and indulged in the system	actually In schools all we have learnt is the history of the country, nothing related to the origins and the Amazigh as a group , but that was decades ago, the new system may include aspects of Amazigh history	as a teacher myself i learnt the history in school then in university/ my father and mother were my source for alot of stories and events because they lived with alderly that told them alot / my subject don't include a lot of Origins history because I teach Arabic, so everything in around Arab history	i remember that most of the history sessions were either about the war or the independence/ the regions history is like tales transmitted from a person to another we talk about it as we are telling stories nothing i can rememeber is in school books	i studied in ghardaia for 15 years, all of my knowledge about my roots and heritage is from there, when i moved i didn't learn much because there was a little mention of anything related to the Amazigh culture or Mzab culture in schools,	i have been only to primary school but i used to hear stories from my father and his father about our history and culture, but all what i really learnt was from real life spending time with the women in the castle and their stories women of my neighborhood were the teachers and the mentors for everything i know	not to much i used to go to women gatherings and listen to brothers who told them stories..... i stopped at middle school so all the knowledge i got was from the quoranic school i kept going to until i was 16	my mother used to tell me what her father used to tell her about the history and living in a society that everything is transmitted i got to listen to other in gatherir where we used to learn abc life and our culture
5	family	but not only the small family it's the bigger one with the grandparents and the uncles and aunts.	still see my big family as respect them and visit on all occasions, I still take the kids to see their relatives	my family the big one the aunts and uncles and my small family husband and kids are my world, we are a family that is very close to all the relatives we share the good and bad times together.	, the family id the first school for the kids so, they get all their knowledge from it primary, as I told you my father was my teacher, he was my school and my source for a lot of information	We are still very attached to our families even after having our owns/ my big family has an Arab side and Chaoui side/ at this age I am still asking for advice and help from my alders	My parents and aunts, ancles are always a big part of the decisions in the family they are the first panel we have to go through / even with my own family we still feel shy and respect them as we are still kids	I am married to an Arab so we are a little bit detached from the big families/ we visit and see them on occasions	even if we live far from the big family, it has an influence and a part of our lives/ w visit we spend more time in the grandparents house than we do any where/ family is everything to us	family is everything i visited alot although i live 500km away but i have to go and see my grandparents, parents, parents in law and even far relatives we hold our family so dear almost we are never apart ...	i am a grandmother now so i not only have sisters and brothers and relatives i have a big family that visits me too, we cherish the family and we never break family bonds family is sacred and without it you are noone	i live with my inlaws for 37 years now, i still visit my parents if i don't they get so upset we are like one cell we can't be divided even if you try you will always get back to your family and roots	family and blood is something very dear to me and us as mzab i know no one that is independent that is something to feel proud of families never break even if parents die i even call my mother in laws mother and father we never live the fan we add to it...
		The grandparents are the pillars of the house, they should be part of any decision in the family, they should be asked for their approval in	Everything I have learnt about my heritage and culture is transmitted by them, they are the most important messengers for the culture all the alders actually without	my grandparents were the source for most of my knowledge and information, I was raised in a family where we all lived together, so my grandmother was the	my grandfather died in the independence war so , my grandmother was everything to my father she taught him about his father about the sacrifices he had done for the	my grand mother was everything in the household she was the one who kept the family together, my grandfather died when i was a child so she was the source for everthing my father knew/ my motherside my grandfather was alwat	i can only remember my grandfather and his authority he was strict and so tough/ my grandmother from my mom side was very kind she taught me alot i used to	i was attached to my motherside so i lived at my grandmother's house until i was 9yo/ my grandfather used to take me with him when ever there a	unfortunately i don't remember my grandparents they were dead by the time i was 6yo , but i had a lot of neighbours who were alderly and I used to sit with them and talk and i still to this day appreciate my culture	i feel privileged that i lived with my grandparent until they passed away, my kids don't have that privilege but i make sure they spend all summer there and among their family our ancestors were a big value that we still use as a source for everything.... their talk they words their beliefs... my grandfather was one of the	our society is based on tribes and respect to the elders no one will have an opinion after the heads of the tribe have decided , marriges events everything.... i remember that a girl and a boy were in love and the head of the tribe did not agree on that marriage because it was againts the rules to meet and talk to men like a big sin, so they were forbade for being together	my ansectors were really known and respected almost all decisions had to go through them, so in the household the family we would do nothing without their appo or permission , my father us to ask them in the little and	

Appendix VII

+	policy interview	community interviews
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Q1	interviewee	333333	noureddine M	bachir M	taha M	rashid M
Q2	ethnicity		Kabyle	Arab	Mzab	Touareg
Q3	job position		director	duty manager	event organiser	head of the direction
Q4	location		tizi ouezo	batna	ghardaia	tamanerasset
Q5	tasks		going through decisions, revising agreements, approving new organisations, dealing with funding	visiting loctions, supervising workers, receiving complaints and dealing with them,	organising cultural events, relating the people with the authorities, integrating events in the educational system	going through renovation tasks, helpig cultural assosiations in events, funding them protecting national heritage, organising cultural days at the direction of culture
Q6	cultural activities		we organise days of Tamazight, of yennayer, spring events, the new agricultural season....	we ave the tchaouit song day we do have schools and libraries through the city that celebrate it,] as usual yennayer, azozer day, timghad musical festival	the day of Mzab song, the birth of prophet, weddings and the azaba groups that we usually ask to accompany us everywhere we go specially the ksour (the castles)	the imzad and tende day, national tuareg celebrations of sbiba, we even join the tribes and promot those acts f culture
Q7	public support		public tends to be part of all of the city's events we have a lot of support from the people	actually not everyone is part of the events that we organise, some of the university students and the people who have some interest in culture attend	we actually host what people plan they tend to do the events and if they need anything we would just help	the tuareg community is responsible for slmost everything we only add some legal perspective to it and help with people's demands
Q8	important aspects of the heritage		actually i would say the villages and the touristic sites	a lot of chaouiya's heritage is lost in between changing times , but we make sure that se are renovating the sites organising days of culture	taghardit is not only a city is a way of life to us everything is heritage from the ksour to the noram] simple life	the cultural heritage in the area is mainly preserved through transmission, i acknowledge people's role in doing so we are just a backup for them
Q9	works done		restoration of the tizgirt heritage site, the old villages in ath el kaid and their practices, the national day for tamazight the 12th edition this year	the restoration of the heritage site Timgad, cultural days for the ich as n'gaous amazigh day and Tazolat chaoui day	the renovation of the ksour as the Atef castle, organising day of mzab song, integrating zawiya in our heritage events to promot the religious side of the city	the hoggar and tassili national parks, protecting the music instruments of the area, integrating some aspects of the culture in the unesco's files

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